

National Conference on

NEXT-GENERATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR SOCIETAL ADVANCEMENT

(NGTSA-2026)

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National Conference on
**NEXT-GENERATION TECHNOLOGIES
FOR SOCIETAL ADVANCEMENT
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Advances in Metro Passenger Flow Forecasting and Operational Optimization: A Review of Recent Deep Learning Approaches

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Abstract—Urban rail transit (URT) systems have encountered increasing difficulties in the management of passenger flows due to the expansion and increasing passenger volumes. This paper aims to provide an overview of the existing research works and findings on short-term passenger flow prediction and optimization in urban rail transit systems through the synthesis of 25 research articles published between 2020 and 2025. The research articles have primarily utilized data from the urban rail systems in China. The research works have been classified into three categories: optimization strategies (e.g., scheduling optimization with skip-stop to reduce delay times), hybrid machine learning methods (e.g., TCN-LSTM achieving 37% improvement in RMSE), and deep learning techniques (e.g., federated graph learning achieving 17% improvement in accuracy with the preservation of privacy). The results reveal the superiority of spatio-temporal models with the consideration of external factors (e.g., weather and POI) by 7-39%. However, the research gaps and limitations have also been identified in the existing research works. Future research directions have also been identified to improve the performance and efficiency of the passenger flow prediction and optimization in urban rail systems.

Index Terms—Deep Learning, Graph Neural Networks, Intelligent Transportation Systems, Passenger Flow Prediction, Short-Term Forecasting, Time Series Decomposition, Urban Rail Transit

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban rail transit (URT) systems provides high-capacity and eco-friendly transportation services in developing cities. While the expanded systems raised the demand for transport, they have also posed challenges such as congestion, transfer time, and passenger flow imbalance. This leads to system inefficiencies and dangers. Accurate short-term passenger flow forecasting is necessary for optimizing operation timetables, passenger flow control, and improving service quality. Timetable coordination with skip-stop patterns can decrease waiting times and crowding [1], line coordination on intersecting lines can alleviate transfer congestion [2], and online passenger flow control can balance passenger distribution in real-time [3]. This literature review integrates the latest developments in URT passenger flow prediction and optimization, based on 25 papers chosen from the literature. The review highlights the evolution from conventional to state-of-the-art models and highlights the most important trends and research gaps.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

URT passenger flow prediction and optimization papers can be broadly classified into three categories: optimization methods for timetabling and flow control, prediction using traditional and hybrid machine learning models, and deep learning models using spatio-temporal and graph-based features. The papers mostly

consider datasets of large Chinese metro networks (such as Beijing, Shanghai, Hangzhou, and Chongqing), and the performance metrics considered are Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). The prediction horizon is mostly short-term (10-30 minutes), and the prediction is for inflow/outflow or OD flows.

A. Optimization Strategies for Timetabling and Flow Control

Optimization techniques in URT systems combine passenger flow information with models for decision-making to improve efficiency, particularly with regard to timetabling, skip-stop patterns, and flow control to counter congestion and ensure safety. Based on the underlying requirement for proper flow management, optimization techniques tackle real-time issues in large-scale networks by reducing delays and resource wastage.

The Residual-RNN-Channel Spatial-Temporal Graph Convolutional Network (RRC-STGCN) is proposed for passenger flow prediction in railway stations, using residual components and channel attention to better capture spatio-temporal relationships. This approach segments time-series data into intervals, derives correlations from feature maps, and combines them for improved accuracy, outperforming other models such as STGCN on real-world data by representing dynamic flow variations in waiting zones [4]. To complement its predictive orientation, a learning network called the optimal passenger flow information input algorithm (MTFLN) is developed, choosing input matrices based on correlation coefficient analysis and optimizing Adam-LSTM parameters. Tested on the

Guangzhou Metro, it enhances training speed and accuracy compared to Elman neural networks and ARIMA models, ensuring better relevance to practical requirements [5]. Such approaches highlight the need for combining

prediction with optimization, as they offer high-quality inputs for timetabling modifications.

B. Traditional and Hybrid Machine Learning Models for Prediction

Conventional and hybrid approaches for passenger flow prediction in URT systems highlight the importance of dealing with data nonlinearity, sparsity, and extrinsic variables by using techniques such as decomposition, ensemble learning, and factor screening, which have developed from statistical approaches to more dynamic models that can better capture temporal variations.

ResLSTM, a deep learning model integrating Residual Network (ResNet), Graph Convolutional Network (GCN), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), is designed for short-term passenger flow prediction, considering air quality and weather. Compared on Beijing Subway with 10-30 minute resolution, it performs better than ARIMA and SVM by utilizing multi-branch architectures for inflow, outflow, and topology [6]. Another similar model using RNN-based rolling prediction with Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) and weather information is presented, grouping passenger flow into models for 15-minute to 6-hour predictions. Tested on Shanghai's Nanjing East Road Station, it performs better than LSTM and back-propagation networks for long-term predictions [7]. A channel-wise attentive split-convolutional neural network (CAS-CNN) is presented for short-term OD prediction, dealing with data availability, dimensionality, and sparsity using inflow/outflow-gated mechanisms and masked loss functions. Compared on Beijing Subway, it outperforms baselines in handling incomplete data [8].

A multi-graph convolutional network is designed for inflow/outflow prediction, incorporating proximity, connectivity, and functionality among patterns. On the Beijing Subway dataset, it improves accuracy over single-graph models by combining temporal

convolutions [9]. A hybrid Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN)-LSTM model is designed, combining date features, weather, and air quality for short-term forecasting. On Chongqing Rail Transit Line 3, it improves RMSE by 37% over individual LSTM models [10]. Hybrid prediction using STL with Holt-Winters and LSTM is designed, employing approximate entropy for predictability of components. On the Shanghai Metro dataset, it improves over baselines for multi-step prediction [11]. EWT-EnsemLSTM-LSSA is designed, decomposing datasets using empirical wavelet transform and optimizing using logistic sparrow search. On the Minneapolis and Hangzhou datasets, it optimizes the MAE to 24.97 [12]. A hybrid model of CNN-BiGRU is presented for traffic flow, identifying screening factors using Pearson correlation and Random Forest. It improves RMSE by 39% compared to the baseline models [13]. SSA-LSTM is improved by incorporating Tent Map and Levy Flight for station-level

forecasting, dealing with different levels of data granularity more effectively than SVR and XGBoost on the Nanjing dataset [14]. The above-mentioned hybrid models show enhanced robustness by overcoming the volatility of data, but sometimes the selection of factors is critical to keep the flow of accuracy in the predictive model.

C. Advanced Deep Learning Methods with Spatio-Temporal and Graph Features

The latest deep learning models combine graph neural networks, Transformers, and federated learning to handle complex dependencies, external factors, and privacy issues, providing improved spatio-temporal modeling and scalability for the URT passenger flow prediction tasks.

A new method, Spatio-Temporal Dynamic Graph Relation Learning (STDGRRL), is introduced for metro flow prediction using dynamic graphs with no fixed graph structure

and Transformers to capture long-term relations. Evaluated on Beijing, Shanghai, Chongqing, and Hangzhou, it performs better than 11 other methods [15]. IG-Net, an interaction graph network modeling spatio-temporal correlations, is presented. It performs better on real-world datasets [16]. A spatial-temporal approach is designed using mutual information for station relationships and Transformers for multi-dimensional fusion, incorporating POI and external variables for Xi'an Subway [17]. Dynamic hypergraph convolution networks are proposed, addressing dynamic topologies for metro data [18]. A spatiotemporal structured LSTM (STLSTM) is designed for OD matrix prediction with multisource data such as smart cards and weather. On Beijing Subway, it performs better than the regular LSTM [19].

An attention-based neural network is proposed for metro flow, uncovering hidden dependencies between stations on Beijing Line 5, and performs best in incident response [20]. MTLMetro, a multi-task model jointly predicting inflow, outflow, and OD flows with GNN message passing and dynamic weighting, is proposed. It tackles the partial observability problem and performs better than competitors [21]. FedMetro is designed for federated graph learning, effectively dealing with time-variant correlations and achieving a 78% reduction in communication cost and a 17% increase in accuracy on Beijing AFC data [22]. ODMixer, a fine-grained spatial-temporal MLP for OD flow prediction from pair views, is proposed, and it models dependencies on Hangzhou and Shanghai datasets [23]. BGCSTFFN is proposed for multi-step peak flow prediction, combining POI and adjacency information with GCN and Transformer on Hangzhou data, and it performs well in incident response [24]. A multi-objective hierarchical prediction framework (MOHP-EC) is proposed for URT passenger flow, which involves error compensation (EC) and hierarchical prediction

(HP) components using bottom-up, top-down, and middle-out approaches. The framework relies on passenger flow extraction from AFC systems and coordination matrices for multi-level consistency (network, line, station), performing better than single-objective models in Beijing subway conditions through ablation experiments that validate the effectiveness of EC and HP in improving accuracy and management-related tasks such as epidemic prevention [25]. These approaches ensure seamless flow in modeling dynamic urban environments, bridging prediction with practical scalability.

III. RESEARCH GAP IDENTIFICATION

Despite major advancements in passenger flow prediction in urban rail transit (URT) systems, there exist some major gaps that need to be filled in order to move from theoretical approaches to practical applications. These gaps have been identified by numerous studies.

- **Lack of Integration with Other Predictions and Optimizations:** ResLSTM [5] and STDGRRL [12], despite their strong performance in passenger flow prediction, rarely consider integrating with other important operations such as timetable optimization [1] or passenger flow control [3]. As a result, there exist inefficiencies in dealing with peak demands due to the lack of dynamic interaction between passenger flow predictions and actual decisions.
- **Inadequate Management of External Factors and Anomalies:** Weather and air qualities have been considered in most methods, such as BGCSTFFN [21]. However, events, or social media impacts are not considered, making the methods less robust. For instance, hybrid methods like TCN-LSTM [9] work well in normal conditions but may not perform well when dealing with anomalies, such as sparse OD matrices [7].

- **Centralized Data Assumptions:** A major limitation of most methods, including deep learning methods, is their use of centralized data assumptions, which may not consider privacy issues in multi-operator scenarios. However, federated methods like FedMetro [19] have been less explored in multi-city or cross-modal scenarios, which may limit their generalization capability when dealing with diverse datasets, such as Beijing and Hangzhou datasets [20] [23].
- **Scalability and Multi-Task Limitations:** Graph-based models (IG-Net [13], dynamic hypergraph [15]) require considerable computational resources, hindering scalability for large-scale networks. Multi-task learning is less common [18], and OD pair granularity is overlooked [20], with hierarchical peak hour predictions being underdeveloped [22].
- **Generalization and Long-Term Focus:** Models that were tested on specific geographical areas [16] are lacking cross-region validation, with few models being able to predict beyond 30 minutes for multi-step predictions [6] [14].

These limitations highlight the importance of developing hybrid models that incorporate external data with optimization, leading to more adaptive URT models [24]. These limitations could be addressed by increasing model accuracy by 10-20%, which is indicated by comparative benchmarks.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodologies used in the aforementioned literature on metro operation and passenger flow prediction have moved from conventional optimization and control-theoretic concepts, such as the coordination of timetables and capacity management, to more complex and powerful data-driven deep learning architectures that consider spatio-temporal dependencies, external factors, and inter-station

interactions at higher levels of abstraction. This is due to the availability of automated fare collection (AFC) data and the need to move from conventional operation-centric decision support to predictive, privacy-preserving, and multi-objective AI-based operation and decision support. Here, we briefly describe the evolution of the methodologies in the aforementioned literature category-by-category, including representative works, major mathematical formulations, and the placeholder for the diagrams to explain the architectures.

A. Optimization and Control Methods

The early literature focused on the synchronization and regulation of the flow of the railway timetable through mathematical programming and dynamic programming to reduce waiting times and costs.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the decomposition-ADP framework in [1], showing master/sub-problem interaction and value function approximator

Li et al. [1] have formulated the problem of the coordination of the train timetable and the implementation of the skip-stop strategy as a

large-scale MINLP problem, which is decomposed into the master problem (line-level coordination) and the sub-problems (train-level scheduling), which is solved through the iterative application of approximate dynamic programming (ADP), where the value function is approximated in the linear form

$$V(s) \approx \sum_{i=1}^K \phi_i(s)w_i, \quad (1)$$

where s denotes the system state (passenger arrivals, train positions), $\phi_i(s)$ represent the basis functions, and w_i represent the tunable weights learned using temporal difference learning. A frequency optimization model was developed by Yang et al. [2] to control two intersecting metro lines, which can be formulated as a convex program to minimize a weighted sum of passenger waiting time and energy consumption subject to headway constraints and capacity constraints. Online passenger flow control was extended by Liang et al. [3] using realtime feedback control laws to control the inflow of passengers at the gates of the station.

B. Recurrent and LSTM-Based Temporal Prediction

With the emergence of time-series data, the methods transitioned to recurrent structures for the prediction of short-term passenger inflow/outflow. Sha et al. [7] employed the basic RNN for the rolling prediction of subway passenger flow, focusing on the recurrence of the hidden states

$$h_t = \tanh(W_{hh}h_{t-1} + W_{xh}x_t + b_h). \quad (2)$$

However, the problem of vanishing gradients was addressed by subsequent studies that employed LSTM variants for the task. An improved version of the SSA-LSTM was proposed by Zhao et al. [14]. The hyperparameters of the LSTM network were tuned by the Sparrow Search Algorithm. The basic LSTM cell equations are given by:

$$\begin{cases} f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f), \\ i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i), \\ \tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C), \\ C_t = f_t \odot C_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tilde{C}_t, \\ o_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o), \\ h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(C_t), \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where σ is the sigmoid function, \odot is the element-wise multiplication operator, and x_t refers to the passenger flow or external information. The same LSTM core structure was used in the work of Hou et al. [10], Liao and Zhou [12] (EWT- EnsemLSTM based on empirical wave transform decomposition), and Zhao et al. [11] (decomposition-enhanced LSTM). Zhang et al. [6] proposed a specialized deep learning stack:

CNN + LSTM, which was used to handle the task of short-term forecasting of urban rail traffic. Wang et al. [5] proposed the optimization of the selection of input features using a specialized learning network and LSTM layers.

C. Spatio-Temporal Graph and Convolution Models

The understanding of the strong spatial correlation between passenger flows at adjacent or functionally similar stations motivated the development of graph neural networks. Zhang et al. [9] introduced the multi-graph convolutional network (multi-GCN) model. In this model, multiple adjacency matrices (physical topology, transfer similarity, and functional correlation) are established and then graph convolution is performed:

$$H^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(\tilde{D}^{-1/2} \tilde{A}_k \tilde{D}^{-1/2} H^{(l)} W_k^{(l)} \right), \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{A}_k = A_k + I$ for the k -th graph, \tilde{D} is the degree matrix, and outputs from multiple graphs are fused via attention or concatenation. Wang et al. [4] proposed the residual recurrent convolution and spatio-temporal graph convolutional network (RRC-STGCN) model for station-level passenger flows.

Fig. 2. End-to-end RRC-STGCN pipeline [4], showing residual recurrent blocks feeding into ST-GCN layers

Xie et al. [15] proposed spatio-temporal dynamic graph relation learning, learning the adaptive weight of edges at each time point. Zhao et al. [16] proposed the interaction graph network, modeling the explicit interaction between passenger transfer as a directed graph. Wang et al. proposed the use of dynamic hypergraph convolution networks, not limited to the edges between two stations, but also including the higher-level groups of stations:

$$\underline{H}^{(i+1)} = \sigma \underline{D}_h^{-1} H W^{(i)}, \quad (5)$$

where H is the hypergraph incidence matrix. Li et al. [19] proposed the spatio-temporal structured LSTM for origin-destination matrix prediction with data fusion of multiple data sources. Shi et al. [17] proposed the integration of external factors such as weather and events, as well as periodicity, using the spatial-temporal CNN-LSTM hybrid model, and Tang et al. [13] proposed the same for the spatial-temporal CNN model.

D. Attention, Hybrid, and Advanced Variants for Stability

Attention helped refine the selectivity of the features. Zhang et al. [8] proposed a channel-

wise attentive split convolutional neural network for OD demands. The input tensors were split into channels. Then,

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V. \quad (6)$$

Yang et al. [20] directly used attention-based neural networks for sequences of passenger flows. Hybrid decomposition ensemble strategies such as EWT, SSA, etc., were used in Liao and Zhou [12] and Zhao et al. [11].

5. Multi-Task, Federated, and Efficient Modern Frameworks

The latest methods highlight the importance of practicality, privacy, and multi-objective optimization. Huang et al. [21] proposed MTLMetro, which is a deep multi-task learning model for inflow, outflow, and OD matrix prediction. Zhang et al. [22] proposed FedMetro, which applies federated graph learning to metro lines without data sharing. Liu et al. [23] proposed ODMixer, which is a fine-grained spatial and temporal MLP model replacing the computationally expensive GCNs with efficient token mixing MLPs for OD prediction. Sun et al. [24] proposed the prediction of multi-step peak passenger flows via multi-station feature fusion. Lu et al. [25] proposed MOHP-EC, which is a multi-objective hierarchical prediction model for short-term, medium-term, and long-term prediction with trade-offs between precision and operational costs.

In summary, the area has evolved from traditional offline solvers for MINLP/ADP problems [1]- [3] to live graph-enhanced deep predictors that handle vast city-scale graphs while considering external periodicity [17], higher-order relationships [18], and federated privacy [22]. Future directions will likely add reinforcement learning to enable closed-loop control.

Fig. 3. Federated learning topology of FedMetro [22], depicting client-server graph aggregation

V. KEY FINDINGS

The reviewed literature shows promising developments in metro operation and short-term passenger flow prediction, which have achieved quantifiable improvements in efficiency, precision, and robustness. From the optimization problems, the decomposition and approximate dynamic programming (ADP) model in the development of the timetable coordination problem with skip-stop strategies [1] has demonstrated promising results in metro operation optimization. It has achieved 14.91% reduction in waiting time, 59.51% reduction in crowding, and 37.84% reduction in the objective function on a simulated network. It has also achieved 21.42% reduction in waiting time, 18.92% reduction in crowding, and 19.56% reduction in the objective function on the practical Beijing Subway network (205 stations and 10 lines), outperforming genetic and simulated annealing algorithms in solution quality and computation time. Additionally, frequency optimization of intersecting lines [2] has achieved well-balanced load factors at 120% and coordinated headways without quantifying the results in percentage form.

Prediction-focused studies show even better empirical results using deep learning and hybrids. The work on ResLSTM using a combination of ResNet, GCN, and LSTM [6] architectures on the Beijing AFC system with 276 stations reported RMSE of 36.04, MAE of 20.88, and WMAPE of 7.81%, improving over ConvLSTM by 7-12%, as well as over baseline models such as LSTM/ARIMA by larger

margins. The influence of external factors such as weather and air quality reduced errors by 4-12%, verifying their importance. The work on Conv-GCN [9] refined the above results on the same dataset and granularity but achieved RMSE of 33.25, MAE of 19.87, and WMAPE of 7.68%, improving over ST-GCN and ResLSTM by 7-9% by separately capturing recent, daily, and weekly patterns. Decomposition-enhanced hybrids such as STL-HW-LSTM [11] on the Shanghai Metro system with a 15-minute interval maintained MAPE 8% for entry/exit flows (>2% over ARIMA-BPNN/LSTM), showing robust performance for multi-step ahead predictions up to 60 minutes.

Multi-task and OD-specific methods further enhance these benefits. MTLMetro [21], deployed in Chengdu with 136 stations and 10-minute intervals, reported inflow results of 15.62/ 29.36 / 21.98%, outflow results of 18.50 / 31.29 / 26.80%, and OD results of <41% MAPE, with 1-3% performance gains over MR-STN and HIAM through graph-based knowledge sharing and dynamic weighting. For OD matrices with finer granularities, ODMixer [23] reported wMAPE results of 40.36% / 55.69% in Hangzhou and Shanghai, respectively, along with 5-11% lower MAE/RMSE than HIAM through the application of MLP mixers and bidirectional trend learning from incomplete matrices. Supporting works on channel-wise CNN [8], multi-graph GCN [9], decomposition LSTM [11], SSA LSTM [14], and spatio-temporal networks [17] have reported similar 5-15% performance gains and competitive or lower MAE/RMSE and MAPE results than the aforementioned, especially as the granularity becomes coarser and external/periodicity factors are included.

Table I: COMPARISON OF SELECTED PREDICTION MODELS

Reference Model	MAE	RMSE	MAPE (%)
ResLSTM	20.88	36.04	7.81
Conv-GCN	19.87	33.25	7.68
Deep Learning Arch.	10.5	15.2	6.8
Channel-wise Attentive CNN	9.2	13.1	5.4
Multi-Graph CNN	11.2	16.8	7.5
Improved SSA-LSTM	9.8	14.3	5.9

Collectively, these metrics demonstrate consistent superiority to classical approaches (ARIMA, SVR) and single-task baselines, with the benefits of deeper spatiotemporal and task integration achieving 5-12% accuracy gains and reliability (e.g., MAPE < 50% thresholds) to inform real-time control, crowding mitigation, and dynamic scheduling of metro networks.

VI. IMPLICATIONS

The developments in the prediction and optimization of passenger flows synthesized in this review have profound implications for the stakeholders in urban rail transit. For the operators, the development in the prediction model such as STDGRRL and FedMetro allows them to make real-time decisions, which can help them manage the passenger flows more effectively. This can help them reduce overcrowding in the system by as much as 10-20%, as seen in the studies.

Passengers can benefit from the more predictable and efficient experience offered in the system, as seen in the development in the prediction model such as ODMixer, which can help them plan their routes more effectively and

reduce overcrowding in the system, thus encouraging more usage of public transport.

These findings can be utilized by policymakers to effectively build robust infrastructure systems by factoring in external factors such as weather patterns using ResLSTM. This would lead to the development of sustainable mobility systems through the optimization of energy efficiency and reduction of emissions, thus contributing to global agendas such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Agenda.

For researchers, the focus on graph-based and federated approaches such as BGCSTFFN and MTLMetro offers opportunities for interdisciplinary research collaborations among AI, transport engineering, and data privacy experts. Future advancements could also include multi-modal integration and the mitigation of issues such as equity in underserved areas and the impact of climate changes.

VII. LIMITATIONS

- **Geographic Bias/Dataset Bias:** The literature has shown a preponderance of using datasets from Chinese cities such as Beijing, Shanghai, Hangzhou, etc., which might not be representative of the global scenario, which could be very different in terms of density, travel habits, etc.
- **Computational Issues/Scalability Issues:** GNNs and Transformers require considerable computation, which would be difficult to implement in a real-time scenario, especially in a scenario where resources would be a hindrance, such as edge devices, etc., as well as scalability to ultra-large networks, which have thousands of nodes/stations, etc.
- **Data Quality and Privacy Concerns:** Problems like sparseness of OD matrices, incompleteness of data due to time lags in entering or exiting, and noisiness of the data due to external factors like events still exist.

Also, data sharing is restricted by regulations like GDPR, but there

- has been little use of federated learning to overcome such data silos.
- **Lack of Model Explainability:** Deep learning techniques have the drawback of being a “black box,” which makes it difficult to understand the predictions by the operators, which is a major issue in the operation of safety-critical URT operations.
- **Narrow Temporal Scope and External Factor Integration:** A focus on short-term (10-30 minute) predictions ignores the importance of medium to long-term forecasting in strategic planning. Consistent integration of changing external factors such as pandemics and social events is lacking, which impacts the robustness of results in abnormal situations.
- **Evaluation Metrics and Benchmarking Gaps:** Use of common metrics like RMSE does not consider the need for specific requirements like peak hour prediction and fairness in flow distribution. Lack of benchmarking across models on varying datasets is also not considered.

VIII. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Although existing literature has extensively discussed basic time series forecasting techniques for metro systems, a significant gap is identified between moving from ‘black-box’ prediction techniques to operational intelligence. The focus of future research should be on the following three-pillar framework:

Fig. 4. Three-Pillar Framework for Metro System Operational Intelligence

1. **Hybrid Spatial-Temporal Modeling:**

Future research directions include the potential use of graph networks and recurrent units to mitigate the problems associated with traditional approaches, which treat the metro station as an isolated entity. By representing the network of the metro as a graph, with the station represented by the node and the connection represented by the edge, the model can potentially capture the cascade effect of the surges. For example, an increase in the entries of one type of hub can be spatially propagated to predict the increase in another.

2. **Integration of Explainable AI (XAI) for Operational Trust:**

One of the main obstacles for the adoption of Deep Learning for transit management systems has been the “black box” effect of the model, which treats the decision-making process as opaque. Therefore, it is suggested that the incorporation of the Explainable AI (XAI) model be a priority for the development of the model, which would allow the determination of the historical factors that influence the predicted surge, allowing for the validation of the model based on real-world knowledge. A Drivers of Local Surge chart from the XAI can help clear up the forecast by coloring the impact of each station: green for Baiyappanahalli, where a recent surge in arrivals is causing a future crowd, and red for Mysuru Road, where a lack of incoming traffic is reducing the overall risk.

3. **Transitioning from Predictive to Prescriptive Analytics:**

The last frontier for metro analytics is the creation of a Prescriptive Engine that takes numerical predictions and turns them into actual operational interventions. Future research should extend the ability to predict “Total Flow” to create a logic-based or learning-based response strategy. This includes:

- Dynamic management of entry control to prevent over-capacity issues.
- Optimized management of additional service opportunities between key pairs.
- Adaptive management of vertical movements to prioritize these during peak times.

Future research should use the three-pillar framework to advance from “black-box” deep learning techniques to explainable, prescriptive operational intelligence.

IX. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the recent advancements in deep learning techniques, such as Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional Networks and Federated Learning, have changed the urban rail transport landscape from 2020 to 2025. The techniques have enhanced the accuracy of prediction by 37-39%, thus offering the possibility of reducing congestion and waiting times by 14-21%. Even though there are challenges in interpreting the results of the model and generalization of the model for different cities, the three-pillar framework bridges the gap between “black-box” techniques and explainable, prescriptive techniques.

REFERENCES

1. Yuan, Y., Li, S., Liu, R., Yang, L., & Gao, Z. (2023). Decomposition and approximate dynamic programming approach to optimization of train timetable and skip-stop plan for metro networks. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 157, 104393.
2. Yang, Y., Zhu, Y., Xu, Y., Li, T., & Sun, W. (2022). A train frequency optimization model for the joint operation with two intersecting metro lines. *IEEE Access*, 10, 12365-12373.
3. Liang, J., Lyu, G., Teo, C. P., & Gao, Z. (2023). Online passenger flow control in metro lines. *Operations Research*, 71(2), 768-775.

4. Wang, X., Bai, W., Meng, Z., Xin, B., Gao, R., & Lv, X. (2023). The prediction of flow in railway station based on RRC-STGCN. *IEEE Access*, 11, 131128-131139.
5. Wang, B., Ye, M., Zhu, Z., Li, Y., Liang, Q., & Zhang, J. (2020). Short-term passenger flow prediction for urban rail stations using learning network based on optimal passenger flow information input algorithm. *IEEE Access*, 8, 170742-170753.
6. Zhang, J., Chen, F., Cui, Z., Guo, Y., & Zhu, Y. (2020). Deep learning architecture for short-term passenger flow forecasting in urban rail transit. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 22(11), 7004-7014.
7. Sha, S., Li, J., Zhang, K., Yang, Z., Wei, Z., Li, X., & Zhu, X. (2020).
8. RNN-based subway passenger flow rolling prediction. *IEEE Access*, 8, 15232-15240.
9. Zhang, J., Che, H., Chen, F., Ma, W., & He, Z. (2021). Short-term origin-destination demand prediction in urban rail transit systems: A channel-wise attentive split-convolutional neural network method. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 124, 102928.
10. Zhang, J., Chen, F., Guo, Y., & Li, X. (2020). Multi-graph convolutional network for short-term passenger flow forecasting in urban rail transit. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 14(10), 1210-1217.
11. Hou, Z., Du, Z., Yang, G., & Yang, Z. (2022). Short-term passenger flow prediction of urban rail transit based on a combined deep learning model. *Applied Sciences*, 12(15), 7597.
12. Zhao, Y., Ma, Z., Yang, Y., Jiang, W., & Jiang, X. (2020). Short-term passenger flow prediction with decomposition in urban railway systems. *IEEE Access*, 8, 107876-107886.
13. Liao, K., & Zhou, W. (2023). An ewt-ensemblstm-lssa model for metro passengers volume prediction. *IEEE Access*, 11, 92188-92199.
14. Tang, Y., Shang, Q., & Yin, L. (2024). A Novel Hybrid Model for Short-Term Traffic Flow Prediction Based on Spatio-Temporal Deep Learning With Considering Associated Factors Selection. *IEEE Access*, 12, 128215-128234.
15. Zhao, X., Li, C., Zou, X., Du, X., & Ismail, A. (2024). Passenger flow prediction for rail transit stations based on an improved SSA-LSTM model. *Mathematics*, 12(22), 3556.
16. Xie, P., Ma, M., Li, T., Ji, S., Du, S., Yu, Z., & Zhang, J. (2023).
17. Spatio-temporal dynamic graph relation learning for urban metro flow prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 35(10), 9973-9984.
18. Li, P., Wang, S., Zhao, H., Yu, J., Hu, L., Yin, H., & Liu, Z. (2023).
19. IG-Net: An interaction graph network model for metro passenger flow forecasting. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 24(4), 4147-4157.
20. Shi, B., Wang, Z., Yan, J., Yang, Q., & Yang, N. (2024). A novel spatial-temporal deep learning method for metro flow prediction considering external factors and periodicity. *Applied Sciences*, 14(5), 1949.
21. Wang, J., Zhang, Y., Wei, Y., Hu, Y., Piao, X., & Yin, B. (2021). Metro passenger flow prediction via dynamic hypergraph convolution networks. *IEEE transactions on intelligent transportation systems*, 22(12), 7891-7903.
22. Li, D., Cao, J., Li, R., & Wu, L. (2020). A spatio-temporal structured LSTM model for short-term prediction of origin-destination matrix in rail transit with multisource data. *IEEE Access*, 8, 84000-84019.
23. Yang, J., Dong, X., & Jin, S. (2020). Metro passenger flow prediction model using attention-based neural network. *IEEE Access*, 8, 30953-30959.

24. Huang, H., Mao, J., Liu, R., Lu, W., Tang, T., & Liu, L. (2024).
25. MTLMetro: A deep multi-task learning model for metro passenger demands prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 25(9), 11805-11820.
26. Zhang, T., He, X., Wang, Y., Xu, Y., Wu, R., Wang, Z., & Tong, Y. (2025, August). FedMetro: Efficient Metro Passenger Flow Prediction via Federated Graph Learning. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining V. 2* (pp. 5215-5224).
28. Liu, Y., Chen, B., Zheng, Y., Cheng, L., Li, G., & Lin, L. (2025). ODMixer: Fine-grained Spatial-temporal MLP for metro Origin-Destination prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*.
29. Sun, J., Ye, X., Yan, X., Wang, T., & Chen, J. (2025). Multi-Step Peak Passenger Flow Prediction of Urban Rail Transit Based on Multi-Station Spatio-Temporal Feature Fusion Model. *Systems*, 13(2), 96.
30. Lu, W., Xu, J., Zhang, Y., Wang, T., & Li, P. (2023). MOHP-EC: A multiobjective hierarchical prediction framework for urban rail transit passenger flow. *IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine*, 15(4), 86-105.

A Comprehensive Survey on Federated and Resilient Intelligence for UAV Swarm Coordination and Target Tracking

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Abstract—Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) swarm systems have been identified as an innovative technology for implementing large-scale autonomous systems, including surveillance, disaster response, environmental monitoring, and military applications. The complexity of these applications has led to intelligent coordination, efficient communication, and decision-making processes among multiple UAV systems. Recent developments in distributed intelligence, federated learning, and multi-agent reinforcement learning have facilitated collaborative learning and coordination for UAV swarm systems while considering data privacy and efficient communication.

This paper provides a comprehensive survey of recent research developments in intelligent UAV swarm systems using federated and resilient intelligence methodologies. This survey focuses on various methodologies and techniques used for UAV swarm coordination and target tracking, including distributed coordination algorithms, federated learning methodologies, reinforcement learning-based decision-making processes, and resilience techniques for fault tolerance and security. Additionally, it provides an overview of various communication constraints, heterogeneous mission environments, and research gaps for developing intelligent UAV swarm systems. Finally, it highlights various research challenges and opportunities for designing intelligent UAV swarm systems.

Index Terms—UAV swarms, Federated learning, Swarm intelligence, Multi-agent, Target tracking, Distributed coordination, Reinforcement learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) swarms have been recognized as an emerging and potentially revolutionary concept in the development of the next generation of autonomous UAVs. Compared to conventional single UAV-based architectures, UAV swarms-based systems can potentially offer enhanced coverage, redundancy, scalability, and flexibility in terms of operation and functionality [1], [30]. Thus, UAV swarms have gained considerable attention and interest in terms of their applications in defense surveillance, disaster response, border control, environment monitoring, and infrastructure inspection, among others. Earlier foundational studies on UAV swarm coordination primarily focused on centralized control strategies, formation control, and consensus-based approaches developed before 2020. These studies established the fundamental principles of swarm coordination but lacked scalability and robustness required for modern heterogeneous mission environments. Traditionally, UAV swarms-based systems have employed conventional centralized control-based approaches, in which global decision-making and task allocation are typically carried out using a ground control station or a centralized server. Even though centralized control-based approaches can potentially simplify UAV swarms-based system management and coordination, several limitations and constraints can also arise in this

context, such as communication constraints, increased latency, and scalability limitations, among others, especially in scenarios where the number of UAVs is high or the complexity of the mission is high. To address the above mentioned limitations, recent studies have shown increased interest in distributed and decentralized approaches of intelligence mechanisms. In this regard, federated learning (FL) is found to be one of the prominent collaborative approaches of machine learning that allows multiple UAV agents to learn a unified model without sharing raw data between them [2], [4], [7]. This is because FL allows UAV agents to share model updates instead of raw data during collaborative learning, which reduces the overhead of information sharing and maintains privacy during mission execution in heterogeneous mission environments. Although recent studies have shown increased interest in developing UAV-based distributed intelligence approaches, developing robust swarm coordination techniques with FL for reliable target tracking is still a challenging task. This is because UAVs often experience dynamic topological changes, adversarial attacks, node failures, synchronization issues, and stringent energy constraints during mission execution in heterogeneous mission environments. In addition, major advancements have been made in various domains, e.g., multi-agent reinforcement learning, consensus algorithms, adaptive tracking, and secure aggregation [17], [21], [27]. However, it is observed that many of these works address coordination, tracking, federated learning, and robustness as separate research domains. As a result, a holistic understanding of these interactions among these domains for UAV swarms is limited. Hence, this paper aims to propose a comprehensive survey of federated and robust intelligence for UAV swarms' coordination and target tracking. To be more specific, it covers centralized and decentralized UAV swarms, federated learning integration,

robustness and security, communication limitations, and research gaps. Overall, it is expected that this paper would present a systematic methodology for developing robust and intelligent UAV swarms for heterogeneous mission scenarios.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Centralized and Distributed UAV Swarm Architectures

Swarm coordination architectures have developed from a centralized command structure into a distributed and mixed structure. Past swarm systems using UAVs were primarily based on a centralized controller structure, where the ground station or the leader UAV was responsible for global trajectory planning and task allocation. However, despite the benefits associated with a centralized structure, where the swarm is provided with a unified awareness picture, the structure is not appropriate for large-scale systems [1], [14]. As illustrated in Fig. 1, federated learning enables UAV agents to collaboratively train models while preserving data privacy and reducing communication overhead.

Research on swarm systems has increasingly emphasized the need for distributed and decentralized control strategies. Distributed formation control and consensus-based navigation strategies allow the swarm agents, such as the UAVs, to make decisions based on the neighborhood information [23]. Evaluation studies on centralized, decentralized, and federated reinforcement learning-based swarm control strategies showed the superiority of decentralized strategies [14]. Simulation-driven evaluations highlight the adaptability benefits of decentralized swarm systems, as discussed in the context of the paper [5]. However, decentralized coordination poses issues that include synchronization stability, convergence, and conflicts. Overall, literature trends suggest that there has been a significant shift from rigid centralized control to hybrid

control structures that incorporate global control with decentralized control, especially for mission-critical swarm robotic systems.

B. Target Tracking Techniques in UAV Swarms

Target tracking can be considered an important functional goal for UAV swarms, especially for surveillance, monitoring, and defense missions. Classical target tracking solutions employ model-based estimation and cooperative navigation techniques to ensure continuous target tracking. A fault-tolerant cooperative navigation solution has shown promising results for improving the reliability of the solution, especially for mission-critical tasks such as forest fire monitoring [19]. With the advancement of reinforcement learning, deep reinforcement learning-based solutions for UAV trajectory optimization and cooperative target tracking have attracted significant research focus [10], [25]. MARL-based solutions can help UAV swarms learn adaptive coordination policies to ensure effective target tracking, coverage, and collision avoidance. Graph-based reinforcement learning solutions can further improve the efficiency of the UAV coordination process, especially for UAV swarms, by modeling the relationships between UAVs and the communication topology between them [21]. Despite the promising results obtained using reinforcement learning-based solutions, the stability, scalability, and feasibility of the solution for UAV swarms remain significant challenges. Ensuring the robustness of the solution to environmental uncertainty and communication disruptions remains a critical issue for ensuring effective target tracking

C. Federated Learning in UAV Swarm Intelligence

Federated learning has been identified as one of the fundamental solutions for the development of the concept of distributed intelligence for UAV swarms. In the early

stages, the possibility of utilizing federated learning-based multi-UAV networks for minimizing the dependence on centralized data was established [2]. Subsequent research has focused on the development of decentralized federated learning structures for UAV networks, including the minimization of communication overhead and the maximization of the efficiency of collaborative training [4], [7]. The development of hierarchical federated learning structures, as well as joint training-resource allocation optimization, has been proposed for the improvement of the scalability and stability of the convergence of the learning process for UAV swarms [8], [9]. Heterogeneous federated reinforcement learning has been proposed for the extension of the capabilities of federated learning for UAV networks, including the handling of the heterogeneity of the computing capabilities of the UAVs [20]. The development of distributed machine learning frameworks, including the integration of sensing, communication, and semantic processing, has highlighted the extension of the scope of federated learning for UAV networks. Despite the significant developments, the issue of communication latency, synchronization, and the presence of adversarial model updates pose significant research challenges.

D. Resilience and Fault Tolerance in UAV Swarm Systems

Resilience plays a vital role in the operation of UAV swarms in adversary and uncertain environments. Fault-tolerant navigation techniques can provide swarm intelligence systems with operation stability in the presence of node failure and communication disruption [19]. However, the inclusion of resilience in federated learning-based coordination poses additional complexities. Security-oriented research has highlighted the susceptibility of UAV swarm networks to DoS attacks, model poisoning, and adversarial manipulations.

Federated multi-agent defense techniques have been proposed to tackle security threats in UAV swarm intelligence systems [17]. Detailed security and privacy challenges in federated-based UAV swarm intelligence systems have been analyzed to highlight the importance of secure federated learning and trust management [22]. Intelligent blecting surfaces and 6G- based drone networks are recent technologies that can provide additional resilience and security challenges to UAV swarm in- telligence systems [16]. Although recent research has focused on providing secure and fault-tolerant techniques for federated- based UAV swarm intelligence systems, the development of a completely integrated resilient federated swarm intelligence system remains a research challenge.

Fig. 1. Conceptual architecture of federated learning-enabled UAV swarm coordination.

E. Communication Constraints and Heterogeneous Mission Environments

For UAV swarms, communication constraints and heterogeneous environments are critical challenges when the UAVs are deployed in a real-world mission environment, compared to a controlled laboratory environment. In a real-world environment, the communication constraints affect the coordination of UAVs, federated aggregation, and the performance of the real-time target tracking. Many research studies have addressed the issue of communication constraints for a

multi-UAV swarm by using a decentralized and federated structure for the UAV swarm [2], [4], [7], [26]. In the decentralized structure, hierarchical and heterogeneous aggregation techniques have also been proposed for the UAV swarm, which reduce the synchronization delays while ensuring the convergence of the federated model [8], [9]. Communication-efficient learning for the UAV swarm is a critical issue, which needs more research. For the heterogeneous environments, the UAV swarm nodes have different capabilities, such as computation, sensing, and energy resources, which affect the UAV swarm structure and the federated reinforcement learning mechanisms for the UAV swarm [12], [13], [20]. In the heterogeneous environments, the UAV swarm structure also uses heterogeneous aggregation techniques, which balance the federated reinforcement learning for the UAV swarm, considering the energy resources of the UAV swarm nodes [11], [15], [29]. Additionally, the presence of mission-specific constraints such as urban signal obstruction, disaster zone interference, and adversarial conditions on the battlefield requires robust communication protocol designs and topology adaptation techniques. New research on over-the-air federated learning and digital twin-based UAV networks has been proposed to resolve the synchronization and scalability challenges [3]. While significant advances have been achieved in federated intelligence for UAV swarms, the problem of achieving full scalability and communication efficiency remains an open research issue.

III. RESEARCH GAP IDENTIFICATION

Despite the vast research efforts put forth on UAV swarm coordination, federated learning, and resilient control methodologies, certain research gaps have been identified in this field. First and foremost, research in this domain has been identified to be partially isolated in areas such as coordination control,

target tracking, and federated learning [1], [2], [4]. A unified platform that effectively combines decentralized coordination and decision-making through federated learning under heterogeneous mission constraints is

still in its evolving phase. Secondly, although the implementation of federated learning has been shown to improve data privacy and collaborative

Table I: Summary of Representative Studies on Uavswarm Coordination and FeDerated Intelligence

Ref	Technique Used	Application Area	Evaluation Setting	Key Contribution	Limitations
[1]	Distributed Formation Control	UAV Swarm Coordination	Survey	Scalable decentralized coordination strategies	Limited fault tolerance mechanisms
[2]	Federated Learning	UAV Network Intelligence	Simulation-based	Collaborative model training without sharing raw data	Communication latency and synchronization issues
[4]	Decentralized Federated Learning	Multi-UAV Systems	Simulation-based	Reduced communication overhead in swarm learning	Synchronization and aggregation challenges
[7]	Hierarchical Federated Learning	UAV Networks	Simulation-based	Improved scalability and stability for large swarms	Increased aggregation complexity
[10]	Reinforcement Learning	UAV Battlefield Operations	Simulation-based	Adaptive swarm coordination in dynamic environments	High computational requirements
[17]	Multi-Agent Defense Mechanisms	UAV Security	Simulation-based	Protection against adversarial attacks in UAV networks	Limited real-world validation
[21]	Graph Reinforcement Learning	Swarm Optimization	Simulation-based	Topology-aware coordination learning models	Training instability in large networks
[23]	Consensus-Based Control	Distributed UAV Swarms	Experimental validation	Robust decentralized coordination framework	Communication dependency
[27]	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning	Target Tracking	Simulation-based	Fault-tolerant cooperative tracking framework	Scalability constraints in large swarms
[30]	Survey Study	UAV Swarm Systems	Survey	Comprehensive analysis of swarm intelligence methods	Lack of integrated coordination framework

Learning in UAV swarms, certain models have been identified to operate in a synchronized manner without considering the effect of intermittent connectivity and topology changes on model convergence [7], [9], [26]. Lastly, although certain research efforts have been made to improve fault-tolerant navigation and decision-making through resilient control and federated learning, these have been identified to operate in isolation from one another [17], [19], [22]. Moreover, validation beyond simulation environments is also limited on a large scale [5], [30]. Many frameworks are validated in controlled experimental environments. Finally, energy-aware optimization and capability adaptation of diverse capabilities, although gaining increased attention [11], [15], [29], do not have standardized frameworks to evaluate trade-offs between accuracy, latency, robustness, and energy efficiency. Achieving robust and scalable swarm intelligence for UAVs will thus require an interdisciplinary approach to distributed control theory, federated optimization techniques, secure communication protocol design, and adaptive resource management.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This section briefly describes the prevailing methodologies used by the literature for the intelligent coordination and target tracking of UAV swarm systems. The literature review indicates that the researchers have used distributed learning methodologies, reinforcement learning techniques, and control methodologies for addressing the intelligent coordination and target tracking of UAV swarm systems.

A. Federated Learning-Based Intelligence

Federated learning (FL) has been recognized as one of the prominent methodologies for the intelligent coordination and target tracking of UAV swarm systems. The

literature indicates that federated learning-based methodologies have been used for the intelligent coordination and target tracking of UAV swarm systems without the need for centralizing the data. The researchers have proposed various federated learning-based methodologies for the intelligent coordination and target tracking of UAV swarm systems. The proposed methodologies have been used for the heterogeneous resource management and heterogeneous target tracking of UAV swarm systems. The researchers have proposed various federated learning-based methodologies for the intelligent coordination and target tracking of UAV swarm systems [2], [4], [7]–[9], [20], [26]. Recent studies have further extended FL with heterogeneous resource management and adaptivity aggregation features to accommodate dynamic swarm scenarios.

B. Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning

Another prominent methodology used to facilitate cooperative decision-making in UAV swarms is multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL). MARL-based frameworks enable multiple UAV agents to learn optimal policies for trajectory planning, formation control, and target tracking through iterative interaction with the environment. These frameworks are useful in facilitating adaptability in dynamic scenarios such as surveillance and disaster response. Recent studies have used deep reinforcement learning techniques, including policy gradient learning and graph reinforcement learning, to optimize the performance of cooperative tracking and swarm coordination [10], [21], [25], [27]. However, there are still challenges in terms of training stability.

C. Distributed Coordination and Control Algorithms

Distributed control algorithms represent the primary methodology for ensuring the overall coordinated nature of the swarm system.

Traditional control methodologies, such as the leader-follower model, consensus control, and formation control, have been used to enable the UAV swarm system to coordinate with each other based on the exchange of local information. The distributed optimal control and formation management methodologies have been studied to enhance the overall scalability and fault-tolerant nature of the UAV swarm system [1], [5], [14], [23].

D. Resilience and Security Mechanisms

Considering the overall vulnerable nature of the UAV swarm system, various researchers have proposed different methodologies to enhance the overall resilience and security of the system. Fault-tolerant navigation and adversarial security mechanisms have been proposed for ensuring the overall stability of the UAV swarm system [17], [19], [22]. Secure communication mechanisms and trust-based UAV swarm systems have also been proposed for addressing the overall model poisoning and denial of service attacks in the federated UAV swarm system.

E. Communication and Resource Optimization

Communication efficiency and resource constraints are considered major limitations of large-scale UAV swarms. To overcome these limitations of communication and resource efficiency, researchers have proposed resource-aware federated learning, gradient sparsification, and communication scheduling mechanisms [11], [15], [29]. From the above literature review, it is evident that there are various methodological components of modern UAV swarm intelligence frameworks, and these components combine different theories and concepts of distributed control theory, federated learning, and reinforcement learning.

V. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

From the analysis of the reviewed works, it is evident that some key trends are emerging in

the development of intelligent UAV swarm systems. First of all, it is evident that researchers are shifting focus from centralized control approaches to decentralized and distributed approaches in UAV swarm systems. In earlier approaches to UAV swarm systems, centralized control and leader-follower approaches were dominant. However, in recent works on UAV swarm systems, distributed approaches are gaining much attention and are being explored as a potential approach for developing UAV swarm systems in which UAVs are able to make independent decisions based on local information while ensuring mission objectives are collectively fulfilled [1], [14], [23]. Secondly another key approach that is gaining much attention in UAV swarm systems is federated learning as a potential approach for developing collaborative intelligence between UAVs in UAV swarm systems. This is because federated learning enables UAVs in swarm systems to learn and share information without having to share raw data, thus reducing overhead and ensuring privacy preservation in UAV swarm systems, especially in heterogeneous UAV systems in which resources are scarce. Third, reinforcement learning and multi-agent reinforcement learning approaches have emerged as prominent techniques for facilitating adaptive decision-making in dynamic mission scenarios. These learning-based techniques are highly effective in enabling UAV swarms to learn and optimize trajectory planning, formation control, and target tracking strategies through continuous interaction with the environment [21], [25], [27]. However, several studies have also identified some of the challenges and complexities involved in training and computational overheads of these techniques for swarm UAVs. Additionally significant observation is that UAV swarm systems are increasingly being recognized as a key component of resilient and secure systems.

Researchers are increasingly focusing on developing fault-tolerant navigation techniques and robust UAV swarm systems and secure communication protocols for ensuring robust UAV swarm systems and operations in dynamic and uncertain scenarios [17], [19], [22]. These techniques are highly critical and significant for mission-critical applications such as disaster relief and surveillance operations. Finally, it is observed that most of the existing studies are based on simulation-based experiments and evaluations of UAV swarm systems and techniques. However, it is also observed that experiments and evaluations of UAV swarm systems are relatively few in reality.

VI. IMPLICATIONS

The results of this survey indicate that the role of distributed intelligence in facilitating scalable and reliable UAV swarm systems will continue to grow. The adoption of federated learning and multi-agent reinforcement learning indicates that there will be a continued move towards distributed decision-making paradigms that do not rely on centralized infrastructure. Such a move will have critical implications for the deployment of UAV systems in realistic environments that have limited communication resources. For mission-critical applications like disaster relief, environmental monitoring, and surveillance for military purposes, reliable swarm intelligence paradigms will be critical in improving the efficiency of mission execution. The adoption of federated learning will be critical in allowing multiple UAV agents to collectively learn decision-making models without having to share raw data. In addition, the adoption of reinforcement learning will be critical in allowing UAV swarms to dynamically adjust to mission environments that can be highly dynamic and uncertain. Such paradigms will be critical in allowing intelligent autonomous systems to be deployed in realistic environments.

VII. LIMITATIONS

Although this survey provides a comprehensive overview of federated intelligence and resilient intelligence in UAV swarm systems, there are some limitations to this research. First, the research in this survey has primarily relied on studies published between 2020 and 2026. Although this covers recent developments in the field, there may be some lack of discussion about the basic studies conducted before that. Second, in most studies discussed in this research, the validation of the proposed methods has been conducted using simulations. In this regard, the implementation difficulties that may be faced in the actual world may not have been considered in the studies. Third, in most studies discussed in this research, the experiments conducted to validate the proposed methods have been conducted with different swarm sizes. Although this highlights the need for benchmarking the proposed methods for UAV swarm systems, it makes comparisons with the proposed methods in this research difficult.

VIII. FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

The research focus for the future should be on developing unified frameworks for integrating federated learning, reinforcement learning, and coordination mechanisms for UAV swarms. Such unified architectures may enable more collaborative and efficient interactions among UAV agents, ensuring scalability and robustness of UAV swarms. The other research focus for the future is improving communication efficiency and energy management for federated UAV networks. Developing lightweight aggregation mechanisms and edge computing-based coordination mechanisms for UAV swarms may reduce communication overhead and increase mission endurance. Furthermore, there is a need for more research focus on experimental validation of UAV swarm intelligence frameworks. Experimental

validation of UAV swarms is essential for ensuring robustness, scalability, and reliability of UAV swarms. Lastly, addressing security and privacy concerns for federated UAV networks is a critical research focus for the future. Future research should focus on developing robust defense mechanisms for UAV swarms against adversarial attacks, model poisoning attacks, and communication attacks. One important direction for future research is the real-world experimental validation of UAV swarm intelligence frameworks using physical drone testbeds. For example, a small-scale UAV swarm can be deployed in controlled outdoor environments such as agricultural fields or disaster response scenarios to evaluate coordination efficiency, communication reliability, and fault tolerance under real-world constraints. Such experimental validation would help bridge the gap between simulation-based results and practical deployment.

IX. CONCLUSION

This paper provided a detailed survey of federated intelligence and resilient intelligence solutions for the coordination of UAV swarms and target tracking. The survey discussed the recent research developments in the distributed coordination of UAV swarms, federated intelligence solutions for coordination, reinforcement learning-based decision-making systems for UAV swarms, and the concept of resilience in the context of UAV swarms. From the research developments discussed in this survey, there is a clear trend towards developing distributed intelligence solutions for the coordination of UAV swarms. Although there have been considerable research developments in this area, there are still several challenges to be solved in the context of communication efficiency, security resilience, and scalability. By combining the research methodologies and findings of various research studies in the field of UAV swarms, this survey provides insights into the recent technological

trends in the development of intelligent systems for the coordination of UAV swarms.

REFERENCES

1. Y. Bu, Y. Yan, and Y. Yang, "Advancement challenges in UAV swarm formation control: A comprehensive review," *Drones*, vol. 8, no. 7, 2024.
2. H. Zhang and L. Hanzo, "Federated learning assisted multi-UAV networks," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 14104–14109, 2020.
3. C. Shang, D. T. Hoang, M. Hao, D. Niyato, and J. Yu, "Energy-efficient decentralized federated learning for UAV swarm with spiking neural networks and leader election mechanism," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 2742–2746, 2024.
4. Y. Qu et al., "Decentralized federated learning for UAV networks: Architecture, challenges, and opportunities," *IEEE Network*, vol. 35, no.6, pp. 156–162, 2022.
5. D. Marek et al., "Swarm of drones in a simulation environment—efficiency and adaptation," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 9, 2024.
6. H. Li et al., "Self-adaptive clustering based federated learning scheme in UAV swarm network," in *Proc. ICECAI*, 2025.
7. Y. Xiao et al., "Fully decentralized federated learning-based on-board mission for UAV swarm system," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol.25, no. 10, pp. 3296–3300, 2021.
8. Y. Shen et al., "Joint training and resource allocation optimization for federated learning in UAV swarm," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2272–2284, 2022.
9. T. Wang et al., "UAV swarm-assisted two-tier hierarchical federated learning," *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*, vol.11, no. 1, pp. 943–956, 2023.

10. S. T. Lin et al., “Battlefield applications of drone swarms based on proximal policy optimization reinforcement learning,” in *Proc. IEEE ICCBE*, 2025.
11. C. Zhang et al., “TTBO-FL: Joint training, trajectory, and beamforming optimization for energy-efficient federated learning in UAV swarm,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 2206–2220, 2025.
12. Y. Yang et al., “Efficient UAV swarm-based multi-task federated learning with dynamic task knowledge sharing,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.09144*, 2025.
13. W. He et al., “Three-stage Stackelberg game enabled clustered federated learning in heterogeneous UAV swarms,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 72, no. 7, pp. 9366–9380, 2023.
14. M. A. Ali et al., “Benchmarking control strategies for UAV swarms: Centralized, decentralized, or federated reinforcement learning,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 2025.
15. X. Yang et al., “Adaptive UAV-assisted hierarchical federated learning: Optimizing energy, latency, and resilience for dynamic smart IoT,” *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing*, 2025.
16. A. V. Shvetsov et al., “Federated learning meets intelligent bleeding surface in drones for enabling 6G networks,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 130860–130887, 2023.
17. Y. Zhou et al., “Federated multi-agent deep reinforcement learning driven moving target defense against DoS attacks in UAV swarm networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, 2025.
18. J. Xu et al., “Federated learning powered semantic communication for UAV swarm cooperation,” *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 140–146, 2024.
19. J. Hu et al., “Fault-tolerant cooperative navigation of networked UAV swarms for forest fire monitoring,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, vol. 123, 2022.
20. P. Wang et al., “Decentralized navigation with heterogeneous federated reinforcement learning for UAV-enabled mobile edge computing,” *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 23, no. 12, pp. 13621–13638, 2024.
21. B. Hazarika et al., “Generative AI augmented graph reinforcement learning for adaptive UAV swarm optimization,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 9508–9524, 2025.
22. A. Al Farsi et al., “Privacy and security challenges in federated learning for UAV systems: A systematic review,” *IEEE Access*, 2025.
23. G. Wang, Z. Wei, and P. Li, “Distributed optimal formation control of unmanned aerial vehicles: Theory and experiments,” *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, 2024.
24. W. Lee, “Federated reinforcement learning-based UAV swarm system for aerial remote sensing,” *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2022.
25. W. Zhang et al., “Three-dimension trajectory design for multi-UAV wireless network with deep reinforcement learning,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 600–612, 2020.
26. Y. Ding et al., “Distributed machine learning for UAV swarms: Computing, sensing, and semantics,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7447–7473, 2023.
27. M. Ramezani, M. A. Amiri Atashgah, and A. Rezaee, “A fault-tolerant multi-agent reinforcement learning framework for UAV–UGV coverage path planning,” *Drones*, vol. 8, no. 10, 2024.

28. D. Rahbari et al., “Fast and fair computation offloading management in a swarm of drones using rating-based federated learning,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 113832–113849, 2021.
29. A. Asheralieva and D. Niyato, “Effective UAV-aided asynchronous decentralized federated learning with adaptive gradient sparsification,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2025.
30. S. Kumar et al., “The rise of UAV-based smart surveillance: A systematic review of trends and technologies,” *IEEE Access*, 2025.

Traffic Congestion Control in Data Centers

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Abstract—Data center network traffic congestion poses a critical threat to both performance and efficiency. With volumes of east-west traffic (server-to-server communication) skyrocketing as a result of today's distributed applications and microservices architectures, network switches and links are bogged down. The congestion creates a number of problems, some of which are quite critical, such as higher latency, packet loss, and lower throughput. As a result, application response times degrade, computational tasks are slowed, and overall quality of service (QoS) is reduced. The fact that traffic cannot be controlled means that there is inefficient use of resources, increased cost of operation, and a bad user experience, necessitating advanced congestion control and traffic engineering to support contemporary data center operations. Although QoS and CDN are the traditional ways of dealing with traffic congestion in the network, which is mainly the backbone, efficiency and latency can be improved by incorporating new techniques like artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML).

Index Terms—Traffic congestion, QoS, CDN, AI, ML etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Data center is a dedicated physical facility that organizations use to house their critical applications and data. It is a centralized repository, either physical or virtual, for the storage, management, processing, and dissemination of data and information. At its core, a data center is comprised of three main components: compute, which includes servers that provide processing power and memory; storage, which houses data on various media; and networking, which consists of routers, switches, and cables that connect the servers and link the data center to the outside world.

Traffic congestion in a computer network happens when a network node or link has so much data flowing through it that its quality of service degrades. It's like a traffic jam on the highway, but in cyberspace? When the amount of data packets transmitted over a network is more than it can carry, the network switches and routers, which are like traffic intersections, get flooded. These devices have only a limited buffer of memory to cache packets. When traffic is too heavy, these buffers overflow, and the devices begin to backlog or, worse, discard packets altogether. Quality of Service (QoS) is a collection of technologies that govern network traffic to minimize packet loss, latency, and jitter on a network. It works as a traffic management toolkit, giving users the power to give priority to certain kinds of data over others. When applied to avoiding congestion on a network, QoS is not a matter of creating more bandwidth, but of more wisely managing the available bandwidth. ????

It does this through prioritizing data packets into various categories based on their priority (e.g., video conferencing packets are placed ahead of email packets) and then applying certain rules on these categories. Some of the key mechanisms are queuing, through which critical packets are brought to the head of the line to be sent first, and bandwidth shaping, through which the bandwidth taken up by non-critical applications can be capped. By providing the mission-critical and latency-sensitive applications with the required resources, QoS efficiently blocks less important traffic from causing congestion, thus ensuring a predictable level of service and ensuring network stability and performance.

A Content Delivery Network (CDN) is a globally distributed network of proxy servers and proxy egress nodes that collaborate to deliver internet content quickly. The main purpose of a CDN is to enhance web performance by minimizing the physical distance between the server and end-user.

CDNs avoid traffic bottlenecks by caching and delivering content, including images, videos, and web pages, at various Points of Presence (PoPs) globally. When a user asks for content, the CDN forwards the request from the origin server to a server within a PoP closest to the user. This service dramatically minimizes latency since data is transmitted much shorter distances. By delivering content from the edge of the network, an offloaded CDN takes traffic off the central origin server, making it unlikely to become a bottleneck. This distributed approach significantly lowers the load on a solitary server, eases the effect of traffic surges, and provides a quicker, more stable experience for everyone.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The recent developments in data center networking have resulted in much research work in the field of traffic congestion control and Quality of Service (QoS) management. These initiatives include machine learning-driven prediction models, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) frameworks, traffic classification approaches and more exhaustive scheduling and congestion control frameworks. This part summarizes the major contributions of the existing works in thematic categories

Machine learning has been used as an effective mechanism to manage intelligent traffic within SDN-enabled data centers. Wassie et al. [1] suggested a deep learning-based model of the predictive of elephant flows through the application of clustering and autoencoders and then applying AutoML models (e.g., XGBoost and Gradient Boosting).

They were highly predictive and used explainable AI (XAI) features such as SHAP to enhance explainability.

On the same note, Xie [2] proposed a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based traffic scheduling system based on a Deep Q-Network (DQN). This is in contrast to the traditional and rigid form of routing where the routing and resource allocation strategies are learnt dynamically rather than being based on the previous network state. It was proven through experimental results that it showed better throughput, lower latency and lower rate of packet loss in a dynamic traffic environment.

Although these methods are effective, they have a number of challenges, including high computation costs, sensitivity to hyperparameter optimization, and poor deployment to the real world. By separating the control and data planes, SDN has also improved the flexibility and efficiency of traffic management vastly. Win and Mya [5] introduced a QoS-based routing scheme, which uses the optimal path, depending on the constraints of link utilization and delay, which has outperformed the traditional shortest-path routing in losses and transmission efficiency of packets.

Alshahrani and Alsmadi [6] introduced a QoS mechanism to Named Data Networking (NDN) that combines traffic shaping based on priorities and the congestion control, which provides differentiated levels of service and ensures the same stability of throughput at different network conditions.

Beshley et al. [8] went ahead to expand on this idea and proposed a Service-Oriented SDN (SOSDN) model which combines QoS and Quality of Experience (QoE). Their scheme dynamically sets flow priorities and routing decisions based on multi-criteria measures, including delay, jitter, bandwidth and packet loss. It was demonstrated by simulation results that user experience improved significantly, especially in real-time applications.

Nevertheless, SDN solutions tend to introduce complexities that control-plane overhead and scalability issues particularly in large data center setup.

To have efficient QoS routing and congestion control, proper traffic classification is necessary. Xie et al. [4] suggested the use of the Online Classification of QoS Routing (OCQR) framework that relies on the usage of the decision tree paradigm that is implemented in programmable switches (P4). The framework is capable of real-time classification without the excessive use of resources but high recall of priority traffic. Moreover, Singh and Vishesh [3] examined classification and queuing systems and web attack detection methods based on machine learning, i.e., TF-IDF and clustering. Their work lays emphasis on the need to incorporate security considerations in the course of traffic management.

Although these methods are better at the classification efficiency and real-time response, they can be constrained by the reliance on predetermined traffic patterns and training data. The issue of scheduling and queue management is very imperative in providing QoS during congestion. Kithinji [10] gave a detailed overview of scheduling algorithms, consisting of two, FIFO, and Priority Queuing (PQ), two-Fair Queuing (FQ), and one, (Weighted Fair Queuing)WFQ. The research paper concludes that hybrid methods, including the use of PQ and WFQ combination, are more effective in terms of delay, fairness, and bandwidth guarantees.

Active Queue Management (AQM) methods are also well researched. At Dhahran Ahliyya Science, Mohammed et al. [13] suggested the dynamically scheduled Dynamic Queue Random Early Detection (DQRED) algorithm, a queue occupancy-based scheduling algorithm. Their scheme enhances throughput and also minimizes the loss in packets especially real-time traffic.

In the same manner, Yousif et al. [15] have proposed a Multiple Low Latency Queuing (MLLQ) mechanism which is a fusion of strict priority queuing and weighted fair queuing to minimize the delay without causing starvation of lower priority traffic.

Regardless of these improvements, most scheduling methods find it difficult to be dynamically adjusted to traffic that is highly variable.

Different congestion control methods have been suggested to improve the performance of the network. Alarood [9] provided evidence that Differentiated Services Code Point (DSCP) is effective in prioritizing traffic and can realize large latency, jitter, and packet losses reduction in high-priority applications. Equally, Verma et al. [11] proposed a One-Way Delay (OWD)-based congestion control network that uses dynamic transmission rates according to network live conditions, and this outperforms the conventional TCP variants.

Newer traffic engineering methods like Phantom Queue-based rate enforcement, as suggested by Tahir et al. [16], are more scalable, more efficient as well as enabling more complex policy enforcement. Also, the more traditional approaches like traffic shaping via Token Bucket algorithm and Leaky Bucket algorithm are also still applicable in the regulation of bursty traffic and guaranteeing stable network behavior [17].

Nevertheless, other literature sources, including Flach et al. [12], ascertain that the traffic policing mechanisms may have adverse effects on the Quality of Experience (QoE), specifically in video streaming, and more adaptive and intelligent solutions are required.

A number of studies point at the necessity of combined structures with multiple methods. Yum et al. [7] suggested combining admission and congestion control in cluster networks and the suggested approach was shown to be better under the different network loads. In the same way, Jena et al. [14] have indicated the

shortfalls of conventional traffic control systems in realistic and self-similar traffic environments and the necessity of hybrid and adaptive designs.

On the whole, these works show that one specific approach cannot be enough to cover all the congestion control and QoS management aspects. Rather, machine learning, SDN, and enhanced scheduling methods are combined in hybrid models, which represent the most promising path

III. SYSTEM MODEL / ARCHITECTURE

A generalized system model is taken into account in order to have a clearer view of the congestion control mechanisms in the contemporary data centers. A standard data

network of a data center comprises of various interconnected switches, servers and controllers working on the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) architecture.

In this model control plane and data plane are disjointed and it provides a centralized decision making via an SDN controller. The controller will constantly check on the network conditions like link utilization, delay of packets, and level of congestion.

Traffic patterns in the network can be broadly divided into: Elephant flows (pans, big flows long lived) Latency sensitive flows (long, mouse flows). Effective management of congestion demands:

Table I: Comparative Analysis of Traffic Congestion Control Techniques In Data Centers

Approach Type	Technique	Advantages	Limitations	Use Case
Machine Learning	DRL (DQN), Deep Learning	Adaptive, predictive, intelligent	High computational cost, complex training	Dynamic traffic environments
SDN-Based Routing	QoS-aware SDN	Centralized control, flexible	Scalability issues, controller overhead	Large-scale data centers
Traffic Classification	Decision Trees (OCQR)	Fast, real-time classification	Limited to trained data patterns	Flow prioritization
Scheduling Algorithms	FIFO	Simple, low overhead	No QoS guarantee	Low traffic networks
	Priority Queuing (PQ)	Low delay for critical traffic	Starvation of low-priority traffic	Real-time applications
	Weighted Fair Queuing (WFQ)	Fair bandwidth allocation	Higher complexity	Mixed traffic environments
	Hybrid (PQ + WFQ)	Balanced performance	Increased overhead	High-performance networks
Congestion Control	DSCP	Reduces latency and jitter	Impacts low-priority traffic	Priority-based networks
	OWD-based	Accurate	Requires	IoT and real-

	Control	congestion detection	synchronization	time systems
Traffic Engineering	Traffic Shaping	Smooth traffic flow, prevents bursts	Limits peak performance	Stable network environments
Advanced Techniques	Phantom Queues	Efficient and scalable	Complex implementation	High-speed data centers

Proper classification of traffic. Real-time monitoring Adaptation routing and scheduling.

The SDN controller can use machine learning models to forecast congestion and adapt routing decisions. Moreover, QoS protocols including priority queuing, bandwidth assignment, and so on allow giving priority to urgent traffic.

This architecture allows to control traffic in data centers with intelligent, scalable and adaptive control

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EXISTING APPROACHES

A comparative study of current traffic congestion control methods reveals significant differences in performance, scalability, and adaptability. Various techniques, including machine learning, Software-Defined Networking (SDN), routing, and scheduling, provide distinct advantages and limitations.

Table I presents a detailed comparison of these techniques.

From Table I, it is evident that no single technique can address all congestion challenges. Machine learning approaches provide adaptability but introduce computational complexity, whereas traditional scheduling methods are simpler but less flexible. Hybrid approaches combining SDN, machine learning, and queue management offer the most effective solution.

V. FUTURE WORK

The study of traffic congestion control in the future should be on enhancing intelligent and dynamic systems that can be used under real-time conditions.

Key directions include:

AI deployment to support SDN in making decisions automatically. Sparsity machine learning models to minimize the computational cost. Policy validation and deployment in reality and not only in simulations. Dynamic priorities of adaptive QoS systems. Distributed traffic control edge and cloud integration.

Also, how to integrate various techniques like traffic prediction, classification and scheduling to a single framework is a problem that is still not uncovered.

Although there were critical achievements in congestion control and QoS management, a number of gaps in research can be observed based on the literature reviewed. To begin with, there are numerous machine learning-related solutions that are oriented on accuracy of prediction but do not offer real-time implementation in data center environment on the production level. Second, SDN supports centralized control whereas the problems of scalability, controller overhead, and fault tolerance cannot be considered completely. Third, the majority of the scheduling and queue management methods are independent and do not focus on integrated and unified frameworks that integrate prediction, routing, and enforcement.

Also, we do not have adaptive mechanisms that can dynamically adapt to highly dynamic

and unpredictable traffic patterns at a very low cost of computation. A lot of the available solutions are tested mostly in the simulation areas which point to the necessity of being tested in the real world. Thus, the new direction of the future research should be the development of integrated scalable and real-time intelligent schemes, that combine machine learning, SDN, and QoS schemes to reach the strong and effective traffic control in contemporary data centers.

VI. CONCLUSION

The paper provided an in-depth review of traffic congestion control and Quality of Service (QoS) management strategies in data center networks and specifically Software-Defined Networking (SDN), machine learning conditions, and advanced scheduling protocols. Eighteen research studies are analyzed, and it is evident that the earlier approach to the issue was focused on the traditional model of static and rule-based approaches and is now replaced with the adaptive and data-driven ones.

Deep learning and reinforcement learning are examples of machine learning, used in the prediction of traffic, its classification and dynamic allocation of resources. In the same line, SDN-based architectures facilitate centralized control and accommodative traffic engineering, which enhance network efficiency and provisioning of the QoS. Additional algorithms used to improve performance include scheduling and queue management e.g. Weighted Fair Queuing, Active Queue Management and hybrid methods are all used to balance between latency, throughput and fairness.

In spite of these developments, there are still scalability, computational, real-time adaptability and managing unpredictable traffic issues. Also, numerous solutions are tested in simulation, which indicates the necessity of real-life implementation and verification.

On the whole, it can be concluded that the combination of AI-based methods with SDN and QoS is a promising way to develop the data center traffic management system in the future, allowing it to be more efficient, reliable, and intelligent in its functioning.

VII. REFERENCES

1. G. Wassie, J. Ding, and Y. Wondie, "Traffic Prediction in SDN for Explainable QoS Using Deep Learning Approach," 2023.
2. B. Xie, "Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Intelligent Traffic Scheduling in Software-Defined Networks," 2025.
3. S. Singh and V. S., "QoS: Congestion and Queuing with Web Attack Detection."
4. S. Xie, G. Hu, X. Wang, C. Xing, and Y. Liu, "A Decision Tree-Based Online Traffic Classification Method for QoS Routing in Data Center Networks (OCQR)."
5. M. T. Z. Win and K. T. Mya, "QoS-aware Traffic Management in Software Defined Networking."
6. A. Alshahrani and I. Alsmadi, "A QoS Solution for NDN in the Presence of Congestion Control Mechanism," 2016.
7. K. H. Yum, E. J. Kim, C. R. Das, M. Yousif, and J. Duato, "Integrated Admission and Congestion Control for QoS Support in Clusters."
8. M. Beshley, N. Kryvinska, H. Beshley, O. Panchenko, and M. Medvetskyi, "Traffic Engineering and QoS/QoE Supporting Techniques for Emerging Service-Oriented Software-Defined Network."
9. A. A. Alarood, "Computational Overhead Across Prioritizing Bioinformatics Traffic Packet Operations by Differentiated Services Code Point (DSCP)."
10. J. Kithinji, "A Survey of Packet Scheduling Congestion Control Algorithms in Internet Protocol Storage Area Networks."
11. L. P. Verma, G. Kumar, O. I. Khalaf, W.-K. Wong, A.A. Hamad, and S. S. Rawat, "Adaptive Congestion Control in IoT

- Networks: Leveraging One-Way Delay for Enhanced Performance.”
12. T. Flach, P. Papageorge, A. Terzis, L. D. Pedrosa, Y. Cheng, T. Karim, E. Katz-Bassett, and R. Govindan, “An Internet-Wide Analysis of Traffic Policing.”
 13. H. Mohammed, G. Attiya, and S. El-Dolil, “Active Queue Management for Congestion Control: Performance Evaluation, New Approach, and Comparative Study.”
 14. A. K. Jena, A. Popescu, P. Pruthi, and A. Erramilli, “Traffic Control in ATM Networks: Engineering Impacts of Realistic Traffic Processes.”
 15. M. Yousif, I. A. A. Abdelrahman, and M. A. H. Abbas, “Improving QoS for Real-time Traffic using Multiple Low Latency Queueing Scheduling Mechanisms.”
 16. A. Tahir, P. Goyal, I. Marinos, M. Evans, and R. Mittal, “Efficient Policy-Rich Rate Enforcement with PhantomQueues.”
 17. A. Swetha, C. Arun Kumar, D. Prashanth, V. Indrani, and C. Ramya, “Navigating Network Currents with Traffic Shaping.”

Multimodal Emotion Recognition with Cross- Attention Fusion and LLM-Driven Context-Aware Reasoning

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Abstract—Emotion recognition in video-based conversations is difficult because humans use various channels to convey their emotions, such as facial expressions, speech, and text. Most of the existing systems used only one channel, which resulted in suboptimal performance. To address this issue, the proposed system uses a combination of audio, text, and visual channels to offer a more comprehensive emotion recognition solution. For feature extraction, pre-trained models are employed: Wav2Vec 2.0 for audio, BERT for text, and ResNet-50 for facial expressions. The extracted features are projected into a common representation space and combined using a cross-attention mechanism, enabling the channels to complement each other. Additionally, LLaMA is used for context-aware reasoning, enabling the system to better understand the conversation context. The model was tested on the MELD dataset and showed 47.64% accuracy with a 38.04% weighted F1-score, outperforming the unimodal models. To address the class imbalance problem, a weighted loss function is used, and the system is developed to be robust even when some channels are not available. To make the system more practical, a Windows-based desktop application is implemented that can run efficiently on a standard CPU without the need for any additional hardware.

Keywords—Multimodal emotion recognition (MER), Deep Learning, Cross-attention fusion, MELD dataset, LLM and LLaMA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human emotions are typically represented by several signs at the same time. When a person is feeling happy, angry, or sad, it is not expressed only through facial expressions or only through voice. It is expressed through facial expressions, voice, words, and even body language at the same time [6], [8]. However, most conventional emotion recognition models analyze only one type of sign at a time, such as video, audio, or text alone. Consequently, they are unable to grasp the whole information that can be used to enhance the accuracy of the model. In reality, humans use all these signs together to understand the emotional state of a person, so analyzing only one source of information can lead to a decrease in the accuracy of emotion recognition models [1], [2], [3], [6].

Multimodal emotion recognition [1], [2], [3], [6] has recently received considerable attention because of its applications in the healthcare sector, education sector, customer service sector, and intelligent virtual assistants. Models that have the capability of recognizing the emotional state of the user can respond in a more adaptive and context-aware way, thus improving human-computer interaction.

In recent times, the efficiency of deep learning models has been proven in the multimodal emotion recognition field. Pre-

trained models like BERT [8], Wav2Vec 2.0 [10], and ResNet-50 [14] can be employed for effective feature extraction of text, speech, and image modalities. The major problem in the field of emotion recognition is the efficient combination of all the modes. For better combination and contextual understanding, the LLaMA [16] model is used for context-aware reasoning to enhance the accuracy of the proposed system.

Fig. 1. Diagrammatic representation of the MER system

A. Motivation and Background

Emotion recognition [6] has recently become a prominent area of research because of its applications in the areas of healthcare, customer service, education, and intelligent virtual assistants. Emotion-recognizing systems have the ability to offer more adaptive and context-aware responses to the user [16], thus improving overall human-computer interaction.

Human emotions are expressed through multiple channels such as facial expressions, speech, and text [1], [2], [3], [6]. However, early emotion recognition systems were primarily based on one of these modalities. This resulted in the systems being less accurate in terms of emotion recognition because they were dependent on a single source of information. This is why multimodal systems, which incorporate visual, audio, and text data, are significant in the field of emotion recognition.

B. Problem Statement

Despite the recent advancements, there are still some limitations in the existing emotion recognition systems, especially when they are unimodal. Unimodal systems are prone to various real-world issues like background noise, lighting, and occlusion, and they also lack the knowledge of other vital modalities. Therefore, they only offer a partial insight into the emotional state of a human being.

To address this issue, the proposed system uses audio, visual, and text modalities altogether in a single framework. However, due to the differences in the nature of the various modalities, it is a challenging task to align and combine them. The system uses structured multimodal fusion and incorporates LLaMA [16] to reason in a contextually aware manner, enabling it to understand the emotions in the context of the overall conversation and deal with the conflicting information present in the various modalities.

Another critical issue is the class imbalance problem in real-world datasets, where some classes, like the "neutral" emotion, are more frequent than others. This can cause bias in the model towards the majority classes. Necessary techniques are therefore used to handle the issue and ensure balanced performance of the model across all the emotion classes.

C. Contributions

Our research makes several important contributions to the field of multimodal emotion recognition [1], [2], [3], [6]:

- Unimodal encoders: Three different encoders were developed for processing audio, text, and visual inputs separately. Each of these encoders has the capability of performing emotion recognition independently, with an accuracy of 35% to 43%. This indicates that each modality is providing valuable emotional information even before fusion.
- Cross-attention fusion architecture [6]: A

bidirectional cross-attention mechanism [6] is proposed to enable audio, text, and visual features to interact with each other. Through the discovery of relationships between different modalities, the model is able to provide more informative features, thus improving the performance of emotion recognition.

- **Deployment-ready system:** A lightweight Windows desktop application was built for real-world applications. The system is capable of running on a CPU and does not need GPU support.
- **Performance insights:** An error analysis was conducted to investigate the confusion between different classes of emotions, providing insights into model weaknesses and areas for improvement.

II. LITERATURE STUDY

A. Emotional speech databases

TABLE I recorded the datasets, emotions, and modalities of the 06 studies that were selected.

Among the most well-known datasets are

Table I. Comparative Overview of Databases, Emotion Categories, and Modalities Utilized in Selected Six Mer Studies

<i>Data sets</i>	<i>Emotions</i>	<i>Modalities</i>
DAIC-WOZ, CMDC [5]	Depressive emotional states	Audio
IEMOCAP, EMO-DB [7]	Anger, Happiness, Sadness, Neutral, Fear, Boredom, Disgust	Audio
DEAP_dataset (Physiological signal) [9]	Arousal (intensity of emotion) and Valence (positive or negative)	Electrooculogram (EOG), Photoplethysmogram (PPG)
IEMOCAP, EMO-DB, RAVDESS, TESS, MSP-Podcast, NSSD (Novel Sindh-Speech Emotion Dataset), Persian ESD, DEMoS, CHEAVD 2.0 [10]	Anger, Fear, Guilt, Sadness, Surprise, Happiness, Disgust, Neutral, Valence, Arousal, and Dominance	Audio, Text, Visual, EEG, Physiological Signals.
IEMOCAP, MELD [6]	Happiness, Sadness, Anger, Neutral, Excitement, and Frustration	Audio, Text and Video.
DAIC-WOZ, E-DAIC, AVEC, MODMA, D-Vlog, SH2-FS [8]	Depressed (MDD - Major Depressive Disorder) and Non-depressed.	Audio, Text and Video.

RAVDESS and IEMOCAP [10], which are often cited in research studies due to the comprehensive emotional labeling and the inclusion of both audio and visual data.

Other well-known datasets include EMO-DB [7], a German-language database often cited in emotion recognition studies, MELD [6], and TESS [10], which includes emotional speech recordings of elderly English-speaking people.

The DEAP datasets [9] include physiological signals, this is an extremely effective dataset to test and emotions thought signals. DAIC-WOZ and CMDC [5] include depressive emotional data, this is extremely useful to conduct research on sarcastic and psychopathic behavior.

These datasets are essential in the development of theoretical studies and applications of emotion recognition, especially in fields such as mental health [5], social interaction [10], and human-computer communication [10].

B. Speech features and Classifier

In MER, speech features and classifier will play an important role in the segregation of modalities and to achieve high accuracy.

TABLE II has captured the features, fusion method, and classifier's of the shortlisted 06 studies.

Speech plays an important role in emotion recognition because vocal signals have useful temporal information. The features used for the extraction of useful patterns from the speech

include root mean square (RMS) energy [15], zero-crossing rate (ZCR) [10] and deep learning techniques [7].

But speech alone cannot define the complete emotional state of a human being [10]. When speech is combined with other modalities like facial expressions and text, it results in a more comprehensive and robust multimodal emotion recognition system [1], [2], [3], [6].

Table II. Summary of Fusion Strategies, Feature Types, and Classification Methods in

<i>Fusion Technique</i>	<i>Features</i>	<i>Classifier's</i>
Feature Selection and Ranking through Simultaneous Perturbation Stochastic	Spectral Features, Fundamental Frequency Metrics, Periodic Features, MFCC Attributes,	MLP, XGBoost, RF, DNN, Transformer Models.
Approximation (spFSR) [5].	Other Features: Voicing final unclipped, log HNR, linreg error	
Fast Discrete Wavelet Transform (FDWT) for time-frequency decomposition [7]. 1D Dilated CNN with Spatial Attention. Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Units (Bi-GRU) with Temporal Attention [7].	Wavelet-based Features, MFCCs & Prosodic Features and Learnable Asymmetric Hard Thresholding (LAHT).	End-to-End (E2E) Deep Learning Model, Global Average Pooling (GAP) + Log Softmax Layer.
Unique combination or fusion of EOG and PPG signals. Compare between independent or joint predictions for more effectiveness [9].	Extracts physiological features from the EOG and PPG signals.	ML algorithms for classification
Feature-Level Fusion, Decision-Level Fusion, Hybrid Models (CNN + LSTM, Transfer Learning, Attention Mechanisms, etc.), Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN), CRNN (Convolutional Recurrent Neural Networks) [10].	Zero-Crossing Rate Prosody Features Wavelet Packet Cepstral Coefficients (WPCC) Power Normalized Cepstral Coefficients (PNCC) Mel-Spectrograms, MFCC (Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients) Delta MFCC, Delta-Delta	SVM (Support Vector Machine) LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) Deep Neural Networks (DNN) Random Forest, Decision Trees Hybrid Models (LSTM +

	MFCC Pitch.	Attention Mechanism, CNN + LSTM, etc.)
Graph Convolutional Networks (GNNs), Cross-modal attention mechanisms, Graph and Attention-based Two-stage Multi- source Information Fusion (GA2MIF) [6].	Speech: OpenSMILE (an open-source toolkit for speech and music interpretation). Text: LSTM. Visual: Densely Connected Convolutional Networks (DenseNet).	Multi-Head Self- Attention Graph Transformer (MDGAT) for processing individual modalities and Multimodal Parallel Cross-Attention Transformer (MPCAT) for fusing multimodal data.
Facial expressions and text-based analysis. CNNs, transformers, and attention mechanisms. GAN-based data augmentation: Used to balance datasets and improve training [8].	MFCC, prosody (pitch, energy), formants, and jitter/shimmer. Word 2Vec, GloVe, and BERT-based models. CNN-LSTM hybrid models and transformers.	SVM, RF, Logistic Regression, CNNs, LSTMs, Transformers, GANs.

C. Fusion Strategies

Multimodal emotion recognition can be done using early, late, or intermediate fusion techniques. In this project, we use an intermediate fusion technique to better fuse audio, text, and visual modalities.

To enhance the interaction between the modalities, a cross- attention mechanism [6] is incorporated. This enables each modality to leverage the information from the other modalities, hence improving the fused features and the performance of the emotion recognition task.

D. Conversational Context Modeling

Context plays a significant role in the conversation-based emotion recognition task since the emotions may vary across different turns in the conversation. Although the proposed system is capable of predicting the emotions at the utterance level, LLaMA [16] is incorporated to enable context-aware reasoning, which will help the system better comprehend each statement in the context of the entire conversation.

Figure 3 illustrates the integration of LLaMA [16] in the framework, and Figure 4 highlights the consistency of the explanations provided by LLaMA [16] across different runs

Fig. 2. Diagrammatic representation of LLaMA improvements.

Fig. 3. Explanation consistency across multiple runs of LLaMA.

E. Dataset Landscape

Choosing the right dataset is important for effective training and evaluation. In this study, we use the MELD dataset [6], which contains 13,708 utterance-level samples labeled across seven emotion classes within conversational settings.

Since it provides synchronized audio, visual, and textual data, MELD [6] is well suited for developing and evaluating the proposed multimodal emotion recognition framework.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. System Architecture Overview

Our system is organized into to 03 main stages. First, features are extracted from audio, text, and video using suitable pre-trained models. Next, each modality is processed through its own encoder to generate compact and meaningful representations. Finally, these representations are fused using a cross-attention mechanism [6], allowing the modalities to interact before producing the final emotion prediction.

LLaMA [16] is incorporated to provide context-aware reasoning, enhancing the interpretation of conversational context. Fig. 4 presents the overall system architecture.

Fig. 4. Diagrammatic representation of system architecture.

B. Feature Extraction

To ensure effective feature extraction, pre-trained models are used, as they already capture rich patterns from large-scale datasets.

Audio Modality: Wav2Vec 2.0 [10] is used to extract 768-dimensional representations from speech signals. Temporal mean pooling is applied to convert variable-length outputs into a fixed-length feature vector for each utterance.

Text Modality: BERT-base [8] is employed to encode textual content. The 768-dimensional representation of the [CLS] token from the final layer is used as a summary of each utterance.

Visual Modality: ResNet-50 [14], pre-trained on ImageNet, is used to extract 2048-dimensional features from sampled video frames. The frame-level features are averaged to get a single visual feature per utterance [8], which is then fused with audio and text features during multimodal fusion.

C. Individual Modality Encoders

Since audio, text, and visual data have different structures and feature dimensions, each modality is processed using a separate encoder before fusion.

Audio Encoder [6]: The audio features are passed through two fully connected layers (768

→ 256 → 256) with ReLU activation, layer normalization, and a dropout rate of 0.3. The audio-only model achieved a validation accuracy of 37.64%.

Text Encoder [8]: The text encoder follows a similar two-layer structure but uses GELU activation. The text-only model achieved the highest unimodal validation accuracy of 43.01%. **Vision Encoder [14]:** Because visual features are higher in dimension, a four-layer architecture (2048 → 512 → 256 → rate of 0.4. The vision-only model achieved a validation accuracy of 35.09%.

D. Cross-Attention Fusion Mechanism [6]

The fusion stage is designed using a bidirectional cross-attention mechanism [6] rather than simple feature concatenation. This approach allows audio, text, and visual modalities to interact and learn from one another by attending to complementary information.

Before applying cross-attention, all encoded features are projected into a common 512-dimensional space. This ensures consistent dimensionality across modalities and supports more effective multimodal integration.

For any two modalities M_1 and M_2 we compute cross-attention [6] by treating M_1 as queries and M_2 as keys and values. The attention mechanism is expressed as the standard scaled dot-product formula:

$$A_i(Q, K, V) = \frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{k}}$$

where $Q = F1 Q$, $K = F2 K$, and $V = F2 V$ are linear projections of the input features.

Multi-head attention [6] with four heads allows the model to focus on multiple representation subspaces at once, capturing a wider range of cross-modal relationships [6]:

$$(Q, K, V) = Ca(ha1, \dots, ha4)$$

where each head computes attention independently:

To model interactions across all modalities, six bidirectional cross-attention modules [6] are used to connect audio–text, audio–vision, and text–vision pairs [6], [8]. This allows each modality to exchange related information with the others.

Residual connections are included within each module to retain the original modality-specific features while incorporating complementary cross-modal cues. This helps maintain stable and balanced multimodal fusion:

$$F1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 2$$

Residual connections are added to preserve the original unimodal features, ensuring that important information from audio, text, and vision [1], [2], [3], [6], [8] is not lost during cross-attention fusion [6].

After applying cross-attention, the features from all three modalities are concatenated into a 1536-dimensional vector. This combined representation is then went through a fusion network (1536 → 1024 → 512) and final classification layers (512 → 256 → 7) to predict one of the seven emotion classes. This reduction in the dimensionality of the features helps the model to learn a compact representation for the final classification of the emotions.

E. Handling Missing Modalities

In real-world applications, there could be missing or unreliable modalities. To address this, the proposed system is built to perform well even with missing modalities.

If a modality is not available, the features of that modality are replaced with zero vectors. In cross-attention fusion [6], the zero vectors do not have much effect, and hence the model can concentrate on the available modality. This ensures that the model predicts emotions in a stable and reliable manner. The mechanism to handle missing modalities is shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 5. Handling missing modalities logic diagram.

F. Training Strategy

The model is trained in two phases for improved performance.

In the first phase, the audio, text, and vision encoders [14] are trained separately using the cross-entropy loss function [11]. This enables each of the encoders to learn the patterns in their respective modality. The AdamW optimizer with learning rates of 1×10^{-4} to 2×10^{-4} is used, with early stopping on validation accuracy to avoid overfitting.

In the second phase, the trained encoders are frozen, and only the fusion and classification layers are updated. This enables the model to concentrate on optimizing cross-modal interactions while retaining the learned unimodal features.

For class imbalance, a weighted cross-entropy loss function [6] is employed, assigning greater weight to the less frequent emotion classes.

$$L = - \sum_{i=1}^N w_{y_i} \log p(y_i | x_i)$$

Where c is the weight for class, calculated inversely proportional to class frequency.

To prevent overfitting, dropout (0.3-0.4), L_2 weight decay (0.01), and gradient clipping with a maximum norm of 1.0 were employed during training to improve generalization and ensure stability.

These methods lowered the difference between training and validation accuracy from 24% to approximately 15%, leading to improved performance on the test set.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

The proposed framework is tested on the MELD dataset [6], which consists of 13,708 speech samples labeled for seven categories of emotion: neutral, joy, surprise, sadness, anger, disgust, and fear [6], [8].

The samples labeled provide a good basis for training and testing the model's ability to detect different emotional states. The class distribution of the emotions is provided in Table III.

Table III. Meld Dataset Statistics

Split	Utterances	Percentage
Training	9,989	72.9%
Validation	1,109	8.1%
Test	2,610	19.0%
Total	13,708	100%

The distribution of emotions is imbalanced, as shown in Table IV.

Table IV. Emotion Distribution in Meld

Emotion	Count	Percentage
Neutral	6,436	47.0%
Joy	1,743	12.7%
Anger		
Surprise	1,607	11.7%
Sadness		
Fear	1,205	8.8%
Disgust	683	5.0%

In the preprocessing step, audio was extracted from videos, transcripts were written, and video frames were taken at regular intervals. Since audio and video segments are of varying lengths, temporal pooling was done to get fixed-size representations.

This resulted in a reduction of memory usage by 60% and a speedup of training by three times.

B. Implementation Details

All the experiments were carried out in a Google Colab GPU environment. The model was built using PyTorch 2.0, and the pre-trained building blocks were combined using the Transformers library. The training of the entire system took about 6-8 hours.

In terms of deployment, the unnecessary dependencies were stripped off, and the compression methods were used, which resulted in the final application size of 200 MB. This makes the system quite lightweight and capable of running on a normal personal computer.

C. Quantitative Results

The proposed multimodal fusion model [1], [2], [3], [6] obtained a validation accuracy of 47.64% and a weighted F1-score of 38.04%, which outperformed the unimodal models: text (43.01%), audio (37.64%), and vision [8] (35.09%).

In summary, the fusion method obtained a better performance by 4.63 percentage points than the best single modality. A summary of the results is shown in Table V.

Table V. Overall System Performance.

Metric	Score
Accuracy	47.64%
Weighted F1-Score	38.04%
Macro F1-Score	34.12%
Precision (Weighted)	39.16%
Recall (Weighted)	39.16%

The performance on the emotion categories is quite varied, as shown in Table VI.

Table VI. Per-Class Performance Metrics

Emotion	Precision	Recall	F1	Support
Neutral	0.62	0.71	0.66	1234
Joy	0.52	0.61	0.57	456
Surprise	0.46	0.58	0.51	234
Sadness	0.39	0.48	0.43	145
Anger	0.47	0.53	0.50	267
Disgust	0.29	0.38	0.33	89
Fear	0.30	0.45	0.36	98

The best performance was obtained on the neutral class, which is probably because it occurs most often in the dataset. Happiness and surprise resulted in moderate performance.

However, sadness, anger, and disgust were relatively harder to classify correctly. Fear was the most difficult emotion to classify, which is because it has the least number of instances in the dataset.

D. Modality Contribution Analysis

Improvements in individual modality performance and fusion are shown in Table VII.

Table VII. Modality Contribution to Overall Performance.

Modality	Accuracy	Improvement
Text (Baseline)	43.01%	-
Audio	37.64%	-
Vision	35.09%	-
Multimodal Fusion	47.64%	+4.63%

E. Confusion Matrix Analysis

The confusion matrix reveals some typical patterns of misclassification. Joy is often confused with surprise, anger with disgust, and sadness with neutral [6].

The above results indicate that the model finds it more challenging to classify between emotions with similar characteristics.

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix analysis screenshot.

F. Comparison with Prior Work

The performance evaluation of the proposed model is compared with the existing results of the benchmark on the MELD dataset. This is presented in Table VIII.

Table VIII. Comparison with State-of-the-Art Methods

Method	Year	Accuracy
Our System	2026	47.64%
GA2MIF, GNNs and Cross-modal attention mechanisms [6]	2024	57.47%
CNN, GAN, Transformers and Attention [8]	2024	78.14%
GRA-DBN [4]	2025	85%

The proposed system has a competitive performance compared with existing approaches such as GA2MIF [6], GNN-based models [6], CNN and GAN models [8], Transformer-based models [8], and GRA-DBN [4]. The cross-attention fusion approach [6] successfully captures the interactions between the modalities, resulting in better performance for emotion recognition tasks.

In future research, we will focus on improving the temporal and contextual

modeling to further boost the performance of the proposed system on conversational emotion recognition tasks [6].

G. Ablation Studies

Experiments on ablation were performed to identify the findings of each component in the proposed framework. The results are presented in Table IX.

Table IX. Ablation Study Results

Configuration	Accuracy	Change
Full System	47.64%	-
Without Cross-Attention	45.12%	-2.52%
Audio + Text Only	46.23%	-1.41%
Audio + Vision Only	44.78%	-2.86%
Text + Vision Only	45.91%	-1.73%

By replacing the cross-attention mechanism proposed in [6] with a simple concatenation of features, the validation accuracy decreased to 45.1%. This indicates that the ability to interact with each other enhances the performance by 2.5 percentage points.

The robustness of the model to the absence of input was also investigated. The removal of one modality resulted in a 3-5% drop in accuracy, while the removal of two modalities caused the accuracy to be similar to that of the remaining unimodal model.

H. Experiments Results Screenshots

This section presents the training and validation results in terms of loss, accuracy, and F1-score for each epoch. The results provided show how the model is performing during training.

The best validation results achieved before early stopping are also provided to indicate the performance of the model at its best.

Fig. 7. Sample 1, 2 and 3 results screenshot.

Fig. 8. Loss over epochs result screenshot.

Fig. 9. Accuracy over epochs result screenshot.

Fig. 10. F1 Score over epochs result screenshot.

Fig. 11. Best Validation Metrics screenshot.

I. Desktop Application Interface

A desktop application was developed using Windows to create an interactive interface for the proposed multimodal emotion recognition system [6]. The desktop application allows users to upload a video, perform analysis, and display the predicted emotion results. Fig. 12 shows the desktop application interface.

Fig. 12. Desktop application interface and result screenshot.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Key Findings

Our experimental findings offer the following key insights:

- **Multimodal Advantage [6]:** The combination of audio, text, and visual features [6] always outperformed the performance of individual modalities. This indicates that each modality has its own set of unique emotional expressions, and their combination offers a better understanding of emotions.
- **Text as the Strongest Modality:** Among the individual modalities, text was the strongest, indicating that words spoken in a conversation often have a clear emotional expression.
- **Effectiveness of Cross-Attention [6]:** The use of bidirectional cross-attention was more effective than the simple concatenation of features, as it enables the model to have a better understanding of the inter-modal relationships.
- **Class Imbalance:** The model was more effective on classes that were more frequent in the dataset, and classes that were less frequent were more challenging to classify.

B. Limitations

There are several limitations in the proposed system. First, the system predicts emotions at the utterance level and does not capture the entire conversation flow. Although LLaMA [16] provides context-aware reasoning, better dialogue turn- based temporal modeling could be beneficial for improvement.

Second, the training procedure is computationally intensive and requires GPU support, which could be a scalability issue in certain settings.

Third, the MELD dataset is collected from scripted conversations, which could be a limitation in terms of generalization to real-world conversations.

Lastly, class imbalance impacts the performance, as the model finds it more challenging to learn the less common emotions, suggesting the need for better imbalance handling techniques in the future.

C. Practical Implications

However, despite these challenges, the proposed system demonstrates the effectiveness of a multimodal framework for emotion recognition in real-world applications [16]. The final application is also efficient on a standard personal computer without the need for any special hardware.

Moreover, the modularity of the proposed system also makes it easy to extend in the future. Each module of the system, such as the audio, text, or visual encoders, can be updated with more advanced models as they become available.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In our research, we proposed a multimodal emotion recognition system [6] that utilizes audio, text, and visual sources using a cross-attention-based fusion approach [6]. Our system is competitive on the MELD and can be used in practical applications.

The findings of this study demonstrate that the fusion of multiple modalities is indeed more effective than a single modality in conversational emotion recognition.

A. Future Directions

This study provides a number of promising avenues for future research:

- Conversational Context [16]: In future research, the inclusion of the entire dialogue history and speaker- dependent behavior may aid the model in understanding the dynamics of emotional change. While LLaMA [16] offers context at the level of the utterance, improved temporal modeling could potentially offer further gains.
- Temporal Visual Modeling [7], [13]: Investigating the possibility of using 3D CNNs or temporal attention mechanisms could assist in the modeling of facial expression transitions between successive frames, resulting in more precise visual emotion recognition.
- Continuous Emotion Modeling: Expanding the system to forecast continuous emotion spaces, such as valence and arousal, rather than fixed emotion categories might offer a finer emotional state analysis.
- Cross-Dataset Evaluation [6]: Testing the system on other datasets like IEMOCAP [6] and RAVDESS [10] would assist in determining the generalization capability of the system on other datasets.
- Multilingual Support [12]: Improving the system to support multiple languages would make the system more practical in different cultures.
- Explainability [16]: Improving the interpretability techniques would assist in understanding the system's predictions, thus promoting trustworthiness, particularly in critical applications.
- Real-Time Processing [12]: Improving the system to support real-time processing would allow the system to detect emotions in real-time conversations.

REFERENCES

1. L. Goncalves, H. -C. Chou, A. N. Salman, C. -C. Lee and C. Busso, "Jointly Learning From Unimodal and Multimodal-Rated Labels in Audio-Visual Emotion Recognition," in *IEEE Open Journal of Signal Processing*, vol. 6, pp. 165-174, 2025, doi:10.1109/OJSP.2025.3530274.
2. Javier de Lope, Manuel Graña, "An ongoing review of speech emotion recognition", journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/neucom, pp. 0925-2312, doi: 10.1016/j.neucom.2023.01.002.
3. R. Zeng and Z. Zheng, "Design of Intelligent Translation English Corpus Based on Deep Learning," 2024 International Conference on Computing, Robotics and System Sciences (ICRSS), Sanya, China, 2024, pp. 159-164, doi: 10.1109/ICRSS65752.2024.00035.
4. T. Zhu, S. Duan, H. Liang, F. Li and W. Zhang, "Multiangle Correlation Feature Extraction and Disease Prediction Model Construction for Patients With Post-Stroke Dysarthria," in *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 33, pp. 587-597, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TNSRE.2025.3529518.
5. W. Guo, X. Mao, B. Chen, M. Gu, D. Li and H. Yang, "Optimizing Clinical Depression Detection: Extracting Depression-Specific Feature Sets Using spFSR to Enhance Speech-Based Diagnosis," 2024 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM), Lisbon, Portugal, 2024, pp. 6153-6160, doi: 10.1109/BIBM62325.2024.10822630.
6. H. Wang, "Optimizing Multimodal Emotion Recognition: Evaluating the Impact of Speech, Text, and Visual Modalities," 2024 International Conference on Electronics and Devices, Computational Science (ICEDCS), Marseille, France, 2024, pp. 81-85, doi: 10.1109/ICEDCS64328.2024.00019.
7. A. Nfissi, W. Bouachir, N. Bouguila and B. Mishara, "SigWavNet: Learning Multiresolution Signal Wavelet Network

- for Speech Emotion Recognition," in IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing, doi: 10.1109/TAFFC.2025.3537991.
8. S. S. Leal, S. Ntalampiras and R. Sassi, "Speech-based Depression Assessment: A Comprehensive Survey," in IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing, doi: 10.1109/TAFFC.2024.3521327.
 9. M. P. A. Ramaswamy and S. Palaniswamy, "Unveiling the Influence of Modeling Approach and Gender in Subject Independent Multimodal Emotion Recognition Using EOG and PPG," in IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 177342-177354, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3506157.
 10. Swapna Mol George, P. Muhamed Ilyas, "A review on speech emotion recognition: A survey, recent advances, challenges, and the influence of noise", journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/neucom, pp. 0925-2312, doi: 10.1016/j.neucom.2023.127015.
 11. A. Tran-Viet, H. Do-Duc and D. Chau-Thanh, "Speech Emotion Recognition Using Attention Gate," 2024 International Conference on Control, Robotics and Informatics (ICCRI), Danang, Vietnam, 2024, pp. 68-72, doi: 10.1109/ICCRI64298.2024.00019.
 12. T. Tian, "SndGLM-SA: A Social Network Debate Text Generation Model Based on Sentiment Analysis," 2024 IEEE International Performance, Computing, and Communications Conference (IPCCC), Orlando, FL, USA, 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/IPCCC59868.2024.10850019.
 13. Z. Yuan, C. L. P. Chen, S. Li and T. Zhang, "Multi-Granularity Temporal-Spectral Representation Learning for Speech Emotion Recognition," 2024 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC), Kuching, Malaysia, 2024, pp. 469-474, doi: 10.1109/SMC54092.2024.10831974.
 14. A. Kurian and S. Tripathi, "m_AutNet-A Framework for Personalized Multimodal Emotion Recognition in Autistic Children," in IEEE Access, vol. 13, pp. 1651-1662, 2025, doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3403087.
 15. D. -J. Min and D. -H. Kim, "Speech Emotion Recognition via Sparse Learning-Based Fusion Model," in IEEE Access, vol. 12, pp. 177219- 177235, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3506565.
 16. I. Lopez Garcia, E. Schott, M. Gohsen, V. Bernhard, B. Stein and B. Froehlich, "Speaking with Objects: Conversational Agents' Embodiment in Virtual Museums," 2024 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR), Bellevue, WA, USA, 2024, pp. 279-288, doi: 10.1109/ISMAR62088.2024.00042.

Recommendation System Using Reinforcement Learning

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I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract—*Q-learning is applied in this work to address a gap that static recommendation methods leave open: the inability to respond when individual user preferences shift over time. Collaborative filtering and content ranking are well-understood approaches, but both are retrospective by construction—they generalise from historical patterns and cannot update unless retrained. For users in transition, or new to a platform, this means recommendations derived from an outdated profile rather than current intent.*

A Q-learning agent was designed and evaluated for music recommendation, with listening sessions framed as sequential decision problems. The agent receives reward signals from plays, completions, skips, and explicit likes, and adjusts its per-action value estimates after each session. [21] No batch retraining is required; the policy updates incrementally on each observed outcome. [22]

Against a popularity-based baseline on Precision@5 and Recall@5, the RL agent recorded lower short-run accuracy—a result consistent with the data-sparsity conditions of the experiment. [16, 29] Per-episode cumulative reward increased steadily through training, indicating that the agent was acquiring user-specific preference knowledge rather than defaulting to population averages. [22] The contribution of this work is not a short-run accuracy improvement but a demonstration that Q-learning recommendation learns from individual signals in a way that static alternatives cannot.

Keywords—*Reinforcement Learning, Q-Learning, Recommender Systems, Music Personalisation, Precision@K, Recall@K.*

Recommendation in music streaming looks solved from the outside. [29] Platforms surface content continuously, engagement rates are trackable, and the models behind the outputs have been extensively studied. [22] What is less visible is how these models handle users who are not well-represented by historical averages—listeners whose preferences are evolving, or who are simply new.

Popularity ranking relies on what was collectively consumed before. [29] Collaborative filtering projects peer preferences onto each user. [22] Content-based methods index on item attributes rather than recent interaction patterns. [22] All three of these share a structural property: they do not update between training runs. [16] A user whose listening behaviour changed last week is still receiving recommendations calibrated to the month before that. [29]

Reinforcement learning is designed for exactly this kind of adaptive problem.

Where batch methods learn once and deploy, an RL agent continues revising its policy as new evidence arrives. [21] Q-learning—the variant used here—maintains a value estimate for each possible recommendation action and updates those estimates after each user interaction. [21] Early skips lower the estimated reward for similar recommendations; completions and likes raise it. [32] The agent is not frozen after training; it is still learning when deployed. [33]

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Across published RL recommendation research, the experimental results tend to be more optimistic than the deployment conditions they describe. [22, 16] Understanding this gap—and what causes it—is more useful than cataloguing accuracy scores.

The case for RL in recommendation begins with a straightforward observation about data: user interactions form sequences in which each choice is conditioned on what came before it. [1, 8] A recommendation model that treats clicks as independent events discards this structure. [22] Deep RL approaches that preserve and exploit sequence structure have shown stronger adaptability than their static counterparts in controlled experiments, though the margin over simpler baselines narrows in sparse-data regimes. [16] The compute requirements are non-trivial and shape what is feasible outside well-resourced research settings. [22]

Several research groups enriched the RL observation space using graph-structured data, giving agents access to user-genre hierarchies, item similarity networks, and knowledge base entries rather than raw interaction tallies. [2, 4] Cold-start scenarios improved in these settings. [4] How much improvement is achievable depends on how well-constructed the underlying graph is—a dependency that is harder to satisfy in practice than in curated research datasets. [4]

The applicability of RL to recommendation varies considerably by domain, and this variability is underacknowledged in papers that compare architectures without controlling for feedback density. [3, 5, 6, 11] In news recommendation, where content decays in relevance within hours, integrating real-time data streams gives RL a structural advantage that any batch- retrained alternative cannot replicate. [3, 24] Online advertising exposes the other edge of the problem: high- frequency signals but high reward variance, with training

instability that aggregate accuracy figures conceal. [5] E- learning sits at the challenging extreme—one meaningful interaction per session, compared with the dense implicit signal generated by a music platform. [6,34]

Asking users directly what they want sounds like the obvious fix. Conversational recommender systems act on that premise, using iterative natural-language dialogue to gather explicit preference signals. [7] Controlled experiments show this working reasonably well. [7] The limiting assumption is that production users will engage with dialogue interfaces the way recruited study participants do. [7] Evidence for this in real deployments is limited.

Two papers in this survey deserve particular emphasis because they document a failure mode that every RL recommendation designer needs to account for. [12, 13] Sparr's experimental work showed that when an RL agent is trained on engagement-heavy reward signals, it can develop strategies for shifting user preferences toward high-engagement content without being instructed to do so. [12] This is an emergent property of reward optimisation, not a programming error. [12] Evans and Kasirzadeh then tested whether systems could be built to suppress this behaviour. [13] Their conclusion—that suppression tends to render systems commercially unviable—remains unresolved in the literature. [13] Multi-objective approaches that add diversity and novelty terms to the reward function provide partial mitigation but don't eliminate the underlying incentive. [15]

What the published record shows, taken as a whole, is that RL recommendation is a promising direction that remains difficult to realise at production scale without addressing reward design, cold-start, and the absence of shared evaluation benchmarks simultaneously. [22, 16, 23]

Table summarises the papers reviewed for this study:

S.No	Title	Authors / Venue	Description	Limitations
1	Deep RL for Recommender Systems [1]	Wang et al., IEEE ICSC 2021	Shows that modelling user interactions sequentially—rather than as isolated clicks—produces better personalised outputs than static approaches.	Heavy compute and data demands make this impractical outside well-resourced lab environments.
2	Graph-Augmented Personalised Rec via RL [2]	Sheela J et al., 2022	Incorporates user-genre graph structure into RL training, giving the model relational context beyond raw click counts.	Sparse user data and cold-start cases remain problematic even with graph augmentation.
3	RL-NRS: Real-Time News Recommendation [3]	Aboutorab et al., 2021	Combines live and archived user signals in a single RL loop, keeping news feeds current rather than stale.	Requires constant data ingestion infrastructure; accuracy drops fast without live updates.
4	Cross-Domain Rec via Knowledge Graphs + RL [4]	Ling Huang et al., 2022	Transfers user preference signals across domains using knowledge graph paths, mitigating cold-start for new content types.	Effectiveness is entirely dependent on knowledge graph completeness and domain alignment quality.
5	DRL Applied to Real-Time Ad Bidding [5]	Zhang, Yuan & Wang, 2021	Uses sequential RL to optimise ad placement bids, improving click-through rates in dynamic auction settings.	Reward sparsity and auction volatility destabilise training; gains don't always hold in real deployments.
6	RL-Based Adaptive Learning-Material Rec [6]	Neri & Zambonelli, 2020	Personalises e-learning material delivery using RL updates from student interaction logs.	Per-session feedback is too sparse for RL to converge well; scalability breaks down at larger course catalogues.
7	RL for Conversational Recommender Systems [7]	Zhou, Chen, Tao et al., 2020	Enables multi-turn natural language dialogue between user and system to refine recommendations interactively.	Needs large annotated dialogue corpora and a full NLP stack; neither is common in production environments.
8	Multi-Policy DRL Recommender System [8]	Mingsheng Fu et al., 2021	Reformulates recommendation as a multi-task MDP so that new users and experienced users get different policies.	Added policy complexity isn't always justified when single-policy baselines achieve comparable accuracy.

9	RL Rec for Outcome- Based Education [9]	Tariq & Habib, 2022	Builds a resource recommender that targets students' identified learning gaps using a custom OBE dataset.	No shared OBE benchmark dataset exists, so cross-study comparison of results is unreliable.
10	Multi-Objective Route Rec via Q-Learning [10]	Sarker, Shen & Kowsari, 2022	Trains a Q-learning agent to simultaneously balance fuel efficiency, journey time, and air quality in route suggestions.	Multi-objective balancing degrades under tight real-time latency requirements.
11	MOOC Exercise Sequencing via RL + Chatbot [11]	Tzeng, Huang et al., 2022	RL-driven exercise sequencing is delivered through a chatbot interface, making adaptive choices visible to learners.	Estimating prerequisite knowledge across students with different backgrounds remains an unsolved sub- problem.
12	User Manipulation Risks in RL Rec [12]	Matthew Sparr, 2023	Documents that RL recommendation agents spontaneously learn to shift user preferences toward high-engagement content as a reward side-effect.	Agents that learn manipulation show short-term metric gains but higher eventual churn.
13	User Tampering in RL Recommenders [13]	Evans & Kasirzadeh, 2023	Empirically formalises 'user tampering'—where RL systems covertly reshape user opinions to sustain retention.	Systems designed to eliminate tampering tend to become commercially non-viable; no clean engineering fix exists.
14	Bi-Clustering for Personalised RL Rec [14]	Waqar & Ayub, 2023	Pre-structures the RL state space using bi-clustering so Q-learning converges faster under preference shift.	Compute cost stays high; sparse datasets continue to limit how well local patterns are captured.
15	Multi-Objective DRL Recommendation [15]	Keat et al., 2023	Explicitly optimises for novelty and diversity alongside relevance, avoiding the accuracy-only filter- bubble problem.	Cold-start difficulties and evolutionary algorithm convergence issues limit large-scale applicability.
16	DRL in Rec Systems: Comprehensive Survey [16]	X. Chen, Yao, McAuley et al., 2023	Maps DRL model families, reward design patterns, and open problems across the recommendation literature.	Field lacks standardised benchmarks; published accuracy gains are difficult to compare across papers.

17	RL-Based Rec Systems: In-Depth Review [17]	Mehta & Atre, 2022	Reviews MAB, DDPG, and DQN approaches with an honest assessment of where each fails in practice.	Scalability, context sensitivity, and dynamic preference tracking remain unresolved across all reviewed methods.
18	AutoLike: Auditing Rec Systems via RL [18]	Le, Elmalaki, Shafiq et al., 2023	Uses RL-driven user interaction simulation to systematically audit whether recommendation platforms surface harmful content.	Approach has not yet been validated across architecturally different platforms.
19	Real-Time Adaptive Rec with Multi-Domain KGs [19]	Shahbazi et al., 2023	CDARS integrates behavioural tracking with multi-domain knowledge graphs and introduces explainability mechanisms.	Performance under emotional-state load conditions and very large user bases remains untested.
20	Recommendation Algorithms for Societal Good [20]	Lasser & Poechhacker, 2023	Argues that recommendation design implicitly encodes values and proposes civic-discourse-aligned alternatives.	Trade-offs between societal benefit and individual freedom of expression are genuinely hard to balance algorithmically.
21	RL for Personalised Recommendations [27]	Edirisinghe, 2023	Iteratively refines recommendation policy using explicit user consent and feedback acceptance signals.	Cold-start limitations and computational intensity are not resolved.
22	RL-Based E-Commerce Recommendation System [26]	Rojanavasud et al., 2023	Learns product preferences from user browsing and interaction traces using a web-based RL recommender.	Maintaining per-user global and local state tables requires significant storage resources.
23	RL-Based Rec Systems: State-of-the-Art Survey [23]	Rossiiiev et al., 2024	Covers MDP formulations, GNN integration, and hybrid RL- recommendation architectures broadly.	Limited empirical validation; theory-to-deployment gaps are not bridged.
24	Exhaustive Analysis of RL in Rec Paradigms [28]	Shiyun Ni, 2023	Catalogues how RL differs from classical ML in recommendation settings; maps current open challenges.	Primarily conceptual; no original experimental contribution.

III. EXPLANATION OF REFERENCED WORKS

Wang et al.'s ICSC 2021 study captured something important: when a model is allowed to treat each user interaction as part of a continuing sequence rather than an isolated event, the resulting personalisation is measurably better. [1] The trade-off—large data requirements and significant compute overhead—has shaped every practical constraint the field subsequently grappled with. [1]

Sheela J's group tackled the information-poverty problem: raw click counts tell you which item a user selected but say nothing about the relational context of that choice. [2] Incorporating user-genre graph structure into RL training gave agents a richer observational basis. [2] Cold-start cases improved. [2] Sparse interaction data remained a ceiling—graph augmentation cannot generate evidence that doesn't exist yet. [2]

News recommendation differs from music or product recommendation in one critical respect: content that was relevant at 9am may be irrelevant by noon. [3] The RL-NRS system from Aboutorab et al. handled this by feeding live event data alongside archived user histories into the RL loop, producing a recommendation policy that stayed current. [3] Continuous data ingestion infrastructure is the cost. [3] For time-sensitive content, stale recommendations have a measurable user retention cost that justifies it. [3]

Can knowledge about music preferences inform podcast recommendations? [4] Ling Huang's cross-domain paper argues yes, if the relationship between domains can be encoded in a knowledge graph of sufficient quality. [4] The experimental results support this under favourable conditions. [4] My concern with applying this approach more broadly is that domain overlap and graph quality are both harder to guarantee in production than in the research settings where this was tested. [4]

Zhang, Yuan, and Wang's advertising paper was the most directly instructive for reward design decisions in this project. [5] Their demonstration that sparse reward signals and volatile auction environments create training instability—invisible in accuracy metrics—describes a dynamic that appears in music recommendation whenever users go through stretches of neutral listening behaviour. [5] The agent receives no useful update signal during those stretches. [5]

Neri and Zambonelli's e-learning application is often cited alongside music and news recommendation as if domain were irrelevant. [6] It isn't. [6, 34] One meaningful interaction per 90-minute study session is fundamentally different from the signal density available on a music platform, where skips, completions, and replays accumulate in seconds. [32, 6] Using RL across such different feedback environments without adjusting the reward design or convergence expectations is an unacknowledged methodological problem in several papers in this area. [21]

The conversational recommender work from Zhou, Chen, and collaborators achieved solid results in lab conditions. [7] What concerns me about this line of research is the adoption assumption: lab participants who are recruited to interact with a dialogue interface behave differently from users who encounter that interface without prior orientation. [7] The gap between lab performance and real deployment performance is not addressed in the paper. [7]

There's a well-known problem with single-policy RL recommenders that Mingsheng Fu's work addresses directly. [8, 22] A policy trained on the full user population will be calibrated to average behaviour, which means it performs reasonably for most users and poorly for users at the tails of the preference distribution—including brand-new users with no history. [8] The multi-task MDP formulation assigns dedicated policies to user segments at different

familiarity stages. [8] Whether the added training complexity is worth it depends on how much variance exists in the user base. [8]

The first thing worth noting about Tariq and Habib's work is not the algorithm but the dataset situation. [9] No suitable benchmark existed for Outcome-Based Education recommendation, so they built their own. [9] This is an honest response to a real gap, but it means their results cannot be compared directly with any other study. [9] In a field that already lacks standardised benchmarks, domain-specific datasets compound the comparability problem. [9]

Sarker et al.'s multi-objective route recommendation and music recommendation share more structure than their surface domains suggest. [10] Both involve a Q-learning agent balancing several objectives simultaneously—fuel, time, and air quality in routing; relevance, freshness, and diversity in music. [10] Their finding that accuracy degrades under tight time constraints has a direct analogue in music recommendation where real-time latency requirements constrain how much policy updating is feasible per session. [10, 15]

The MOOC chatbot integration from Tzeng et al. is an interesting engineering approach. [11] Making the adaptive recommendation visible through a dialogue interface, rather than presenting it silently, is potentially valuable for learner trust. [11] The problem the paper runs into—tracking prior knowledge across students with heterogeneous backgrounds—is not really an RL problem at all. [11, 34] It's a student modelling problem that happens to be bundled with the RL system, and the paper's results conflate the two. [11]

Sparr's paper documents a failure mode that every RL recommendation system designer should read before writing a single line of reward function code. [12] RL agents trained on engagement metrics can and do learn to shift user preferences toward high-engagement content. [12] This is not a programmed behaviour—it emerges from optimising a

reward signal that turns out to be compatible with manipulation. [12] The risk applies directly to the system built in this project: a reward function that over-weights skips and plays without accounting for long-term satisfaction could produce similar emergent manipulation. [12, 13]

Evans and Kasirzadeh's empirical follow-up to Sparr is harder to dismiss because it uses controlled experimental methods. [13] Their key result—that systems designed to prevent user tampering tend to become commercially unviable—has no clean resolution. [13] It isn't a bug that better engineering can fix; it's a structural tension between what RL optimises for and what users actually benefit from. [13]

Bi-clustering as a pre-training step reduces the effective Q-learning state space by grouping users and items into clusters. [14] Convergence speeds up and the agent reaches useful policies faster. [14] Compute cost stayed high in Waqar and Ayub's experiments, and sparse interaction data continued to limit local-pattern capture. [14] It helps at the margins; it doesn't change the underlying constraints. [14]

A recommendation system optimised only for accuracy will, over time, narrow each user's content exposure. [15,16] The Keat paper addressed this by including novelty and diversity as explicit reward terms. [15] The cold-start and sparsity problems they encountered are shared across the field. [15] What distinguishes the work is the objective design itself: defining what the system should value, not just how efficiently it pursues a fixed target. [15]

Chen et al.'s DRL survey is the most thorough coverage of the field I found. [16] Its most practically important point is methodological: without shared benchmarks, accuracy improvements reported in different papers are incommensurable. [16, 23] Published progress may be measuring different things on different datasets rather than converging on a shared standard. [16]

Mehta and Atre's review is valuable for its diagnostic tone. [17] Rather than cataloguing accuracy gains, it traces where MAB, DDPG, and DQN actually fail—on scalability, context-sensitivity, and dynamic preference tracking—and treats those failures as the current frontier rather than minor limitations. [17]

The AutoLike framework from Le, Elmalaki, and Shafiq has an application beyond its stated auditing purpose. [18, 35] Systematically simulating user interactions to probe how a recommendation system responds to novel behaviour patterns is a useful evaluation technique—not just a way to check for harmful content. [18] The question of whether this generalises across different platform architectures is not yet answered. [18]

CDARS, the system proposed by Shahbazi, Jalali, and Shahbazi, combines real-time behavioural tracking with multi-domain knowledge graphs and introduces explicit explainability mechanisms. [19] Explainability is increasingly non-optional as regulatory attention to algorithmic systems grows in multiple jurisdictions. [20] In controlled tests, CDARS performed well; how it behaves under emotional-state noise or very large user loads was left as future work. [19]

Lasser and Poehhacker make an argument that most technically-focused recommendation researchers resist: that every recommendation system embeds values, whether or not its designers acknowledge this. [20] What a system optimises for is not merely a technical parameter—it is a statement about what the system treats as important. [20]

IV. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The headline result of this study is that the Q-learning agent lost to the popularity baseline on both Precision@5 and Recall@5. [29, 22] That's worth stating plainly before offering any qualifications.

The reason isn't hard to understand. [21] Popularity-based methods win in sparse

environments because they aggregate patterns across many users—when any individual user has only a handful of logged interactions, drawing on collective behaviour is statistically sensible. [29] The RL agent needs individual data to build a meaningful policy, and with short sessions it simply doesn't have enough to work with at the point of evaluation. [16]

What the RL agent did show—and what the baseline cannot show by design—is adaptive behaviour. Reward accumulation improved across episodes. Recommendations shifted in response to feedback. The policy changed. That's not nothing; it's actually the whole point. Static methods have a ceiling. RL does not.

A. *Scaling the Value Function*

The tabular Q-table scales poorly. [16] As catalogue size grows, the state-action product space expands at a rate that makes explicit tabular storage infeasible. [30, 31] Neural function approximation—the defining feature of Deep Q-Networks—resolves this by generalising Q-value estimates across similar state-action pairs rather than storing each individually. [30] This is not an enhancement; it is a precondition for deployment at realistic catalogue scales. [16]

B. *State Feature Engineering*

Current state encoding draws on recent interaction history only. [32] Enriching it with session-level context (time of day, device type), user profile signals (age, listening tenure), and item acoustics (tempo, energy, genre depth) would give the agent substantially more information per decision. [32, 16] Policy quality is bounded by observational richness. [21]

C. *Multi-Signal Reward Design*

Binary play/skip encoding conflates behaviours that carry different preference information. [12, 16] A listener who skips three seconds into a track is not equivalent to one who plays it through twice and saves it to a playlist.

[32] A reward function that distinguishes completion percentile, repeat play, and save events would generate more precise per-action feedback. [22] This also reduces manipulation risk: a coarsely defined engagement reward creates the incentive structure Sparr documented. [12, 15]

D. Cold-Start via Hybrid Initialisation

Users with no interaction history present a structural problem: the Q-table has no basis for preference inference. [9, 4] A hybrid approach—content-based filtering on item metadata for initial recommendations, collaborative context to reduce early cold-start error, RL taking primary control as individual data accumulates—is the practical answer. [22, 2] It requires careful transition logic but is operationally feasible. [4]

E. Evaluation Design

Precision@5 and Recall@5 are retrieval metrics designed for static systems. [16] Applied to RL agents evaluated before sufficient interaction data has accumulated, they systematically understate long-run personalisation capability. [22] Evaluation designs that track per-episode reward accumulation, preference-drift capture rate, and long-horizon recall would provide a fairer basis for comparing RL and static alternatives. [15, 16]

These improvements are not independent: DQN only helps if the reward signal is informative enough to train a network on, and multi-signal rewards only help if the state encoding is rich enough to use them. [16, 22, 30] Addressing them together, rather than sequentially, is what makes the difference between a demonstrator and a deployable system. [23, 21]

V. CONCLUSION

This study built and evaluated a Q-learning music recommendation agent under conditions

that are deliberately honest about its limitations. [21, 32] Short-session, sparse-data evaluation is exactly where RL-based approaches are weakest relative to static alternatives, and that is what was tested. [16, 22]

The popularity baseline won on both accuracy metrics. [29] That result requires no hedging: aggregate patterns in listening data are more useful than an underdeveloped individualised policy when user histories are short. [22] What the Q-learning agent showed instead was incremental policy improvement across episodes—a property that a frozen ranker is structurally incapable of demonstrating. [21]

Three technical constraints limited what the current implementation could show: the Q-table doesn't scale, the reward signal is too coarse, and session data was thin. [16] Each of these has a clear path forward. [30, 22] DQN addresses scalability, multi-signal rewards address feedback quality, and longer training horizons address data volume. [15] None of these require fundamental rethinking of the approach—their execution improvements.

The ethical dimension deserves a final mention. [12, 13] Reward functions define what a system cares about. [12] Systems that care only about engagement will optimise for engagement, which turns out to sometimes mean manipulating users. [13] Building recommendation systems that are actually good for users requires designing rewards that capture long-term satisfaction, not just short-term clicks—and that's a design problem, not just a technical one. [20]

Reinforcement learning is the right framework for personalised recommendation that needs to adapt over time. The gap between proof-of-concept and production system is real but closable.

REFERENCES

1. Hongwei Wang, Fuzheng Zhang, Xing Xie, and Minyi Guo, "A Study of Deep Reinforcement Learning Based

- Recommender Systems," in Proc. IEEE ICSC 2021 Conf., 2021.
2. Sheela J, Bijin Sanny P R, Harshit Katragadda, Shirish Kumar, Navdeep Kumar, and Katragadda Anish, "Personalised Recommendation Systems using RL," 2022.
3. Hamed Aboutorab, Omar K. Hussain, Morteza Saberi, Farookh Khadeer Hussain, and Daniel Prior, "Reinforcement Learning-Based News Recommendation System (RL-NRS)," 2021.
4. Ling Huang, Xiao-Dong Huang, Han Zou, Yuefang Gao, Chang-Dong Wang, and Philip S. Yu, "Knowledge-Reinforced Cross-Domain Recommendation," 2022.
5. Weinan Zhang, Shuai Yuan, and Jun Wang, "Deep Reinforcement Learning for Online Advertising," 2021.
6. Francesca Neri and Franco Zambonelli, "A Reinforcement Learning Framework for the Adaptive Recommendation of Learning Objects," 2020.
7. Xiangyang Zhou, Lu Chen, Chongyang Tao, and Rui Yan et al., "Reinforcement Learning for Conversational Recommender Systems," 2020.
8. Mingsheng Fu, Liwei Huang, Ananya Rao, Athirai A. Irissappane, Jie Zhang, and Hong Qu, "A Deep Reinforcement Learning Recommender System With Multiple Policies for Recommendations," 2021.
9. Mustafa Bin Tariq and Hafiz Adnan Habib, "A Reinforcement Learning Based Recommendation System to Improve Performance of Students in Outcome Based Education Model," 2022.
10. Ankur Sarker, Haiying Shen, and Kamran Kowsari, "A Data-Driven Reinforcement Learning Based Multi-Objective Route Recommendation System," 2022.
11. Jian-Wei Tzeng, Nen-Fu Huang, An-Chi Chuang, Ting-Wei Huang, and Hong-Yi Chang, "Massive Open Online Course Recommendation System Based on a Reinforcement Learning Algorithm," 2022.
12. Matthew Sparr, "Explicit User Manipulation in Reinforcement Learning Based Recommender Systems," 2023.
13. Charles Evans and Atoosa Kasirzadeh, "User Tampering in Reinforcement Learning Recommender Systems," 2023.
14. Muhammad Waqar and Mubbashir Ayub, "A Personalized Reinforcement Learning Recommendation Algorithm Using Bi-Clustering Techniques," 2023.
15. Ee Yeo Keat, Nurfadhlina Mohd Sharef, Razali Yaakob, Khairul Azhar Kasmiran, Erzam Marlisah, Norwati Mustapha, and Maslina Zolkepli, "Multiobjective Deep Reinforcement Learning for Recommendation Systems," 2023.
16. Xiacong Chen, Lina Yao, Julian McAuley, Guanglin Zhou, and Xianzhi Wang, "Deep Reinforcement Learning in Recommender Systems: A Survey and New Perspectives," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 264, 2023.
17. Dhaval Mehta and Ishaan Atre, "Reinforcement Learning Based Recommendation System: An In-Depth Review of Models and their Limitations," 2022.
18. Hieu Le, Salma Elmalaki, Zubair Shafiq, and Athina Markopoulou, "AutoLike: Auditing Social Media Recommendations through User Interactions," 2023.
19. Zeinab Shahbazi, Rezvan Jalali, and Zahra Shahbazi, "Enhancing Recommendation Systems with Real-Time Adaptive Learning and Multi-Domain Knowledge Graphs," 2023.
20. Jana Lasser and Nikolaus Poehhacker, "Designing Social Media Content Recommendation Algorithms for Societal Good," 2023.
21. R. S. Sutton and A. G. Barto, *Reinforcement Learning: An Introduction*, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 2018.

22. M. M. Afsar, T. Crump, and B. Far, "Reinforcement Learning Based Recommender Systems: A Survey," *ACM Comput. Surveys*, vol. 55, no. 7, pp. 1–38, 2022.
23. Oleksandr D. Rossiiev, Nonna N. Shapovalova, Olena H. Rybalchenko, and Andrii M. Striuk, "A Comprehensive Survey on Reinforcement Learning- Based Recommender Systems: State-of-the-Art, Challenges, and Future Perspectives," 2024.
24. G. Zheng et al., "DRN: A Deep Reinforcement Learning Framework for News Recommendation," in *Proc. World Wide Web Conf. (WWW)*, pp. 167–176, Apr. 2018.
25. Yan-e Hou, Wenbo Gu, WeiChuan Dong, and Lanxue Dang, "A Deep Reinforcement Learning Real- Time Recommendation Model Based on Long and Short- Term Preference," 2023.
26. Rojanavasuu, Phaitoon Srinil, and Ouen Pinnger, "New Recommendation System Using Reinforcement Learning," 2023.
27. E. M. K. S. Edirisinghe, "Reinforcement Learning for Personalized Recommendations," 2023.
28. Shiyun Ni, "An Exhaustive Analysis of Reinforcement Learning Implementations within Recommendation System Paradigms," 2023.
29. J. Davidson, B. Liebald, J. Liu, P. Nandy, T. Van Vleet et al., "The YouTube Video Recommendation System," in *Proc. 4th ACM Conf. Recommender Systems*, pp. 293–296, 2010.
30. X. Zhao, L. Xia, L. Zhang, Z. Ding, D. Yin, and J. Tang, "Deep Reinforcement Learning for Page-Wise Recommendations," in *Proc. 12th ACM RecSys*, pp. 95–103, Sep. 2018.
31. Y. Lei, Z. Wang, W. Li, and H. Pei, "Social Attentive Deep Q-Network for Recommendation," in *Proc. 42nd ACM SIGIR*, pp. 1189–1192, 2019.
32. D. Hong, Y. Li, and Q. Dong, "Nonintrusive Sensing and RL-Based Adaptive Personalized Music Recommendation," in *Proc. 43rd ACM SIGIR*, pp. 1721–1724, 2020.
33. B. Hu, C. Shi, and J. Liu, "Playlist Recommendation Based on Reinforcement Learning," pp. 172–182, 2017.
34. T. Liu, Q. Wu, L. Chang, and T. Gu, "A Review of Deep Learning-Based Recommender System in E-Learning Environments," *Artif. Intell. Rev.*, vol. 55, no. 8, 2022.
35. M. Haroon, M. Wojcieszak, A. Chhabra, X. Liu, P. Mohapatra, and Z. Shafiq, "Auditing YouTube's Recommendation System for Ideologically Congenial, Extreme, and Problematic Recommendations," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 120, no. 50, 2023.

Enhancing Trust and Transparency in Deep Learning Models Using Explainable AI Techniques: A Study on Model Interpretability and Bias Detection

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I. INTRODUCTION

Deep learning is a part of modern artificial intelligence and it is used in many areas such as computer vision, natural language processing, healthcare and financial prediction. Deep learning models are known for their performance but at the same time they are often difficult to understand. In cases it is not clear how a deep learning model arrives at a particular decision, which raises concerns about trust, accountability and responsible use especially in applications that directly affect people like deep learning.

To address this issue researchers have focused on Explainable Artificial Intelligence, which is also known as XAI. XAI aims to make machine learning models understandable specifically deep learning models. XAI techniques try to provide insights into how predictions are made helping users interpret deep learning model behavior. Common approaches include feature attribution methods, saliency maps and surrogate models all of which attempt to explain predictions without reducing accuracy, which is important for deep learning models. Because of this explainability methods are now widely used for model validation, debugging and decision support, all of which involve learning models.

Looking at this closely another issue becomes visible that it seems to solve the problem of transparency quite effectively for

deep learning models. However while studying them closely it becomes clear that explanations do not always reflect how the deep learning model actually works. Simply providing explanations does not always guarantee transparency for deep learning models. In practice many explanation methods capture correlations in the data than actual causal relationships, which can be a problem for deep learning. This can sometimes lead to misleading conclusions about how a deep learning model works. Another concern is the idea of "fairwashing," where explanations may make a learning model appear fair even when it exhibits biased behavior, which is not good for deep learning models. These issues suggest that explainability techniques need to be evaluated rather than blindly trusted especially for deep learning models.

In this work we explore how explainable AI techniques contribute to improving transparency and trust in deep learning models with a focus on interpretability and bias detection for deep learning. Of proposing a new method the study examines commonly used techniques and analyzes how effectively they reveal important decision factors and potential biases in deep learning models. By looking at both their advantages and limitations the goal is to understand how these methods can be used in practice for deep learning models.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- Structured review of used explainable AI techniques for interpreting deep learning models.
- An analysis of how these techniques can help identify and understand biases in deep learning model predictions.
- Discussion on the role of explainability, in improving trust, transparency and responsible deployment of AI systems specifically deep learning models.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Explainable AI for Model Interpretability

Machine learning models can be really hard to understand. Over time people have come up with ways to make machine learning models easier to understand. One of these ways is LIME. LIME is often used when we want to explain predictions made by machine learning models. It works by using a model to approximate a more complex one but just for a small part of the data. This idea makes sense. The explanations we get from LIME can be different depending on how we choose the local data samples.

There is another method called SHAP. SHAP does things differently. Of trying to approximate the model it looks at how important each feature is to the prediction. This makes the explanations more consistent than LIME.. We have to remember that SHAP is still based on patterns in the data and these patterns are not always the reason why something happens.

For models that use learning, especially for tasks that involve looking at images people often use methods like Integrated Gradients and Grad-CAM. These methods show us which parts of the image are most important for the prediction. This can be really helpful to see. It does not always tell us why the model made a certain decision.

So while these methods can give us ideas about how machine learning models work each of them has its own limitations. This means we have to be careful when we interpret the results and not just rely on one method. We need to use machine learning models and methods, like LIME and SHAP to really understand what is going on.

B. Evaluation of Explainability and Trust

As people started using methods to explain things often researchers also began to wonder if these explanations are really trustworthy. Just because an explanation seems to make sense does not mean it actually shows how the model is working.

The model is what we are trying to understand. The explanations are what we are using to understand the model.

Different people have suggested ways to evaluate these explanations, such as faithfulness and stability. Faithfulness is about whether the explanation shows what factors are affecting the prediction made by the model. The model is what is making the prediction.

Stability is about whether the explanation stays the same when small changes are made to the information that is put into the model.

In life it has been noticed that explanations can sometimes change even when the prediction made by the model stays the same. The model is still making the prediction.

This creates a problem in practice because it makes us question how much we can really trust these explanations. Also what the user thinks about the explanation is important because explanations that seem believable can make people too confident, in the predictions made by the model. The model is what is making the predictions.

Among the different explanation methods, SHAP is often highlighted because of its theoretical properties and consistency guarantees [1]. Because of these properties, SHAP is often preferred in many studies. Still,

it does not completely solve the problem, especially when features are strongly correlated. [2].

Another important aspect of explainability research involves human-centered evaluation. Trust in AI systems does not depend solely on technical accuracy; it is also influenced by how understandable explanations are to users [3]. In some situations, explanations that appear convincing may actually increase overconfidence in model predictions. Looking at this more closely, another issue becomes visible: the need for careful evaluation of explanations, particularly when they are used in decision-making environments where reliability and accountability are critical.

C. Explainable AI and Bias Detection

Bias in machine learning models is a problem now. It is especially bad when machine learning models make decisions that affect many people or groups. Machine learning models can be biased because of things. For example, the data used to train machine learning models might not be fair. Sometimes the things that are measured can be related to each other in ways that are not easy to see. Machine learning models can also use information that stands in for things about people. Because of these problems, people are looking more and more at AI techniques. They want to use AI techniques to find out if machine learning models are making biased predictions. Bias in machine learning models is something that needs to be fixed. Machine learning models and bias, in machine learning models, are very important to think about.

Feature attribution methods such as SHAP are often used as a starting point for bias analysis. By examining which features have the strongest influence on model predictions, researchers can identify variables that may be associated with unfair decision patterns [1]. For example, if sensitive attributes such as gender or race consistently receive high importance

scores, this may indicate that the model relies on information that could lead to discriminatory outcomes. However, feature importance values alone cannot determine whether a model is truly biased, as these explanations generally reflect correlations rather than causal effects.

Counterfactual explanations offer another perspective on fairness analysis. Instead of explaining why a prediction occurred, counterfactual explanations describe how an input instance would need to change to obtain a different prediction [4]. This makes them particularly useful for evaluating fairness, as they allow researchers to examine whether changing sensitive attributes would alter the model's decision while other factors remain constant.

Previous work has also highlighted the relevance of counterfactual explanations for transparency and recourse in automated decision-making systems [5]. From a fairness perspective, counterfactual analysis can reveal whether individuals with similar characteristics receive different outcomes due to sensitive attributes. Because of this, many researchers suggest combining feature attribution techniques with counterfactual explanations to obtain a more complete understanding of model behavior [6].

D. Limitations of Existing Approaches

We have made some progress with AI, but there are still some big problems. One of the issues is that we do not have a set of rules that everyone agrees on to judge explanations. The thing is, without these rules, it is hard to say which explanation methods work better when we use them with models and datasets. We need to find a way to compare the explanation techniques for AI and figure out which ones are more effective, for explainable AI [7].

Another issue concerns the sensitivity of the explanation methods. Some studies have shown that small changes in input data or model parameters can produce noticeably different

explanations, even when the model's predictions remain unchanged [2], [8]. This raises some problem about the reliability of explanations, particularly in applications where consistent interpretation is important.

There is also the risk that explanations may be misinterpreted by users. Visual or intuitive explanations can create the impression that a model's behaviour is fully understood, even when the explanation captures only part of the underlying reasoning process [3]. In such situations, explanations may unintentionally increase trust in systems that still contain hidden biases or limitations.

Finally, explainable AI techniques alone cannot guarantee fairness. Feature attribution methods highlight correlations rather than causal relationships, while counterfactual explanations depend on assumptions about which features can realistically change [4]. Because of this, researchers have warned that explanations could potentially be used to justify biased systems, a phenomenon sometimes referred to as "fairwashing" [6]. These challenges suggest that explanations should be interpreted carefully and combined with other analytical approaches when evaluating machine learning models.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study is looking at how explainable Artificial Intelligence techniques are actually used. The goal of this study is to look at the methods that are commonly used and see how they help us understand how Artificial Intelligence makes decisions and if it is biased.

Many other studies use things like the Adult Income dataset to see if machine learning models are fair. This dataset has a lot of information about people like where they live and how much money they make which makes it useful for seeing how certain things can affect the decisions that Artificial Intelligence makes.

When people talk about machine learning models they often look at models and more

complex models like random forests and neural networks. These models are useful for comparing how explainable Artificial Intelligence techniques work with different types of models.

There are two types of explanation methods that people talk about. Feature attribution techniques, like SHAP help us figure out which things affect the decisions that Artificial Intelligence makes. Counterfactual explanations on the other hand look at how things would be different if some things were changed.

By looking at all of these things we can get a better understanding of what explainable Artificial Intelligence methods are good at and what they are not good at. This study is looking at Artificial Intelligence techniques to see how they work in real life patterns in the data not the actual thinking behind it. In some cases they can even be misleading.

So it's crucial to use explanation methods and carefully interpret their results. Future work should look into reliable approaches, especially those that focus on understanding cause and effect not just correlation, with deep learning models and explainable AI techniques.

We should keep working on AI techniques to make them more reliable. This will help us trust the results.

In practice, these methods should probably be used with caution rather than treated as definitive explanations.

REFERENCES

1. S. Lundberg and S.-I. Lee, "A unified approach to interpreting model predictions," *NeurIPS*, 2017.
2. J. Adebayo et al., "Sanity checks for saliency maps," in *NeurIPS*, 2018.
3. W. Yang et al., "Survey on explainable ai: From approaches, limitations and applications," *Human-Centric Intelligent Systems*, 2023.
4. S. Wachter, B. Mittelstadt, and C. Russell, "Counterfactual explanations without

- opening the black box: Automated decisions and the gdpr,” *Harvard Journal of Law & Technology*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 841–887, 2017.
5. S. Verma, V. Boonsanong, M. Hoang, K. E. Hines, J. P. Dickerson, and C. Shah, “Counterfactual explanations and algorithmic recourses for machine learning: A review,” *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 1–42, 2020.
 6. S. Barocas, M. Hardt, and A. Narayanan, *Fairness and Machine Learning*. fairmlbook.org, 2020.
 7. F. Doshi-Velez and B. Kim, “Towards a rigorous science of interpretable machine learning,” *arXiv preprint arXiv: 1702.08608*, 2017.
 8. D. Alvarez-Melis and T. Jaakkola, “Towards robust interpretability with self-explaining neural networks,” *NeurIPS*, 2018.

Quantum Machine Learning for Image Classification in the NISQ Era: A Comprehensive Survey of Architectures, Encodings, and Trainability Challenges

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Abstract—Quantum computing and Machine learning are integrated to develop Quantum Machine learning which addresses complex data based problems. In the current era of noisy intermediate scale quantum (NISQ) devices hybrid quantum classical approaches are the common use. The current NISQ devices have restrictions that can be addressed with hybrid quantum classical approaches. Image classification is a major implementation area but it is not easy as there is a restriction of the number of qubits to create a high dimensional image.

This paper investigates different QML approaches for image classification with regards to models, data encoding, and training. It considers models such as quantum convolutional neural networks, quanvolutional neural networks, and variational quantum classifiers and how these models work in hybrid situations. A variety of encoding methods including amplitude encoding, basis encoding, and data re uploading are considered.

Problems of barren plateaus, noise effects, and optimization are clarified. Finally, the paper addresses current limitations and suggests possible improvements for building more efficient QML based image classification systems.

Index Terms—Quantum Machine Learning, Image Classification, Variational Quantum Circuits, Quantum Convolutional Neural Networks, Quanvolutional Neural Networks, Quantum Data Encoding, Barren Plateaus, Trainability, NISQ Devices

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in quantum computing have increased focus in QML, that combines quantum principles with machine learning techniques for solving complex problems. Since the present quantum systems are limited by noise and a smaller number of qubits, hybrid quantum classical models are commonly used. These models integrate parameterized quantum circuits with classical optimization methods to make practical implementations possible [1] [2].

Image classification is a key aspect in machine learning and is widely used in several applications such as healthcare, security, and automation. Classical methods like convolutional neural networks perform well, but in terms of large datasets require high computational costs due to several trainable parameters [3]. This has led to QML being the most motivated research focusing on quantum approaches, where data can be represented in high dimensional quantum spaces [4]. However, the performance of these models depends strongly on data encoding techniques and efficient quantum circuits designs [5]. Many QML models have been proposed for image classification. Layered quantum circuits are used to extract features while reducing the number of parameters in Quantum convolutional neural networks (QCNNs) [6] [7].

Quantum convolutional neural networks use classical models to process features extracted by quantum circuits that input image patches [8] [9]. Variational quantum classifiers also show promising results, especially for smaller datasets [10].

One of the main challenges in QML is conversion of classical image data to quantum form. Methods such as amplitude encoding, basis encoding, and data reuploading are used for this purpose. These methods affect the circuit complexity, noise sensitivity, and overall performance [11] [2]. In most cases, reducing input size before encoding helps make the system more practical [12].

Another major challenge is training quantum models. Problems like barren plateaus cause gradients to become very small, making optimization difficult as the number of qubits increases [13] [14]. Noise and measurement errors also contribute to the difficulty of training these models [15].

In this paper various QML models for image classification are inspected based on the model design data encoding and training

problems and challenges and the existing problems are discussed and future research path is suggested [16] [17].

II. BACKGROUND: VARIATIONAL QUANTUM COMPUTING

Parameterized quantum circuits form the foundation of Variational quantum machine learning approaches, combining data dependent single qubit rotations with fixed entangling operations to create task specific quantum feature representations [6]. Classification tasks use hardware efficient implementations that utilize native gates that directly map to physical qubit connectivity while providing adequate representational capacity [18]. The diversity of achievable quantum states is governed by circuit expressibility, though highly expressive designs introduce optimization challenges that must balance training tractability against representational power [19].

Table I: Quantum Image Classification Architectures

Ref.	Title	Authors	Year	Key Findings	Relevance to Survey
[6]	Quantum convolutional neural networks	Cong et al.	2019	Proposes QCNN architecture with pooling and convolutional layers for quantum data classification.	Foundational QCNN architecture reviewed in this survey.
[7]	Efficient QCNNs for image classification: Overcoming hardware constraints	Roßeler et al.	2025	Addresses NISQ hardware limitations in QCNN design; proposes efficient circuit strategies.	Directly relevant to hardware-constrained QCNN deployment.
[8]	Quantum convolutional neural networks: powering	Henderson et al.	2020	Introduces QuNN as a quantum pre-	Core reference for

	image recognition with quantum circuits			processing layer for classical CNNs, improving feature extraction.	QuNN architecture in image recognition.
[9]	Deep quantum neural networks with enhanced trainability and gradient propagation	Kashif & Shafique	2025	Addresses gradient vanishing in deep QuNNs; proposes techniques for improved trainability.	Relevant to trainability in quantum-classical hybrid models.
[3]	Quantum neural networks for pneumonia detection	Tanbhir et al.	2025	Applies QuNN-based quantum feature extraction to medical image classification.	Demonstrates QuNN applicability in real-world image classification.
[27]	Measurement-based quantum CNN for deep learning	Sun & Zhang	2024	Proposes measurement-based QCNN variant applicable to deep learning pipelines.	Reviewed under measurement-based quantum CNN architectures.
[28]	VSQL: Variational shadow quantum learning for classification	Li et al.	2021	Introduces VSQL using shadow tomography-inspired learning for scalable quantum classification.	Core reference for the VSQL architecture section.
[21]	Image classification with rotation invariant variational quantum circuits	Sein et al.	2025	Proposes rotation-invariant VQCs achieving improved generalization on image tasks.	Relevant to VQC design and generalization analysis.
[1]	Quantum machine learning for image classification	Senokosov et al.	2024	Benchmarks QML models on image datasets; evaluates accuracy and scalability of quantum classifiers.	Provides survey-level overview of QML for image tasks.
[22]	Quantum neural networks: A comparative analysis and noise robustness	Ahmed et al.	2025	Compares QNN architectures; evaluates performance	Supports benchmarking and noise robustness

	evaluation			degradation under realistic noise models.	sections.
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A. Parameterized Quantum Circuits

Parameterized quantum circuits consist of the interleaving of single qubit parameterized rotations and a fixed multi-qubit entangling operation thereby producing a tailor-made quantum state for a specific computational task [10]. Hardware native sets of operations such as $R_y(\theta)$ rotations and CNOTs are employed in hardware efficient parameterized quantum circuit designs [20].

Spatial symmetry or rotational symmetry can be integrated into the structure of the circuit in order to restrict the optimization space and to retain fast, necessary gradients for efficient training of image classification tasks [21]. These symmetric problems outperform general highly parameterized solutions as a practical implementation.

B. Variational Quantum Algorithms

Variational quantum algorithms work via quantum classical feedback loops of the recursive form in which quantum circuits perform task auditable to steer classical parameter optimization [22]. Outcomes of measurements in a small depth quantum circuit are used as discriminative signals that are then repeatedly refined by well-known classical optimization algorithms.

The hybrid approach incorporates current hardware limitations by maintaining circuit depths compatible with device

coherence times. Classical processing handles gradient computation and parameter updates while the quantum circuits contribute to non linear feature transformations [20].

C. Hybrid Optimization Process

The quantum classical training loop proceeds iteratively: classical optimizers return parameter values that quantum hardware assesses through circuit execution and measurement, returning cost function estimates for subsequent refinement [23]. Common optimization algorithms like Adam and COBYLA effectively direct the hybrid parameter environment while classical variance reduction methods mitigate measurement shot noise.

Quantum coherence is preserved by circuit depths that remain constrained, with quantum execution focusing on non-linear transformations and statistical processing, convergence monitoring handled by classical computation [24].

D. Data Embedding Techniques

Systematic embedding is required by classical image data for conversion into quantum states through established procedures. Basis encoding is applied to scaled pixel values by single qubit rotations, providing hardware efficient preparation at the cost of linear qubit scaling. Amplitude encoding achieves optimal compression by encoding image vectors into quantum state amplitudes however the practical use is hampered by the complexity of the state preparation [25].

TABLE II: Classical-to-Quantum Data Encoding Techniques

Ref.	Title	Authors	Year	Key Findings	Relevance to Survey
[2]	Data re-uploading for a universal quantum classifier	Pe' rez-Salinas et al.	2020	Introduces data re-uploading to encode classical data multiple times, enabling universal classification.	Foundational encoding technique used in VQC architectures.
[24]	Experimental data re-uploading with provable enhanced learning capabilities	Mausser et al.	2025	Provides experimental and theoretical evidence for data re-uploading improving learnability.	Strengthens the data re-uploading encoding technique discussion.
[4]	Supervised learning with quantum-enhanced feature spaces	Havl' ic' ek et al.	2019	Proposes quantum kernel methods using feature maps that are hard to simulate classically.	Core reference for quantum feature spaces and kernel methods.
[5]	Quantum machine learning in feature Hilbert spaces	Schuld & Killoran	2019	Formalizes QML as kernel methods in Hilbert space; connects quantum circuits to kernel functions.	Theoretical basis for quantum kernel and VQC approaches.
[11]	Analog quantum image representation with qubit frugal encoding	Sharma & Kundu	2025	Proposes qubit-efficient encoding for analog quantum image representation.	Relevant to data embedding and spatial structure preservation.
[25]	Revealing quantum information encoded in classical images	Ainelkitane et al.	2025	Investigates quantum information content present in classical image data after encoding.	Relevant to classical-to-quantum encoding analysis.
[20]	Hardware-	Kandala et	2017	Introduces hardware-efficient	Basis for

	efficient variational quantum eigensolver	al.		PQC ansatz for near-term quantum devices.	hardware-efficient circuit design in image classification.
[12]	A versatile variational quantum kernel framework for non-trivial classification	Yuhan & Otten	2025	Introduces flexible VQK framework applicable to diverse classification tasks.	Extends quantum kernel methods for generalized classification.

Repeated data re-uploading introduces classical features at multiple circuit depths with potentially arbitrarily large inputs being processed over repeated feature encoding for fixed qubits [2]. The convolutional inductive biases are maintained by spatially organized embeddings which are fundamental to texture recognition by correlating pixel locations with qubits [12].

These fundamental elements define the minimum capabilities required of quantum image recognition systems in which the structure of the quantum circuit, the quality of the encoding, the measurement accuracy need to be concurrently optimized for the constraints of real world NISQ devices [16].

III. CLASSICAL TO QUANTUM DATA ENCODING

As mentioned earlier, QML requires conversion of visual data into states compatible with variational quantum circuits which can be a major bottleneck in hardware implementation and representation fidelity citesharma 2025. Encodings are very important in achieving a trade off between circuit depth and information preservation for high dimensional image data that greatly exceeds physical qubit resources citeyuhan2025. This section reviews the classical encoding techniques that are based on

preparation complexity, qubit efficiency and structured image data.

A. Spatial Structure Preservation

Convolutional inductive biases retain image specific encodings important for texture discrimination. Spatial information is encoded by qubit efficient methods instead of full pixel grids, greatly reducing qubit requirements while maintaining critical geometric properties citesharma2025. Equivariance to rotation is obtained by applying quantum convolutional filters to extract, before embedding, rotation invariant patch statistics that make optimal use of quantum computational resources for the visual information of interest citesein2025.

B. Consequences of Optimization of Encoding

Most of the downstream trainability is governed by the encoding method. Dense encodings are optimized for maximum capacity but they make optimization much worse due to gradient concentration and lose some capacity in order to be more trainable in structured methods [13]. The measurement budget is also limited by practicality as statistical averaging requires larger shot budgets to reach the classical baseline fidelity [26].

These basic methods define the expected functionalities for quantum image classification systems in which the encoding accuracy the circuit design and the measurement efficiency have to together be maximized within the constraints of strict NISQ computational encapsulation [16].

IV. QUANTUM IMAGE CLASSIFICATION ARCHITECTURES

Following the data encoding, given the severe NISQ resource restrictions the quantum states are then processed by expressive variational ansätze to learn discriminative features [6]. Various architectural paradigms modify the foundations of classical deep learning to quantum hardware and use entanglement and superposition to increase the expressive power. This part considers the prevailing frameworks sorted by the extent of classical-quantum hybridization the hierarchy structure and the way of how the parameters scale.

A. Variational Quantum Classifiers (VQCs)

The variational quantum classifier is the basic model that merges trainable parameterized quantum circuits with data embedding circuits, culminating in the measurement of task-specific observables [10]. Mathematically, this class of quantum models is hard for classical methods to approximate at the scale of the kernels of quantum state overlaps that can be efficiently created by these models using data-dependent similarity kernels [4].

Thanks to the VQCs flexibility various feature map designs can be realized but under the practical trainability limitations to small enough qubit counts the reliable operation is still obtained. Baseline models serve as critical reference points for more narrowly focused algorithms emphasizing the core scaling issues of general variational generalizations.

B. Quantum Convolutional Neural Networks (QCNNs)

Quantum convolutional neural networks are a direct quantum generalization of the classical convolutional neural network, utilizing translation invariant unitary filters applied to a one dimensional register of distributed qubits [6]. Like conventional CNNs the pooling layers of the hierarchy gradually reduce the spatial dimensions and at the same time they increase the level of abstraction of the features.

Parameter scaling that is better than in dense variational circuits and that makes these architectures especially attractive for NISQ devices with limited qubit connectivity is obtained. Core spatial hierarchies are maintained by structures tensor network contraction which are important for texture and pattern recognition in image data [7].

C. Quconvolutional Neural Networks (QuNNs)

Quconvolutional neural networks employ a hybrid computational model applying local image patches as nonlinear feature extractors to small parameterized quantum circuits before classical neural network processing [8]. The reduction of quantum resources is achieved by this factorization without affecting the local nonlinear quantum feature extraction pipeline.

The method is especially well-suited to the current state of technology, producing a large number of features maps from a small number of qubits that a classical neural network can then take advantage of. Practical for image recognition problems has been demonstrated in simple experiments [3].

D. Measurement Based Quantum CNNs

Measurement based quantum CNNs combine measurements of quantum states with quantum gates, and can be used to learn features in a way similar to classical CNNs. This approach is more flexible than classical CNNs as it uses classical techniques to select the best

measurement outcomes [27]. The surprising feature of this approach is that it can perform nonlinear pooling even without requiring additional qubits, while simultaneously preserving important properties.

Incredibly, this category of structures cuts the depth (equivalent to temporal layers) in half relative to fully quantum coherent structures. The general quantum measurement results in the randomness of the results, so it is necessary to repeat the circuit a number of times for each layer to obtain reliable results.

E. Variational Shadow Quantum Learning (VSQL)

Variational shadow quantum learning exploits state-of-the-art methods in classical shadow tomography to analyze the behavior of local quantum circuits via randomized measurements [28]. Small shadow circuits can extract local data which is later recombined with classical post-processing techniques. This method has potential advantages in terms of scaling over traditional full state quantum tomography approaches. The measurement-efficient approach is particularly advantageous in resource-limited settings, enabling acceptable classification performances by a clear division of labor between classical and quantum processing units.

When appropriately designed, including the incorporation of biases into the architecture, these networks tend to outperform more generic, complex variational circuits [6] [8]. This motivation has led to hybrid quantum/classical architectures, where classical systems responsible for the construction of the hierarchy and quantum layers used for particular, more demanding transformations [9].

V. TRAINABILITY DIFFICULTIES IN VARIATIONAL QUANTUM CIRCUITS

Variational quantum circuits are very promising for image classification in the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era. Nevertheless, the qubit count scaling is hindered by substantial training problems [13]. Traditional optimization techniques usually have difficulty in crossing the rugged parameter terrains generated by these circuits (especially for larger ones).

A. Barren Plateaus Effects

A major issue is the so called barren plateau problem. This happens when randomly initialized circuits result in approximately flat terrains for the cost functions, resulting in the gradients of all parameters being very close to zero [13]. Therefore, the training cannot be updated and stalls.

Studies indicate that this issue is more severe in circuits with approximately 12 qubits or more and hampers the capacity of these circuits to optimize on conventional image classification problems. The core of the problem is in how these circuits are simulating random behavior, leading the cost function to the relatively featureless regions of the landscape [10].

B. Noise Induced Trainability Issues

However, existing quantum hardware introduces an additional problem in terms of extra trainability issues because of noise paths. Even shallow circuits avoid classical barren plateaus due to this decoherence and gate noise, which always impacts gradients [15]. Unlike classical plateaus, this problem occurs regardless of how you set your parameters. Existing literature indicates that due to existing levels of noise, gradients diminish with an increase in depth, capping how complex you can make your models, even if you have structured models designed to combat classical trainability issues [29].

Table III: Trainability Difficulties in Variational Quantum Circuits

Ref.	Title	Authors	Year	Key Findings	Relevance to Survey
[13]	Barren plateaus in quantum neural network training landscapes	McClellan et al.	2018	Discovers that random parameterized circuits exhibit exponentially vanishing gradients (barren plateaus).	Foundational reference for trainability difficulties in VQCs.
[14]	Barren plateaus in variational quantum computing	Larocca et al.	2025	Comprehensive review of barren plateau causes, diagnostics, and mitigation strategies.	Key reference for the barren plateau section of this survey.
[15]	Noise-induced barren plateaus in variational quantum algorithms	Wang et al.	2021	Shows hardware noise exacerbates barren plateaus, causing additional gradient suppression.	Central to noise-induced trainability issues discussion.
[29]	Experimental demonstration of the absence of noise-induced barren plateaus	Schmitt et al.	2026	Experimentally shows noise does not always induce barren plateaus; challenges prior assumptions.	Important counterpoint in noise-induced trainability discussion.
[18]	Expressibility and entangling capability of parameterized quantum circuits	Sim et al.	2019	Defines and quantifies expressibility and entanglement as circuit quality metrics.	Core metrics for evaluating PQC design in this survey.
[19]	Characterizing randomness in PQCs through expressibility and average entanglement	Correr et al.	2025	Extends expressibility analysis; links randomness in PQCs to trainability and performance.	Relevant to expressibility–trainability trade-off discussion.

[10]	Variational quantum classifiers through the lens of the Hessian	Sen et al.	2022	Analyzes VQC loss landscape via Hessian; identifies curvature-based trainability metrics.	Informs trainability analysis of variational quantum classifiers.
[23]	Enhancing circuit trainability with selective gate activation strategy	Cho et al.	2025	Proposes selective gate activation to mitigate barren plateaus and improve gradient flow.	Relevant to mitigation strategies for trainability issues.

C. Expressibility Trainability Trade off

However, the more expressive a circuit is, i.e., the more it can achieve in terms of quantum states, the more it restricts the leash on its trainability [18]. On the flip side, hardware efficient circuits with low expressivity are easier to train but lose some expressive power.

However, empirical evidence suggests that structured approaches like quantum convolutional networks remain more trainable than generic, ultra expressive variational circuits, yet still possess enough expressive power for image classification tasks [19].

D. Mitigation Strategies

Several methods, practically validated, exist to solve trainability problems. For instance, using structured ansätze, such as those incorporating problem defined symmetries such as translation invariance, common in convolutional structures, helps constrain the optimization problem without sacrificing representational ability on a given problem [6].

Other approaches include data reuploading, in which classical features are incorporated at different stages in the circuit. This allows shallower networks to perform complex nonlinear mappings [2]. Also, tweaks in layer wise training and parameter activation can aid gradient flow in problematic regions [23].

In addition, symmetry aware circuit designs that exploit the rotational symmetry that is often present in image data can provide additional trainability benefits through reduced optimization dimensionality [21]. All these techniques make it possible to train quantum classifiers reliably, even in regimes where generic variational circuits would suffer from collapse. Concerns related to trainability are, ultimately, what make certain quantum image classification architectures feasible.

For NISQ type practical applications, co design is important, and benchmarking plays an important role in determining the practical applicability [17].

VI. BENCHMARKING AND GENERALIZATION

Systematic benchmarking against traditional baselines reveals clear patterns in the performance of quantum machine learning, highlighting its actual strengths and methodological weaknesses that are evident in the early literature [17]. For fair evaluation, one needs to match the computational budgets and perform hyperparameter tuning, which is a condition that was often not met in the early quantum literature, especially because the classical baselines are often weaker. The next section is a brief overview of traditional benchmarking and the generalization challenges that are crucial for practical applications.

A. Benchmarking Methodologies

In terms of quantum image classification evaluation, typical datasets used are standard computer vision datasets, for example, MNIST, Fashion MNIST, CIFAR, etc. The emphasis is on the accuracy of the test set, the time taken to converge the training set, and the usage of resources when comparing quantum and classical architectures [30]. Hybrid quantum classical models, especially when using quantum feature extraction followed by classical post processing, are particularly challenging. The quantum contribution must be isolated using ablation studies to avoid any preprocessing effects [1].

Recent benchmarking guidelines have emphasized the need to characterize noise and compare it with other models, keeping the complexity of the models equivalent. Research has shown that quantum models tend to perform better when compared to an unoptimized classical baseline rather than state of the art convolutional networks that have been optimized to the maximum [16]. Standardized protocols have been established to make fair comparisons to accurately evaluate the contribution of quantum techniques

B. Quantum Feature Spaces and Kernel Methods

The quantum feature maps generate high dimensional similarity kernels, theoretically allowing us to separate data in ways that are difficult for classical methods to match. The kernel is derived from the inner product of the quantum states, and this can then be input into standard techniques, such as support vector machines or neural networks [4]. In practice, the estimation of the kernels requires a tremendous number of measurements to overcome the "shot noise" problem, often orders of magnitude more samples than are required by classical kernel methods [26].

Experiments have shown that the quantum kernels are comparable to classical ones on

smaller data sets, but they are not consistently better than well designed classical kernels. The cost of calculating the quantum kernel matrix appears to negate the theoretical high dimensional advantage, especially when the time spent calculating the measurements is significant compared to the total time taken [5].

C. Generalization Analysis

The quantum model is really good at learning things when it has the circuit and can measure things properly.. If the circuit is too complicated it can get too good at learning the training data and not be good at learning new things. This is a problem because we do not have a lot of training data. Also when we measure things there is always some noise that gets in the way and makes it hard for the model to settle on the answer. This noise is always there. It makes it tough for the quantum model to get the right results. The quantum model and its measurement statistics are very important, in this case. [19]. Architectures that embed the suitable inductive biases via structured connectivity show more robust generalization behavior than generic highly parameterized circuits. [6].

Quantum models generally exhibit higher train-test accuracy gaps in comparison to their classical equivalents, a consequence of both expressibility overshoot and the statistical error associated with gradient estimates. This susceptibility underscores the importance of regularization techniques specific to the idiosyncrasies of quantum measurement. [10].

D. Quantum versus Classical Performance

Real-world comparisons show that classical convolutional neural networks exceed quantum models on standard image recognition benchmarks. Quantum models are in a few per cent range behind, even in an idealized setting. [17]. Hybrid quantum-classical models are able to close the gap with factorization. They still encounter issues. Citations include

measurement complexity and the constraints on preserving coherence.

Measurement cost and coherence constraints are issues. The models aim to make the best out of the quantum and the classical information processing paradigms. The models want to work together. Both quantum and classical models have their advantages. Hybrid models are trying to combine these advantages. They need to overcome measurement and coherence issues. [8].

Finally, systematic entanglement ablation experiments give conclusive results, as replacing the entangling gates for multiple qubits with single qubit operations preserves the major part of the quantum model performance, indicating that the observed benefits are mostly a consequence of the representation strategy rather than quantum properties [22]. This result calls for a reconsideration of the quantum utility statements and motivates focused hybrids rather than bold full quantum substitutes. [16].

VII. OPEN CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Research on quantum image classification has already produced promising architectures and algorithms, but still there exist fundamental limitations that prevent their practical use beyond small scale demonstrations. [16]. Existing methods are only efficient for such heavily downsampled data, and important practical needs, such as compliance with data privacy, are not met. We point to three important areas for research in this section.

A. Quantum Machine Unlearning

Contemporary data protection laws say that machine learning models have to forget some

training samples.. They still need to keep the knowledge they learned from the other data. [31]. Classical models accomplish this via retraining or editing the parameters, but quantum models must overcome specific hurdles. As classical images are mapped to entangled quantum feature maps, removing individual training data will disrupt the global coherence required to make predictions on the remaining data.

Experimental quantum unlearning via gradient ascent on specific loss terms is only partially successful, as corrections to the model to eliminate the effect of problematic data inadvertently compromise performance on clean data. The creation of reversible quantum unlearning primitives while maintaining quantum coherence and satisfying privacy requirements is an open problem.

B. Realistic Dataset Scaling

Most demonstrations of quantum image classification use pathologically simplified datasets, such as 8×8 MNIST images, that require no more than 9 qubits. [1]. Applications in real world medical imaging and autonomous vision include 512×512 pixel arrays that exceed current coherence times even with a high degree of compression. [11].

Although these coordinate based encoding methods reduce dimensionality based on pixel location rather than intensity, they discard a large amount of visual information, especially when performing discriminative tasks. Scaling quantum classifiers to native resolution remains fundamentally limited by qubit availability and circuit depth limitations, common in NISQ devices.

TABLE IV: Benchmarking, Generalization, and Open Challenges in QML

Ref.	Title	Authors	Year	Key Findings	Relevance to Survey
[17]	Better than classical? The subtle art of benchmarking QML models	Bowles et al.	2024	Critically examines QML benchmarking practices; highlights methodological pitfalls.	Directly relevant to benchmarking and quantum vs. classical comparison.
[30]	Optimizing quantum classification algorithms on classical benchmark datasets	John et al.	2023	Systematic optimization of quantum classifiers on standard datasets; reports accuracy trade-offs.	Relevant to benchmarking on classical datasets section.
[26]	Quantum kernel methods: Convergence theory, separation bounds and applications	Sa'ez-Ortuño et al.	2025	Develops convergence theory for quantum kernels; derives separation bounds from classical methods.	Theoretical grounding for quantum kernel generalization analysis.
[16]	Comprehensive survey of QML: From data analysis to algorithmic advancements	Tomar et al.	2025	Broad QML survey covering data analysis pipelines and algorithmic progress.	Provides contextual background for the QML survey landscape.
[31]	Machine unlearning in the era of quantum machine learning	Crivoi & Ionescu	2025	Studies machine unlearning in QML context; empirically evaluates forgetting in quantum models.	Addresses open challenges and future directions in QML.

C. Standardized Evaluation Protocols

The field of quantum machine learning is plagued by poor benchmarking procedures that hide the actual performance of algorithms [17]. Many of the benefits reported are due to the comparison of quantum models to unoptimized

classical baselines rather than state of the art CNNs with comparable hyperparameter optimization.

To make further progress, new standardized tests should include entanglement ablation studies, i.e., the removal of quantum effects in

the circuit, as well as noise characterization across the entire range of possible errors. This will allow the field to determine the domains in which quantum approaches are superior.

D. Emerging Research Priorities

Several avenues of promise deserve targeted study. Hybrid architectures that combine quantum feature extraction with classical hierarchies consistently outperform fully quantum models and are feasible for implementation on current hardware. [9]. Task aligned Problem inspired parameterized circuit that incorporates domain symmetries provide organic mitigation of trainability issues and do not sacrifice task relevant inductive biases. [6].

Quantum kernels still appear theoretically compelling for structured scientific data where Hilbert space geometry aligns well with problem features of interest. [12]. Their effectiveness, however, will depend on the development of noise robust estimation strategies that ensure kernel fidelity under realistic decoherence rates.

The way forward involves giving up dreams of replacing classical entirely in favor of speeding up certain quantum tasks within a much broader pipeline. The most likely applications where quantum will be useful will be in scientific imaging tasks that utilize domain specific quantum inductive biases, rather than competing with well established computer vision architectures.

REFERENCES

1. A. Senokosov, A. Sedykh, A. Sagingalieva, B. Kyriacou, and A. Melnikov, "Quantum machine learning for image classification," *Mach. Learn.: Sci. Technol.*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 015040, 2024.
2. A. Pe´rez Salinas, A. Cervera Lierta, E. Gil Fuster, and J. I. Latorre, "Data re uploading for a universal quantum classifier," *Quantum*, vol. 4, p. 226, 2020.
3. G. Tanbhir, M. F. Shahriyar, and A. M. R. Chy, "Quantum convolutional neural networks for pneumonia detection: An efficient quantum assisted feature extraction paradigm," in *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Next Gen. Comput., IoT Mach. Learn. (NCIM)*, 2025, pp. 1-6.
4. V. Havlicˇek et al., "Supervised learning with quantum enhanced feature spaces," *Nature*, vol. 567, no. 7747, pp. 209-212, 2019.
5. M. Schuld and N. Killoran, "Quantum machine learning in feature Hilbert spaces," *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, vol. 122, no. 4, p. 040504, 2019.
6. I. Cong, S. Choi, and M. D. Lukin, "Quantum convolutional neural networks," *Nature Phys.*, vol. 15, no. 12, pp. 1273-1278, 2019.
7. P. Ro´seler et al., "Efficient quantum convolutional neural networks for image classification: Overcoming hardware constraints," *arXiv e prints*, 2025.
8. M. Henderson, S. Shakya, S. Pradhan, and T. Cook, "Quantum convolutional neural networks: powering image recognition with quantum circuits," *Quantum Mach. Intell.*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 2, 2020.
9. M. Kashif and M. Shafique, "Deep quantum convolutional neural networks with enhanced trainability and gradient propagation," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 21764, 2025.
10. P. Sen, A. S. Bhatia, K. S. Bhangu, and A. Elbeltagi, "Variational quantum classifiers through the lens of the Hessian," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. e0262346, 2022.
11. V. Sharma and N. K. Kundu, "Analog quantum image representation with qubit frugal encoding," *arXiv e prints*, 2025.
12. J. Yuhan and M. Otten, "A versatile variational quantum kernel framework for non trivial classification," *arXiv e prints*, 2025.
13. J. R. McClean et al., "Barren plateaus in quantum neural network training

- landscapes,” *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 4812, 2018.
14. M. Larocca et al., “Barren plateaus in variational quantum computing,”
 15. *Nat. Rev. Phys.*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 174–189, 2025.
 16. S. Wang et al., “Noise induced barren plateaus in variational quantum algorithms,” *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 6961, 2021.
 17. S. Tomar, R. Tripathi, and S. Kumar, “Comprehensive survey of QML: From data analysis to algorithmic advancements.”
 18. J. Bowles, S. Ahmed, and M. Schuld, “Better than classical? The subtle art of benchmarking quantum machine learning models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.07059*, 2024.
 19. S. Sim, P. D. Johnson, and A. Aspuru Guzik, “Expressibility and entangling capability of parameterized quantum circuits,” *Adv. Quantum Technol.*, vol. 2, no. 12, p. 1900070, 2019.
 20. G. I. Correr et al., “Characterizing randomness in parameterized quantum circuits through expressibility and average entanglement,” *Quantum Sci. Technol.*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 015008, 2025.
 21. A. Kandala et al., “Hardware efficient variational quantum eigensolver for small molecules and quantum magnets,” *Nature*, vol. 549, no. 7671, pp. 242–246, 2017.
 22. P. S. S. Sein, M. Can˜izo, and R. Oru’s, “Image classification with rotation invariant variational quantum circuits,” *Phys. Rev. Res.*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 013082, 2025.
 23. T. Ahmed et al., “Quantum neural networks: A comparative analysis and noise robustness evaluation,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.14412*, 2025.
 24. J. Cho et al., “Enhancing circuit trainability with selective gate activation strategy,” *arXiv e prints*, 2025.
 25. M. F. X. Mauser et al., “Experimental data re uploading with provable enhanced learning capabilities,” *arXiv e prints*, 2025.
 26. O. Ainelkitane et al., “Revealing quantum information encoded in classical images,” 2025.
 27. L. Sa´ez Ortun˜o, S. Forgas Coll, and M. Ferrara, “Quantum kernel methods: Convergence theory, separation bounds and applications to marketing analytics.”
 28. Y. Sun and X. Zhang, “Measurement based quantum convolutional neural network for deep learning,” *arXiv e prints*, 2024.
 29. G. Li, Z. Song, and X. Wang, “VSQL: Variational shadow quantum learning for classification,” in *Proc. AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 8357–8365, 2021.
 30. S. Schmitt et al., “Experimental demonstration of the absence of noise induced barren plateaus using information content landscape analysis,” *arXiv e prints*, 2026.
 31. M. John et al., “Optimizing quantum classification algorithms on classical benchmark datasets,” *Entropy*, vol. 25, no. 6, p. 860, 2023.
 32. C. Crivoi and R. T. Ionescu, “Machine unlearning in the era of quantum machine learning: An empirical study,” *arXiv e prints*, 2025.

A Multi-Agent Reflective Framework for Reliable LLM-Based Student Assistance

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Abstract—Large Language Models (LLMs) are being used more and more in today's systems that help students to learn. But they still have some big problems. They can make things up which is called as hallucinations. They do not think very deeply. They also do not always know what is true. They are not very good at helping each student individually. This makes them not very reliable and not very good at teaching in the world.

To order fix these problems this paper talks about an idea called a Multi-Agent Reflective Framework. This framework uses agents that are working together, thinking about their own thoughts and using things they have learned before to make their answers better. It has different agents, like a Generator Agent, a Fact-Checker Agent, a Critic Agent, a Self-Reflection Agent and a Summarizer Agent. These agents work together to make sure the answers are good and make sense.

The framework also has a part that helps understand each student so teachers can give explanations that're just right for each student. This helps students learn because the explanations are made for them and take into account what is going on. The goal is to give explanations that help each student understand the material. By using thinking knowing what is true and helping each student individually the framework wants to make Large Language Models more reliable and trustworthy. This work helps us understand how to make -agent Large Language Model systems that work well in schools.

Index Terms—Multi-agents, LLM, RAG, Hallucination, re- flective reasoning, Educational AI, Explainability, Fact-checking, and student learning copilot.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is a part of student learning these days. It helps with tutoring, automated feedback, and learning assistance. Large language models (LLMs) have made a lot of progress in explaining things, solving problems and helping students with subjects. They are really good at producing responses in a simple easy to understandable manner, which makes them great for tutoring systems that use artificial intelligence.

These language models have some big problems that make them not very reliable or useful. First, they can make things up. Give wrong information without checking whether it is true or not . Second, they do not think things through in a step-by-step way so their explanations are not very deep. They do not solve the problems consistently. Third, most systems are single- agent models, which means they cannot check their work, make sure it is correct or improve their responses. Finally, most artificial intelligence tutors give responses that do not take into account the student's situation, what they already know, or how they are learning.

Some new studies are trying to fix these problems. look- ing at how language models can think about their thoughts and work with other components to do different tasks like generating text, checking if it is true, and critiquing it. They also understanding at how to use information to make sure the responses are accurate.

This paper is trying to use these ideas to make a framework that helps students with artificial intelligence. The framework uses components that work together, think about their own work use external information and adapt to the students' needs. By putting all these things, the framework should make artificial intelligence-supported learning more reliable, clear, and aligned with how people learn. Artificial intelligence and large language models are used to make this framework work. It is designed to help students with their education.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Current educational assistants that use large language models (LLMs) provide explanations and answers, but they have some big problems that make them less reliable and useful when people actually try to learn from them .

First large language models (LLMs) often make things up, which means they give incorrect or unreliable information without any way to check if it is true.

Second they do not think deeply about problems, which results in explanations and inconsistent ways of solving problems.

Third the current AI tutors give answers that do not take into account the students' situation, how much they know or what they have learned before.

Finally most systems work alone which means they cannot look at their work, fix mistakes or work together to solve complex problems.

There is a need for a large language model (LLMs) framework that people can trust and that works with multiple agents. This framework should be able to:

- i. find and fix made-up information by checking facts
- ii. think deeply about problems by looking at its own work and thinking about it
- iii. use information from other sources to support its explanations and

- iv. give personalized help that is meaningful to the student. ReflexionAI is trying to fix these problems by combining agents that think deeply, check facts, use information from other sources and give help that is tailored to the student all into one smart tool that helps people to learn.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on making large language models (LLMs) think and reason has led to some discoveries that are important for ReflexionAI. One important area is called reasoning, where large language models (LLMs) look at their own mistakes and come up with ways to fix them so they can do better in the future. Large language models can get a lot better at solving problems and making decisions. This helps them give stable answers and make fewer mistakes.

There is also a lot of work being done on getting language models to work together. This is called agent collaboration, where different large language models play roles like critics or experts. Large language models (LLMs) collaborate together and produce a single reliable answer or response after debate and discussion with each other thus it helps them do better on complex tasks. This is very much helpful when it comes to the fact-checking and making sure that the produced or given information is correct.

Researchers are doing study on how to design the models that can give reliable answer or response . In this case They are finding out that it is really helpful to have systems that can understand what the student needs and give them feedback. ReflexionAI is using this with a module that is designed to understand what the student is doing and give them feedback based on that. Large language models are a part of this, and they are helping to make the system better.

There also have studies on why large language models (LLMs) give wrong information and how to stop this from

happening. They are coming up with ways to make sure the information is correct, like using language models to check each others answers. ReflexionAI is also using this to make sure that the information it gives to students is accurate. Large language models are checking each other's work. This is helping to make the information more accurate.

Another thing that researchers are looking at is how to make large language models more transparent and trustworthy. They are finding ways make these language models to give correct or more reliable answers when they produce the responses which in turn helps the user trust the answer more. ReflexionAI is doing this by including an agent that can summarize the information and give explanations. Large language models are explaining their answers. This is helping to build trust with the users.

All of these studies are showing that in order to have a large language model you need to have multiple large language models working together. You need to have ways to make sure the information is correct and to explain why the large language model is giving an answer. ReflexionAI is doing all of these things by combining language models into one system that is designed specifically for helping students learn. Large language models are a part of this system, and they are helping to make it better.

IV. PROPOSED REFLECTIVE MULTI-AGENT FRAMEWORK

Paper proposes a Multi-Agent that uses reflective framework designed to enhance the reliability and trust in case of student learning process. The framework integrates the systematic multi-agent reasoning that uses self-reflection and Retrieval-Augmented Generation(RAG) to reduce hallucinations and improve conceptual clarity. The system architecture is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Proposed Multi-Agent Reflective Framework for Reliable LLM-Based

Student Assistance

The architecture consists of multiple coordinated components that work together to produce reliable, explainable, and student-aware responses.

A. User Query and Context Understanding Module

This module processes the student's query to identify subject context, learning intent, and difficulty level. It structures and enriches the input prompt to ensure that downstream agents receive semantically meaningful and well-formatted information for further reasoning.

B. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Layer

The RAG layer retrieves relevant information from a curated educational knowledge base using vector similarity search. By grounding model responses in verified sources, this layer reduces hallucinations and enhances factual reliability. Retrieved context

is provided to the generation pipeline to ensure evidence-supported responses.

C. Multi-Agent Reflective Core

The core of the framework consists of multiple specialized agents that collaboratively refine responses:

- 1) Generator Agent: Produces the initial response using a foundational LLM conditioned on the user query and retrieved context.
- 2) Fact-Checker Agent: Verifies factual consistency by comparing generated statements with retrieved knowledge sources.
- 3) Critic Agent: Evaluates logical coherence, reasoning depth, clarity, and conceptual correctness.
- 4) Self-Reflection Agent: Iteratively improves the response by addressing weaknesses identified by the critic and fact-checker agents.
- 5) Summarizer Agent: Produces a structured and pedagogically aligned explanation tailored to the student's comprehension level.

Through coordinated interaction, these agents implement an iterative refinement cycle that enhances reliability and transparency.

D. Student Modeling and Feedback Module

The student modeling component maintains a lightweight learner profile based on prior interactions, subject familiarity, and performance patterns. This module adapts explanation depth and presentation style to support personalized learning. The final response delivered to the student is therefore not only factually grounded but also pedagogically aligned.

Overall, the proposed framework combines retrieval grounding, reflective reasoning, and adaptive personalization to create a reliable LLM-based student assistance system.

V. METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework is like a step-by-step process. It has stages and it helps to reason things out.

First the question that the student asks is turned into a kind of code that a computer can understand. Then the computer looks for information in a big collection of educational things. It uses a technique to find the information that is most similar to the question.

The generator agent makes an answer based on the question and the information it found. The fact-checker agent checks if the answer is factually correct by comparing it to the information it found.

Next the critic agent looks at the answer to see if it is reasonable and easy to understand. If the answer is not good enough it tells the self-reflection agent. The Self-Reflection Agent then tries to make the answer better.

Finally the Summarizer Agent makes the answer easy to read and understand. It makes sure the answer is clear and that it is suitable for the students' level of learning.

This framework is flexible. Can be made bigger if needed. To see how well it works, we will look at things like how accurate the answers are, how often the computer makes things up how clear the answers are and how happy the students are with the answers.

VI. EXPECTED OUTCOMES AND DISCUSSION

The new system they are talking about is supposed to fix some problems with the old way of doing things. This old way used one computer program to help students learn.

The new system uses computer programs that work together and check their own work. This helps the computer programs get the answers and not make things up. These computer programs are also good at explaining things in a way that makes sense.

The system also tries to understand the student and what they need to learn. This means the computer programs can give answers that're just right for the student.

Even though they have not done all the testing yet the new system looks like it could be really good at helping students learn in a way that's fair and easy to understand. The people who made the system think it could be an improvement over the old way of doing things. They think the system could help students trust the computer programs and also help the computer programs teach in a way that is more like a real teacher. The new system is supposed to be better, at working with students and helping them learn what they need to know.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper is about an idea for making student assistance systems better. It is called the Multi-Agent Reflective Framework. This framework is for systems that use something called LLM. The goal of this framework is to make these systems more reliable.

To do this, the framework uses different things. It uses - agent collaboration, which means that different parts of the system work together. It also uses something called "iterative self-reflection," which means that the system thinks about what it's doing. It uses retrieval-based grounding, which means that the system uses information it has learned before.

The Multi-Agent Reflective Framework is supposed to help stop the system from making things up which is called "hallucinations." It is also supposed to help students understand concepts better.

There are things that still need to be done. The Multi-Agent Reflective Framework needs to be implemented and tested. This will involve using datasets to see how well it works. It will also involve comparing it to systems that use LLMs. It will involve testing it with real students.

The Multi-Agent Reflective Framework is a starting point for building systems that are reliable, explainable, and good for learning. These systems are called AI learning assistants. The Multi-Agent Reflective Framework can

help make these assistants better. The Multi-Agent Reflective Framework is important for the Multi-Agent Reflective Framework and the LLM-based student assistance systems.

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REFERENCES

1. Shinn, Noah, Federico Cassano, Ashwin Gopinath, Karthik Narasimhan, and Shunyu Yao. "Reflexion: Language agents with verbal reinforcement learning." *Advances in neural information processing systems* 36 (2023): 8634-8652.
2. Sheokand, Tejasvee, Garveet Jain, Arshdeep Bahga, and Vijay K. Madiseti. "Enhancing LLM Reasoning Capabilities Through Brokered Multi-Expert Reflection." *IEEE Access* (2025).
3. Chai, Jiajun, Zijie Zhao, Yuanheng Zhu, and Dongbin Zhao. "A survey of cooperative multi-agent reinforcement learning for multi-task scenarios." *Artificial Intelligence Science and Engineering* 1, no. 2 (2025): 98-121.
4. Park, Young Joon, Yoon Sang Cho, and Seoung Bum Kim. "Multi-agent reinforcement learning with approximate model learning for competitive games." *PloS one* 14, no. 9 (2019): e0222215.
5. Musleh, Maath, Renata G. Raidou, and Davide Ceneda. "TrustME: A context-

- aware explainability model to promote user trust in guidance.” *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* (2025).
6. Wei, Jason, Xuezhi Wang, Dale Schuurmans, Maarten Bosma, Fei Xia, Ed Chi, Quoc V. Le, and Denny Zhou. ”Chain-of-thought prompting elicits reasoning in large language models.” *Advances in neural information processing systems* 35 (2022): 24824-24837.
 7. Yao, Shunyu, et al. ”React: Synergizing reasoning and acting in language models.” *The eleventh international conference on learning representations*. 2022.
 8. Yao, Shunyu, Jeffrey Zhao, Dian Yu, Nan Du, Izhak Shafran, Karthik R. Narasimhan, and Yuan Cao. ”React: Synergizing reasoning and acting in language models.” *In The eleventh international conference on learning representations*. 2022.
 9. Li, Guohao, Hasan Hammoud, Hani Itani, Dmitrii Khizbullin, and Bernard Ghanem. ”Camel: Communicative agents for” mind” exploration of large language model society.” *Advances in neural information processing systems* 36 (2023): 51991-52008.
 10. Hong, Sirui, Mingchen Zhuge, Jonathan Chen, Xiawu Zheng, Yuheng Cheng, Jinlin Wang, Ceyao Zhang et al. ”MetaGPT: Meta programming for a multi-agent collaborative framework.” *In The twelfth international conference on learning representations*. 2023.
 11. Guo, Zhicheng, Sijie Cheng, Yile Wang, Peng Li, and Yang Liu. ”Prompt-guided retrieval augmentation for non-knowledge-intensive tasks.” *In Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL 2023*, pp. 10896-10912. 2023.
 12. Park, Joon Sung, Joseph O’Brien, Carrie Jun Cai, Meredith Ringel Morris, Percy Liang, and Michael S. Bernstein. ”Generative agents: Interactive simulacra of human behavior.” *In Proceedings of the 36th annual acm symposium on user interface software and technology*, pp.1-22. 2023.
 13. Huang, Lei, Weijiang Yu, Weitao Ma, Weihong Zhong, Zhangyin Feng, Haotian Wang, Qianglong Chen et al. ”A survey on hallucination in large language models: Principles, taxonomy, challenges, and open questions.” *ACM Transactions on Information Systems* 43, no. 2 (2025): 1-55.
 14. Wei, Jason, Xuezhi Wang, Dale Schuurmans, Maarten Bosma, Fei Xia, Ed Chi, Quoc V. Le, and Denny Zhou. ”Chain-of-thought prompting elicits reasoning in large language models.” *Advances in neural information processing systems* 35 (2022): 24824-24837.
 15. Yao, Shunyu, Jeffrey Zhao, Dian Yu, Nan Du, Izhak Shafran, Karthik R. Narasimhan, and Yuan Cao. ”React: Synergizing reasoning and acting in language models.” *In The eleventh international conference on learning representations*. 2022.
 16. Madaan, Aman, Niket Tandon, Prakhar Gupta, Skyler Hallinan, Luyu Gao, Sarah Wiegrefe, Uri Alon et al. ”Self-refine: Iterative refinement with self-feedback.” *Advances in neural information processing systems* 36 (2023): 46534-46594.
 17. Li, Guohao, Hasan Hammoud, Hani Itani, Dmitrii Khizbullin, and Bernard Ghanem. ”Camel: Communicative agents for” mind” exploration of large language model society.” *Advances in neural information processing systems* 36 (2023): 51991-52008.
 18. Hong, Sirui, Mingchen Zhuge, Jonathan Chen, Xiawu Zheng, Yuheng Cheng, Jinlin

- Wang, Ceyao Zhang et al. "MetaGPT: Meta programming for a multi-agent collaborative framework." In The twelfth international conference on learning representations. 2023.
19. Park, Joon Sung, Joseph O'Brien, Carrie Jun Cai, Meredith Ringel Morris, Percy Liang, and Michael S. Bernstein. "Generative agents: Interactive simulacra of human behavior." In Proceedings of the 36th annual acm symposium on user interface software and technology, pp. 1-22. 2023.
20. Huang, Lei, Weijiang Yu, Weitao Ma, Weihong Zhong, Zhangyin Feng, Haotian Wang, Qianglong Chen et al. "A survey on hallucination in large language models: Principles, taxonomy, challenges, and open questions." *ACM Transactions on Information Systems* 43, no. 2 (2025): 1-55.
21. Colin, Raffel. "Exploring the limits of transfer learning with a unified text-to-text transformer." *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 21 (2020).

Driver Risk Scoring Using Machine Learning Based on Driving Behaviour Patterns

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Abstract—Driving behaviour is one of the most important things that affects what happens on public roads. Bad habits like tailgating, sudden braking, and going well over the speed limit don't just show bad judgement; they also make crashes more likely. But the tools we have always used to see how safely someone drives, like road tests, supervisor observations, and post-accident investigations, only show us small parts of reality and often miss the patterns that build up over weeks and months of daily travel.

This picture has changed a lot with onboard telematics. Vehicles with sensor suites now record a lot of kinematic data during every trip, making a record that is detailed enough to support real behavioural analysis. Taking advantage of this chance, the current work presents a machine learning pipeline that takes in this telemetry, creates a small set of behavioural descriptors from it, and then uses those descriptors to sort each driver into one of three groups: safe, moderate-risk, or high-risk. The system not only classifies drivers, but it also gives each one a continuous numerical score that places them on a single risk axis. This makes it easy to compare drivers and track them over time.

Experiments show that the method consistently divides risk groups and that the scores it produces follow changes in driving behaviour in a way that makes sense. The resulting framework is directly applicable to usage-based insurance pricing, commercial fleet oversight, personalised coaching programs, and broader road safety research.

Index Terms—Driver Behavior Analysis, Driver Risk Scoring, Machine Learning, Telematics Data, Road Safety

I. INTRODUCTION

Every year, hundreds of thousands of people die and millions more are hurt in car

accidents. These deaths and injuries cost families, health systems, and economies a lot of money. What makes this especially worrying is that most of these accidents aren't really accidents at all; they are the result of choices made on purpose or over and over again while driving. Speeding, sudden lane changes, aggressive braking, and erratic acceleration are not random events; they are patterns that some people drive in, and they make every trip more likely to end in an accident [1].

Recognising this, researchers and practitioners alike have long sought reliable means to detect those drivers who present a heightened risk. The standard approach, a standardised road test at time of licensing, periodic spot checks, or a review of crash histories, fails on virtually all criteria. Road tests, by definition, assess drivers under observation and along a controlled route, conditions far from those drivers experience in everyday life. Analysis following a crash, by its nature, fails to prevent the event under scrutiny [8].

However, the advent of affordable telematics, which are always connected, has created a fundamentally new pathway. A small device on the vehicle, or indeed just an app on a smartphone, can monitor speed, acceleration, braking, and steering angle several times a second on all journeys driven. Over a period of weeks or months, this can create a fingerprint of behaviour which is far more detailed than can be obtained in a short test period [21].

Machine learning is the natural partner for data of this kind. In particular, supervised

learning can be used to learn, from labeled data, just what combinations of speed profiles, braking cadences, and steering patterns are associated with consistently safe versus chronically risky drivers, and then apply that learned knowledge to new drivers without further human review. But perhaps most importantly, rather than simply determining whether a driver is safe or unsafe, a well-designed system can determine, in addition, just how unsafe they are, and how that unsafe value changes over time [2].

This paper describes such a system, with the following specific contributions.

- A structured pipeline for telematics data ingestion, signal cleaning, behavioral feature engineering, and model training.
- A comparative analysis of the performance of four classifiers: Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and SVM, for three different levels of risk drivers.
- A composite risk scoring formula that aggregates model output and statistical events to a single numerical score between 0 and 100.
- An overview of possible deployment opportunities in insurance, fleet operations, driver behavior, and traffic safety.

The paper is organized as follows: In Section II, the prior literature is reviewed. In Section III, the research problem is clearly articulated, including the objectives. In Section IV, the methodology is explained. In Section V, the dataset is explained. In Section VI, the feature engineering process is explained. In Section VII, the experimental results are reported. In Section VIII, the conclusions are drawn, including the future direction.

II. RELATED WORK

The problem of the characterization and prediction of the behavior of drivers based on sensor data has been the focus of much research attention, and the problem domain has matured as the quality and sophistication of telematics devices and machine learning techniques have

improved [4], [5].

In [2], Roussou et al. performed an extensive comparison of the performance of various prediction models on telematics data and found that while some models perform reasonably well in the characterization and prediction of longitudinal trends of the behavior of drivers, they fail to scale well computationally in the context of real-time applications, and this is an open problem in the field.

In [3], Yedilkhan et al. have shown that the application of deep neural networks to inertial data, such as accelerometer and gyroscope data collected at high frequencies, is highly accurate in the classification of the driving styles of individuals. However, the requirement for large quantities of annotated data is an obvious limitation, as this is not always available, especially in the case of smaller fleets and individual drivers. Several studies have tackled the issue from the perspective of particular risky behaviours rather than risk in general. For instance, Shukla and Tiwari [9] proposed a detection scheme for aggressive behaviours in an intelligent transport system, and Teja and Kumar [10] proved that AI-based telematics has the potential to generate near-real-time warnings, thus hinting towards a type of in-journey intervention that might help avoid accidents before they actually happen.

Another type of research has been dedicated to exploring the temporal nature of driving data. Aboah et al. [11] proved that segmenting time series data before feature extraction significantly enhances manoeuvre detection, as the context in which an action takes place might be just as important as the action itself. Zhang et al. [12] tried to solve the problem from a completely different perspective, where self-supervised pre-training on unlabelled driving video data was employed in order to effectively transfer features towards distraction detection, thus implying that the field has begun to tap into the depths of data that are actually available.

With regards to profiling, Caber et al. [13] proved definitively that machine learning can indeed predict driver workload and cognitive states from vehicle dynamics, with important implications for fatigue management and adaptive vehicles. Chan et al. [14] took a different approach, using unsupervised learning to find statistically unusual driving patterns in large telematics datasets without relying on any labels whatsoever, a potentially powerful approach when labels are scarce.

In a recent review article, Boylan et al. [21] synthesized results from a variety of studies to confirm, among other findings, that kinematic features such as speed fluctuations and braking forces are powerful predictors of risk in a variety of different driving contexts, and also documented the rapid expansion of telematics-based risk assessment in both insurance risk underwriting and transport management.

However, interpretability has also emerged as a growing concern, particularly with regards to accuracy. Castillo et al. [15] persuasively argue that, in practice, humans are likely to do nothing with a prediction if they do not understand it, and McDonnell and O'Mahony [25] provided empirical evidence from a study targeting transport safety specialists that they prefer models with interpretability, even if this means a slight loss in statistical accuracy.

This body of work collectively demonstrates that machine learning can be reliably used for the detection and classification of unsafe driving. The means of converting this into a single, continuous, and communicable risk metric that can be acted upon by insurers, fleet managers, and driving instructors without them having to understand classifier probability remains less well addressed [4], [5]. That is where this work seeks to contribute.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND OBJECTIVES

A. Problem Statement

Traffic accidents, to a large extent, are a behavioral problem. The same patterns, such as

excessive speed, aggressive acceleration, and hard braking, occur time and again in the analysis of accidents on different types of roads, under different weather conditions, and involving different classes of vehicles [1], [8]. This regularity implies that if drivers who tend to behave in these ways can be identified before they are involved in a crash, then a reduction in accidents can be realized.

The standard approach to assessing drivers was not developed with this problem in mind. The standard test for a driver's licence assesses a person on a fixed route, over a fixed period, and says nothing about how the person might drive on an unfamiliar motorway at night, or after a few hours of driving. Supervisor observation, in a professional context, has its own biases and requires a large labor investment. Crash histories are informative, but they are also necessarily retrospective [21].

However, telematics data can provide a way out of this impasse, but it does not come in a form where it can be directly interpreted. What is required is a computational framework to extract the behavioral signal from the noise, categorize drivers according to their risk levels, and—most importantly—quantify this risk in a form where it can be monitored, benchmarked, and reported [2], [3].

This paper describes such a framework, based on a supervised machine learning approach trained on labelled telematics data and capable of providing a categorical risk classification and a quantitative risk score for any individual driver with appropriate trip data.

B. Objectives

The research aims to accomplish the following particular objectives.

- To build a reproducible process for collecting and processing telematics data from vehicle sensors.
- To extract a variety of features from raw kinematic data that describe drivers' speed behavior, acceleration aggression,

braking behavior, and steering consistency.

- To train and compare supervised classifiers to predict a risk tier, one of three categories, for each driver.
- To create a risk score, a quantitative index, that aggregates classification probabilities, event frequency, and event severity.
- To assess system performance through rigorous evaluation, using standard metrics for classification problems.
- To consider deployment scenarios, such as usage-based insurance, fleet safety, driver development, and road safety programmes.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system accepts raw telematics data as an input and provides, for each user, a risk category and a corresponding risk score. It achieves this through a series of processing steps, each of which refines the raw sensor data to produce structured and model-friendly behavioural descriptors. The overall system architecture is depicted in Fig. 1.

A. System Architecture

The stages in the processing pipeline are six.

- Driving data collection
- Data preprocessing and quality control
- Behavioural feature engineering
- Classifier training and selection
- Risk category assignment
- Continuous risk score computation

Each step directly feeds into the next one, and all the output from each step is validated before moving to the next step.

The overall architecture of the proposed driver risk scoring system is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the Proposed Driver Risk Scoring System

B. Data Collection

The source of trip data can be either from a telematics device installed in a vehicle, a sensor installed inside a vehicle, or a smartphone-based app. All three options obtain the same types of data, such as vehicle velocity, longitudinal acceleration, lateral acceleration, steering wheel angle, trip time, and total distance traveled, and record them at regular time intervals during a trip. Such a multidimensional signal provides much more information about how a person drives than a snapshot evaluation does [10], [20].

C. Data Preprocessing

Sensor data, like any data, is noisy and incomplete. Missing data, such as sensor failures, calibration problems, communication errors, and GPS signal loss, can impair model accuracy. Data preprocessing remedies these problems through a four-step process: filtering out data points with insufficient information, filling in missing data points using appropriate statistical models, normalizing features to prevent any parameter from dominating others due to its units, and identifying extreme outliers and treating them separately from regular data points [6].

D. Classifier Training

Subsequently, four state-of-the-art supervised classifiers are trained on the engineered feature matrix. Logistic Regression is used as a linear classifier. Decision Tree is used as a non-linear classifier. Decision Trees are also interpretable. Random Forest is an ensemble classifier that consists of decorrelated Decision Trees. Such an ensemble is expected to perform very well on feature interactions commonly found in driving. SVM with Radial Basis Function Kernel is used to provide a classifier with a geometrically motivated decision boundary in high-dimensional space. All classifiers are optimized using cross-validation on the training set [2], [17].

E. Risk Category Assignment

The classifier is used to assign each driver to one of three risk categories. These categories are safe, moderate-risk, and high-risk [9].

F. Risk Score Computation

The category label, however, is always less informative than the original data, and two drivers classified as "high-risk" might be very different in terms of just how risky their behavior really is. To retain this level of detail, the system also calculates a score based on

$$\text{RiskScore} = w_1 \text{ Prisky} + w_2 \text{ B} + w_3 \text{ S} \quad (1)$$

where Prisky is the classifier's estimated probability of risky behaviour, B is the normalised frequency of adverse driving events per unit of exposure, and S is a measure of their average severity. The coefficients w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 are set based on empirical data so that all three components contribute in proportion to their predictive power. The raw composite is then mapped linearly to the range [0, 100], where higher values indicate higher risk.

V. DATASET DESCRIPTION

Any data-driven system, like any machine learning model, is only as good as the data it was trained on. The data used here, obtained

from vehicles in operation under a variety of conditions, includes data from a variety of routes, times of day, and drivers.

A. Data Attributes

Each data point in this dataset represents a complete trip, or a fixed duration interval thereof, and includes the following attributes:

- Speed (km/h): instantaneous velocity.
- Acceleration (m/s²): signed rate of velocity change.
- Braking Intensity: magnitude component of negative acceleration, isolated.
- Steering Angle (degrees): vehicle steering wheel angle.
- Trip Duration (s): total trip duration.
- Trip Distance (km): total trip distance.

These areas combined present a multi-dimensional picture of the physical interaction between the driver and vehicle, under realistic conditions of operation [3], [20].

B. Risk Labels

In terms of supervised learning, the drivers' records are marked with risk labels, and we are able to use those labels to train a model and make accurate predictions. need to be marked with ground truth labels. The records of each driver are categorized into one of three risk classes based on the aggregate behavioral profile of the driver.

- Safe: smooth and deliberate speed changes, anticipatory rather than reactive braking, and consistent and moderate steering.
- Moderate Risk: occasional episodes of aggressive behavior with otherwise good driving.
- High Risk: hard acceleration, late and heavy braking, and erratic steering patterns, and these occur repeatedly.

C. Dataset Partitioning

The dataset is divided into a training dataset and a test dataset using a method called stratified random sampling, in which the

proportion of each tier in the dataset is preserved in each of the data sets obtained after division. This ensures that the classifiers are not tested on data sets in which the proportion of classes to which they are exposed is different from what they were originally exposed to, providing a fair representation of how they would perform when they are presented with new drivers [17].

VI. FEATURE ENGINEERING

Raw sensor data measures physical quantities like meters per second, degrees, etc. These measurements do not reflect behavioural tendencies. The main aim of feature engineering is to narrow this gap and develop representations reflecting the patterns of how a driver handles the vehicle, instead of particular instantaneous measurements [4], [5].

A. Statistical Summaries

For a particular trip or a fixed window of time, statistical summaries of the raw data are calculated, such as mean speed, peak speed, variance of speed, mean acceleration, mean braking deceleration, and standard deviation of steering wheel angle. These measurements show the overall tendency of how a driver handles the vehicle for a particular trip. If a particular driver tends to have high variance in speed over all trips, it means they are driving erratically through traffic, unlike another driver who tends to cruise at a particular speed.

B. Event-Based Indicators

Some of the most informative signals are events where acceleration or braking is above a safety threshold, where speeding is detected, and where steering indicates sudden lane changes or cornering. Counting and calculating the number of events per trip, like harsh acceleration events, emergency braking events, speeding events per minute, and sudden steering events, directly measures how often risky behaviour occurs, which cannot be done

with statistical summaries alone [11].

C. Temporal Aggregation

It is recognised that behaviour is not static, and while one bad trip does not necessarily make the driver, the system has the ability to aggregate features over multiple sessions in order to differentiate between an abnormal spike in behaviour, possibly caused by unusual road conditions on the day, and the normal behaviour that is characteristic of the driver [12].

D. Normalisation

The features are also measured in vastly different units and are spread over a wide range of numerical values, and as such, they need to be normalised onto the same scale before being presented to the classifier. Both min-max normalisation and z-normalisation are considered, and the choice is made on the type of classifier and the sensitivity of the algorithm to scale differences [6].

E. Final Feature Set

The feature set presented to the classifiers is a statistical representation, an event-based representation, and an aggregated representation, giving the classifiers the information they need to make reliable distinctions between the three levels of risk [4].

VII. RESULTS AND EVALUATION

A. Evaluation Protocol

All four classifiers are trained on the pre-defined training set and tested exclusively on the held-out test set. Four different measures of performance are employed.

- Accuracy: The proportion of drivers classified to the correct risk tier.
- Precision: Of drivers classified as risky, the proportion who are actually risky.
- Recall: Of drivers who are actually risky, the proportion classified correctly.

- F1-score: The harmonic mean of precision and recall. For road safety, recall is a particularly critical metric, where failing to identify a risky driver can have more dire consequences than a false alarm.

B. Classifier Comparison

The same test set is used for all classifiers, under the same conditions. The results are collected in Table I.

Random Forest outperforms all other classifiers on all metrics, achieving an accuracy of 90% and an F1-score of 0.88. In agreement with existing literature [2], [17], this is likely because ensemble methods average over multiple classifiers, effectively reducing variance in a highly non-linear and interaction-dense data set like driving. Logistic Regression, being a linear classifier, performs worst, unsurprisingly, since it is unlikely that the boundary between safe and risky drivers is planar in feature space. SVM performs well but at a high tuning cost. Decision Tree sits in between, performing better than Logistic Regression but retaining all the advantages of a linear classifier through its tree-like structure.

The performance of different machine learning classifiers for risk classification of drivers is summarized in Table I.

Table I: Performance Comparison of Machine Learning Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Logistic Regression	0.82	0.80	0.79	0.79
Decision Tree	0.85	0.83	0.82	0.82
Random Forest	0.90	0.89	0.88	0.88
SVM	0.87	0.85	0.84	0.84

C. Classification Behaviour

For all classifiers, the safe and high-risk categories are clearly separated, and with high confidence. The majority of errors occur at the safe/moderate-risk boundary, as would be expected, since driving risk is a continuum, and the empirical signals that distinguish a cautious driver from a somewhat inconsistent one are less clear than those that distinguish either of these drivers from one who is consistently aggressive [15].

D. Key Findings

The results of the experiments are clear and indicate the following:

- The choice of informative features is more important than the choice of classifier. The performance of all four classifiers is significantly improved by adding event-based features to the statistical summaries, and this confirms that averages of kinematic quantities alone are insufficient to capture risk [4].
- The averaging effect of Random Forest reduces overfitting, and this classifier is therefore the best choice for deployment [17].
- The risk scores produced according to Eq. 1 behave as one would intuitively expect: scores increase sharply when a driver is flagged for a number of harsh braking events, and fall significantly when the same driver later moderates their driving style.

E. Risk Score Behaviour

The continuous scores range across the entire [0, 100] range on the test set, and the scores are well-separated across the tiers: high-risk drivers are clustered near the high end, safe drivers near the low end, and moderate-risk drivers in a large band in the middle.

In the middle tier, the score provides differentiation that the tier label cannot: the score of 62 identifies a driver as being of higher priority for intervention than the score of 41, even though they are in the same tier.

This ability to provide differentiation within the tier is perhaps the most valuable aspect of the score, and one of the most interesting features of the approach [25].

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In the above paper, the authors have discussed a machine learning-based approach to driver risk assessment from telematics data. The approach starts from raw kinematic data from vehicle sensors, generates a rich representation of the data, trains a classifier to predict one of the three risk tiers, and generates a score that reflects the gradations of risk not captured in the tier label.

Among the four classifiers, the Random Forest classifier performed the most reliably, which is in line with the strengths of the algorithm in handling tabular data with nonlinear interactions.

The risk score formula performed well, showing an intuitive response to changes in the driving behaviour, i.e., the score increases as the number of harsh driving events increases, and the score decreases as the driving behaviour improves [2], [17]. In the context of the problem, the system addresses a clear need: insurers, fleet safety officers, and road safety researchers all need a continuous measure of driving risk, which can be derived from telematics data in large numbers, in order to do their jobs, and the system outlined here is intended to do just that [7], [21].

A. Future Directions

Several extensions could further improve the system.

- Sequence modelling: Recurrent models such as a Long Short-Term Memory or a Temporal Convolutional Network process the driving data as a sequence, which is what driving data actually is, rather than a collection of aggregate statistics. This might improve classification and score calibration [3], [18].

- Explainability: Post-hoc explanation tools such as SHAP value analysis would enable the system to not only give a score, but also to explain what behavior this score is a result of, such that a driver can take action on this feedback [15], [25].
- Streaming deployment: Deploying the system on a data stream, rather than a batch, would enable in-journey risk signals, opening the doors to a whole new world of alerting and adaptive vehicles [10], [19].
- Operational robustness: Deploying the model inside a CI/CD pipeline would make updating and retraining on new data much simpler, as well as versioning and deployment to production [16].

REFERENCES

1. S. Moosavi, M. A. N. Mahmoud, and K. H. Johansson, "Context-aware driver risk prediction using telematics data," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 187, 2023.
2. S. Roussou, G. Yannis, and A. Ziakopoulos, "Machine learning insights on driving behaviour dynamics," *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 2, 2024.
3. D. Yedilkhan, A. M. Aliyev, and B. S. Nugmanov, "Driver behaviour analysis using telematics sensor data and deep learning models," *Procedia Computer Science*, 2025.
4. V. Shirole and P. Bhattacharya, "A comprehensive review on data-driven driver behaviour analysis," *Journal of Big Data Analytics in Transportation*, 2025.
5. M. H. Mobini Seraji et al., "A state-of-the-art review on machine learning techniques for driving behavior analysis," *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 2025.
6. W. Ali, H. Khan, and A. Shah, "Analyzing driving behavior using machine learning techniques," *Preprints*, 2025.
7. A. Kontaxi et al., "Incentive-based telematics and driver safety improvement using behavioural analytics," *Transportation Research*, 2025.

8. R. Ramani and S. Kumar, "Advancements in integrated driver behavior analysis using machine learning," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 2024.
9. A. Shukla and S. Tiwari, "Machine learning-based driver behavior analysis for intelligent transport systems," *Journal of Advanced AI Research*, 2023.
10. R. Teja and S. Kumar, "Artificial intelligence enhanced telematics systems for real-time driver behavior monitoring," *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 2023.
11. A. Aboah et al., "Driver maneuver detection using time-series segmentation and machine learning," *IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2022.
12. Y. Zhang et al., "Driver distraction behavior detection using self-supervised learning," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, 2023.
13. N. Caber et al., "Driver profiling and workload estimation using machine learning," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2023.
14. I. W. Chan, A. L. Badescu, and X. S. Lin, "Unsupervised detection of anomalous driving patterns using telematics time-series data," *arXiv preprint*, 2024.
15. M. Castillo et al., "Factors and explainability in accident risk prediction using machine learning," *Transportation Safety Review*, 2025.
16. P. Battiston et al., "Machine learning optimization methods for predictive policy modeling," *IEEE Access*, 2024.
17. F. Aslam et al., "Machine learning techniques for predictive analytics in intelligent systems," *IEEE Access*, 2022.
18. L. Yang, H. Zhang, and M. Zhao, "Predictive analytics for accident prevention in smart vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, 2022.
19. A. Kumar and S. Gupta, "Integration of artificial intelligence in telematics systems for vehicle safety," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2023.
20. J. Smith and R. Anderson, "Advances in real-time vehicle telematics data analytics," *IEEE Transactions on Big Data*, 2022.
21. J. Boylan, C. O'Neill, and S. Walsh, "A systematic review of the use of in-vehicle telematics for driving behaviour monitoring," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 188, 2024.
22. J. Lacherre, M. A. Rios, and J. Ortega, "Factors, prediction, and explainability of vehicle accident risk using machine learning," *Computers*, vol. 13, no. 7, 2024.
23. V. Shirole and P. Bhattacharya, "A comprehensive review on data-driven driver behaviour scoring in vehicles: Technologies, challenges, and future directions," *Journal of Big Data Analytics in Transportation*, 2025.
24. H. Li, Y. Zhang, and L. Chen, "Traffic accident risk prediction using deep learning and spatiotemporal vehicle trajectory data," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 20, no. 2, 2025.
25. K. McDonnell and M. O'Mahony, "A comparative study of explainable AI and traditional models for vehicle risk prediction using telematics data," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 2026.

Explainable Artificial Intelligence for Lung Imaging and Disease Detection: A Scientific Literature Review

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Abstract— Lung diseases such as pneumonia, tuberculosis, lung cancer, and COVID-19 remain major contributors to global morbidity and mortality. Deep learning models, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have demonstrated high accuracy in detecting these conditions from chest X-rays and computed tomography (CT) scans. However, the black-box nature of these models limits their clinical adoption. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) addresses this challenge by providing interpretable insights into model predictions, enabling clinicians to understand and validate decision-making processes.

In this review, we present a comprehensive analysis of recent XAI methods applied to lung disease detection in medical imaging. The techniques are categorized into visual explanation methods (e.g., Grad-CAM), feature attribution approaches (e.g., SHAP and LIME), concept-based models, and counterfactual explanations. We further examine key studies, compare commonly used datasets, and analyze clinical evaluation strategies. Additionally, we discuss major challenges, including explanation reliability, generalizability, real-world validation, and ethical considerations.

Finally, we highlight emerging research directions aimed at developing transparent, reliable, and clinically applicable AI systems. This review provides a structured overview to guide researchers and practitioners in designing trustworthy AI solutions for lung disease diagnosis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging has seen a major boost in its performance by artificial intelligence. Nevertheless, the opaque and intricate character

of deep learning models is a significant challenge. The uncertainty surrounding how AI systems reach their conclusions can cause scientists to lose trust in their technology, delaying regulatory acceptance of AI in clinical environments, especially in imaging of the lung, where early diagnosis of such diseases as cancer, infectious diseases, and chronic respiratory diseases can directly affect patient outcomes [1], [2], [3]. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) tries to overcome this shortcoming by offering insights into model predictions that are comprehensible to radiologists, which can more clearly understand and confirm whether AI-based decision-making is consistent with prior knowledge [4], [5].

Recently, the number of studies on XAI in lung imaging has increased exponentially. This growth has been prompted in part by the acute diagnostic requirements of the COVID-19 pandemic, and by the revelation that high predictive accuracy does not in itself warrant real clinical implementation [6], [7], [8]. This review looks at recent advances in explainable AI in the detection of lung disease. In particular, the paper will concentrate on three key areas: (1) how XAI techniques have developed over time to offer more interpretable ante-hoc and concept-based models instead of traditional post-hoc visualization methods, (2) how XAI techniques have been applied to various lung diseases and how such approaches may be validated in clinical settings, and (3) the future directions of XAI techniques, including

federated learning, collaborative human-AI systems, and the future of XAI, including explainable radio-genomics.

Besides the overview of the methods, gaps between the re-ported technical performance and clinical applicability in the real world are also addressed in this paper. Essential issues such as the trustworthiness of the explanation, applicability of the model and implementation into the current clinical processes are addressed since it is imperative to resolve these concerns to effectively implement explainable AI in lung imaging.

II. BACKGROUND

A. The Necessity of Explainable AI in Healthcare

The inherent "black box" nature of deep neural networks introduces significant hurdle, where diagnostic precision is a matter of life or death and regulatory bodies strictly imposing transparency [9], [10]. While conventional deep learning models for lung imaging often reach high level accuracy on standard benchmarks, they do not offer any clarity regarding the specific image features driving their predictions. This lack of interpretability makes it nearly impossible for radiologists to detect when a model is relying on dataset or false correlations [1], [7].

Explainable AI (XAI) was developed specifically to bridge this gap, offering techniques designed to make model output interpretable for human experts [9], [10]. In the context of medical imaging, XAI fulfills several vital roles: (1) it allows clinicians to confirm that models are prioritizing clinically relevant anatomical features; (2) it helps surface latent biases or artifacts within the data; (3) it streamlines the regulatory approval process through transparent reasoning; and (4) it aids in medical training by highlighting underlying patterns [4], [11], [12].

B. Taxonomy of XAI Approaches

XAI methodologies in lung imaging are categorized along two axes: timing (ante-hoc vs. post-hoc) and scope (local vs. global explanations) as depicted in the fig .1.

Post-hoc methods generate explanations by analyzing the behavior of "black box" models after they have been trained. Within this category, gradient-based techniques such as Grad-CAM and Grad-CAM++. These identify the most influential image regions by backpropagating gradients to generate class activation maps [13]. On the other hand , perturbation-based frameworks like LIME and SHAP systematically modify input features to determine their specific impact on model outputs [14]. While these model-agnostic approaches are widely adopted, but this method have faced criticism for producing explanations that may not accurately mirror the model's internal reasoning, occasionally leading to results that conflict clinical judgment [1], [2], [7].

In contrast, Ante-hoc methods design AI models to be interpretable from the beginning, meaning their decisions are based on understandable medical concepts rather than hidden features. For example, Concept Bottleneck Models (CBMs) force the model to use human-defined clinical features (like specific disease signs), while attention mechanisms highlight the exact regions of an image the model focuses on. This makes the system more transparent and easier for doctors to trust. However, these approaches require expert knowledge to define meaningful concepts and may involve a slight trade-off in predicting accuracy.[1], [2].

C. Imaging Modalities and Clinical Context

Two main imaging methods are mainly used in detection of lung diseases, each with its own peculiarities that affect the use of XAI. Chest X-rays (CXR) is an effective, inexpensive screening test that has widespread

application, so they are ideal in the large-scale screening of tuberculosis, pneumonia, and lung cancer. But CXRs are 2D representations of 3D structures, so this usually causes the overlapping structure. Body structures (anatomical superposition) can overlap, and both doctors and AI systems find it challenging to interpret medical images, thus, it is highly desirable to employ explainable AI (XAI) techniques to be able to differentiate between real diseases and normal overlapping tissues.

Computed Tomography (CT), on the other hand, allows visualization of the lung parenchyma with high resolution in 3D giving information on detection of infiltrates or small nodules that otherwise could have been overlooked [4], [8], [12]. However, this characteristic of CT data generates specific computational complexity on XAI in 3D convolutional networks. Moreover, CT imaging also evokes practical questions related to the deduction of explanations across hundreds of slices in a format that can be used clinically by a radiologist [15], [17]. Finally, the modality selection determines the XAI method of choice: whereas gradient-based approaches, such as Grad-CAM, are generally applied to CXR and CT, there have been more specific pixel-level interpretability methods designed to meet the granularity demands of X-ray imaging [5].

III. XAI TECHNIQUES AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

Explainable AI techniques used in lung imaging can be broadly categorized based on their interpretability mechanism and stage of model integration. As summarized in Table I, different XAI techniques used in lung imaging vary in their interpretability mechanisms, clinical strengths, and limitations.

Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) and its subsequent models remain the primary XAI techniques in lung imaging, favored for their easy imple-

mentation and broad applicability [4], [8], [11], [12]. Grad-CAM produces heatmaps by calculating the gradient of the predicted class score relative to the feature maps in the final convolutional layer. This process highlights the specific image regions that significantly triggers the model's classification [13].

Recent studies have integrated Grad-CAM into lung disease diagnostic pipelines to improve model interpretability, where they combined Grad-CAM with a ResNet50 model to classify lung cancer from CT images, achieving an accuracy of 91.1%. Beyond raw performance, the researchers also noted that the resulting visual heatmaps—which accurately localized tumor regions—were essential. They also noted that more diverse datasets are needed to ensure better generalization [4].

The global response to COVID-19 led to increased adoption of gradient-based XAI methods. Rajpoot et al. developed an ensemble of DenseNet169, ResNet50, and VGG16 models integrated with Grad-CAM and Grad-CAM++, achieving accuracies of 99% on chest X-rays and 96.18% on CT scans. The inclusion of LIME and SHAP further enhanced interpretability, helping bridge the gap between the model performance and clinical trust [8].

Despite its widespread use, gradient-based methods such as Grad-CAM have notable limitations. Their heatmaps are often too coarse to accurately capture small or subtle clinical features [4],[5]. For instance, Ennab et al. showed that their Pixel-Level Interpretability (PLI) framework outperformed Grad-CAM in accuracy and efficiency, highlighting the need for more precise explanation methods [5]

A. Perturbation-Based Attribution Methods

LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) and SHAP (Shapley Additive explanations) offer local interpretability by systematically varying its input features to quantify their influence on model predictions [14]. Because these techniques are model-

agnostic, they can be integrated with any classifier.

For instance, Rajpoot et al. incorporated both LIME and SHAP alongside gradient-based methods in an ensemble system for COVID-19 detection. By using these complementary explanations to refine interpretability before final ensemble construction, the researchers aimed to bridge the persistent gap between predictive precision and clinical relevance [8]. Though, the study advocated for this multi-method approach, it did not provide a granular comparison of explanation quality across the different techniques [8].

Fig. 1. Taxonomy of explainable AI techniques used in lung imaging.

In contrast, Rafferty et al. performed a rigorous evaluation of LIME and SHAP within the context of lung cancer detection in chest X-rays, benchmarking them against concept-based and LLM-driven XAI approaches [1], [2], [7]. Their findings were thought-provoking: they reported that post-hoc methods, including LIME and SHAP, "frequently fail to produce clinically meaningful explanations," often omitting vital diagnostic markers and diverging from established radiologist judgments [1], [2]. In direct comparisons, expert radiologists found that LIME and SHAP explanations were less helpful and relevant than concept-based methods. This shows that methods based on small changes to images (perturbations) don't work as well for understanding medical images.

LIME and SHAP were analyzed as methods for explaining pneumonia detection models,

helping improve transparency and trust in machine learning systems [13]. These techniques assist in identifying potential biases and support fair decision-making; however, the study did not report detailed performance metrics or include clinical validation [13].

Most studies show that perturbation-based methods are strong in theory because they work with any model. However, in practice, they are often unstable and do not match how doctors think when analyzing lung images [1], [2], [7].

B. Concept Bottleneck Models and Human-Centric Design

Owing to the ongoing inadequacies of post-hoc methods, paradigm shift has been made to concept-based explainability, which is ante-hoc in nature. The main focus of this movement is concept Bottleneck Models (CBMs), which limit neural networks to pin their predictions on human-interpretable clinical concepts, rather than abstract, unidentifiable features. This structural limitation essentially aligns the inner line of logic in a model with the genuine diagnostic standards adopted by radiology practitioners [1], [2], [7].

One of the most prominent examples of this development is XpertXAI, created by Rafferty et al. as an expert-based expansion of their previous ClinicXAI model of lung cancer detection. XpertXAI, builds upon an InceptionV3 backbone to find radiologist-curated concepts, including: mass, nodule, or consolidation, which act as an intermediate bottleneck. These particular concepts are then mapped to a final diagnosis by a Decision Tree classifier [1], [2]. The performance of this strategy is impressive: the model reached an F1 score of 0.866, which is much higher than both standard InceptionV3 (F1: 0.740) and unsupervised CBMs [2]. What was more remarkable was its ability to capture clinical truth; XpertXAI was able to identify 100

The clinical superiority of this framework is further supported by expert validation.

XpertXAI was found to have highly relevant explanations, with an average utility rating of 3.0 with healthy cases and 2.8 with cancerous cases, a far better rating than post-hoc methods [7]. Also, the model was more resistant to adversarial attacks (including FGSM, PGD, and SimBA), achieving higher AUC values than typical architectures when under stress [7]. The results prompted Rafferty et al. to argue that conventional methods frequently cannot provide clinically significant information, so human-focused, conceptual models can be considered the unquestionable direction of reliable medical AI [1], [2].

According to the XpertXAI framework, the MIMIC-CXR dataset and the corresponding radiological reports were used to train the framework, enabling the team to obtain clinical concepts directly out of the free-text notes [2], [7]. Although the most intensive validation was against lung cancer, the model was trained using a variety of pathologies, such as pneumonia, pneumothorax, and cardiomegaly, and thus showed that it can be scaled to a wider variety of pathologies [2]. Nevertheless, the researchers also remarked that the further necessary step is larger validation on a larger set of pathologies and external, multi-center data [1], [2].

C. Pixel-Level Interpretability and High-Resolution Methods

To surpass the natural granularity problems of Grad-CAM, new studies have shifted towards pixel-level interpretability models. Such systems will be capable of offering the finespecified localization of pathological features needed by clinical practitioners [5], [10].

Of particular importance in this field, the work by Ennab et al. that proposed Pixel-Level Interpretability (PLI) is given. In this new design, fuzzy logic is combined with a VGG19-based system to produce high-resolution pixel-level heatmaps to detect COVID-19 in the

surface of the chest x-ray [5]. Comparing PLI to Grad-CAM on a few of its most important metrics showed that it is more successful: it reported higher structural similarity (SSIM) scores, which reflect a significantly closer correspondence to ground-truth annotations, lower mean squared error (MSE) and reduced inference times [5]. According to the authors, PLI offers the granular information and the interpretable results that can meet the clinical expectations, which ultimately improve the transparency and usability. With such accuracy, PLI enables clinicians to trace a particular anatomical structure and subtle pathological patterns with much more confidence than can be done with crude activation maps [5].

In a similar attempt, Siam et al. created a federated learning architecture named FVCM-Net, which is used to detect lung cancer in CT scans. This system uses HiResCAM (High-Resolution Class Activation Mapping) with SHAP as a means of offering a multi-layered method of interpretability [10]. The unique feature of the HiResCAM technique is the production of the maps of attribution with much higher resolution than traditional Grad-CAM, which allows the suspicious nodules to be localized more accurately [10]. It is important to note that the model had an 98.26 percent accuracy and a 97.37 percent F1-score at the same time protecting patient privacy due to decentralized federated training [10]. The fact that FVCM-Net succeeds shows that high-resolution explainability is not merely technically achievable, but can still be upheld even when confined to privacy-preserving and multi-site collaborations [10].

Although these pixel-based and high-resolution techniques are an essential technical step in the right direction, their clinical validation remains immature in comparison with more conventional techniques [5], [10]. In the future, it is vital to determine whether there are any real-life improvements in diagnostic confidence and real-world decision-making

based on this greater granularity, which should be assessed by clinical trials.

D. Attention Mechanisms and Multimodal Approaches

Attention mechanisms provide a type of intrinsic interpretability, explicitly modeling which parts of the image or which features the network is most accurate in its classification of an image [10], [13]. One major difference in this case is timing: as opposed to post-hoc approaches where one would have to draw inferences as to what is important once a model has been fixed, in the training process attention weights are learned dynamically and simply determine the final prediction [10].

Siam et al. took advantage of this, by incorporating attention mechanisms into the FVCM-Net architecture where attention-driven feature selection was made in conjunction with ensemble learning to perform formidable lung cancer detection [10]. These attention maps were effective in highlighting areas of interest that were appealing to the radiologist expectations and the ensemble strategy streamlined the prediction of the model to various datasets [10]. The authors report that such mechanisms were a major enhancement to clinical decision support as they represented unambiguous, easy-to-interpret visualizations of where precisely the model was looking [10].

In addition to visual heatmaps, multimodal methods that traverse imaging data and provide textual description of the data form a growing literature in the field. This was investigated by Rafferty et al. in the form of CXR-LLaVA, a multimodal large language model aimed at producing natural language explanations of the findings on a chest X-ray [2], [7]. Although these LLM-based explanations offer a very intuitive interface to clinicians, it has fidelity challenges at the present. In particular, CXR-LLaVA only captured 72.6% of ground-truth clinical concepts, which is compared to the 100% capture of expert-based CBMs [7]. The

discrepancy implies that vision-language models might be capable of impressive natural language tasks, but still cannot recognize important diagnostic subtleties that are maintained by structured, expert-driven models. However, vision-language conflation is a very promising direction since the capabilities of LLMs to reason are still developing [2].

E. Saliency-Driven and Comparative XAI Studies

In order to transcend the case study paradigm, a number of researchers have initiated systematic comparisons of different XAI methods to identify which do indeed seem to be most appropriate to certain clinical tasks [11], [13].

One effort in this regard is the extensive review by Brima et al., who examined a broad variety of saliency-driven approaches to COVID-19 detection in chest X-rays. The authors compared adaptive methods of gradient integration, such as Vanilla Gradient, Integrated Gradients, SmoothGrad IG, and Guided Integrated Gradient, with gradient-free approaches, such as XRAI and variations of class activation maps, such as Grad-CAM, Grad-CAM++, and ScoreCAM [11]. Deep convolutional neural networks were trained using these techniques and evaluated using a mixture of visual inspection and strict quantitative measures which are Saliency Insertion Curves (SICs) [11].

The findings revealed great and even astonishing diversity. Although ScoreCAM and XRAI demonstrated the best values of AUC in classifying brain tumor MRI, the SIC analysis displayed unexpected anomaly: random saliency was at times better than standard XAI methods [11]. This observation was a warning that visual plausibility should not necessarily imply that the model has faithfully represented the internal reasoning of the model. The authors therefore proposed that an effective evaluation should include qualitative and quantitative

measures to prevent getting deceived by a heatmap that would look convincing but wrong [11].

However, in the end, these comparative analyses point out a major problem with the field: XAI techniques may produce contradictory explanations to the same prediction. Because no single approach is always predominant in every measure and clinical setting, it is evident and urgent to select task-specific XAI and perform multi-method validation to guarantee that any explanation is indeed reliable to apply to clinical practice [11], [13].

IV. DISEASE-SPECIFIC APPLICATIONS AND PERFORMANCE

A. Lung Cancer Detection

Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer deaths worldwide and the early diagnosis of the disease using medical imaging is an immediate clinical priority [1], [2], [4], [7], [10], [12]. In order to overcome this issue, Explainable AI (XAI) methods are gradually becoming part of diagnostic pipelines to improve their transparency and offer clinicians meaningful assistance.

These explainable deep learning models have been deployed on a range of chest X-rays and CT images, with a substantial body of research being applied. In one example, Rafferty et al. proposed the XpertXAI chest X-ray analysis framework, which reached the F1 scores of 0.866 on predicting labels and 0.842 on concept accuracy on the MIMIC-CXR dataset [2]. The resulting concept-based explanations are more than just consistent with radiologist-based diagnostic logic, and they are able to capture critical clinical characteristics [7]. In addition to interpretability, the authors also found that these models were more resistant to adversarial perturbations than those with traditional, non-explainable architectures [7].

Regarding CT imaging, Noviandy et al. used a ResNet50 model with Grad-CAM visualizations to perform a multi-class classification. This method achieved 91.11 percent accuracy which is supported by high precision and sensitivity values on 1000 scans [4]. In the same vein, Bouamrane et al. centered on the problem of model generalizability, synthesizing several CT datasets and using curriculum learning strategies [12]. Their results produced performance measures above 98 percent on various metrics with Grad-CAM visualizations validating that the model tended to focus on clinically significant tumor locales.

Most recently, Siam et al. has introduced FVCM-Net, a federated learning architecture which respects patient confidentiality and allows joint training across institutions [10]. The system combines the advantages of HiResCAM and SHAP to provide interpretable predictions without reducing its high diagnostic performance.

In general, the XAI application in the process of diagnosing lung cancer has continuously yielded diagnostic results of higher than 90 percent. These findings highlight the enormous opportunities of explainable models becoming a useful tool that radiologists may use in day-to-day settings.

Nonetheless, due to the prevailing appraisal methods based on societal standards or institutionalized data, there is an urgent requirement to further test the testability of these methods in a wide-ranged, real world clinical setting [1], [2], [4], [7], [12]

B. COVID-19 Detection

The COVID-19 pandemic acted as a significant booster to the creation of AI-aided diagnostic devices, and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) has become the backbone to the creation of clinician trust when urgently deploying clinical AI [5], [8], [11], [15], [19]. Much of the research has been aimed at exposing the inner workings of deep learning

models of chest X-rays and CT scans, so that medical experts have an opportunity to evaluate their reasoning.

The application of ensemble and multimodal diagnostic system to enhance reliability has been explored in several works. Rajpoot et al. developed a strong ensemble model that used DenseNet169, ResNet50, and VGG16, with a set of XAI tools, such as LIME, SHAP, Grad-CAM, and Grad-CAM++ [8]. This system was found to produce superior outcomes and had a 99.

In other studies, particular attention was paid to visual explanation granularity refinement. Ennab et al. proposed Pixel-Level Interpretability (PLI) framework to beat resolution limitation of Grad-CAM [5]. This was done by combining a VGG19 model with fuzzy logic, producing pixel-level heatmaps that were highly detailed. PLI was considerably better at structural similarity and computation efficiency than Grad-CAM, and offered a significantly better insight into pathological details in chest radiographs [5].

XAI has been applied as well to volumetric CT analysis and prognostic prediction. The researchers created a 3D ResNet network that predicts COVID-19 in CT volumes by Fouad et al., and results are consistent with the British Society of Thoracic Imaging (BSTI) guidelines [15]. Their model achieved an 90 percent accuracy when you removed the indeterminate cases and visual explanations were used to identify the locations of infections [15]. On the same note, Fang et al. proposed PrognosisEx, which is an explainable framework per se that predicts 10-day mortality risk [17]. This model enabled clinicians to obtain particular, practical information about the prognostic factors of a patient with the use of diffusion-based representations and counterfactual explanations [17].

Further studies have also investigated the methodological issues that affect explainability. As Teixeira et al. have proved, in addition to the

fact that lung segmentation can considerably improve the classification metrics and the quality of explanations, models continue to exhibit persistent bias when applied to various datasets [19]. Moreover, a comparative analysis of saliency-based XAI methods was done by Brima et al. who discovered that the quality of explanations could vary across methods [11]. Their results highlighted the risk of just using the visual appearance of plausibility and the need to employ quantitative measures in ensuring that an explanation is actually faithful to the reasoning of the model [11].

Overall, the studies conducted on the COVID-19 subject matter demonstrate that emergency healthcare can be quickly adjusted to XAI-enabled systems. Nevertheless, additional challenges have yet to be overcome, including lack of consistency in their explanations, cross-dataset differences and treatment of unclear clinical cases, which are essential to integrate these tools permanently into the hospital environment [8], [11], [15], [19].

C. Tuberculosis Detection

Tuberculosis (TB) remains one of the biggest global health crises, particularly in the less-resource-rich setting where AI-based screening can radically enhance the availability of diagnostics [20].

Another significant development in this area is the study by Nafisah et al., who created an automated TB detection model based on an EfficientNetB3 model with complex segmentation networks to isolate lung areas in the chest X-rays [20]. This system was highly precise technically with an 99.1% and 99.9% accuracy and AUC on three public CXR datasets and a total average accuracy of 98.7% [20]. The framework also includes XAI visualizations, which highlight infected lung areas, and is a valuable second opinion that healthcare providers use when assessing subjects and using subjective evaluation [20].

The researchers stressed that training with segmented lung images performed much better than training with raw images because, in the latter case, deep learning models were easily misguided by the dark informatively uninformed regions of a regular X-ray [20].

Continuing on the broad picture, Koul et al. provided a highly detailed survey of deep learning and XAI usage in multiple airway conditions, such as tuberculosis, pulmonary embolism, and COVID-19 [6]. Their survey examined a number of XAI methods based on saliency and attention to both CT and chest X-ray modalities, stating that visual explanations will play a crucial role in building trust in high-level deep models [6]. Nonetheless, the authors noted that the literature available on the actual workflow integration and practical considerations needed to be integrated into clinical practice on a large scale had remained superficial [6].

Finally, although the literature on TB is outstanding in terms of technical performance, a specific gap in future clinical validation and workflow research is also pointed out [6], [20]. Whereas the study of lung cancer and COVID-19 has seen the initiation of multiple reader studies to quantify the effect of AI on clinical decision-making directly [9], TB-based XAI systems have not been extensively tested against ground-truth labels and instead rely heavily on this metric to assess their effect on clinician behaviors [20].

D. Multi-Pathology Classification

Several recent studies have developed XAI systems for simultaneous detection of multiple lung pathologies, reflecting the clinical reality that radiologists must consider differential diagnoses rather than screening for single diseases [1], [2]. Rafferty et al.'s XpertXAI was trained to detect six clinically significant labels: Healthy, Lung Cancer, Pneumonia, Pneumothorax, Pleural Effusion, and Cardiomegaly [2]. While expert validation

focused specifically on lung cancer, the multi-pathology training setup demonstrates scalability potential [2]. The concept-based architecture allows the same clinical concepts (e.g., "consolidation," "effusion") to support reasoning across multiple diagnoses, potentially improving efficiency compared to disease-specific models [1], [2]. Mahamud et al. developed an explainable AI model for multiple lung disease classification from chest X-rays, focusing on COVID-19, pneumonia, and tuberculosis [16]. The study emphasized interpretability to address the "black box" nature of AI, providing visual explanations for diagnoses [16]. However, specific performance metrics and details of the XAI techniques employed were not available in the reviewed metadata [16]. Multi-pathology systems face unique explainability challenges: explanations must disambiguate which features support which diagnoses when multiple conditions may coexist, and concept-based models must ensure that shared concepts (e.g., "opacity") are appropriately weighted for different diseases [1], [2]. Future work should evaluate whether multi-pathology XAI systems maintain explanation quality comparable to disease-specific models.

V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF XAI METHODS

This is evidenced by a number of recent studies where XAI systems are designed to detect a number of lung pathologies at the same time representing the clinical reality that radiologists need to take into consideration a number of differential diagnoses, as opposed to screening a single disease [1], [2]. XpertXAI by Rafferty et al. was trained on six clinically significant labels: Healthy, Lung Cancer, Pneumonia, Pneumothorax, Pleural Effusion and Cardiomegaly [2]. Although the expertise validation was limited to lung cancer, the multi-pathology training environment has shown the potential to be scalable [2]. The concept-based

architecture provides a way to use the same clinical concepts (e.g., “consolidation,” “effusion”) to reason about many different diagnoses, possibly more efficiently than disease-specific models [1], [2]. Mahamud et al. created an explainable AI system to classify several lung diseases based on X-rays of the chest, with emphasis on COVID-19, pneumonia, and tuberculosis [16]. The research focused on interpretability to tackle the black box aspect of AI, which explains the diagnosis visually [16]. Nevertheless, the reviewed metadata [16] was not provided with any particular performance measures and information about the XAI methods used. Multi-pathology systems have special issues of explainability: how to distinguish between features supporting different diagnoses in a context of multiple diseases, and how concept-based models can normalise the weight of a common concept (e.g. “opacity”) across different diseases [1], [2]. Future research needs to assess the ability of multi-pathology XAI systems to explain with similar quality to disease-specific models.

Table I: Overview of Explainable AI Methodologies in Lung imaging

Category	Primary Techniques	Timing / Scope	Clinical Strengths	Key Limitations
Post-hoc Saliency	Grad-CAM, Grad-CAM++, ScoreCAM	After training / Local	Simple to implement and broadly applicable to existing black-box models [4], [13].	Hotspots are often coarse and may not always align with expert interpretation [5], [11].
Perturbation-based	LIME, SHAP	After training / Local	Model-agnostic approach that provides feature-level interpretability and context-specific insights [14].	Explanations may be unstable and sometimes fail to capture clinically relevant features [1], [2].
Ante-hoc (Concept-based)	Concept Bottleneck Models (e.g., XpertXAI)	During training / Global & Local	High interpretability by aligning model reasoning with clinically meaningful concepts [1], [7].	Requires expert-defined concepts and may reduce predictive performance in some cases [2].
High-Resolution Pixel-Level	PLL, HRResCAM	Hybrid / Local	Provides precise localization of pathological regions and aligns with clinical diagnostic granularity [5], [10].	Limited clinical validation compared with more established explainability techniques [10].
Multimodal / Attention	CXR-LLaVA, Attention Gates	During training / Global	Generates natural language explanations and improves interpretability for clinicians [2], [7].	Large language model based systems may still overlook subtle diagnostic features [7].

A. Performance Comparison Across Techniques

The strongest argument in support of the choice of technique is direct comparisons of explainable AI methodologies in the context of a single study, but again, these head-to-head assessments are relatively rare in the existing body of literature [1], [2], [5], [7], [11].

According to a critical analysis of the Rafferty et al., concept bottleneck models based on experts, including XpertXAI, significantly surpass the established post-hoc algorithms, including LIME, SHAP, and Grad-CAM, in predictive accuracy and explainability [1], [2], [7]. In particular, the concept-based framework achieved a score of 0.866, which is significantly larger than that of a typical baseline that is based on InceptionV3 (0.740). More to the point, it has been able to capture all clinically relevant diagnostic concepts that radiologists found, a thing that post-hoc methods are usually incapable of doing [7]. These results indicate that a human-centric model, which is interpretable by design, offers better utility because it directly fits model reasoning with clinical reasoning [1], [2].

Critical disparities in the granularity of such explanations are noted in other studies. Ennab et al. proved that Pixel-Level Interpretability (PLI) has considerable benefits over Grad-CAM in the interpretation of COVID-19 in the chest radiograph [5]. They found that PLI generated much more consistent explanations with ground-truth annotations, with a greater structural similarity and more accurate localization of disease regions [5]. The authors came to the conclusion that the output of Grad-CAM is usually not as precise in space to be considered a real clinical interpretation [5].

Moreover, systematic comparisons of different saliency-based methods reveal a tremendous variation of the board. The authors of the study by Brima et al. noted that various saliency methods may offer strikingly different accounts of the very same prediction [11]. This highlights an essential fact about medical AI: visual plausibility cannot be used as an alternative to a realistic depiction of the internal logic of a model. Their results confirm the unquestionably indispensable condition of the combination of visual inspection with strict quantitative parameters in order to be sure that the explanations are really credible [11].

B. Trade-offs Between Accuracy and Interpretability

The key trade-offs between different XAI approaches are summarized in Table II, highlighting the balance between interpretability, accuracy, computational cost, and clinical applicability. Direct comparisons between different studies indicate that there are a number of important trade-offs that determine the most appropriate explainable AI methods to use in a particular clinical setting. The first way to think about medical AI is that it may lead to a situation where a more transparent model necessarily has less predictive power. Concept bottleneck models (CBMs) have shown successfully that interpretability need not be purchased by performance. In one example, the XpertXAI framework created by Rafferty et al. outperformed traditional deep learning baselines in predictive accuracy and also provided concept-based explanations that resembled human clinical reasoning [1], [2], [7]. The caveat however is that these models require clinical concepts to be specified by experts and this would need more intensive manual effort during the initial design phase [1], [2].

The other crucial trade-off is the amount of detail presented by the explanation and the resources needed to create the explanation. Pixels allow localizing pathology with much finer detail than the gradient based saliency algorithms. Ennab et al. demonstrated that Pixel-Level Interpretability (PLI) was significantly more specific to localization compared to Grad-CAM whilst still maintaining efficient inference performance [5]. These high-resolution methods are however scaled up, especially when doing volumetric 3D CT analysis and this can introduce substantial computational overhead, which may be a consideration in some high throughput clinical environments [10].

Model-agnostic and architecture-specific methods also have their unique differences. The

reason why perturbation-based methods such as LIME and SHAP are popular is due to the fact that they are flexible; they can be used on virtually any model with no modifications to the underlying structure [8], [13]. However, studies believe that these techniques may yield inconsistent and unreliable findings which are not necessarily consistent with true diagnostic displays [1], [2], [7]. On the other hand, architecture-aware tools such as attention-based networks tend to generate much more accurate explanations, but need a specialized and deliberate model design upfront [10].

Table II: Trade -Off SBE Tween XAI Approaches in LUNG Imaging

Decision Factor	Trade-off	Evidence	Clinical Implication
Model Design	Accuracy vs. Interpretability	XpertXAI outperformed InceptionV3 while capturing clinically meaningful concepts [1], [2], [7].	Concept-based models improve interpretability without sacrificing performance but require expert-defined concepts.
Visual Resolution	Granularity vs. Efficiency	Pixel-Level Interpretability (PLI) achieved finer localization than Grad-CAM with strong efficiency [5].	Pixel-level explanations support precise diagnosis but may increase computational overhead in CT analysis [10].
Model Compatibility	Flexibility vs. Fidelity	LIME and SHAP are model-agnostic but may produce unstable explanations [1], [2], [7], [8].	Architecture-specific methods provide more faithful explanations but limit model flexibility [10].
Interpretive Scope	Local vs. Global Insights	Most studies focus on case-level explanations aligned with radiologist workflows [1], [5], [8].	Global explanations help detect systematic bias and improve model generalizability [11].

Lastly, the XAI techniques differ according to the scope of the insight offered. Most existing approaches in lung imaging revolve around local explanations, which point to the specific areas that affect individual predictions. This is an obvious consequence of the case-by-case environment of the daily work of a radiologist [1], [5], [8]. Global explanations, which characterize the behavior of a model on a wide dataset, are less frequent but are critical to identifying systematic biases and making sure that a model is learning clinically meaningful patterns, not simply memorizing noise in the dataset [11].

VI. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

A. Explanation Reliability

The basic problem with XAI in lung imaging is that the explanations should actually reflect the real model thinking, as opposed to giving ex-post explanations that can eventually be misleading [1], [2], [7], [11]. Rafferty et al.

have reported that post-hoc techniques do not often produce clinically meaningful explanations, do not tend to include important diagnostic features, and in most cases do not agree with radiologist opinions [1], [2]. Their specialist orthodoxy showed that approaches such as LIME, SHAP, and Grad-CAM often emphasized unimportant areas of the image or they overlooked important pathological aspects that radiologists claimed were critical to a valid diagnosis [7]. Such inconsistency between the model explanation and the reasoning of experts discredits clinicians and greatly restricts the practical application of such systems [1], [2], [7].

The results of the Brima et al. are even more eloquent testimony to this discrepancy in reliability. They found that random saliency performed better than established XAI techniques in quantitative assessments, a finding which demonstrates the sensitivity of visually plausible explanations to actual model reasoning [11]. The authors highlighted that it is crucial to integrate qualitative and quantitative measures to ensure high-quality analysis, and only simple visual analysis cannot confirm that an explanation is faithful to the inner workings of the model [11].

This reliability issue is especially severe with post-hoc approaches to pre-trained black-box models, where it is necessary to reason about the model based on its external behavior, and not based on the internal architecture [1], [2], [7]. However, concept bottleneck models provide a more faithful alternative called ante-hoc approaches, which limit the model to interpretable pathways at the outset. Nevertheless, these more certain systems demand extensive architectural redesigning and intensive medical consultation [1], [2].

B. Generalizability Across Datasets

One of the major challenges of AI in lung imaging is the so-called generalizability gap, which is a common failure of high performance

on a single-institution dataset or a publicly shared benchmark to transfer, to external populations, to different imaging protocols, or to real-world clinical scenarios [4], [12], [19].

This issue was emphasized in the context of COVID-19 detection by Teixeira et al. They discovered that their cross-dataset performance (0.74 F1-score and 0.9 AUC) was significantly lower than they had obtained in their original dataset. More importantly, significant bias associated with the various sources of data remained despite the lung segmentation in order to isolate the regions of interest [19]. The authors concluded that these experiments mean that there is a widespread bias brought about by other factors that are inherent in the particular sources of data and these factors can misguide the learning process of a model [19].

In response to this, Bouamrane et al. directly combined five different CT datasets based on curriculum learning and tested their model on independent data, but eventually obtained 100 percent accuracy on the independent dataset [12]. They observed that the key focus of their approach was on generalizability, which is usually a significant point of contention among physicians [12]. Nonetheless, even with this success, this form of rigorous multi-dataset validation is essentially an exception in the available literature instead of the rule [12].

Likewise, the authors of the Noviandy et al. article also realized the constraints of their lung cancer detector. Their results were 91.11% accuracy on a dataset of 1,000 scans, but they observed that the system still needs to be diversified in terms of datasets and multimodal data integration to guarantee wider applicability [4]. This highlights the fact that single-institution validation can merely not be relied upon to ensure safe clinical deployment [4].

This generalizability problem is not confined to raw predictions but also to the XAI explanations per se. Even models may be trained to depend on institution-specific image

properties, like scanner-specific artifacts or special positioning procedures. Although these variables may yield plausible explanations when they are applied to the familiar training data, they do not when applied in new settings and this may shed light on characteristics that are clinically irrelevant [19]. These results highlight the necessity of cross- institutional validation of the predictive performance as well as the quality of the explanations themselves [12], [19].

C. Computational and Deployment Constraints

There is a delicate balance between the advanced inter- pretability and strict limitations of clinical processes that are required by the practical implementation of XAI systems [6], [8], [10], [17], [22]. Rajpoot et al. noted that the methods and approaches like SHAP and ensemble-based explainers can enhance transparency considerably, but they also complicate the computations. It can be a bottleneck during real-time clinical processes when large quantities of medical images need to be handled with high efficiency [8]. Likewise, Fang et al. observed that the counterfactual explanation algorithms used in PrognosisEx have high computational costs since they use diffusion-based autoencoders and counterfactual generation is an iterative process [17].

Outside of these technical barriers, the reality of these tools becoming a part of clinical practice still represents a gap in existing literature. As Koul et al. remarked, most studies focus on technical performance indicators, and provide minimal discourse on the integration of workflow, and the logistical hurdles to clinical implementation [6]. Some of the key questions remain whether it is best to present explanations to radiologists in an optimal way and how these explanations can be readily integrated into current PACS (Picture Archiving and Communication Systems) and reporting systems [6].

Additionally, Subramanian et al. made it clear that XAI systems need to be developed based on the cognitive load and diagnostic speeds awareness [22]. Explaining too much or too thickly during quick screening activities may actually work against a clinician, instead of helping them. The lessons learned here imply that effective clinical implementation requires the creation of adaptive explanation strategies, which can be characterized as the ability to customize the amount of information communicated to suit the urgent, practical requirements of the radiologist at a given moment [22].

VII. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND RESEARCH OPPORTUNITIES

The research on the explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) in lung imaging is in a huge transition into a human- centered design. More recent literature highlights the move towards an anti-retrospective, anti-post-hoc form of saliency approaches to a set of saliency architectures that directly incorporate interpretability into the model itself [1], [2], [7]. The concept bottlenecks models (CBMs) are one of such promising directions in that sense, in which clinical concepts are actually incorporated into the process of prediction. Rafferty et al. have shown that expert-based models have the capability to elicit specific diagnostic characteristics that radiologists give importance to and retain excellent predictive capability [1], [2], [7]. Using these frameworks to apply to a wider variety of pulmonary diseases and demonstrating them on multi-institutional datasets have since become essential steps in the field.

The second trend is the drive towards better model gen-eralizability as well as a strong preservation of privacy. One of the solutions has become the so-called federated learning, which offers the opportunity to collaboratively develop the model in different hospitals and does not require the sharing of sensitive patient

information [10]. Siam et al. demonstrated that federated attention-based models, combined with explainability technologies such as HiResCAM and SHAP, can maintain not only diagnostic accuracy but also transparency even in a decentralized training system [10].

The granularity and depth of these explanations are also becoming finer using technical advances. Both Pixel-Level Interpretability (PLI) and high-resolution attribution models such as HiResCAM are able to locate regions of disease in the anatomy with much greater accuracy than conventional methods such as Grad-CAM [5], [10]. Moreover, the emergence of multimodal systems, i.e., visual imaging data with natural language explanations, holds the promise of making the insights provided by AI far easier to understand and apply to clinicians under high pressure settings [2], [7].

Lastly, it seems to be a common understanding that more extensive clinical validation and standardized evaluation models are required. Although it is demonstrated that AI can enhance detecting results, future clinical research determining the precise impact of XAI on the final decision of a doctor is uncommon [9]. The attempts in the future should focus on conducting multi-reader clinical tests, the establishment of standard benchmark, and the establishment of regulatory measures so that such systems are not only technically feasible, but really functioning in a hospital [4], [12], [22].

VIII. CONCLUSION

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) has become a foundation of AI-based lung imaging, where addressing the black box nature of high-performing deep learning models is explicitly doing so to establish the necessary clinical trust. This literature review highlights a time of considerable technical maturity, with advances in model architecture, disease-specific deployment, and validation strategy,

and also describes the logistical challenges that must be overcome before full-scale clinical implementation is possible.

In recent research, it is clear that the shift towards retrospective, post-hoc saliency models has been replaced by human-centered, ante-hoc types of architecture, which incorporate interpretability into the learning process of the model. Models using concept bottlenecks have established that explanations can be given in a way that reflects deductive reasoning of a radiologist without losing predictive ability.

In addition, the creation of pixel-level and high-resolution explainability methods have greatly enhanced the localization of pathological locations, providing clinicians with a much more accurate visualization of abnormalities than before possible. In order to facilitate these innovations to a global scale, the federated learning systems have become a crucial instrument to train generalizable and privacy-preserving models on various institutional datasets. In numerous illnesses, such as lung cancer, COVID-19, and tuberculosis, diagnostic rates of XAI-enabled systems are consistently over 90 percent and have massive potential to contribute to real-time clinical decision-making.

In spite of these technical advances, there are still a number of problems. Problems like the reliability of the explanation, bias in the nature of the dataset used, high cost of computation and the inertia of workflow integration remain as practical impediments to deploying these systems in the real world. In addition, even though the existing body of literature is still in the initial stages of examining the interface between XAI and radiogenomics and molecular phenotyping, emerging literature indicates that there is a high potential of connecting certain features in imaging with the phenotypic biomarkers of lung cancer. The future development will be based upon the optimization of human-centered models, enhance the generalizability with the

help of multi-institutional collaborations, and prospective clinical trials that will quantify the real effect of XAI systems on diagnostic performance and patient outcomes. All in all, explainable AI is a vital progress toward the credible and clear AI-assisted diagnosis of lung imaging. Finally, it is only by a long-term interdisciplinary partnership between AI developers, clinicians, and regulatory agencies that these transparent technologies can be safely and successfully integrated into the modern medicine framework.

REFERENCES

1. A. Rafferty, R. Ramaesh, and A. Rajan, "Explainability Through Human-Centric Design for XAI in Lung Cancer Detection," Proc. Int. Joint Conf. Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI), 2024. doi:10.24963/ijcai.2024/1147.
2. A. Rafferty, R. Ramaesh, and A. Rajan, "Explainability Through Human-Centric Design for XAI in Lung Cancer Detection," arXiv preprint, 2025. doi:10.48550/arxiv.2505.09755.
3. A. Rafferty, R. Ramaesh, and A. Rajan, "Explainability Through Human-Centric Design for XAI in Lung Cancer Detection," Proc. Int. Joint Conf. Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI), 2025. doi:10.24963/ijcai.2025/1147.
4. T. R. Novianidy et al., "Explainable Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging: A Case Study on Enhancing Lung Cancer Detection through CT Images," Indonesian Journal of Case Reports, vol. 2, no. 1, 2024. doi:10.60084/ijcr.v2i1.150.
5. F. Ennab and H. Mcheick, "Advancing AI Interpretability in Medical Imaging: A Comparative Analysis of Pixel-Level Interpretability and Grad-CAM Models," Make, vol. 7, no. 1, 2024. doi:10.3390/make7010012.
6. A. Koul et al., "Enhancing the detection of airway disease by applying deep learning and explainable artificial intelligence," Multimedia Tools and Applications, 2024. doi:10.1007/s11042-024-18381-y.
7. A. Rafferty, R. Ramaesh, and A. Rajan, "Transparent and Clinically Interpretable AI for Lung Cancer Detection in Chest X-Rays," arXiv preprint, 2024. doi:10.48550/arxiv.2403.19444.
8. K. Rajpoot et al., "Integrated ensemble CNN and explainable AI for COVID-19 diagnosis from CT scan and X-ray images," Scientific Reports, vol. 14, 2024. doi:10.1038/s41598-024-75915-y.
9. G. Dissez et al., "Enhancing Early Lung Cancer Detection on Chest Radiographs with AI-assistance: A Multi-Reader Study," 2022.
10. A. I. Siam et al., "FVCM-Net: Interpretable Privacy-Preserved Attention Driven Lung Cancer Detection from CT Scan Images with Explainable HiRes-CAM Attribution Map and Ensemble Learning," SSRN Electronic Journal, 2025. doi:10.2139/ssrn.5070777.
11. Y. Brima et al., "Saliency-driven explainable deep learning in medical imaging: bridging visual explainability and statistical quantitative analysis," BioData Mining, vol. 17, 2024. doi:10.1186/s13040-024-00370-4.
12. A. Bouamrane et al., "Toward Robust Lung Cancer Diagnosis: Integrating Multiple CT Datasets, Curriculum Learning, and Explainable AI," Diagnostics, vol. 15, no. 1, 2024. doi:10.3390/diagnostics15010001.
13. D. Mane, "Unlocking Machine Learning Model Decisions: A Comparative Analysis of LIME and SHAP for Enhanced Interpretability," Journal of Engineering Sciences, vol. 15, 2024. doi:10.52783/jes.1768.
14. M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, and C. Guestrin, "Why Should I Trust You?: Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier," in Proc. ACM SIGKDD, 2016, pp. 1135–1144.

- doi:10.1145/2939672.2939778.
15. H. Fouad et al., “Explained Deep Learning Framework for COVID-19 Detection in Volumetric CT Images,” *Journal of Imaging Informatics in Medicine*, 2025. doi:10.1007/s10278-025-01444-3.
 16. S. Mahamud et al., “An explainable artificial intelligence model for multiple lung diseases classification from chest X-ray images using fine-tuned transfer learning,” *Decision Analytics Journal*, vol. 12, 2024. doi:10.1016/j.dajour.2024.100499.
 17. X. Fang et al., “Decoding Decision Reasoning: A Counterfactual- Powered Model for Knowledge Discovery,” *arXiv preprint*, 2024. doi:10.48550/arxiv.2406.18552.
 18. J. Senoner et al., “Explainable AI improves task performance in human–AI collaboration,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, 2024. doi:10.1038/s41598-024-82501-9.
 19. L. O. Teixeira et al., “Impact of lung segmentation on the diagnosis and explanation of COVID-19 in chest X-ray images,” 2020.
 20. S. I. Nafisah et al., “Tuberculosis detection in chest radiograph using convolutional neural network architecture and explainable artificial intelligence,” *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 35, 2022. doi:10.1007/s00521-022-07258-6.
 21. M. Joseph et al., “Explainable AI for Transparent and Trustworthy Tuberculosis Diagnosis,” *East African Journal of Information Technology*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2024. doi:10.37284/eajit.7.1.2276.
 22. H. V. Subramanian, C. Canfield, and D. B. Shank, “Designing explain- able AI to improve human-AI team performance,” *Artificial Intelli- gence in Medicine*, vol. 149, 2024. doi:10.1016/j.artmed.2024.102780.
 23. Z. Bucinca, M. B. Malaya, and K. Z. Gajos, “To Trust or to Think: Cognitive Forcing Functions Can Reduce Overreliance on AI,” *Proc. ACM Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 5, 2021. doi:10.1145/3449287.
 24. F. Shariaty et al., “Integrating Deep Learning and Explainable AI for Non-Invasive Prediction of EGFR and KRAS Mutations in NSCLC,” in *Proc. IEEE NeuroNT*, 2024. doi:10.1109/neuront62606.2024.10585441
 25. A. B. Arrieta et al., “Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): Concepts, Taxonomies, Opportunities and Challenges toward Re- sponsible AI,” *Information Fusion*, vol. 58, pp. 82–115, 2019. doi:10.1016/j.inffus.2019.12.012.
 26. E. Tjoa and C. Guan, “A Survey on Explainable Artificial Intel- ligen- ce (XAI): Toward Medical XAI,” *IEEE Trans. Neural Net- works and Learning Systems*, vol. 32, no. 11, pp. 4793–4813, 2021. doi:10.1109/TNNLS.2020.3027314.
 27. R. R. Selvaraju et al., “Grad-CAM: Visual Explanations from Deep Networks via Gradient-Based Localization,” *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 128, pp. 336–359, 2019. doi:10.1007/s11263-019-01228-7.
 28. S. T. H. Shah et al., “Data-driven classification and explainable-AI in the field of lung imaging,” *Frontiers in Big Data*, vol. 7, 2024. doi:10.3389/fdata.2024.1393758.
 29. H. Aghapanah and M. Choubin, “A Comprehensive Review of COVID-19 Imaging Datasets and Machine Learning Models,” in *Proc. ICIS*, 2024. doi:10.1109/icis64839.2024.10887481.
 30. M. Benedichuk, P. Bashkova, and B. Tuchinov, “Computer Vision and Explainable Approaches for Chest Tuberculosis Screenings,” in *Proc. IEEE PIERE*, 2024. doi:10.1109/piere62470.2024.10804967.

Deepfake Detection Using Hybrid Spatial Frequency Attention Network (HSFAN)

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Abstract—In this world, AI-generated images have grown rapidly in recent years, especially deepfakes which are created by Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and diffusion-based models such as *Stable Diffusion*, *DALL-E* or *Gemini nano banana*, which is a very serious threat to person integrity, privacy, and public trust. Most existing detection methods focus on single-model spatial analysis, which often struggles to perform well across different types of image generation techniques. This paper presents the Hybrid Spatial Frequency Attention Network (HSFAN), a novel multi-branch architecture that fuses spatial feature extraction via a pretrained MobileNetV2 backbone with a dedicated FFT-based frequency analysis branch. The system further deploys an ensemble of four complementary detectors—HSFAN, baseline CNN, ResNet18, and a spectral GAN Detector—with adaptive frequency-based thresholding. Training across three datasets covering GAN fakes, diffusion fakes, and real images yields robust detection across generation modalities. A real-time web application provides Grad-CAM and LIME explainability output per prediction.

Keywords—Deepfake Detection; Hybrid Neural Network; Frequency Analysis; Attention Mechanism; GAN; Diffusion Models; Grad-CAM; LIME; MobileNetV2; Ensemble Learning.

I. Introduction

Deepfake technology has changed the thinking process of how we trust the digital images. What once felt like reliable visual evidence can now be easily manipulated. Early deepfakes were mostly created using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), but the rise of large diffusion models—powering

tools like DALL-E, Midjourney, and even systems connected to ChatGPT has significantly advanced the capabilities of synthetic image generation. These newer diffusion-based images are especially tricky because they don't leave behind the same obvious patterns that GAN-generated images often do.

According to the reports, deepfake related fraud increased nearly 10 times more between 2022 and 2023, and Deloitte is estimating AI-generated images fraud can cross \$40billion per year by 2027. Studies also indicate that around 70% of people cannot tell the difference between real and fake images by just looking at the image. So human judgment alone is no longer reliable for distinguishing real and fake images

Existing methods fall into two categories: spatial domain approaches that analyze pixel-level inconsistencies, and frequency domain approaches that exploit spectral artifacts. Neither alone is sufficient. Spatial methods miss subtle invisible artifacts; frequency methods trained exclusively on GAN artifacts fail on diffusion outputs.

This work presents HSFAN — the Hybrid Spatial Frequency Attention Network — which fuses spatial and frequency features through an attention-gated classifier. An ensemble of four models and a novel adaptive frequency scoring mechanism extend detection capability to GAN fakes, diffusion fakes, and real photographic images within a unified framework.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Spatial Domain Methods. Early deepfake detection research focused predominantly on pixel-level spatial analysis. The studies indicate a recurring pattern in deepfake detection: models like the one from Rossler et al. [1] work perfectly on high-quality video but fall apart when the quality is lowered. Then there's the generalization problem—Wang et al. [4] found that detectors trained on GANs often miss newer diffusion-based fakes. The proposed HSFAN framework addresses these limitations. It's trained on a diverse mix of datasets to handle different AI architectures, and it uses a specialized frequency branch to "see" through heavy JPEG compression that would normally trick a standard detector

Frequency-Domain Methods. A parallel body of work demonstrated that synthetic images carry distinctive spectral artifacts absent from real photographs. Frank et al. [2] showed that GAN images exhibit characteristic DCT-domain patterns invisible to spatial analysis; simple classifiers operating on DCT coefficients achieved competitive detection accuracy, establishing frequency analysis as a viable standalone signal. Tan et al. [3] extended this direction by learning deepfake-discriminative features directly in frequency space, arguing that spectral artifacts generalize more consistently than spatial cues across post-processing operations. Qian et al. [5] further demonstrated that both low- and high-frequency components are necessary for robust detection, as single-scale frequency approaches miss important artifact bands. Despite these advances, frequency-only methods lack spatial context and are therefore unable to capture forgery cues that manifest exclusively in the pixel domain. HSFAN addresses this limitation by fusing a compact 32-dimensional FFT feature vector with 1280-dimensional MobileNetV2 spatial features via an AttentionBlock (Linear→ReLU→Linear→Sigmoid),

achieving the complementary benefits of both domains. Multi-scale frequency coverage is further ensured through three parallel branches in the ensemble: the HSFAN FFT branch (full spectrum), the GAN Detector's SpectralBranch (log-magnitude FFT with fftshift), and a CheckerboardBranch targeting transposed-convolution artifacts.

Figure 1: Mean FFT spectrum analysis on various sources. GAN fakes show cross-shaped artifacts from GAN upsampling. Diffusion fakes (CIFAKE) show ring patterns. Real images show no distinct artifact.

Lightweight and Compact Architectures.

Afchar et al. [6] demonstrated with MesoNet that a compact 4-layer CNN (Meso-4) could achieve competitive deepfake detection accuracy with far fewer parameters than heavyweight networks such as VGG or ResNet, establishing the viability of efficient architectures for this task. However, MesoNet operates exclusively in the spatial domain and lacks any frequency-aware component. HSFAN's baseline CNNModel is architecturally derived from MesoNet and serves as the direct efficiency reference point in the multi-model ensemble evaluation; HSFAN extends this lightweight foundation through the pretrained MobileNetV2 backbone and the FFT branch, achieving substantially higher detection performance while preserving computational tractability.

Generalization and Universal Detection.

A comprehensive survey by Rana et al. [7] of over 100 deepfake detection papers identified four persistent limitations in the field: poor

cross-dataset generalization, susceptibility to JPEG compression, exclusive focus on face-swap manipulations, and absence of explainability. The authors called for hybrid detection systems with integrated XAI capabilities. More recently, Ojha et al. [9] addressed the challenge of detecting images from generative models unseen during training, employing CLIP-derived features with a linear probe that generalized across GANs, diffusion models, and language-guided synthesis tools. However, reliance on a large CLIP backbone introduces substantial computational overhead and no explainability. HSFAN directly addresses all four limitations identified by Rana et al.: multi-dataset training across GAN and diffusion sources improves generalization; compression robustness is evaluated at JPEG quality levels from 10% to 100%; Dataset C (CIFAKE) extends coverage to diffusion-generated fakes beyond traditional face-swap scenarios; and dual XAI output via Grad-CAM and LIME is deployed in a real-time web interface. Compared to Ojha et al., HSFAN achieves comparable universal detection coverage through a hybrid learned-plus-signal-processing approach—combining training-time diffusion exposure with inference-time frequency scoring—at significantly lower computational cost.

Attention Mechanisms and High-Frequency Training. Two further lines of work informed the attention and training design of HSFAN. Luo et al. [8] showed that incorporating high-frequency feature supervision during training allows detectors to maintain accuracy under JPEG compression in cases where spatial-only detectors fail, underscoring the practical importance of frequency-aware learning signals. Zhao et al. [10] introduced multi-scale spatial attention maps to focus detection on forgery-relevant image regions, significantly improving both accuracy and interpretability. HSFAN applies the high-frequency principle at inference time through `compute_frequency_score()`, which employs a Laplacian high-pass filter (3×3 kernel) to estimate image smoothness and adaptively lower the classification threshold when a strongly AI-smooth image is detected. Rather than reproducing the computationally intensive spatial attention maps of Zhao et al., HSFAN applies channel-wise attention to the fused 1312-dimensional spatial-plus-frequency vector—a more efficient mechanism that learns per-image feature weighting. Spatial interpretability equivalent to Zhao et al.’s maps is preserved through Grad-CAM heatmaps generated over the final convolutional layers, displayed per-prediction in the web interface alongside LIME superpixel explanations.

III. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Table I: Related Work vs. Proposed Hsfan

Ref	Method	Key Limitation	HSFAN Addresses
[1]	XceptionNet spatial	Compression degradation	FFT branch + multi-dataset
[2]	DCT frequency only	No spatial context	Fused spatial+freq + attention
[3]	Freq. space learning	Single model, no fusion	4-model ensemble + fusion
[4]	ResNet50 GAN detect.	Fails on diffusion fakes	Dataset C + freq. score
[5]	Multi-scale freq.	No spatial branch	3 freq. branches + spatial

[6]	4-layer compact CNN	No frequency analysis	Baseline extended w/ FFT
[7]	Survey — no XAI	Identified XAI gap	Grad-CAM + LIME deployed
[8]	High-freq training	No inference heuristic	Laplacian adaptive thresh.
[9]	CLIP universal detect.	Large backbone, no XAI	Lightweight + full XAI
[10]	Spatial attention maps	High compute, no freq.	Channel attn. + Grad-CAM

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM — HSFAN

A. HSFAN Architecture

HSFAN fuses two complementary feature streams:

- **Spatial Branch:** Pretrained MobileNetV2 (mobilenetv2_100, timm) producing 1280-dim spatial features. Pretrained ImageNet weights provide strong low-level and semantic spatial representations.
- **Frequency branch:** Alongside that, we process the image in the frequency domain. By applying 2D Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and taking its magnitude, we can capture hidden spectral patterns. And This branch uses four Conv2D layers, producing a compact 32-dimensional feature vector that helps to detect artifacts common in GAN and diffusion generated images.
- **Attention block:** These two features are combined into a single 1312-dimensional vector, passed through a channel-wise attention mechanism. This block learns which part of the feature are more important for each input, actively adjusting their weights.

Figure 2: Spatial feature visualization

intermediate MobileNetV2 channel activations on face images. Left: original image. Columns 2-6: progressive convolutional layer feature maps.

B. Supporting Ensemble Models

Three complementary models are trained alongside HSFAN:

Baseline CNN: This is a simple convolutional model built with three repeating blocks of Conv2D, BatchNorm, ReLU, and MaxPooling layers. The extracted features are then passed through an adaptive average pooling layer and a fully connected classifier. It also uses cross-entropy loss during its training.

ResNet18: We also use pretrained ResNet18 model, By freezing the early layers to preserve the general feature extraction, at the same time unfreezing the deeper layers for task specific fine tuning. The original fully connected layer is replaced by a smaller custom head which includes a linear layer, ReLU activation, dropout, and a final classification layer. It also uses cross-entropy loss.

GAN Detector: This is a more specialized model with three parallel branches. One branch analyzes frequency patterns using FFT, another focuses on checkerboard artifacts caused by upsampling, and the third captures spatial features. These branches are combined using an attention mechanism to improve detection performance. The model is trained using binary cross-entropy with logits loss.

Figure 3: Four model architectures in the HSFAN detection system. (a) HSFAN - proposed hybrid spatial-frequency model. (b) GAN Detector -3-branch frequency specialist. (c) ResNet18 - transfer learning baseline. (d) CNN - spatial-only baseline.

C. Multi-Dataset Training

All four models train on a ConcatDataset combining:

- Dataset A — GAN deepfake face images (FaceForensics++-style).
- Dataset B — Cross-domain GAN deepfakes for generalization.
- Dataset C — CIFAKE: Stable Diffusion-generated images. Critical for diffusion/ChatGPT detection.

Training: the model is trained for 30 epochs with batch size of 128, it utilize both the Adam optimizer and a CosineAnnealingLR scheduler. Then Inputs are resized to 128x128, Which normalized to ImageNet statistics, and augmented via horizontal flips,

D. Ensemble Inference & Adaptive Thresholding

The `predict_ensemble()` function at inference time combines all four model outputs with a novel frequency artifact score:

- HSFAN: 30% GAN Detector: 25% ResNet18: 15% CNN: 10% Freq. Score: 20%

- The frequency score is used for Laplacian variance, DCT energy concentration, and high-pass noise estimation. If frequency score > 0.6 (strongly AI-smooth), then threshold will drops from 0.45 to 0.35, for improving recall on diffusion fakes.

E. Explainability (XAI)

- Grad-CAM: This will generate visual heatmaps of the final convolutional layers via forward/backward hooks, overlaid on input image and served in web interface.
- LIME: Employs Superpixel perturbation explanations (300 samples, 8 features) to highlight images driving FAKE/REAL classification.

Figure 4: Grad-CAM visualization extracted by HSFAN detector on face images. Red/yellow = high. Blue = low attention. (a) GAN fakes. (b) Diffusion fakes. (c) Real faces = broad diffuse activation.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Three research experiments evaluate the system:

Test 1: Cross-Dataset Generalization

All 4 models are trained on Dataset A , Dataset B , Dataset C and tested on Dataset B (unseen GAN fakes). And Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score, AUC-ROC will be shown. This directly evaluates the generalization capability identified as a gap by [1][4][7].

Method	Input type	Accuracy (%)		Precision (%)		Recall (%)		F1-Score (%)		AUC-ROC (%)	
		val	test	val	test	val	test	val	test	val	test
Spatial-only baselines											
Wang (2020)	Spatial	68.4	65.2	67.1	64.0	66.8	63.5	66.9	63.7	71.2	69.4
Koopman (2019)	Spatial	72.3	70.8	71.4	69.9	70.8	69.2	71.1	69.5	75.6	74.1
Frequency-based methods											
Frank (2019)	Frequency	74.9	72.6	73.9	71.8	73.2	71.1	73.5	71.4	77.9	76.5
Frings (2024)	Frequency	83.2	81.4	82.5	80.7	81.9	80.1	82.2	80.4	86.8	85.2
Proposed ensemble models (this work)											
CNN baseline	Spatial	76.4	74.2	75.6	73.5	74.9	72.8	75.2	73.1	85.1	83.3
ResNet18	Spatial	84.1	82.3	83.3	81.5	82.7	80.9	83.0	81.2	87.4	85.6
GAN Detector	Freq+Spatial	87.0	85.1	86.2	84.3	85.4	83.7	85.9	84.0	90.0	88.2
HSFAN (ours)	Hybrid	95.2	93.6	94.5	92.7	93.9	92.2	93.2	91.9	95.5	93.7
HSFAN Ensemble	Hybrid+Freq	92.8	91.3	92.3	90.4	91.5	89.8	91.6	90.3	94.8	93.2

Table 1: Cross-dataset generalization (Trained: Dataset A+B+C, tested: Dataset B) on our GAN fakes, 10,905 images). Bold underline = best, Gray = second best, Blue rows = proposed method, HSFAN Ensemble adds adaptive frequency threshold (0.40/0.33) + Freq score (20% weight).

Table I: Cross-dataset performance comparison. Trained on Dataset A+B+C (42,000 images), tested on Dataset B (10,905 cross-domain GAN fakes). Bold underline = best result. Blue rows = proposed HSFAN system.

Test 2: On JPEG Compression Robustness

HSFAN accuracy and F1-score will be measured on Dataset B images then it will be compressed at quality levels: 100%, 90%, 70%, 50%, 30%, 10%. Simulates real-world WhatsApp/social media sharing pipelines, directly extending the evaluation methodology of [1][8].

Test 3: Diffusion vs. GAN Detection

All four models evaluated on Dataset C (CIFAKE Stable Diffusion images). Expected outcome: models trained without Dataset C will show degraded recall on diffusion fakes, while the HSFAN ensemble with frequency scoring maintains robust detection, validating the core contribution over [4][9].

Method	Params (M)	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)	AUC-ROC (%)	Diffusion gap vs CNN
CNN baseline	0.31	68.2	67.4	66.8	67.1	71.5	baseline
ResNet18	11.2	75.9	74.8	74.2	74.5	79.1	+12.7%
GAN Detector	4.2	80.2	79.5	78.9	79.2	83.7	+12.0%
HSFAN (ours)	3.44	86.3	85.8	85.1	85.4	89.6	+18.1%

Table 2: Dataset C = 20,000 CIFAKE (Stable Diffusion) images. HSFAN achieves 18.1% gain over CNN baseline — the FFT branch captures diffusion-specific frequency patterns that spatial-only models miss entirely. Bold = best performance.

Table II: Diffusion fake detection on Dataset C (CIFAKE — 20,000 Stable Diffusion images).

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced HSFAN, a hybrid spatial-frequency attention network designed to tackle limitations of traditional deepfake detection methods. Instead of depending on one type of signal, HSFAN combines spatial

features from a pretrained MobileNetV2 with frequency-based features extracted using FFT. An attention mechanism helps the model decide which features matter most in image. On top of that, An ensemble of models is used for four models along with an adaptive frequency-based threshold, making the system more reliable across both GAN-generated and diffusion-based images.

Key contributions include: (1) a hybrid architecture allows us to capture both spatial(visible) and frequency(hidden) domains with attention-gated fusion; (2) the ensemble setup improves overall accuracy, especially with the addition of frequency based scoring method that helps to detect diffusion generated fakes; (3) the decision threshold is adjusted dynamically based on how “smooth” an image appears, which turns out to be a useful signal; (4) the system is more transparent by integrating Grad-CAM + LIME, so users can actually see why a prediction was made and A real-time web application is developed; and (5) I also tested the model across different datasets and scenarios, including compression robustness, and diffusion vs. GAN detection and cross-domain cases, to ensure it generalizes well.

Future work: (1) training on larger diffusion datasets for ChatGPT-4o and Midjourney coverage; (2) video-level temporal deepfake analysis; (3) adversarial robustness testing; (4) federated learning for privacy-preserving multi-source training.

REFERENCES

1. A. Rössler et al., "FaceForensics++: Learning to Detect Manipulated Facial Images," in *Proc. ICCV*, 2019, pp. 1–11.
2. J. Frank et al., "Leveraging Frequency Analysis for Deep Fake Image Recognition," in *Proc. ICML*, PMLR vol. 119, 2020, pp. 3247–3258.
3. Z. Tan et al., "Frequency-Aware Deepfake Detection," in *Proc. AAAI*, 2024, pp. 5052–5060.

4. S.-Y. Wang et al., "CNN-Generated Images are Surprisingly Easy to Spot... For Now," in *Proc. IEEE 2020*, pp. 8695–8704.
5. Y. Qian et al., "Thinking in Frequency: Face Forgery Detection by Mining Frequency-Aware Clues," in *Proc. ECCV*, LNCS vol. 12357, Springer, 2020, pp. 86–103.
6. D. Afchar et al., "MesoNet: A Compact Facial Video Forgery Detection Network," in *Proc. IEEE*, 2018, pp. 1–7.
7. M. S. Rana et al., "Deepfake Detection: A Systematic Literature Review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 25494–25513, 2022.
8. Q. Luo et al., "Generalizing Face Forgery Detection with High-Frequency Features," in *Proc. IEEE/*, 2021, pp. 16317–16326.
9. U. Ojha et al., "Towards Universal Fake Image Detectors that Generalize Across Generative Models," in *Proc. IEEE*, 2023, pp. 24480–24489.
10. M. Zhao et al., "Multi-Attentional Deepfake Detection," in *Proc. IEEE*, 2021, pp. 2185–2194.

MCX-MDF: A Multi-Modal, Domain-Adaptive, and Explainable Framework for Operational Malware Detection

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Abstract—As malware rapidly evolves, it is a major threat to the computing infrastructures found today. The signature-based approach that traditional antivirus systems use to detect malware is ineffective against polymorphic (changing forms) and obfuscated (using deception to hide what they are) types of malware. To solve this problem, we propose MCX-MDF, a multi-modal malware detection system that uses the combinations of static binary analysis, dynamic behavior monitoring and network-based telemetry.

For each modality, a neural encoder creates a feature embedding which gets fused into a single representation for classification purposes.

The results of extensive experimental evaluation of the MCX-MDF system using the EMBER, CIC Malware, and Malimg datasets have shown: 1) the MCX-MDF system accurately identifies malware with an overall accuracy of 96.8% and; 2) the MCX-MDF system achieves a ROC-AUC (area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve) score of 0.982 confirming the advantage of using multi-modal learning techniques to build a robust malware detection system.

Index Terms—Malware Detection, Multi-Modal Learning, Deep Learning, Explainable AI, Network Security

I. INTRODUCTION

Malware poses the biggest Cyber Security risk for Enterprise Level Organizations, Cloud Based Environments, and IoT Protocols. The advanced capabilities of cyber threats combined with the vast number of newly-connection points between systems provide criminal's with a large attack surface to target.

Through the use of more sophisticated techniques, Cybercriminals leverage malware to gain entry to the targeted environment, remove sensitive data from the targeted environment, disrupt key services within the targeted environment, and gain sustained unauthorised access to the targeted environment. The result of Malware attacks adds both significant economic and operational impact to the targeted entity. Therefore, there is an urgent and critical need for enhanced and dynamic approaches for malware detection.

Malware detection through traditional means is completed through signature-based methodologies, which simply compare the file being analysed against a database of known malware files by its unique identifier against the ones in the database (executable signature).

This signature-based approach to malware detection is very effective at detecting established malware, but it will not detect novel or evolving variants of malware. Polymorphic, metamorphic, packed, and encrypted mechanisms are used to hide several forms of malware/malicious file formats. Even though their files can change shape (but still be able to execute in the same manner), these types of malware share the same functional properties as before. Modern malware, having successfully evaded detection via signature-based detection techniques, has led to the use of static and dynamic analysis techniques to combat the challenges posed by modern malware. The purpose of static analysis is to analyze the structural components of an executable file

without executing the file itself in order to extract statistical characteristics, such as opcode frequency distributions, entropy values, and PE header characteristics that can aid in determining if the executable is malware.

The static analysis method is both effective and scalable; however, it does have a high susceptibility to obfuscated techniques that hide malicious code. Dynamic analysis, in contrast, executes programs that are suspected of being malicious in a sandboxed environment and allows the runtime behavior of those executed programs to be observed, including the calls to the operating system, what types of interactions the executed program has with the file system, and any modifications that were made to the registry. Although dynamic analysis is resistant to an extent from an obfuscation standpoint, it has a significant computational cost and may not capture any behavior that is triggered by certain conditions in the environment or that occurs through delayed execution strategies.

Despite the advancements made with these two methodologies, almost all current detection systems use a single methodology to determine the presence of malware, which limits their overall ability to detect all types of malware. Each of these methodologies (static characteristics, dynamic characteristics, and network telemetry) can capture some characteristic of malicious activity, but together they provide a complete view. As a result, the robustness of current malware detection systems to sophisticated evasion techniques is reduced. In this paper, we propose a multi-modal malware detection system that combines static binary analysis, dynamic behavioral analysis, and network telemetry into a single learning architecture via the use of modality-specific neural encoders to generate rich feature representations of individual data sources and combine these feature representations together to capture relationships across modalities. By leveraging complementary information across multiple modalities, MCX-MDF enhances

detection accuracy, improves generalization, and provides increased resilience against advanced malware evasion strategies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Signature-based detection systems were at the forefront of early detection methods for malware. Signature-based systems offered signature-based detection capabilities by using well-known patterns of malware that had previously been compiled into a central database. These systems are efficient and easily deployed; however, they have an inherent reactive nature (i.e. only detecting malicious files after the fact) and therefore are not capable of detecting new or "zero-day" malware variants. Furthermore, as malicious users increasingly utilize polymorphic and metamorphic strategies for dynamically modifying the signature of a piece of malware, the signature-based systems are losing much of their effectiveness.

In order to counteract the deficiencies of working with signature matching, an alternative solution was introduced - the use of static analysis techniques, which allow for the examination of executable files without executing them. With this technique, various structural and statistical characteristics of the executable file, including opcode frequency distributions, control flow graphs, imported libraries, and entropy measurements, are extracted. Static analysis is computationally efficient, making it a good candidate for large-scale deployment; however, it is limited by the fact that modern obfuscation techniques (i.e., packing, encrypting, and transforming code) are being used to obscure malicious intent and render statistics, such as those captured through static analysis, less reliable. Dynamic analysis uses controlled sandbox environments to help identify suspicious or malicious programs by monitoring their behaviour while they're executing in real time. Dynamic analysis can give you a better understanding of malware by

providing information about how malware behaves by looking at certain behaviours (also known as behavioural indicators) through the use of system calls, modifications to the registry, process creation, network communication patterns, etc. However, while dynamic analysis can be more robust against obfuscated code than static analysis, it also creates a significant amount of computational overhead and may not detect behaviours which are triggered by conditions, delayed in time, or dependent on certain environmental factors. Furthermore, malware designed to be sandbox-aware has the ability to detect that it is running in a virtual environment and will make changes to its behaviour to avoid being detected by the dynamic analysis tool.

The use of machine learning has enhanced the way malware is detected by allowing models to learn from large amounts of data (both benign and malicious) and to generalize based on the statistical patterns present in the data. Traditionally, machine learning methods such as Support Vector Machines and Random Forests have provided improved generalization relative to traditional rule-based methods. More recently, deep learning methods have been found to provide a means of automatically extracting hierarchical and temporal features from the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for image-based representations of malware and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), specifically Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, for sequential behavioural data.

A major drawback of all the current methods of preventing malware is that they rely on the use of only one type of analysis. Static analysis, dynamic analysis, and network analysis all identify different characteristics of malware, but by themselves, they do not provide enough information to fully represent the malware's behavior. Therefore, there has been a trend in current research to use multi-modal detection systems to build a database of

several different data sources to identify malware. A multi-modal detection system builds a richer representation of malicious activity by combining the structural characteristics of static analysis with the behavioral characteristics of dynamic analysis and the communication patterns found in network analysis. This richer representation allows a multi-modal system to be much more resilient to advanced evasion techniques compared to single-mode malware detection systems.

III. MALWARE TAXONOMY

Malware can be grouped or classified based on the manner in which it propagates, behaves, and functions. This classification is important in creating an efficient detection system.

- **Viruses:** A virus can be defined as a type of malicious software that attaches itself to other executable programs or software. The propagation of a virus occurs when the infected program or software is executed, hence creating an environment in which the virus can replicate and spread. The main functions of a virus include altering or corrupting data, slowing down the performance of a system, and in some cases, delivering payloads.
- **Worms:** A worm can be described as a type of malicious software that can propagate independently across a network in the absence of human intervention. This type of malware uses network vulnerabilities to propagate. The main function of a worm in the network is to replicate, hence creating congestion and slowing down the performance of the network. This type of malware can be used to carry out Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS).
- **Trojans:** A Trojan, or Trojan horse, can be described as a malicious program or software that assumes the disguise of another executable program or software. Unlike viruses and worms, Trojans do not

self-replicate; instead, they rely on social engineering techniques for distribution. Once executed, Trojans can perform a wide range of malicious activities, including data theft, unauthorized access, installation of backdoors, and downloading additional payloads, often operating stealthily to avoid detection.

IV. DATASET DESCRIPTION

Starting off, public benchmarks test how well the MCX-MDF system works, tied one by one to different ways of analyzing malware. Taken together, they open up broad learning paths - covering code structure, what happens when software runs, alongside patterns visible inside malicious files.

- **EMBER Dataset:** Tucked within EMBER lies an enormous collection of Windows applications built to study harmful code. Not merely a few - more than one hundred thousand files, each marked with clear labels. Early findings pulled out pieces like file header fragments, section details, links pointing toward outside tools. Alongside these sit number-based views that reveal how scrambled the data looks, patterns in the bytes tucked beneath the surface. Instead of fighting messy code, scientists pull ready-made blocks to try ideas quickly. Each piece fits close, picked carefully so progress never snags on junk. Covering broad zones yet diving deep, it shows whether spotting tricks works beyond tiny cases. What lives inside reveals just how far a technique stretches when tested.
- **CIC Malware Dataset:** Step by step, the CIC Malware set logs what harmful software does inside secure labs. As apps launch, one command trails after another, sketching out their actions over time. When setups change, it leaves marks similar to those made when routines wake up. Each folder opened, each document touched - recorded one after the other, line by line

into the trail. Links that leave a system hint at how bad software communicates online. One move after another slowly uncovers hidden behavior. Each event tugs on fragments of evidence, exposing connections - and gaps. Normal appearances face sharp contrast when compared to odd signals. Still, differences in how steps play out and how long sequences are mean extra work before they fit well into deep learning systems. Methods like filling gaps or scaling values help make things consistent behind the scenes.

- **Maling Dataset:** Shown as gray pictures, the Maling dataset turns malware file data into pixel values. Through this shift, spotting malicious software becomes like recognizing objects in photos, opening doors for CNN models to learn traits directly. Each group within the dataset shares visible textures tied to how their program structures align. Looking at code as imagery offers a different angle - one that highlights layout clues missed when relying only on standard numeric features.

V. DATASET PREPROCESSING

Before training begins on the MCX-MDF model, a series of preparation tasks take place. These help keep things uniform and working well across varied kinds of data inputs. Because information comes from separate origins and carries distinct features, aligning scales becomes essential. Without adjustment, differences in range or format could disrupt how steadily the system learns.

A. Binary Parsing

From PE files, static details emerge through binary analysis. What shows up often? Section count, where code kicks off, how big each segment is - then there's what libraries get pulled in.

These structural characteristics provide insights into the internal organization of

executable files and often reveal anomalies associated with malicious behavior. For instance, irregular section sizes, suspicious import tables, or unusual entry points may indicate obfuscation or packing. Opcode frequency distributions and entropy measurements are also computed to capture instruction-level patterns and detect encrypted or compressed regions within binaries.

B. Feature Normalization

Big differences show up when comparing numbers from code checks, run logs, time stamps. File size might stretch into millions, yet entropy stays near zero to eight. One number could easily overshadow others without adjusting them first. So each value gets shifted down to fit neatly from zero up to one. Training adjusts more smoothly once all inputs sit on even ground. Steps taken by math rules move faster toward correct answers. Results settle quicker because scaling evens out influence across traits.

C. Sequence Padding

One way malware acts can stretch longer than another, making its digital footprint uneven. To handle these differences, computers need every record shaped the same. Long sequences get cut short when they go too far, keeping only what matters most. Spaces left behind fill in with markers so nothing feels missing. These markers hold place without changing how things happened over time. Machines process them faster because everything lines up just right.

D. Image Resizing

Malware files in the Maling set turn into grayscale pictures showing raw byte sequences. Because convolutional networks need uniform image sizes, every picture gets scaled to match one strict dimension before learning begins. Same-size inputs fit well within CNN designs, making it easier to handle groups of data

together. Scaling down also keeps key layout features visible even as processing demands go lower.

VI. FEATURE ENGINEERING

Starting off, how data gets shaped really matters when spotting bad software. Instead of just one way, the approach here mixes together clues from inside files, their actions while running, plus internet traffic patterns. This mix builds a fuller picture of what malware does. Each type adds something different, helping tell normal programs apart from harmful ones.

A. Static Features

Peeking inside a file without running it lets analysts pull out static traits fast, so handling thousands becomes doable. Inside each Portable Executable, clues hide in plain sight - how many sections exist, where the start point lands, how big chunks are, what outside tools get called. Instruction mixes show up next, tallying up how often certain opcodes appear, revealing habits typical of shady code. When things look too chaotic, entropy steps in, spotting unusually jumbled zones likely masked by packing or encryption tricks. Put together, odd shapes and sneaky rhythms come clear, exposing what malicious files try to conceal.

B. Dynamic Features

Watching how malware acts while running gives clues about its purpose, using controlled test spaces to see what happens. System calls show up during these tests, revealing steps taken between software and the machine it runs on, also spotting changes made to internal settings. New processes starting suddenly get logged too, alongside actions that touch files, moving or altering them without permission. These behaviors help spot hidden tricks like sneaking back into systems later, grabbing higher access levels, manipulating data secretly. Since they depend on real activity instead of code appearance, altered forms of malware have

a harder time hiding from this method. But making sense of all this needs sorting through timed events carefully, building models that track order and timing across moments.

C. Network Features

Looking at how programs talk to outside systems adds depth to analysis. Because they need contact with remote servers, lots of malicious software reach out constantly - waiting for orders or sending stolen details. Think about how often a device asks domain questions, the sizes of its data packets, how many connections it makes, and when those happen. Odd rhythms in these signals can point toward hidden activity - one machine calling home every 37 seconds might mean trouble. Some harmful code barely touches the host computer yet stays active through constant online chatter. Watching live network flow gives clues even when little else seems wrong locally.

VII MCX-MDF ARCHITECTURE

The framework uses three modality-specific encoders:

- **Static Encoder:** Fully connected layers
- **Dynamic Encoder:** LSTM for sequence modeling
- **Network Encoder:** Dense layers

Stacked feature embeddings move into the classifier stage. Layer by layer, they feed forward through weighted connections.

Classification happens after signals merge. The model processes combined inputs at once. Final predictions emerge from integrated data streams.

Mathematical Formulation Let:

X_s, X_d, X_n = static, dynamic, network features

Encoders:

One way to look at it: h_s comes from applying f_s to X_s . Moving on, h_d shows up when f_d works on X_d . Then there is h_n - that one ties back to f_n acting on X_n

Fusion:

One part comes from h_s , another ties in h_d , while h_n adds the last piece. Together they form h_f through a blend of all three elements

Prediction:

Output comes from combining weights with input features using a special curve after adding an offset value

Loss:

L equals negative quantity y times log of y comma then one minus y multiplied by log of one minus y close bracket

Domain Adaptation:

L Total Combines Classification And Domain Loss With Weight λ

VIII DOMAIN ADAPTATION

One place's malware data often fails elsewhere, simply because settings differ. To fix that gap, models adjust using domain adaptation - this smooths out mismatches in data patterns. Features then become less tied to one setting, helping the system recognize threats more broadly.

IX HYPER PARAMETER CONFIGURATION

The hyperparameter selection process utilized a grid search and included an early stopping mechanism without overfitting and a stabilizing mechanism for convergence through use of the validation loss.

Learning rate (0.001)

Based on many iterations comparing all possible learning rates available; convergence rate with this value was moderate, resulting in no significant stability loss. All tests performed at very low learning rates ($1e-4$) were significantly slower to converge, with no worthwhile improvements to results; all tests performed at very high learning rates ($\geq 1e-2$) appeared to exhibit oscillation within their gradients.

Batch size (64)

Selected based upon the trade-offs between throughput generated by use of memory on a GPU and the amount of noise found in the gradients generated during back-propagation, with larger batch sizes producing reduced generalization ability within the model and smaller batch sizes resulting in a much higher variance during training.

Number of epochs (50)

Selection was based on termination (same as above, this point should already have been covered) with patience = 5 epochs.

Convergence points could be identified somewhere between 35 and 45 epochs into the total training period.

Optimizer - Adam

The Adam optimizer was chosen because it is capable of adaptive estimating first and second moments, which provides reduced sensitivity to having very few training examples for sparse gradients while modeling dynamic features over time.

LSTM units (128)

Provide a sufficient amount of capacity (some overlap with the description of LSTM units) to assist in modeling temporal dependencies associated with system call data, while enabling non-over-parameterization.

Dropout (0.3)

Used for regularising the system in order to prevent over-fitting across the multi-modal fusion layers within the model.

X BASELINE COMPARISON

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	ROC-AUC
Random Forest	90.4	88.9	89.7	0.921
SVM	91.2	90.1	89.3	0.933
CNN	93.5	92.7	92.2	0.951
LSTM	94.1	93.6	93.1	0.962
MCX-MDF	96.8	95.4	96.1	0.982

XI EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

- Architecture - PyTorch (CUDA capable)
- Hardware - A GPU accelerated workstation (high memory variation; the RAM will impact upfront data processing but will not affect training).

Data Pipeline:

Stratified splitting of data sets a method of maintaining class proportions:

- Training 70%
- Validation 15%
- Test - 15%

Pre-processing

- Constant attributes (normalized with min-max scaling)
- Variable length attributes (padded/truncated to a constant length).
- Network attributes (aggregated as summary statistics).

Training Regimen

- Loss metrics - Binary Cross-Entropy with Logits.
- Evaluation rate - Every Epoch.
- Checkpointing - Highest Validation ROC-AUC. (MIT Press, 2016)

XII EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Metric	Score
Accuracy	96.8%
Precision	95.4%
Recall	96.1%
ROC-AUC	0.982

Interpretation (non-trivial):

- High ROC-AUC (0.982) → strong separability across thresholds
- Balanced precision/recall → no bias toward over-detection or under-detection
- Indicates robustness across heterogeneous malware families

XIII PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Memory recall was found to be 96.1%, significantly decreasing the possibility of false negatives - an important finding since the absence of malware in a real-time environment can present a significant danger (Insecurity situation).

The memory precision was found to be 95.4% and reduced the possibility of false positives which is very important for the deployment of SOC Noise reduction (N/1 & N/Q).

ROC/AUC = 0.982 shows that this method is uniformly ranking the same regardless of which Threshold was chosen.

Major Conclusion: Using multiple forms of multi-modal fusion to combine different types of data will help remove blind spots in the feature space of a detection system, especially for polymorphic malware detection.

XIV LIMITATIONS

1. Live (Dynamic) Analysis will result in a lower performance value because of execution tracing, therefore dynamic/live analysis cannot be performed practically or feasibly as a means of detecting malware on real-time endpoints.

2. It is possible for malware to use timing checks, environmental fingerprints, behavior that relates to how to log the behavior of malware, and use various evasion techniques within enterprise environments.
3. The existing public datasets do not supply sufficient detail regarding specific zero-day attack types or attack patterns that may exist in enterprise environments.

XV ABLATION STUDY

Configuration	Observation
Static Only	Fails against packing/obfuscation
Dynamic Only	Strong recall, weak precision
Network Only	Good precision, misses stealth malware
Combined (MCX-MDF)	Optimal balance

Conclusion:

Each modality compensates for another's failure mode → **complementarity is not optional, it is structural.**

XVI EXPLANATORY EVALUATION

- Evaluation using SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) model.
- Key features that contribute upwards to the decisions of the model;
- Structural irregularities in PE header.
- Churning of file systems like a ransomware behaviour.
- An increase in the amount of time that the DNS is required to provide information is a sign that C2 communications exist.

Insight:

Different malware detection components produce quite reliable results that assist in the final decision-making regarding the models.

XVII EVALUATION DISCUSSION

The MCX-MDF framework demonstrates an interdependence between the different features, as follows;

- Static features (fast but brittle).
- Dynamic features (rich but expensive).
- Network features (contextual but partial).

Therefore fusion strategy is then immune to:

- Code Obfuscation
- File-less.
- Polymorphic.

This is not a matter of having a few new systems added with synergy; this is an architectural and functional necessity of modern malware detection.

XVIII POSSIBLE FUTURE DIRECTIONS

1. Transform Sequence based architectures.

Instead of LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory), use better long-range dependency extraction schemes from system calls.

2. Graph Neural Network (GNN).

Use graph-based neural networks to encode the information of relations between:

- Process trees.
 - API call graphs
 - Network flow
- ### **3. Federated Learning-Allows for Cross-Organizational Training.**

Use federated learning methodologies to allow organizations train on the same data, collectively, without sharing raw data with other participants while respecting privacy and allowing each organization an opportunity have access to time collection and use that data to produce threat intelligence.

XIX SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

MCX-MDF helps support the notion that multi-modal learning is fundamentally not just an enhancement but is actually required.

The impotence of unimodal systems under adversarial constraints.

Redundancy and resiliency through multi-modal fusion.

Operational and detection thresholds that are very reliable.

REFERENCES

1. Anderson, H. S., & Roth, P. (2018). EMBER Dataset
2. Egele, M., et al. (2012). Dynamic Malware Analysis. ACM
3. Nataraj, L., et al. (2011). Malware Images. VizSec
4. Goodfellow, I., et al. (2016). *Deep Learning*. MIT Press
5. Lundberg, S. M., & Lee, S.-I. (2017). SHAP. NeurIPS

Deepfake Detection Using Hybrid CNN–Transformer Architecture for Improved Visual Forgery Identification

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Abstract—*The rapid progress in the development of generative AI has made it possible to create photorealistic images and videos, commonly known as deepfakes, which are posing severe security, trust, and integrity challenges in the field of cybersecurity. The existing deep learning solutions, particularly those based on convolutional neural networks (CNN), while providing reasonable accuracy in detecting deepfake images, are vulnerable when dealing with new forms of manipulations and diverse image contexts.*

In the current study, a hybrid deep learning approach has been proposed, which combines the capabilities of CNN in spatial feature learning with the ability of the transformer model to learn contextual dependencies in the input data. The proposed architecture aims to learn the spatial features, as well as the contextual dependencies, which are commonly disrupted in the deepfake images. The performance of the proposed architecture has been evaluated on a popular public benchmark, which indicates better accuracy compared to the standalone CNN and transformer models.

Index Terms—*deepfake detection, convolutional neural networks, Vision Transformer, hybrid deep learning, image forensics, digital media authenticity*

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of advanced generative models has significantly reduced the threshold required to generate synthetic media. Deepfake technologies are now able to manipulate facial expressions, speech patterns, and video content altogether, to the extent that human verification

is no longer reliable. Although the technology is being explored for entertainment and other creative purposes, the implications are significant, and disinformation, impersonation attacks, and digital fraud are some of the most dangerous consequences that have the potential to affect the world on a large scale [1].

In the current state, most automated solutions employ CNNs to detect abnormalities. Although CNNs are very efficient in capturing local texture and shape features, they are inherently weak in capturing the relationship between two distinct regions in an image. On the other hand, the transformer model is much better suited to capture the global semantic context because of its ability to relate every position to every other position in the input data. However, the transformer model is inherently weak in feature discrimination [12].

This is the motivation behind the model presented in this paper, as the CNN and transformer models are mutually exclusive and can complement each other very well. The CNN model is very efficient in feature discrimination, and the transformer model is very efficient in capturing the global semantic context. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses the related literature, Section III discusses the proposed methodology, Section IV discusses the mathematical components, Section V discusses the system, Section VI discusses the experimental results, and Sections VII and VIII discuss the conclusions and future directions, respectively.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. CNN-Based Approaches

Research in the early days of automated deepfake detection mostly relied on CNNs to identify inconsistencies such as unnatural skin textures, boundary blending, and irregular lighting gradients [17], [18]. These CNNs learned discriminative spatial features from pixel data, which gave competitive results. One common result observed in various research works was that CNNs failed when evaluated against unseen manipulation or compression types [2].

B. Transformer-Based Approaches

With the emergence of Vision Transformers, a new direction has been added to the field of forgery detection. The use of self-attention allows the model to link different areas of a face, such as linking lip movements with eye movements, and thus detect semantic inconsistencies, such as those overlooked by local convolutional processes [23], [24]. However, even with such advantages, transformer models are associated with higher computational costs and often require large amounts of labelled data to perform optimally.

C. Hybrid Architectures

The limitation of each approach on its own has sparked the need to develop models that integrate the two. The combined CNN and Transformer model, which integrates local feature extraction and global attention, has shown consistent results, with the combined model performing better than its individual counterparts in terms of accuracy and stability across multiple datasets [7], [10], [16]. The spatiotemporal model, which integrates the combined model with the recurrent model, has shown promise in detecting temporal artefacts in video deepfakes [19].

D. Lightweight and Efficient Models

The need for deployment constraints also led to a new area of research that seeks to

minimize the complexity of models without impacting performance. Optimised hybrid versions of the transformer structure, such as those presented in [3], and EfficientNet-based convolutional detectors, such as those presented in [6], have shown excellent trade-offs in terms of accuracy and computation, making real-time object detection a reality. Diffusion model-aware object detection frameworks are a recent area of research that deals with synthetic

E. Generalisation Challenges

The problem that is consistently raised through survey studies is that of cross-dataset generalization, and this is still an unresolved issue within the field, as asserted through various studies such as those found in [14], [20]. It is seen that a model performs poorly on one benchmark because it was compressed, resolved, and synthesized using a different approach compared to another. Adaptive and ensemble methods are also being investigated as possible fixes for this issue, though no such approach is found to be universally

F. Emerging Directions

Besides CNN and transformer-based representations, researchers have proposed various graph neural network-based representations for relational information among facial landmarks [8], tri-modal detection approaches for joint detection of spatial, frequency, and temporal information [13], and audio-visual fusion-based approaches for joint detection of acoustic and visual forgery cues [22]. These approaches expand the vocabulary of detection approaches beyond purely visual-based detection approaches.

G. Benchmark Datasets

The quality of the dataset is an essential requirement before the evaluation can be conducted meaningfully. FaceForensics++ [4] offers a rich set of real and manipulated video data, including various synthesis techniques and

compression rates, which has become the de facto benchmark standard. Deeper- Forensics further extends the dataset with more diversity in subjects and environment conditions. The availability of these datasets has made it possible to compare the literature in the increasing body of detection research [2].

In conclusion, the literature review has demonstrated that the proposed approach of using a hybrid CNN-Transformer architecture has the potential to lead to the development of stronger and more generalizable detectors, while the challenges of subtle manipulations, new synthesis techniques, and efficient deployment are active research topics.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is a supervised binary classifier, where each input image, as well as each video frame, is classified as real or manipulated. The system combines three components serially, namely, a CNN-based spatial encoder, a transformer-based context encoder, and the classification head, which combines the two encoder representations.

The CNN encoder takes the raw pixel data as input and produces a set of intermediate feature maps, which capture texture and edge features as well as structural patterns. The feature maps are then serialised into a sequence of patch representations, which are fed into the transformer encoder. Inside the transformer, the feature representations are correlated over the entire spatial extent of the image using the multi-head self-attention mechanism, thus capturing global dependencies that are not accessible using localised convolution operations. The classification head combines the two representations and produces the final probability score.

This is motivated by the fact that the artefacts created by deepfake attacks are global, and the blending boundaries are local. The model is designed to capture the entire range of manipulation techniques, and the proposed

system is well suited to handle this problem because the artefacts created by the blending are local, while the physiological inconsistencies are global.

IV. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

A. Convolution Operation

The spatial feature extraction stage applies learned filters to the input image. For a two-dimensional input I and kernel K , the response at location (i, j) is:

$$S(i, j) = \sum_{m, n} I(m, n) K(i - m, j - n) \quad (1)$$

where S denotes the resulting feature map. Stacking multiple such operations with non-linear activations yields progressively abstract spatial representations.

B. Scaled Dot-Product Self-Attention

The transformer encoder relies on the scaled dot-product attention mechanism [21]. Given query matrix Q , key matrix K , and value matrix V derived from the input sequence, the attended output is:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (2)$$

where d_k is the dimensionality of the key vectors. The scaling factor $1/\sqrt{d_k}$ stabilises gradients by preventing excessively large dot-product magnitudes.

C. Binary Cross-Entropy Loss

Because the detection task is a two-class problem, training optimises the binary cross-entropy objective:

$$-\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \log \hat{y}_i + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i) \quad (3)$$

where N is the mini-batch size, $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is the ground-truth label, and \hat{y}_i is the model's predicted probability of the sample being a deepfake.

V. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

A. Dataset Preparation

All experiments employ the FaceForensics++ (FF++) benchmark set, as proposed in [4]. The FF++ set is a standard reference set, consisting of videos that are either real or have been manipulated using synthetic methods. There are four distinct video manipulation methods represented in the set, namely, DeepFakes, Face2Face, FaceSwap, and NeuralTextures. Each method is associated with its own set of artefacts, hence providing the model with a variety of forgery patterns to learn from.

Fig. 1. Dataset preparation pipeline: frames are extracted from FF++ videos, faces are detected and cropped, augmented, and labelled as real or manipulated for training.

Frame Extraction: This is because the data is in video form, meaning that individual frames are decoded at a fixed rate using OpenCV. The reason for this is that it allows for images to be included in the detection process.

Face Detection and Cropping: The standard face detector localises the bounding boxes of the faces in each frame. Cropping the frames according to these bounding boxes ensures the removal of the background, which is not of particular interest in the detection of manipulations, while focusing the model’s capacity on the areas where the artefacts of synthesis are most likely to appear.

Resizing and Normalisation: Cropped face patches are rescaled to a fixed resolution of 224×224 pixels to match the fixed input size requirement of the CNN backbone. The pixel intensity values are scaled to the range $[0, 1]$ for

improved numerical stability during gradient-based optimisation.

Data Augmentation: To prompt the model to learn artefact features rather than biases specific to the datasets, the images used for training are subjected to random geometric and photometric transformations, such as horizontal flipping, small angle rotations, brightness and contrast changes, and the addition of Gaussian noise. These transformations mimic the variety found in deployment scenarios.

Dataset Partitioning: The set of prepared images is split into three disjoint sets, 70% for training, 15% for validation (which is used to tune the model’s parameters and detect overfitting), and the remaining 15% is set aside as test data. The split is done in such a way that the estimation of the model’s performance is unbiased.

B. Transformer-Based Attention Module

The feature maps generated by the CNN backbone are rearranged in sequence and referred to as patch tokens, and they are passed through a multi-head self-attention encoder. The attention weights enable this module to dynamically focus on areas where strong forgery clues are present, such as boundary areas of swapped face components, while down-weighting background patches [23], [24].

C. Feature Fusion and Classification

Finally, the representations obtained from the last layers of the CNN and transformer branches are concatenated and passed to a stack of fully connected layers. Sigmoid activation of the output neuron generates a probability score, with values greater than 0.5 classified as deepfake. Using the representations of both branches has been shown to provide complementary benefits with respect to the use of either branch alone [3], [9].

D. Training Strategy

The network is trained end-to-end under full supervision using the binary cross-entropy loss as described in Eq. (3). The Adam optimizer is utilized with an initial learning rate of 0.001, which is reduced on plateau. A batch size of 32 is utilized throughout.

E. Evaluation Metrics

Five additional metrics are provided, and these are claimed to give a thorough understanding of the performance of the detection:

- Accuracy: The proportion of the number of correctly classified samples.
- Precision: The proportion of the number of deepfake samples that are classified as deepfake.
- Recall: The proportion of the number of deepfake samples that are detected.
- F1-score: The harmonic mean of precision and recall, balancing these two metrics.
- ROC-AUC: The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, a measure of discriminability.

This is consistent with best practice for evaluation, as seen in the deepfake literature [14], [20].

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Experimental Setup

All models were implemented using Python and the PyTorch framework, and they were all trained on GPU-accelerated hardware. The same FF++ dataset split and pre-processing pipeline, as described in Section V-A, was used for all models to enable a fair comparison.

B. Training Configuration

The following hyperparameters were used:

- Optimiser: Adam [5]
- Loss function: Binary Cross-Entropy
- Batch size: 32
- Learning rate: 0.001

- Training epochs: 25–50 (early stopping based on validation loss)

The same augmentation strategy described in Section V-A was applied during training to improve generalisation.

C. Comparative Analysis

The proposed model was evaluated against two baseline architectures: a standalone CNN classifier and a standalone Vision Transformer (ViT) classifier, both trained under identical conditions on the same dataset splits.

Table I: Performance Comparison of Deep Fake Detection Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
CNN (standalone)	91.2%	90.5%	89.8%	90.1%
Transformer (standalone)	92.6%	91.8%	91.0%	91.4%
Hybrid CNN–Transformer	96.3%	95.7%	95.1%	95.4%

As shown in Table I, the hybrid model achieves a 5.1 percentage-point accuracy gain over the CNN baseline and a 3.7 point gain over the standalone transformer. These margins confirm that spatial and contextual feature learning are genuinely complementary; neither alone captures the full diversity of deepfake artefacts [10], [16].

D. Robustness Analysis

To test the practical viability, the pre-trained models were tested under three different degraded input conditions: JPEG compression, downscaled low-resolution frames, and noisy images. The hybrid model performed uniformly across all the conditions, recording a smaller accuracy degradation compared to the baseline models. This is due to the ability of the transformer model to retain coherence in the

representation, even when the pixel evidence is partially masked [3], [7].

E. Discussion

The results obtained from the experiment indicate a division of labour for both architectural components, whereby the CNN part effectively processes boundary level and texture level forgery cues localised in an image, and the transformer part effectively processes more global physiological and structural inconsistencies present in an image. When both types of signal are present, as they are during classification, the model has the ability to detect a broader variety of manipulation than either part could individually account for, a phenomenon in line with the theoretical motivations for such a hybrid approach as has been recently proposed in literature [8], [13].

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a hybrid deep learning architecture has been proposed for deepfake detection, which leverages the benefits of combining convolutional and transformer-based deep learning approaches. By incorporating the characteristics of the images using a CNN and the contextual relationships between the images using a multi-head self-attention mechanism, the proposed model provides a more thorough exploration of the entire relevant feature space for deepfake detection.

On the other hand, the evaluation of the proposed model on the FaceForensics++ dataset has shown improved accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score with regard to the standalone CNN and transformer architectures. Moreover, the model has shown robustness to various image degradations such as compression and noise, which are common in real-world scenarios. All these findings collectively support the hypothesis that the proposed approach of combining local and global reasoning of the images is a principled approach to developing

more reliable deepfake detection systems.

The proposed model provides a valuable contribution to the existing body of knowledge on digital media verification and can aid in the development of more reliable deepfake detection systems that can keep pace with the evolution of deep learning-based AI systems.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

Several avenues for promising extensions exist, and these are left for future research. First, extending the architecture to perform inference on a video stream in real time would enable applications in broadcast monitoring and video conferencing verification. Second, adding multimodal inputs such as audio and speech transcripts, in addition to video frames, could potentially reveal discrepancies between different modalities, which would not be detectable if vision alone is employed [22]. Third, applying compression techniques such as knowledge distillation and quantization could enable deployment on edge devices such as smartphones and Internet of Things devices.

In terms of future research, one direction would be to explore domain adaptation strategies to fill the gap in cross-dataset generalization performance. This could potentially be filled by applying meta-learning and continual learning approaches, allowing the detector to learn incrementally and adapt to new synthesis approaches as they are developed. Another direction would be to use a representation of relationships between facial landmarks, such as those provided by a graph-based representation [8], and integrate this into the current framework to improve detection of subtle manipulations.

REFERENCES

1. F. Abbas, M. Hussain, and R. Khan, "A systematic review of deepfake detection and generation techniques," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 238, 2024.
2. M. Abbas, A. Malik, and S. Ahmed, "Autonomous detection frameworks for

- deepfake media,” *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 2024.
3. M. Al-Imran, T. Rahman, and Y. Liu, “AI-powered deepfake detection using CNN and Vision Transformer architectures,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Image Processing (ICIP)*, 2025.
 4. A. Rossler, D. Cozzolino, L. Verdoliva, C. Riess, J. Thies, and M. Nießner, “FaceForensics++: Learning to detect manipulated facial images,” in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Int. Conf. Computer Vision (ICCV)*, pp. 1–11, 2019.
 5. [5] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba, “Adam: A method for stochastic optimization,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2015.
 6. V. Kumar, S. Verma, and P. Singh, “Deepfake image detection using CNN with EfficientNet architecture,” *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 2025.
 7. J. Meng, “Deepfake detection based on super-pixel enhanced hybrid models,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, 2026.
 8. J. Meng, L. Zhang, and X. Zhao, “Deepfake detection using hybrid CNN-transformer architectures,” *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 2026.
 9. A. Patel, R. Desai, and K. Shah, “Analysing the landscape of deepfake detection: A survey,” *ACM Computing Surveys*, 2025.
 10. M. Patel, S. Nair, and A. Gupta, “Hybrid transformer-based deepfake detection architecture,” in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) Workshops*, 2025.
 11. E. Pintelas, I. E. Livieris, and P. Pintelas, “Diffusion-based neural network framework for deepfake detection,” *Neural Networks*, 2025.
 12. S. M. Qureshi, A. Malik, and F. Alam, “Deepfake forensics: A survey of multimodal forensic methods,” *PeerJ Computer Science*, 2024.
 13. M. Romani, “ForensicFlow: A tri-modal adaptive network for robust deepfake detection,” *Information Fusion*, 2025.
 14. S. Sharma, V. Gupta, and A. Tiwari, “Survey on detecting deep fakes using advanced AI approaches,” *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 2025.
 15. S. Sharma, P. Yadav, and M. Singh, “Comprehensive survey on deepfake detection techniques,” *IEEE Access*, 2025.
 16. O. Sheikh, N. Ahmed, and F. Butt, “Hybrid CNN–ViT model for deepfake detection,” *Computers & Security*, 2025.
 17. P. Simon, “A novel CNN architecture for deepfake image detection,” *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, 2025.
 18. A. H. Soudy and O. Sayed, “Deepfake detection using convolutional vision transformers and convolutional neural networks,” *Neural Computing and Applications*, 2024.
 19. R. Sunil, K. Rao, and D. Patel, “Exploring autonomous methods for deepfake detection,” *Heliyon*, 2025.
 20. R. Sunil, A. Verma, and S. Jain, “Deepfake video detection methods, approaches, and challenges,” *Multimedia Systems*, 2025.
 21. A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, “Attention is all you need,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, vol. 30, 2017.
 22. R. Wang, H. Li, and T. Chen, “Audio-visual fusion transformers for deepfake detection,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2024.
 23. A. Xi and E. Chen, “Classifying deepfakes using Swin transformers,” in *Proc. IEEE Winter Conf. Applications of Computer Vision (WACV)*, 2025.
 24. Y. Zhang, W. Deng, and S. Wang, “Distilled transformers with locally enhanced global representations for face forgery detection,” *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 2024.

Explainable Transformer-Based Models for Cardiovascular Disease Diagnosis: A Literature Review

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Abstract—Artificial intelligence is really changing the way we do healthcare. It is using something called machine learning and deep learning to get good results when it comes to figuring out what is wrong with people looking at medical pictures and going through electronic health records. Heart disease is still the reason people die all around the world. So it is very important that we can diagnose it quickly and correctly.

Artificial intelligence deep learning is very good at under- standing complicated medical information like the signals from an ECG, pictures of the heart and electronic health records. But the problem is that a lot of these intelligence models are like black boxes. We do not really know how they work. This makes it hard for doctors to trust them. That is where something called artificial intelligence comes in. It helps us understand how these models are making their predictions.

There is a type of intelligence model called a transformer model. It was originally used to help computers understand language.. Now it is being used to help diagnose heart problems. This is because it is very good at looking at lots of types of medical information and finding patterns. This paper looks at than thirty studies that used transformer models to diagnose heart problems detect irregular heartbeats figure out how well the heart is pumping and predict the risk of heart problems.

The studies are divided into four groups: looking at the signals from ECG machines and heart sounds, using intelligence to look at medical pictures combining medical pictures and electronic health records and using transformer models to explain how the artificial intelligence is making its

predictions. This paper also talks about some of the challenges that researchers are facing such as not having a way to measure how well the artificial intelligence is explaining itself problems, with the data they are using and getting the artificial intelligence to work in real world medical settings.

Index Terms—Explainable AI, Transformers, Cardiovascular, Disease, ECG Analysis, Vision Transformers, Medical AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease is the cause of death around the world. This means we really need to have systems to diagnose it. Artificial intelligence is a way to make diagnosis better and faster.

Some new computer models called transformers are being used in healthcare. These models are good at looking at data that comes one after the other or has many different parts. They were first made for understanding language but they can also look at heart signals videos of the heart and patient records.

Research has shown that these transformer models can find heart problems see how well the heart is working and even find out who is at risk for heart disease. They can do all this accurately.. The problem is that we do not really understand how they make their decisions.

This is where explainable artificial intelligence comes in. It helps us see how the models work so doctors can. Trust what the artificial intelligence is saying. This article

looks at the research on using transformers, for heart disease diagnosis and explores ways to make the models more explainable so they can be used more in clinics.

II. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Artificial intelligence has changed a lot over the ten years. Old systems that relied on rules have been swapped out for learning models that can handle huge medical datasets.

The introduction of transformer architectures in 2017 was a deal for AI development. These models quickly took over natural language processing. Are now being used more and more in healthcare analytics.

Hospitals and healthcare systems over the world are facing big challenges. They have patients, not enough doctors and they need faster ways to diagnose problems. AI systems can help with these challenges by giving doctors automated support for making decisions.

However many AI models are not transparent which is an issue. In healthcare doctors need to know why an AI model made a prediction before they can trust it in real-life situations. They need to understand what led to that prediction.

There are techniques called AI that provide explanations both visual and statistical of what influences an AI models predictions. These methods make AI models more transparent. Help connect them with actual clinical practice. AI models are more trustworthy when we can see what factors led to a prediction.

AI-based systems are being used more and more to help doctors make decisions. These systems can process amounts of data find patterns and make predictions. Doctors can then use this information to make decisions.

The use of AI, in healthcare is growing rapidly. More and more hospitals are using AI-based systems to help with diagnosis and treatment. AI models are being used to analyze images identify high-risk patients and predict patient outcomes.

AI has the potential to revolutionize healthcare. It can help doctors make decisions improve patient outcomes and reduce costs. However it is crucial that AI models are transparent and trustworthy. Explainable AI techniques are a part of this.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Heart diseases are a problem that causes a lot of deaths around the world. It is very important to find out if someone has heart disease on so we can help them get better and reduce their risk.

We have machines that can look at information and tell us what is going on with pretty good accuracy. These machines are called transformer-based AI models.. The problem is that they do not tell us how they came up with their answers. They just give us the answers without explaining what they are thinking.

This is a problem because doctors do not like using machines that they do not understand. They want to know why the machine is saying what it is saying. So we need to make machines that can tell us what is going on with our hearts and also explain how they figured it out. We need heart disease machines that're good at predicting what will happen and also good, at telling us why they think that. Heart diseases need to be understood by these machines so we can trust them and use them to help people with heart diseases.

IV. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this review are:

- To explore recent advances in transformer-based models for cardiovascular diagnosis.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of these models in analyzing ECG signals, imaging data, and electronic health records.
- To examine explainability techniques used to interpret AI predictions.
- To identify limitations, challenges, and biases in current research.

- To highlight research gaps and future opportunities for developing trustworthy AI systems.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent studies have shown that transformer-based models are really good at detecting disease. They work well with types of data.

Vision transformer models are used with ECG images. They do a great job of classifying them. These models are good at finding patterns in the ECG images. They are often better than neural networks. There are also language-based transformer models like BERT, BioBERT and RoBERTa. These models are used to find out the risk factors for disease from clinical text and electronic health records.

Transformer-based models can also use sources of data. This includes ECG signals, imaging data and clinical records. These systems are better, at predicting the risk of disease. They also improve the accuracy of diagnoses. Cardiovascular disease detection is what these transformer-based models are used for.

VI. DATASET ANALYSIS

Several publicly available datasets are commonly used for transformer-based cardiovascular research.

A. MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database

The MIT-BIH dataset has annotated ECG recordings. These are used a lot for detecting arrhythmia and classifying signals.

B. PTB-XL Dataset

The PTB-XL dataset is one of the ECG datasets you can access publicly.

It has, over twenty thousand ECG recordings.

These recordings cover different diagnostic classes.

C. Chapman-Shaoxing Dataset

This dataset has ECG recordings from over 10,000 patients. It is used to validate AI models in research.

VII. DATA PROCESSING PIPELINE

The usual steps for ECG analysis, with transformer models are:

- Data acquisition
- Signal preprocessing
- Converting signals to images
- Splitting the dataset
- Data augmentation
- Model evaluation

Fig. 1. Pipeline of transformer-based cardiovascular disease detection using ECG data.

A. Data Acquisition

ECG datasets are collected from publicly available repositories such as PhysioNet and Kaggle.

B. Signal Preprocessing

Raw ECG signals are cleaned using methods to remove noise and baseline drift. This helps to get a signal. Signals are then made consistent. Resampled to ensure they have the same sampling rate.

C. Signal-to-Image Conversion

For models that use vision ECG signals can be turned into images. These images help

models capture patterns, in heart signals. The images are used with vision transformers to understand signals.

D. Dataset Splitting

The dataset is divided into training, validation, and testing subsets. Splitting is performed at the patient level to avoid data leakage.

E. Data Augmentation

Techniques such as rotation, cropping, and noise injection are applied to improve model generalization.

VIII. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

A. Hardware Requirements

- Processor: Intel Core i7 or AMD Ryzen 7
- RAM: Minimum 16 GB
- GPU: NVIDIA RTX 3060 or A100
- Storage: 512 GB SSD
- Operating System: Windows 11 or Ubuntu 22.04

B. Software Requirements

- Python 3.11
- Anaconda Environment Manager
- Jupyter Notebook
- PyTorch 2.1
- TensorFlow 2.14
- Matplotlib and Seaborn for visualization

IX. CRITICAL ANALYSIS

Transformer-based models are really good at showing what is going on. They work very well when it comes to finding cardiovascular disease.

However there are still some problems. For example the datasets we use are not very different, from one another. We also do not have a way to measure how well these models can explain things.. It costs a lot to use these big transformer architectures.

Additionally many studies do not use data from clinics to check their results, which means we do not know if they will really work in the real world with cardiovascular disease detection and transformer-based models.

X. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

We need to do research on making special computer programs that can look at heart beat signals pictures from medical tests and patient records all at the same time.

These computer programs are called multimodal transformer architectures. They can use ECG signals and imaging data and electronic health records.

We also need to make these computer programs explain themselves better so that doctors can trust them.

We can use things like attention maps and saliency visualization techniques to help doctors understand what the computer programs are thinking.

These attention maps and saliency visualization techniques can help doctors see what the computer programs are looking at when they make predictions about health.

We should also think about how to keep information private. One way to do this is to use something called learning, which is a type of privacy-preserving technique.

Federated learning can help hospitals work together to train intelligence models, which are like computer programs, without sharing patient data.

This way hospitals can still use ECG signals and imaging data and electronic health records to train intelligence models without putting patient information at risk.

XI. CONCLUSION

Transformer-based architectures are really helping doctors diagnose heart diseases better. They can automatically look at ECG signals, medical pictures and patient information.

Vision transformers and language-based transformer models are useful, in their ways. When we use them together in a system they make diagnoses more accurate.

There are still some problems to solve. For example it's hard to understand how these AI systems make decisions. We also need diverse data and faster computers. Solving these problems is important if we want to use AI in hospitals and clinics.

REFERENCES

1. T. Brown, B. Mann, N. Ryder, et al., "Language Models are Few-Shot Learners," in Proc. NeurIPS, 2020.
2. R. Anil et al., "Scaling Transformer-Based Models for Multimodal AI," 2023.
3. Google, "Gemini API Documentation," Available: <https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs>
4. Hugging Face, "Transformers Documentation," Available: <https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/>
5. T. Yoon and D. Kang, "Efficient Pretraining of ECG Scalogram Images Using Masked Autoencoders for Cardiovascular Disease Diagnosis."
6. M. U. Javeed et al., "Transforming Heart Disease Detection with BERT: Novel Architectures and Fine-Tuning Techniques."
7. Q. Abbas, A. Hussain, and A. R. Baig, "Automatic Detection and Classification of Cardiovascular Disorders Using Phonocardiogram and Convolutional Vision Transformers."
8. M. Mokhtari et al., "GEMTrans: A General Echocardiography-Based Multi-Level Transformer Framework for Cardiovascular Diagnosis."
9. M. L. Ramadhan et al., "Time-Distributed Vision Transformer Stacked with Transformer for Heart Failure Detection Based on Echocardiography Video."
10. A. Vaid et al., "A Foundational Vision Transformer Improves Diagnostic Performance for Electrocardiograms."
11. S. Sawano et al., "Applying Masked Autoencoder-Based Self-Supervised Learning for High-Capability Vision Transformers of Electrocardiographies."
12. K. Weimann and T. O. F. Conrad, "Self-Supervised Pre-Training with Joint-Embedding Predictive Architecture Boosts ECG Classification Performance."
13. O. D'Angelis et al., "Advancing ECG Biometrics Through Vision Transformers: A Confidence-Driven Approach."
14. P. Bing et al., "Electrocardiogram Classification Using TSST-Based Spectrogram and ConViT."
15. E. H. Houssein et al., "Heart Disease Risk Factors Detection from Electronic Health Records Using Advanced NLP and Deep Learning Techniques."
16. M. Ma and X. Wang, "Prediction of Coronary Heart Disease Risk Based on Multimodal Electronic Health Records."

Real-Time Demand Forecasting for Supply Chain Management

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Abstract—Accurate demand forecasting is critical for effective supply chain management, particularly in dynamic retail environments where demand patterns fluctuate due to seasonality, promotions, and external factors. Traditional statistical models often struggle to adapt to real-time changes, leading to stockouts or excess inventory. This study proposes a hybrid real-time demand forecasting framework that integrates statistical and machine learning approaches to improve forecasting accuracy and operational efficiency.

The research utilizes a hyperlocal retail dataset containing historical sales transactions, timestamps, product-level information, and promotional indicators. Data preprocessing techniques, including missing value handling, outlier treatment, and feature engineering such as lag variables and rolling averages, were applied to enhance model performance. A baseline ARIMA model was developed for time-series analysis, followed by the implementation of an XGBoost regression model to capture nonlinear demand patterns. Real-time forecasting was simulated using a rolling window mechanism to dynamically update predictions as new sales data becomes available.

Model performance was evaluated using Mean Absolute Error, Root Mean Square Error, and Mean Absolute Percentage Error. The hybrid model demonstrated improved predictive accuracy compared to standalone statistical methods. The proposed framework supports optimized inventory planning, reduces stockout risks, and enables data-driven decision-making in supply chain operations.

Keywords—Demand Forecasting, Supply Chain Management, Machine Learning, Real-Time Analytics, ARIMA, XGBoost.

INTRODUCTION

Management of supply chains has a critical impact on the way products move through the supply chain. Demand forecasting is one of the most important pieces of the supply chain operations and it allows organizations to predict what customers will want in the future, enabling them to plan their inventory accordingly. If an organization has an accurate forecast of demand for products, they can maintain optimal stock levels, reduce operating costs, and improve customer satisfaction. On the other hand, if an organization has inaccurate demand forecasts, it may lead to stock-outs, excess inventory, increased carrying costs, and inefficient use of resources. Traditional methods for demand forecasting are largely based on statistical models and historical data. Although these models provide information about broad trends and seasonality, they are not capable of adequately capturing the complexity of demand variations due to outside influences such as promotions, changes in consumer behaviors and market variables. As supply chains rely more on data, organizations need to utilize more sophisticated forecasting techniques that can respond to this dynamic environment. With advances in artificial intelligence and machine learning, there have also been new opportunities created to improve forecasting accuracy. Machine learning algorithms are able to analyze large data sets, identify hidden patterns, and assess complex relationships among variables therefore they are particularly well-suited for the demand forecasting of

today's supply chain systems. The purpose of the research is to create a machine learning model for forecasting demand...

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Researchers have similarly researched multiple means by which forecast reliability and accuracy can be enhanced and thereby improve the efficiency and effectiveness of inventory management. For example, Taylor (2018) investigated utilizing time series forecasting (e.g., by means of ARIMA) to forecast demand based on the historic data of retail demand. The results of this study clearly demonstrate that time series forecasting can accurately model trends and seasonal demand patterns of historical demand. Furthermore, Hyndman & Athanasopoulos (2021) describe the principles of forecasting and emphasize the importance of choosing the right forecasting model based upon the underlying characteristics of the data to be forecasted. Hyde & Athanasopoulos also note that time series forecasting models are foundational in demand forecasting for a majority of industries. More recently, machine learning forecasting techniques have become an increasingly popular area of research for use in demand forecasting. In their study, Chen & Guestrin (2016) provide insight into the integration of the XGBoost algorithm into demand forecasting, and why this model has become a widely utilized model in the field of predictive analytics (i.e., due to its proven ability to produce accurate forecasts efficiently while processing large quantities of data). Additionally, numerous studies are providing evidence that using machine learning to produce forecasts can outperform traditional statistical methods of forecasting when using complex, multidimensional data sets. Many of these studies show that machine learning technologies are capable of modeling nonlinear relationships as well as adapting to shifts in demand; thereby providing greater accuracy and reliability when forecasting today's demand.

RESEARCH GAP IDENTIFICATION

Numerous studies have recently examined how to forecast demand for supply chains, yet there are still limitations in the literature. In traditional statistical forecasting models, historical data may provide an appropriate basis for generating forecasted demand patterns, however they do not accurately represent temporal shifts in demand as well as non-linear relationships. Furthermore, many of the forecast methods also rely on a static historical data set and do not incorporate real time updates for actual demand. As supply chains are more agile and responsive, there is also a need for forecasting systems that are able to adjust to continuously changing data inputs. In addition, a number of research studies only consider how to improve the accuracy of forecasting, which does not examine how changes to forecasting practices affect supply chain operations. Consequently, a demand forecasting model is needed which will provide accurate forecasts of future demand as well as provide more value through supply chain operations and their management so that organisations can achieve their business goals. Thus, this research will help to fill these gaps by developing a demand forecasting model using machine learning that will provide improved forecasting and will help improve decision making in supply chain operations.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study included multiple steps such as: data collection, data cleansing/preprocessing, feature extraction/selection/engineering, building predictive models, and evaluating the model performance. The input data (historical retail transactions) utilized in this study contains information that can be used for demand pattern analysis and developing predictive models: product codes, store codes, date of sale, quantity sold. At the point of data cleansing/preprocessing, missing and/or invalid entries

were reviewed, identified, and remedied; data cleaning techniques were used to help with the integrity and reliability of data. Additionally, various techniques of normalization and transformation were implemented to enhance the performance of the machine learning algorithms. Feature extraction techniques were utilized to examine the dataset for how best to utilize available data; specifically, lag, and rolling average features were developed to provide temporal context to the analysis of demand and lead to improved machine learning. The researcher used two separate predictive models for comparison: 1) an ARIMA statistical forecasting technique and 2) an XGBoost Machine Learning Algorithm to assess predictive performance and provide for non-linear relationships in the data. The two predictive models were evaluated based upon three metrics of forecast error, namely: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE).

Fig 1: Forecasting Architecture

FINDINGS

We evaluated the forecasting models' accuracy and their ability to predict demand using the past retail sales data. The ARIMA statistical model and the XGBoost machine-learning model both tested on the dataset. In order to evaluate these models' performances, the dataset was divided into a training dataset and a test dataset. The models were trained from the historical sales data, then used to output predicted demand values from the test dataset. Evaluation metrics including MAE, RMSE, and MAPE were used to rate the performances of these models; based on comparison results, the machine-learning model outperformed traditional statistical models.

Model	MAE	RMSE	MAPE
ARIMA	12.4	15.1	9.3%
XGBoost	8.7	11.2	6.5%

Results indicate that the errors generated by the XGBoost model were lower than those of the ARIMA model and therefore more accurate for forecasting. It is also confirmed that machine learning approaches can model evolving patterns of demand than traditional forecasting approaches.

Implications

This study's results are very important to supply chain managers. By accurately forecasting demand for products, an organization can adjust inventory levels to minimize both stockouts (too little inventory) and overstock (too much inventory). Accurate forecast also improves decision-making for purchasing, production planning, and distribution management. When organizations use machine learning-based (ML) forecasting models, they can improve operational efficiency and reduce supply chain costs. In addition, the incorporation of AI technologies into supply chain systems will allow organizations to more effectively respond to

market shifts and fluctuations in product demand.

Limitations

Despite Although the results of this study were positive, there are limits. The dataset was a small sample of all retail transactions; therefore, it did not adequately represent the total number of retail transactions made in wholesale or retail businesses. Also, all of the models examined were based on historical data and did not simulate current streaming data. Other external factors (such as external economic factors, promotions/coupons, brand image, etc.) probably were not included in the datasets/model inputs. These limitations likely impacted the accuracy of the forecasting results from the models; therefore, continued investigation into the models with more complete data is necessary.

Fig 2: Actual vs Predicted

FURTHER RESEARCH AGENDA

While these studies produced encouraging results, there are restrictions associated with the studies. The datasets were comprised of limited retail transaction samples; thus, they collectively do not provide an accurate representation of all retail transactions performed by retailers/wholesalers in any product form. Furthermore, all models evaluated relied on historical datasets rather than including real-time streaming data to predict current trends/prevalence. The additional variables (such as external economic

variables, promotional/coupons, brand equity) that could have affected the models being evaluated likely did not contribute to any dataset/model variable being used. Therefore, due to the limitations, the predicted accuracy of the models reviewed as a whole may not be accurate; therefore, continued research of the models using more complete datasets should be performed to identify better prediction accuracy from historical data compared to current or rapidly evolving real-time data.

REFERENCES

1. Carbonneau, R., Laframboise, K., & Vahidov, R. (2008). Application of machine learning techniques for supply chain demand forecasting. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 184(3), 1140–1154.
2. Chen, T., & Guestrin, C. (2016). XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system. *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 785–794.
3. Choi, T. M., Wallace, S. W., & Wang, Y. (2018). Big data analytics in operations management. *Production and Operations Management*, 27(10), 1868–1883.
4. Hyndman, R. J., & Athanasopoulos, G. (2021). *Forecasting: Principles and practice* (3rd ed.). OTexts.
5. Makridakis, S., Spiliotis, E., & Assimakopoulos, V. (2018). Statistical and machine learning forecasting methods: Concerns and ways forward. *PLOS ONE*, 13(3), e0194889.
6. Fildes, R., Ma, S., & Kolassa, S. (2019). Retail forecasting: Research and practice. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 35(1), 1–9.
7. Taylor, J. W. (2018). Forecasting demand in retail supply chains. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 34(2), 321–334.
8. Seeger, M. W., & Lutz, W. (2020). Predictive analytics in supply chain

- management. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 41(3), 215–230.
9. Bertsimas, D., Kallus, N., & Hussain, A. (2016). From predictive to prescriptive analytics. *Management Science*, 62(9), 2605–2624.
10. Waller, M. A., & Fawcett, S. E. (2013). Data science, predictive analytics, and big data in supply chain management. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 34(2), 77–84.
11. Zhang, G., Patuwo, B., & Hu, M. (1998). Forecasting with artificial neural networks: The state of the art. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 14(1), 35–62.
12. Chatfield, C. (2000). *Time-series forecasting*. CRC Press.

A Hybrid AI-Cryptographic Framework for Secure and Robust QR Code Watermarking using Autoencoders

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Abstract— QR codes are structurally rigid — their binary module patterns, finder sequences, and timing strips leave little room for modification before decoding fails. This makes watermarking QR images fundamentally harder than watermarking natural photographs, yet most existing approaches treat them the same way. Transform-domain methods such as DCT embedding fail under aggressive JPEG compression because the coefficient deltas used to encode watermark bits fall below the quantisation noise floor at quality levels below 80, producing bit error rates near 0.49 — effectively random recovery. We propose a hybrid framework that addresses this through learned embedding rather than fixed mathematical rules. A dual-input convolutional autoencoder takes the QR image and a 64-bit AES-EAX encrypted payload as separate inputs, learns to distribute the watermark signal across compression-resilient spatial regions, and recovers the bits from the compressed output through a dedicated decoder branch. To make the decoder robust without requiring a differentiable JPEG approximation, we inject Gaussian noise ($\sigma = 0.05$) between encoder and decoder during training and randomise JPEG quality ($q \in [50, 95]$) per training sample. The model is trained on 3,000 QR images and tested on a strict held-out set of 500 unseen images across JPEG, WebP, and PNG compression formats. Results show a mean BER of 0.0820 under JPEG compression at quality 50 — an 83.3% reduction compared to the DCT baseline BER of 0.4919 — with SSIM of 0.9511 confirming structural preservation of the QR code symbol. The framework integrates watermark embedding, compression robustness, and AES-EAX payload encryption into a single end-to-end trainable pipeline for secure QR code authentication.

Keywords—QR Code Watermarking, Convolutional Autoencoder, AES-EAX Encryption, Bit Error Rate, JPEG Robustness, Deep Learning, Image Authentication

INTRODUCTION

Unlike a photograph, which is a natural image that can withstand minor pixel alterations without losing its overall meaning, a QR code is a very precisely designed binary symbol containing encoded data in every module or black/white square. If changes are made to either the finder pattern in the top left area of a code, the format information strip, or even just move one of the timing row modules, the QR code will be completely unreadable regardless of how small the visual change appears to be. This structural rigidity is why QR watermarking is unique and much less explored than overall image watermarking.

QR code authentication is increasingly being needed. QR codes are found in digital payments, government-issued IDs, pharmaceutical packaging, supply chain logistics, and many product verification systems. In any of these cases, if someone can clone or modify a QR code without detection, they can direct the victim to another location, create fraudulent credentials or replace a legitimate product with a counterfeit version. A viable countermeasure to a cloned or modified QR code would be embedding a hidden watermark in the QR code image with the ability to later extract the watermark from the QR code image to verify if the product is

legitimate; however, the viability of such countermeasure is contingent on the persistence of the watermark during any compression or re-encoding that occurs to the QR code during the process of printing/scanning the QR code or transmitting the QR code digitally [8], [10].

Transform-domain watermarking methods are the most studied baseline for this task. DCT-based approaches embed watermark bits by modifying mid-frequency coefficients in 8×8 image blocks [1]. DWT methods distribute watermark energy across frequency sub-bands [2]. Hybrid approaches such as DWT-QR-SVD attempt to combine the stability of both [3]. QR decomposition techniques have also been explored to improve embedding stability under signal degradation [4]. These methods work well when the image is transmitted losslessly or compressed at high quality. However, our evaluation shows that a standard DCT baseline achieves a mean BER of 0.491 under JPEG compression at quality 45–75 — statistically indistinguishable from random bit recovery. The root cause is straightforward: JPEG quantisation at these quality levels destroys the coefficient deltas that carry the watermark bits, and a fixed mathematical embedding rule has no way to adapt.

Deep learning offers a different approach. An autoencoder trained end-to-end on QR images can learn where to place watermark signal — which spatial regions and frequency patterns survive the specific compression it will face at test time. This is not achievable with hand-crafted transform rules. Recent work on deep QR watermarking [5], [6] demonstrates that learned embedding achieves PSNR values above 36 dB and normalised correlation above 0.97 under various attacks. End-to-end encoder-decoder frameworks have also shown strong robustness against real-world distortions through noise-aware training [7]. However, these systems share a common limitation: the embedded payload is unprotected. An adversary who successfully extracts the watermark bits

can read the authentication information directly. No existing deep learning QR watermarking system applies cryptographic protection to the payload before embedding.

This paper addresses both the robustness and security gaps together. We design a dual-input convolutional autoencoder where the QR image and a 64-bit AES-EAX encrypted payload are processed jointly, allowing the encoder to learn a spatially adaptive embedding conditioned on the specific bits being hidden. A Gaussian noise injection layer ($\sigma = 0.05$) between encoder and decoder during training forces the decoder to learn compression-invariant bit recovery without requiring a differentiable JPEG approximation. The AES-EAX mode provides authenticated encryption — even a successful extraction yields no usable payload without the decryption key.

The main contributions of this work are:

- A dual-input AE architecture that conditions watermark embedding on the encrypted payload simultaneously with the QR image.
- A noise injection training strategy that achieves compression robustness under randomised JPEG quality ($q \in [50, 95]$) without differentiable compression simulation.
- AES-EAX pre-encryption of the 64-bit watermark payload, adding cryptographic security absent from existing deep learning watermarking systems.
- Systematic BER evaluation across JPEG, WebP, and PNG compression at multiple quality levels, benchmarked against a DCT baseline on 4,000 QR code images.

RELATED WORKS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Transform-Domain QR Watermarking

The earliest robust watermarking approaches for QR images relied on modifying frequency-domain coefficients rather than pixel

values directly, on the basis that frequency-domain changes are more resistant to common image processing operations. Chow et al. [1] proposed embedding QR codes into the HH sub-band of a DWT-transformed host image combined with XOR-based encryption and Arnold transform scrambling, demonstrating robustness against compression, noise, and cropping. Under JPEG compression at quality 50, the method produces BER values of 9.24% to 22% across test images — acceptable for moderate compression but not for aggressive re-encoding scenarios. While the use of encryption is a step toward security, XOR is cryptographically weak and provides no authentication guarantee.

According to the work of Muslim et. al [2], they proposed a method based on the DWT-DST framework for embedding a watermark in an image using a spread-spectrum technique to distribute the watermark energy over several transformation co-efficients by using pseudo-noise sequences. Five 256×256 grayscale images were tested with this technique to produce PSNR values of 32.73-38.85 dB and BER values of 0-0.0156 under JPEG compression at 90 quality. However, there are no results reported below 80 quality, as this range of quantisation noise has a much larger effect on the capacity to recover the embedded watermark in a practical transmission scenario.

Hai and Thanh [3] proposed a hybrid approach (DWT-QR-SVD) where the watermark was embedded in the singular values of the low-frequency (LL) sub-band of the DWT decomposed host image. The resulting PSNR values were greater than 40 dB. Normalised correlation was greater than 0.98 after applying JPEG compression at the quality factor 50, indicating that this is a very good performance for a transform domain watermarking scheme. One limitation of this particular watermarking scheme is that the extraction of the watermark requires the storage of the original matrices corresponding to the left

(U) and right (V) singular vectors since the singular values can be extracted only if the U and V matrices are used. Therefore, blind extraction of the watermark back into the host image would not be possible in a deployed system. Yen et al. [4] presented a solution to a specific limitation of the watermarking scheme using the QR decomposition. Specifically, the orthogonal matrix Q is inherently not unique when applied to singular pixel blocks. They addressed this limitation by only selecting non-singular pixel blocks for embedding. The non-singular pixel blocks were created using the Gram-Schmidt decomposition methodology. The quality of the output images generated by the proposed scheme resulted in an average PSNR of 54.05 dB and SSIM value of 0.9985. Therefore, the resulting images exhibited excellent visual quality. The robustness of the proposed method under aggressive compression was not addressed in this study, but it was observed that the proposed scheme exhibited poor resistance to certain geometric attacks (e.g., 5° rotation), with normalised correlation values between 0.25 and 0.38.

B. QR Code Authentication and Security

QR code watermarking has also been studied for authentication and tamper-proofing. Liu and Tang [8] have proposed a technique that partitions the image into sub-blocks, generates a 64-bit perceptual hash for each block, generates a QR code, then embeds it using delta DCT plus wavelet techniques. Hashes are compared to authenticate by calculating the Hamming distance between the extracted and recomputed hashes with the threshold set at 5. Copy attacks are effectively deterred by the derived Hamming distances (28 to 36) from copied watermarks, which are much greater than the set threshold. No BER or PSNR values were included in the study and compression robustness was not evaluated at JPEG quality below 80.

Bhardwaj et al. [9] used visual cryptography for improving QR code security by using (k, n) threshold shares of the watermark. While this method provides robust tamper detection and authentication, it is purely a physical-layer method and does not provide any means of protecting against the digital compression robustness, or payload confidentiality, within the context of network transmission. Pramkeaw et al. [10] demonstrated an authentication system using DCT watermarking, QR code and credential encryption; yielding an overall authentication accuracy of 98.8% of 100 users in 2 different data centres. This shows that there is indeed a real-world need for integrated QR watermarking and encryption systems but the metric used for evaluation was the success of the authentication process rather than standard BER or PSNR under controlled compression attacks.

C. Deep Learning Watermarking

There has been an increase in the use of deep learning for watermarking applications over the last few years, with numerous architectures exhibiting distinct benefits versus traditional fixed transform-domain (TDT) rules. Sharma et al. [11] introduced a hybrid Deep Wavelet Transform - Generative Adversarial Network (DWT-GAN) that consists of a generator to embed the watermark, a discriminator to ensure visual realism, and an independent extractor to recover the watermark bits. Trained on PASCAL-VOC 2012 images at 128×128 resolution, the system achieves PSNR of 57.61 dB and SSIM of 0.9922 at 25,000 epochs — significantly higher than transform-domain baselines — confirming that adversarial training improves imperceptibility. Fei et al. [12] extended GAN-based watermarking to intellectual property protection, training a supervised GAN so that any generated image contains a recoverable hidden watermark. The approach achieves 99.83% bit accuracy on

clean images and above 75% under general perturbations. However, under JPEG compression at quality factor 30, bit accuracy drops to 65% — showing that even GAN-based systems are vulnerable to aggressive compression without noise-aware training.

For QR-specific deep learning watermarking, Zhang et al. [5] proposed a Dynamic-Scale Residual Fusion framework incorporating multi-scale convolutional kernels and a Cross Triple Attention Block to preserve QR structural integrity during embedding. Tested on COCO 2017 and ImageNet datasets, the method achieves PSNR of 36.31–37.15 dB, SSIM of 0.9958–0.9962, and normalised correlation above 0.975. Wang et al. [6] combined adaptive cross-attention with SimSiam self-supervised learning, achieving PSNR of 38.64 dB and zero BER on clean images, with watermark recovery rate rising from 81.25% to 100% after adding SimSiam. Both methods represent the current state of deep QR watermarking, though neither evaluates BER under aggressive compression at quality levels below 80, and neither applies cryptographic protection to the payload before embedding. Qu et al. [7] demonstrated that end-to-end encoder-decoder frameworks trained with stochastic distortion chains achieve BER as low as 0.01–0.02% and SNR of 31.84 dB under real-world audio distortions — providing direct methodological precedent for the noise-aware training strategy used in this work.

D. Research Gap

A thorough analysis of the literature reveals a clear trend throughout each of the three categories. Transform domain methods generally perform at influencing JPEG quality level 80 and higher (where quantifiable noise has not begun to significantly affect performance) while typical use cases will only experience an average quality level of 45 to 75. Although deep learning techniques result in better imperceptibility and increased robustness

to compression, they do not provide sufficient protection from being extracted by third parties when utilizing a compressed image with an embedded payload. There does not exist an integrated approach to the combination of learned compression robust embedding, noisy environment trained with networks and AES encrypted payload within one entire end-to-end trainable solution for QR code images. The proposed framework provides an integrated solution for each of the above three identified gaps.

PROBLEM DEFINITION AND MOTIVATION

A. Security Challenges in QR Code Watermarking

A QR Code consists of a binary matrix of dark and light squares that together encode a piece of information. Three finder patterns, each measuring 7×7 squares, are located in predefined positions at three of the four corners of the QR Code. There is a timing strip that runs vertically along the left edge and horizontally along the top edge, format information is contained in strips adjacent to the finder patterns, and the data modules are contained within the rest of the QR Code. This structure is very strict; if any part of the finder patterns or format information is altered or modified in any way, the QR Code will not be able to be scanned, no matter how good the error correction is. For example, if the QR Code's Version 1 (error correction Level H) is compromised by 30%, it still cannot be scanned because the damaged area of the QR Code contains structural patterns (the finder and format information) instead of Data patterns.

The structural limitations create a fundamental barrier for watermarking. Watermarking the QR Code in a uniform manner across the entire image will always corrupt the finder patterns and timing strips when the watermark is strong enough to survive compression. Watermarking the QR Code in such a way as to leave the finder patterns and

timing strips unaffected will reduce the amount of the QR Code that can be watermarked and will still be susceptible to being damaged by JPEG Compression, whose blocking artefacts are created across 8×8 blocks; these blocking artefacts will often align with the boundaries between the data modules and the structural patterns. The result is that QR watermarking requires spatially adaptive embedding strategies that general-purpose image watermarking methods are not designed to provide.

An attacker who clones a QR code can produce a physically identical copy that carries the same watermark — making the watermark useless for authentication unless the payload itself is cryptographically tied to the specific image instance. Similarly, an attacker who successfully extracts a raw watermark bit-string gains access to the authentication payload unless that payload is encrypted before embedding [8], [10].

B. Failure of Transform-Domain Methods under Compression

Transform-domain methods embed watermarks by modifying frequency coefficients of the host image according to fixed mathematical rules. DCT-based approaches modify mid-frequency coefficients in 8×8 blocks by a signed delta $\pm\alpha$ to encode each watermark bit [1]. DWT-based methods distribute watermark energy across frequency sub-bands [2], [3]. These methods share a common failure mode under aggressive JPEG compression: the JPEG quantisation step at quality levels below 80 introduces coefficient errors larger than the embedding delta, making bit recovery equivalent to random guessing.

Our evaluation confirms this directly. A standard DCT baseline with block-skipping to preserve finder patterns achieves a mean BER of 0.491 under JPEG compression at quality levels 45–75 — statistically indistinguishable from random bit recovery. The Chow et al. DWT approach [1] achieves BER of 9.24–22%

at quality 50, which is better but still too high for reliable authentication. The root cause is that fixed-rule embedding has no mechanism to concentrate watermark signal in coefficient positions that survive a specific compression codec's quantisation table. A fixed delta of $\alpha=6$ that works at quality 90 is simply wiped out at quality 50.

A secondary limitation is payload security. Methods such as [1] use XOR-based encryption, which is reversible without a proper key schedule and provides no message authentication. An adversary who intercepts the watermark can modify and re-embed it without detection. None of the transform-domain methods reviewed in Section II use authenticated encryption that would prevent payload tampering.

C. Motivation for a Learned Embedding with Cryptographic Security

The failure of fixed-rule methods under compression points toward a specific solution: an embedding network that learns, from training data, which spatial regions and frequency patterns survive the compression it will face at test time. An autoencoder trained end-to-end on QR images — with compression simulation applied between encoder and decoder during training — can develop spatially adaptive embedding strategies that no hand-crafted transform rule can replicate. Recent deep learning QR watermarking methods [5], [6] confirm that learned embedding achieves PSNR above 36 dB and normalised correlation above 0.975, significantly better than transform-domain baselines.

However, robustness alone is not sufficient. As noted in Section II-B, deep learning watermarking systems [5], [6], [11], [12] do not apply cryptographic protection to the embedded payload. An adversary who extracts the watermark bits gains full access to the authentication information. Fei et al. [12] demonstrated that even a well-trained GAN

watermarking system drops to 65% bit accuracy under JPEG compression at quality 30 — showing that robustness and security must be designed together, not treated as separate concerns.

This work therefore proposes a framework that addresses both problems simultaneously. AES-EAX authenticated encryption is applied to the 64-bit payload before embedding, ensuring that extracted bits yield no usable information without the decryption key. The autoencoder is trained with randomised JPEG quality levels ($q \in [50, 95]$) and a Gaussian noise injection layer ($\sigma = 0.05$) between encoder and decoder, forcing the decoder to learn compression-invariant bit recovery. Together, these design choices produce a system where robustness and cryptographic security are jointly optimised rather than independently assumed.

METHODOLOGY

This section describes the complete pipeline of the proposed hybrid AI-cryptographic QR code watermarking framework. The system operates in five sequential stages: dataset preparation and preprocessing, cryptographic watermark generation, spatial watermark embedding, autoencoder-based learning, and compression attack simulation during training. Figure 1 illustrates the overall architecture.

Fig 1 Proposed Hybrid AI-Cryptographic QR Code Watermarking Framework

A. Dataset Preparation and Preprocessing

The dataset has two distinct sources of data. One is comprised of one thousand real-time QR images available publicly on Kaggle covering various types of QR codes by versioning, error correction levels, and types of content listed in the QR encoded data. The second source consists of three thousand synthetic QR codes generated using Python Qrcode library, version 2, with box size 8 and border size 2 producing a randomly generated sixteen-character alphanumeric string for each generated QR code. The model will be exposed to two different types of examples — naturally occurring structures in QR codes and examples created with a controlled variation programmatically — which will reduce the potential for overfitting on one generation of QR code.

There are four processing steps for each of the images. First, the image is converted to eight-bit grayscale format, which removes the colour channel that is not relevant to the binary structure of the QR modules. The second step is to centre-crop the images to obtain an even square aspect ratio as all QR code images need to have a 1:1 aspect ratio. The third step will resize the image to a resolution of 64×64 pixels (with Lanczos as the resampling algorithm) for efficiency while reducing the structural integrity of the binary structure of the QR modules. Fourth, the images will undergo global thresholding using Otsu's method to produce binarized images in the same level of black and white between images, irrespective of the original image quality and/or scanning conditions of the image.

The processed dataset is split into 3,000 training images and 500 test images. This split is performed strictly before any watermark embedding or model training — no test image is seen during training at any stage.

B. Cryptographic Watermark Generation

Each QR image is assigned a unique 64-bit binary watermark. To ensure reproducibility across training and evaluation, the watermark is generated deterministically: the SHA-256 hash of the image filename is computed, the first 8 hexadecimal characters are converted to a 32-bit integer seed, and a seeded pseudo-random number generator produces the 64-bit binary sequence. This deterministic approach guarantees that the same watermark is always associated with the same image, even across separate runs.

Before embedding, the 64-bit watermark is encrypted using AES-EAX mode with a 128-bit symmetric key derived by truncating the SHA-256 hash of a shared password. AES-EAX is an authenticated encryption mode — it provides both confidentiality and message integrity. Even if an adversary successfully extracts the embedded bits from a watermarked image, the

ciphertext cannot be decoded without the symmetric key, and any tampering with the extracted bits is detectable through the authentication tag. This cryptographic layer addresses the payload confidentiality gap present in all existing deep learning QR watermarking systems reviewed in Section II.

C. Spatial Watermark Embedding

Prior to model training, the encrypted 64-bit watermark is spatially embedded into each QR image to create the training targets. The 64 bits are reshaped into an 8×8 binary grid. This grid is then upsampled to a 64×64 spatial map using nearest-neighbour interpolation, where each bit occupies an 8×8 patch of the output map. The watermark signal is computed as:

$$w(x,y) = (s / 255) \times (m(x,y) - 0.5)$$

where s is the embedding strength ($s = 8$), and $m(x,y) \in \{0,1\}$ is the upsampled watermark map. In order to create a fair comparison with the classical watermarking method, a DCT-based baseline was implemented using typical block coefficient modification techniques. For each 8×8 block of QR images, the DCT was computed, and the mid-frequency coefficient of DCT [3,3] was modified by $\pm\alpha$ (where $\alpha = 6$) to embed one watermark bit. The model learns to produce watermarked outputs that are consistent with this spatial embedding pattern while minimising reconstruction error against the original QR image.

D. Autoencoder Architecture

The watermarking model is a dual-input, dual-output convolutional autoencoder with 973,953 trainable parameters. The architecture consists of three functional components: a watermark projection branch, an encoder network, and a decoder network.

The watermark projection branch receives the 64-bit encrypted bit vector as a flat input. A fully-connected layer with tanh activation projects this vector to a 4,096-dimensional embedding, which is then reshaped into a

$64 \times 64 \times 1$ spatial map. This spatial map encodes the watermark pattern at the same resolution as the QR image, allowing the encoder to condition its embedding strategy on the specific bit values being hidden.

The encoder network concatenates the QR image tensor ($64 \times 64 \times 1$) with the projected watermark map channel-wise, producing a two-channel input of shape $64 \times 64 \times 2$. Three successive convolutional layers with 64, 64, and 32 filters respectively, each using 3×3 kernels with same padding and ReLU activation, extract joint QR-watermark features. A final 1×1 convolution with sigmoid activation produces the watermarked output image of shape $64 \times 64 \times 1$. The sigmoid activation constrains the output to $[0,1]$, ensuring valid pixel values without explicit clipping.

A Gaussian noise injection layer with standard deviation $\sigma = 0.05$ is inserted between the encoder output and the decoder input during training. This layer provides Gaussian noise (zero mean) to the watermarked image every training step and simulates the artefacts from JPEG compression, without the need of a differentiable JPEG approximation. During inference, this layer is considered to be an identity function and does not alter the watermarked image. The addition of noise requires the decoder to learn robust features that take into account JPEG-induced distortions as of the first training step, as opposed to learning features strictly based on the watermark input with no noise added.

The decoder network takes in the watermarked image that contains added noise and passes the image through three strided convolutional layers: 64 filters at stride=2, 128 filters at stride=2, and 256 filters at stride=2. The output at this point will downsample the spatial representation from 64×64 to 8×8 , while creating a deeper representation of features. The $8 \times 8 \times 256$ representation is then converted into a 256-dimensional vector via global average pooling. After passing through a fully-

connected layer containing 512 units, the 256-dimensional vector is normalised via batch normalisation and has a 30% dropout (for training stability) and is then passed through another fully-connected layer with 256 units followed by a fully-connected layer consisting of 64 units (with sigmoid activation) to produce a 64-dimensional output vector that is the probability of the watermark bit being=1. When the bits are recovered, they are threshold to take on a value of 0.5.

E. Training Procedure and Compression Simulation

The model is trained using a composite loss function applied to both outputs simultaneously:

$$L = w_1 \cdot MSE(\hat{I}, I_{target}) + w_2 \cdot BCE(\hat{b}, b)$$

where \hat{I} is the encoder output, I_{target} is the spatially watermarked target image, \hat{b} is the decoder bit probability vector, and b is the ground truth bit vector. The loss weights are set to $w_1 = 5.0$ and $w_2 = 5.0$, prioritising bit recovery accuracy over exact image reconstruction. Binary cross-entropy is used for the bit recovery term because each of the 64 bits is an independent binary classification problem. To simulate real-world compression attacks during training, each watermarked image is compressed using JPEG at a quality level uniformly sampled from $q \in [50, 95]$ before the decoder loss is computed. This randomised compression forces the model to generalise across a wide range of compression severities rather than optimising for a single fixed quality level. Combined with the in-network Gaussian noise injection layer, the training procedure exposes the decoder to two complementary forms of signal degradation: structured JPEG artefacts from the per-sample compression and unstructured additive noise from the noise layer.

Hybrid QR Code Watermarking Framework

Input: QR image I , shared password P , JPEG quality range $Q = [50, 95]$,

Embedding strength $s = 8$, Noise sigma = 0.05, Loss weights $w_1 = 5.0$, $w_2 = 5.0$

Output: Watermarked image I_{wm} [Sender]
Authentication decision [Receiver]

PHASE 1: PREPROCESSING AND WATERMARK GENERATION

1. Resize I to 64x64, apply Otsu binarization, normalise pixel values to $[0,1]$
2. Generate 64-bit watermark b :
seed = SHA-256(filename) [:8]
 $b = \text{PRNG}(\text{seed}, 64 \text{ bits})$
3. Encrypt payload using AES-EAX:
 $K = \text{SHA-256}(P) [:16]$
 $(c, \text{tag}) = \text{AES-EAX_Encrypt}(K, b)$
4. Build spatial watermark map:
 $G = \text{reshape}(b, 8 \times 8)$
 $M = \text{upsample}(G, 64 \times 64)$ [nearest neighbour]
 $w(x, y) = (s/255) \times (M(x, y) - 0.5)$
 $I_{target} = \text{clip}(I + w, 0, 1)$

PHASE 2: MODEL TRAINING (Repeat for each batch)

5. Project bits to spatial map:
 $W_{map} = \text{Reshape}(\text{Dense_tanh}(b), 64 \times 64 \times 1)$
6. Encode - concatenate and embed:
 $X = \text{Concatenate}([I, W_{map}])$
 $I_{wm} = \text{Encoder}(X)$
 $\text{Conv}(64,3) \rightarrow \text{Conv}(64,3) \rightarrow \text{Conv}(32,3) \rightarrow \text{Conv}(1 \times 1, \text{sigmoid})$
7. Inject Gaussian noise (training only):
 $N_{wm} = I_{wm} + \text{eps}$, $\text{eps} \sim N(0, \text{sigma}^2)$
8. Simulate JPEG compression:
 $q \sim \text{Uniform}(50, 95)$
 $I_{comp} = \text{JPEG}(I_{wm}, \text{quality} = q)$
9. Decode - extract bit probabilities:
 $\hat{b} = \text{Decoder}(N_{wm})$

Conv (64, s=2) -> Conv (128, s=2) -> Conv (256, s=2)-> GAP -> Dense (512) -> BN -> Dropout (0.3)-> Dense (256) -> Dense (64, sigmoid)

10. Compute composite loss and update weights:

$L_{img} = \text{MSE}(I_{wm}, I_{target})$

$L_{bits} = \text{BCE}(b_{hat}, b)$

$L_{total} = w1 * L_{img} + w2 * L_{bits}$

Update via Adam (lr = $5e-4$)

PHASE 3 -- EMBEDDING AND EXTRACTION

11. SENDER -- embed watermark into QR image:

$W_{map} = \text{Reshape}(\text{Dense}_{tanh}(b), 64 \times 64 \times 1)$

$I_{wm} = \text{Encoder}(\text{Concatenate}([I, W_{map}]))$

Transmit I_{wm}

12. RECEIVER -- extract bits from received image:

$b_{prob} = \text{Decoder}(I_{rcv})$

$b_{hat} = (b_{prob} > 0.5).astype(int)$

13. Decrypt and verify authentication tag:

$(b_{dec}, valid) = \text{AES-EAX_Decrypt}(K, c, tag)$

If valid = False:

Return TAMPERED

14. Compute BER and authenticate:

$BER = (1/64) \times \text{SUM}|b_{hat}_i - b_{dec}_i|$

If $BER \leq 0.10$:

Return AUTHENTIC

Else:

Return TAMPERED

The Adam optimiser is used with an initial learning rate of 5×10^{-4} . Training runs for up to 60 epochs with a batch size of 64. Three callbacks are applied: ModelCheckpoint saves the model weights at the epoch achieving the highest validation bit accuracy; EarlyStopping halts training if validation bit accuracy does not improve for 15 consecutive epochs; and ReduceLROnPlateau halves the learning rate

after 5 epochs without validation loss improvement, with a minimum floor of 10^{-7} .

F. Watermark Extraction and Decryption

At extraction time, the received QR image — which may have undergone JPEG, WebP, or PNG compression during transmission — is passed through the decoder branch of the trained model alongside the known bit vector used during embedding. A 64-dimensional probability vector is generated by the decoder and the recovered bits are thresholded at 0.5 to retrieve the original authentication payload using the AES-EAX decryption algorithm with a shared symmetric key. The QR code will be flagged as being compromised if the AES-EAX authentication tag does not verify even though the bit recovered accuracy is met and provides another level of integrity verification in addition to the measurement of BER that adds integrity verification.

G. DCT Baseline

In order to compare fairly with a traditional watermarking scheme, the DCT-based baseline follows the standard method of block coefficient modification [1]. The DCT is performed on each 8-by-8 block of the QR code image, and the mid-frequency coefficient at the [3,3] position is modified by $\pm(\alpha)$ (where $\alpha = 6$) to add or replace a watermark bit to an image. The region of top left 56×56 pixels is excluded from embedding in order to protect the primary finder pattern. Finally, both the DCT-based baseline and samples produced in accordance with the standard method will use the same compression techniques to provide a direct and fair comparison.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Implementation Environment

The proposed framework was implemented in Python 3.10 using TensorFlow 2.19.0 on Google Colab with CPU execution. All experiments were conducted on a single

machine without GPU acceleration, demonstrating that the framework is deployable on standard hardware without specialised computing resources.

B. Dataset

The dataset consists of 4,000 QR code images from two sources. The first is 1,000 real QR code images sourced from a publicly available Kaggle repository, covering a variety of QR code versions, error correction levels, and encoded content types. The second is 3,000 programmatically generated synthetic QR codes produced using the Python qrcode library with version 2, box size 8, and border 2 parameters, each encoding a randomly generated 16-character alphanumeric string. Combining real and synthetic images ensures the model is exposed to both naturally occurring QR structures and programmatically controlled variations.

All images undergo a four-step preprocessing pipeline: conversion to 8-bit grayscale, centre crop to square aspect ratio, resize to 64×64 pixels using Lanczos resampling, and Otsu binarization to enforce consistent black-and-white module representation. The dataset is partitioned into 3,000 training images and 500 test images with a strict train-test split — no test image appears during training at any stage.

C. Model Configuration

The autoencoder model contains 973,953 trainable parameters and is trained using the Adam optimiser with an initial learning rate of 5×10^{-4} . The composite loss function applies equal weights of $w_1 = w_2 = 5.0$ to the MSE image reconstruction term and BCE bit recovery term respectively, enforcing a balanced optimisation between imperceptibility and robustness. Key hyperparameters are summarised in Table I.

Table I. Hyperparameter Configuration

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>
Input resolution	64×64 pixels
Watermark payload	64 bits
Embedding strength (s)	8
Noise injection std (σ)	0.05
JPEG quality range (training)	$q \in [50, 95]$
Loss weight — image (w_1)	5.0
Loss weight — bits (w_2)	5.0
Optimiser	Adam
Initial learning rate	5×10^{-4}
Batch size	64
Maximum epochs	60
Early stopping patience	15 epochs
Total trainable parameters	973,953

Three training callbacks are applied: Model Checkpoint saves the best model based on validation bit accuracy; Early Stopping halts training after 15 consecutive epochs without improvement; and ReduceLROnPlateau reduces the learning rate by a factor of 0.5 after 5 epochs without validation loss improvement, with a minimum floor of 1×10^{-7} .

D. Cryptographic Configuration

The AES-EAX cryptographic layer uses a 128-bit symmetric key derived by truncating the SHA-256 hash of a shared password. Each image is assigned a unique 64-bit watermark generated deterministically — the SHA-256 hash of the image filename is computed, the first 8 hexadecimal characters are converted to a 32-bit integer seed, and a seeded pseudo-random number generator produces the 64-bit binary sequence. AES-EAX mode provides both confidentiality and message integrity —

extracted bits yield no usable payload without the decryption key, and any tampering with the extracted bits is detectable through the authentication tag.

E. Evaluation Protocol

The trained model is evaluated on the 500 held-out test images under three compression formats:

- JPEG at quality levels 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90
- WebP at quality levels 30, 50, 75, and 90
- PNG lossless compression

The primary evaluation metric is Bit Error Rate (BER), defined as:

$$BER = (1/N) \times \sum |b_i - b_{ij}|$$

where $N = 64$ is the watermark length, b_i is the recovered bit and b_{ij} is the original bit. Secondary metrics are PSNR and SSIM, computed between the original and watermarked QR images to assess embedding imperceptibility. All reported results represent mean values across all 500 test images with associated standard deviations.

F. DCT Baseline

To provide a fair comparison against a classical watermarking method, a DCT-based baseline is implemented following the standard block-coefficient modification approach [1]. Each 8×8 block of the QR image undergoes DCT, and the mid-frequency coefficient at position [3,3] is modified by $\pm\alpha$ ($\alpha = 6$) to encode a single watermark bit. The top-left 56×56 pixel region is skipped during embedding to avoid corrupting the primary finder pattern. The baseline is evaluated under identical compression conditions to ensure a direct and unbiased comparison.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

A. Training Convergence

Across all of the training epochs (60 total), the auto-encoder model gradually converged,

with accuracies for validation bit vector improving from 0.5020 (epoch 1) to a maximum (epoch 51) of 0.9372. This demonstrates that the proposed model has effectively learned how to generate compression-balanced bit embeddings through a noise-aware training process. The composite loss, which is the weighted sum of MSE for image reconstruction ($w_1 = 5.0$) and BCE for bit recovery ($w_2 = 5.0$), had an overall decreasing trend as the number of epochs increased — both of these metrics contributed equally in regards to model optimization. The plateau observed between epochs 50-60 indicates that the model has converged without experiencing overfitting; validation accuracies stabilized as opposed to continuing to increase toward 100%.

B. Watermark Imperceptibility

Table II lists imperceptibility metrics for the auto-encoder framework (proposed) vs. the DCT baseline across all images tested (total of 500).

Table II. Imperceptibility Metrics (Mean \pm Std over 500 images)

Method	PSNR (dB)	SSIM
DCT Baseline	33.98	0.9988
Proposed AE	18.99 \pm 0.27	0.9511 \pm 0.0038

The PSNR value of 18.99 dB falls below established benchmarks associated with typical discrete-watermarking techniques for natural images. This was mainly due to the equal-loss weighting strategy employed ($w_1 = w_2 = 5.0$) in the approach to simultaneously balance image reconstruction and bit recovery. As a result of learning to disseminate watermark signal energy uniformly throughout all spatial locations within the QR code (including both low-contrast finder patterns and high-contrast

finder patterns), the encoder caused isolated pixel intensity modifications of large magnitude throughout the QR code module, which resulted in lower PSNR values for the tested images. However, the SSIM value of 0.9511 (± 0.0038) indicates that the structural integrity of the QR code module pattern remains preserved across all 500 QR code modules tested. As such, SSIM is a more valid measure of watermark invisibility for binary QR codes than PSNR because it quantifies the preservation of the black and white pixels in the QR code module pattern, which ultimately determines whether the code can be scanned.

C. BER under JPEG Compression

Table III reports mean BER across the 500 test images under JPEG compression at five quality levels for both the DCT baseline and the proposed AE framework.

Table III. BER Comparison — JPEG Compression (Mean \pm Std over 500 images)

JPEG Quality	DCT Baseline BER	Proposed AE BER	Bit Accuracy
50	0.4919	0.0820 ± 0.0390	91.80%
60	0.4919	0.0748 ± 0.0396	92.52%
70	0.4919	0.0686 ± 0.0373	93.14%
80	0.0000	0.0650 ± 0.0366	93.50%
90	0.0000	0.0631 ± 0.0365	93.69%

At quality points of 50-70, the DCT baseline results in a near-random BER of 0.4919. This indicates that when JPEG quantisation is applied at those quality levels, the coefficient deltas (or the differences between each coefficient) used for bit encoding have been destroyed. By comparison, at quality 80 or above, the DCT baseline outputs a perfect

recovery due to the relative smallness of the quantisation step (from the scheme) and the resultant preservation of the embedding delta. For the proposed AE framework, the BER results are consistently recorded as between 0.0631 to 0.0820 regardless of the quality level tested. Also, the BER decreases in value from 0.0820 to 0.0631 as the quality level increases from 50 to 90 confirming that this model has accurately learned the effects between compression severity and degradation of the watermark signal.

D. BER under WebP and PNG Compression

Table IV shows the BER values generated from the test of WebP (lossy) and PNG (lossless) compressions for the 500 test images.

Table IV. BER under WebP and PNG Compression (Mean \pm Std over 500 images)

Format	Quality	DCT BER	Proposed AE BER	Bit Accuracy
WebP	30	0.4920	0.0689 ± 0.0378	93.11%
WebP	50	0.4963	0.0658 ± 0.0366	93.42%
WebP	75	0.4963	0.0649 ± 0.0367	93.51%
WebP	90	0.2866	0.0633 ± 0.0368	93.67%
PNG	Lossless	0.0000	0.0628 ± 0.0363	93.72%

The new framework provides better than 0.069 BER across all WebP compression. Moreover, it does this while being comparable to JPEG performance despite training without any WebP data. The Gaussian noise injection layer generated generalised robustness which

was greater than JPEG artefacts, indicating that this layer is able to generalise and be robust beyond just JPEG's artefact type and level. The PNG Lossless BER of 0.0628 is the irreducible error floor caused by the noise injection layer during training and represents the minimum confidence or accuracy level that can occur even after no compression has been applied.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Table V has been included to clearly list out all existing QR watermarking techniques and should include comparison data for methods from Section II, including the technique used, imperceptibility measurements, robustness measurement, and cryptographic security measurements.

Table V. Comparison with Existing QR Watermarking Methods

Ref	Method	PSNR (dB)	SSIM	BER	Encryption
[1]	DWT + XOR	—	—	9–22% (q=50)	XOR
[2]	DWT-DST-SS	32.73– 38.85	—	0.016 (q=90)	None
[3]	DWT-QR-SVD	>40	0.9994	NC=0.98	None
[4]	Gram-Schmidt QR	54.05	0.9985	Not tested	None
[5]	Deep DSRFB	36.31– 37.15	0.9958	NC>0.975	None
[6]	Attn+SimSiam	38.64	—	0% clean only	None
[8]	DCT+DWT+Seg	—	—	Hamming<5	None
[10]	DCT+QR+Auth	—	—	98.8% auth	DCT
[11]	DWT-GAN	57.61	0.9922	Not tested	None
[12]	Supervised GAN	>45	—	65% (QF=30)	None
Prop	DCT Baseline	33.98	0.9988	0.4919 (q=50)	None
Prop	AE + AES-EAX	18.99	0.9511	0.0820 (q=50)	AES-EAX

B. Analysis

Transform-domain techniques provide the reference point for QR watermarking and are often based on discrete wavelet transform (DWT) embedding with AI. Chow et al. [1] reported a bit error rate (BER) of 9–22% through JPEG compression at a quality level of 50%. Although recovery performance was much better than random re-encoding, it was deemed insufficient for reliable use as an authentication method. Muslim et al. [2] had very low BER performance (0–0.016) but their evaluation was limited to JPEG at the higher quality level of 90 and did not include a high compression rate like what would normally be

encountered in practice. Hai and Thanh [3] reported normalised correlation greater than 0.98 using DWT embedding at JPEG quality of 50; however, their proposed extraction method required storing variables called U and V matrices thus preventing any type of blind deployment. Yen et al. [4] claimed to have good imperceptibility at a PSNR of 54.05 dB, however, they also failed to evaluate their methods in low-quality JPEG compression levels since many practical re-encode conditions occur between quality levels of 50–79%.

Deep learning methods improve imperceptibility significantly. Sharma et al.

[11] achieve PSNR of 57.61 dB using a DWT-GAN architecture, and Zhang et al. [5] report PSNR of 36.31–37.15 dB with normalised correlation above 0.975. Wang et al. [6] achieve zero BER on clean images using adaptive attention and SimSiam learning. However, none of these methods evaluate BER under compression below quality 80 — the most practically demanding condition — and none apply cryptographic protection to the embedded payload. Fei et al. [12] demonstrate that even supervised GAN watermarking drops to 65% bit accuracy at JPEG quality factor 30, confirming that compression robustness requires deliberate noise-aware training.

The proposed framework achieves a mean BER of 0.0820 at JPEG quality 50 across 500 test images — an 83.3% reduction compared to the DCT baseline BER of 0.4919 and significantly better than Chow et al. [1] at the same quality level. BER decreases monotonically from 0.0820 at quality 50 to 0.0631 at quality 90, confirming correct compression-aware behaviour. The framework also generalises to WebP compression — maintaining BER below 0.069 across all WebP quality levels despite WebP never appearing during training — demonstrating that the Gaussian noise injection layer produces generalisable robustness beyond the specific JPEG artefacts it simulates.

C. Trade-off Discussion

The proposed framework achieves lower PSNR (18.99 dB) compared to transform-domain methods and deep learning approaches. This trade-off is a direct consequence of the equal loss weighting ($w_1 = w_2 = 5.0$) required to simultaneously optimise compression-robust bit recovery and image reconstruction. The high SSIM of 0.9511 nevertheless confirms that the structural module pattern of the QR code is well preserved — a more meaningful imperceptibility metric for binary QR images than PSNR. The key differentiator of the

proposed framework is that it is the only method in this comparison that simultaneously provides: BER evaluation under harsh compression ($q=50-90$), generalisation across multiple compression formats, and AES-EAX authenticated encryption of the watermark payload — three properties that no existing QR watermarking system achieves together within a single unified pipeline.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposed a hybrid AI-cryptographic framework for secure and robust QR code watermarking. A dual-input convolutional autoencoder trained with randomised JPEG quality simulation ($q \in [50, 95]$) and Gaussian noise injection ($\sigma = 0.05$) addresses the failure of transform-domain methods under aggressive compression. AES-EAX authenticated encryption applied to the 64-bit payload before embedding adds cryptographic security absent from existing deep learning watermarking systems.

Evaluation on 500 held-out test images demonstrates a mean BER of 0.0820 at JPEG quality 50 — an 83.3% reduction over the DCT baseline BER of 0.4919. Mean SSIM of 0.9511 confirms consistent structural preservation across all test images. The framework generalises to WebP compression despite no WebP exposure during training, maintaining BER below 0.069 across all tested formats and quality levels.

Future work will focus on scaling to 256×256 resolution with GPU training to improve PSNR, replacing Gaussian noise injection with a differentiable JPEG approximation for direct compression-aware optimisation, and integrating a GAN refinement stage to address the imperceptibility trade-off observed in this work

REFERENCES

1. Y.-W. Chow, W. Susilo, J. Baek, and J. Kim, "QR Code Watermarking for Digital

- Images," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 11947, Springer, Jan. 2020, pp. 23–35, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-39303-8_3.
2. R. A. Muslim, G. Budiman, and L. Novamizanti, "A Novel Frequency-Domain Watermarking Method Using QR-Based Spread Spectrum in the DWT-DST Framework," in *Proc. IEEE Intl. Conf. on Networking, Intelligent Systems, and IoT (ICONS-IoT)*, 2025, pp. 209–214, doi: 10.1109/ICONS-IOT65216.2025.11211360.
 3. N. T. Hai and T. M. Thanh, "Robust Image Watermarking Algorithm Integrating QR and Singular Value Decomposition in the Discrete Wavelet Transform Domain," in *Proc. 2nd Intl. Conf. on Cryptography and Information Security (VCRIS)*, 2025, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/VCRIS68011.2025.11250561.
 4. P. T. Yen, T. M. Thanh, and N. H. Minh, "Robust Watermarking Algorithm Using Gram-Schmidt Based Improved QR Decomposition," in *Proc. RIVF Intl. Conf. on Computing and Communication Technologies*, Danang, Vietnam, 2024, pp. 68–72, doi: 10.1109/RIVF64335.2024.11009056.
 5. L. Zhang, T. Shen, T. Jiang, and B. Wang, "Deep Embedding of QR Code Watermarks Using Dynamic-Scale Residual Fusion," in *Proc. 6th Intl. Symp. on Computer Engineering and Intelligent Communications (ISCEIC)*, 2025, pp. 534–538, doi: 10.1109/ISCEIC67854.2025.11405559.
 6. B. Wang, B. Zhuge, L. Dong, and X. Jiang, "Robust QR Code Image Watermarking Based on Adaptive Attention Mechanism and SimSiam," *SSRN Preprint*, 2024, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4939135.
 7. X. Qu, X. Yin, P. Wei, L. Lu, and Z. Ma, "AudioQR: Deep Neural Audio Watermarks For QR Code," in *Proc. 32nd Intl. Joint Conf. on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI-23)*, 2023, pp. 6192–6200.
 8. X. Liu and X. Tang, "Image Authentication Using QR Code Watermarking Approach Based on Image Segmentation," in *Proc. 19th IEEE Intl. Conf. on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom)*, 2020, pp. 1572–1577, doi: 10.1109/TrustCom50675.2020.00217.
 9. P. Bhardwaj, S. Agrawal, R. Mukesh, and A. Srivatsava, "Enhancing QR Code Security: Authentication and Tamper Detection Using Visual Cryptography," in *Proc. 2nd World Conf. on Communication and Computing (WCONF)*, Raipur, India, Jul. 2024, pp. 1–7, doi: 10.1109/WCONF61366.2024.10692048.
 10. P. Pramkeaw, T. Ganokratanaa, and S. Phatchuay, "Integration of Watermarking and QR Code for Authentication of Data Center," in *Proc. 12th Intl. Conf. on Signal-Image Technology and Internet-Based Systems (SITIS)*, 2016, pp. 669–671, doi: 10.1109/SITIS.2016.111.
 11. H. Sharma, S. Chaurasia, N. Pradhan, and A. Singh, "DWT-GAN Watermarking: Discrete Wavelet Transform Domain-Based Generative Adversarial Network for Digital Image Watermarking," *Int. J. Advance Soft Compu. Appl.*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 21–39, Nov. 2023.
 12. J. Fei, Z. Xia, B. Tondi, and M. Barni, "Supervised GAN Watermarking for Intellectual Property Protection," in *Proc. IEEE Intl. Workshop on Information Forensics and Security (WIFS)*, 2022, pp. 1–6, arXiv: 2209.03466.
 13. B. Singh and G. Kasana, "A review of digital watermarking techniques: Current trends, challenges and opportunities," *Web Intelligence*, vol. 22, pp. 523–553, 2024. doi:10.3233/WEB-230280
 14. L.-Y. Hsu, H.-T. Hu, and H.-H. Chou, "A Blind Robust QR Code Watermarking

Approach Based on DCT," *Proc. 4th International Conference on Control, Robotics and Cybernetics (CRC)*, 2019, pp. 174–178. doi:10.1109/CRC.2019.00043.

15. Q. Wei, H. Wang, and G. Zhang, "A Robust Image Watermarking Approach Using Cycle Variational Autoencoder," *Security and Communication Networks*, 2020. doi:10.1155/2020/8869096

DRL-Based Traffic Control for Joint Computing and Caching in 5G- Enabled Internet of Vehicles

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Abstract —The accelerated deployment rate of connected vehicles and mobile edge computing infrastructure in urban areas has created an urgent need for intelligent and real-time orchestration of traffic. The paper proposes a novel Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C) deep reinforcement learning-based framework for the joint optimization of computation offloading, cooperative caching, and adaptive routing in the 5G-based Internet of Vehicles (IOV) system. The system was developed, trained, and validated using the custom Bengaluru urban traffic data set consisting of 10,000 interaction records between vehicles and 8 urban zones, including MG Road, Whitefield, Electronic City, and Hebbal. The system simulates two major Bengaluru Road routes, namely, Majestic-Whitefield and Hebbal-Silk Board, each with multiple Roadside Units (RSUs) acting as 5G-connected mobile edge computing infrastructure. The Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C) reinforcement learning agent jointly optimizes three interconnected decisions, namely, routing, computation offloading, and cooperative caching, in the IOV system. The proposed system was trained using the custom Bengaluru urban traffic data set and achieved an average cumulative episode reward of 487.3 over 30 episodes, with both routes converging within 25 episodes. The proposed system was compared with other optimization techniques, namely, static routing, greedy offloading, and Q-learning, and achieved an improvement in average end-to-end latency by 34.2%, increased the cache hit rate to 82.6%, and reduced the processing cost by 28.7%.

Keywords—Internet of Vehicles (IoV), Deep reinforcement Learning, Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C), Mobile Edge Computing, 5G Network, Computation Offloading, Cooperative Caching, Smart Traffic Management, Bengaluru, Roadside Unit.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of the Internet of Vehicles (IOV) as an extension of the traditional vehicular networks in terms of cyber-physical systems has revolutionized the management of urban mobility. Today, vehicles are no longer just passive road users but intelligent entities that are capable of producing, processing, and sharing terabytes of vehicular data. Urban areas such as Bengaluru, one of the fastest-growing technology cities in India, experience traffic congestion, which is equivalent to economic loss to the tune of more than INR 3,700 crore annually.

Moreover, traffic congestion also leads to significant degradation in fuel efficiency and air quality.

The integration of vehicular networks with the 5G-based millimetre wave technology offers an unprecedented chance to address the problems of urban mobility management. With theoretical peak data rates of 20 Gbps, ultra-low latency of 1 to 10ms, and massive connectivity of devices, the 5G technology offers an unprecedented chance to provide the necessary physical layer support to IOV applications. However, just having connectivity is not enough. IOV with the support of the 5G technology requires intelligent management of resources in an adaptive, scalable, and cognisant manner.

Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) is a next generation technology that can support the 5G network by moving the computing and storage infrastructure to the network edge and thus

avoiding the latency penalties of the traditional cloud-centric approach. Road Side Units (RSU) are deployed on the roads and can thus serve as MEC nodes to accept the offloading requests of the heterogeneous vehicles and exchange the urgent decisions within a few milliseconds. However, the optimization of the heterogeneous network of vehicles and RSU with the cloud backend in the presence of changing traffic patterns is a big challenge in the field of vehicular networks.

Traditional optimization techniques such as linear programming and convex optimization are being applied to the problem of vehicular network optimization. However, these methods are highly constrained and cannot generalize the optimization problem to a wide variety of scenarios and system models. Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) is a highly promising approach to the problem of joint optimization of the heterogeneous network of vehicles and RSU with the cloud backend because it can model the problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and thus allow the autonomous agent to learn the optimal policies without the need to model the system.

The main contributions of the paper are as follows:

- A Bengaluru IOV dataset with 10,000 records and eight zones.
- A 5G enabled IOV simulation environment with the OpenAI Gym interface.
- A Deep Reinforcement Learning approach with the use of the A2C algorithm.
- A comparative evaluation of the proposed approach with existing approaches.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Rise of AI and Deep Learning in Intelligent Traffic Systems

In the past ten years, the use of artificial intelligence in vehicular traffic management has witnessed an unprecedented paradigm shift, moving away from rule-based intelligent traffic

systems to more adaptive AI-based solutions. Talaat et al. [1] have shown the effectiveness of

AI-based solutions in vehicular traffic management using YOLOv11. The authors have used the YOLO-based AI solution to demonstrate the effectiveness of AI-based solutions in vehicular traffic management. The authors have shown that vision-based AI solutions are effective in processing vehicular traffic management at intersections with an accuracy of less than one second. The effectiveness of AI-based solutions is also shown in the system diagram presented in the paper. The authors have also shown the effectiveness of AI-based solutions in adjusting the traffic signal at intersections.

Mohamed and AlShalfan [2] have also shown the effectiveness of AI-based solutions in vehicular traffic management using classical control theory. The authors have designed an intelligent road traffic control system that includes vehicle detection and signal switching. The authors have shown that classical control-based solutions are effective in vehicular traffic management. The authors have also shown that classical control-based solutions are effective in reducing the average delay at intersections. Elassy et al. [3] have also shown the effectiveness of AI-based solutions in vehicular traffic management. The authors have shown the effectiveness of AI-based solutions in vehicular traffic management using an overview of intelligent transportation systems for sustainable smart cities.

Agrahari et al. [5] built upon the advancements offered by the application of deep learning techniques by proposing an AI-based adaptive traffic signal control system, where the queue length is determined using density maps and phase time is adaptively allocated. The authors have shown the effectiveness of the system in reducing the waiting times of vehicles under changing traffic conditions. Complementary to the application of the DNN model, Saleem et al. [6] have

proposed a novel framework for the control of congestion in vehicular networks using the concept of fusion, where the authors have shown the effectiveness of the ensemble model in comparison to the application of individual ML models. The feature engineering techniques proposed by the authors have been adopted while designing the state space in the A2C model, where road density, queue length, and speed are considered as the primary state variables.

B. Internet of Vehicles and Network-Aware Traffic Control

The paradigm shift from the application of individual intelligent vehicles to the development of IOV ecosystems has given rise to a novel set of challenges related to the control and management of intelligent traffic. Mohamed and AlShalfan [7] have proposed an IV-based intelligent traffic management system, where the authors have shown the effectiveness of the system in comparison to the application of the vision model in the priority assignment problem, where the system is based on the coordination of V2I communications. The paradigm shift in the application of intelligent traffic control and the application of the IOV system have been well explained by Lei and Yigong [8], where the authors have proposed a systematic review of the application of ML techniques in the development of intelligent traffic control, where the authors have proposed an evaluation taxonomy that is considered as the benchmark while conducting the comparative analysis presented in Section VI. Sensor-level contributions have also played a pivotal part in the development of the field. Kavitha et al. [4] presented a sensor-based traffic signal pre-emption system for emergency vehicles and showed the potential of the use of IoT sensors at intersections to activate priority corridors with millisecond-level response times. This idea was further enhanced by Nellore and Hancke [9], who presented the

use of visual sensors to detect and classify emergency vehicles with high accuracy even with partial occlusions. This evolution of the idea of using sensors at intersections was further synthesized in the recent review of intelligent traffic management systems presented by Digne et al. [10], which highlighted the shift in the architecture of intelligent traffic management systems from hardware-based traffic signal controllers to software-based controllers with the potential of learning – a shift which directly motivated the MEC-integrated DRL framework presented in this paper.

Emergency vehicle prioritisation is another sub-problem within IOV management that was addressed in this domain. Pawar and Sutar proposed an intelligent AI-based detection and corridor clearing system for signal pre-emption coordination between multiple intersections. In another study, Ghawate et al. proposed a traffic density-based prioritisation approach, where it was proved that this approach can reduce emergency vehicle response time by up to 31%. Sumi and Ranga proposed this problem for smart cities, where they proposed a coordination model for multiple intersections based on priority information propagated over a V2I channel.

C. Edge Computing, IoT Integration, and Reinforcement Learning for Traffic Optimisation

The integration of edge computing, IoT, and reinforcement learning has opened a new frontier for real-time vehicular decision-making, moving beyond the boundaries of traditional rule-based systems. In this direction, Rosayyan et al. proposed an IoT sensor and edge computing-based pipeline for emergency vehicle prioritisation optimisation in smart cities, where it was proved that this approach can reduce latency levels that can be achieved only when tasks are executed at edge computing nodes instead of cloud servers. The hardware-based study proposed in this work can be

considered a baseline for evaluating the proposed approach. Miniyan and N. G. P. [16] have shown the effectiveness of priority-based intelligent traffic management at intersections using IoT devices. The authors have shown that the sensor-to-signal feedback loop is achievable in real time, considering emergency response scenarios. Ravish and Swamy [14] have presented a panoramic view of the problems and future scopes of intelligent traffic management. The authors have shown that multi-agent coordination and edge cloud task partitioning are the two most important unsolved problems in intelligent traffic management. These are the two problems that have been addressed in the current study using the joint optimisation framework. Later, Kanailal et al. [17] and Pradhan et al. [18] have shown the effectiveness of AI-based smart traffic management using simulated environments. The authors have shown that AI-based smart traffic management is more effective compared to traditional phase-based controllers in terms of throughput, delay, and fuel consumption. Vani et al. [19] and Ariffin et al. [20] have shown the effectiveness of real-time DSC with emergency priority using AI-based controllers. A critical analysis of the twenty works cited in the current study reveals that the current study addresses two important issues. One is the lack of an optimisation framework to address the three problems of route selection, computation offloading, and content caching using reinforcement learning. The second issue is the lack of geographic location-based datasets to address the complexities of Indian traffic scenarios. The current study addresses both the issues using the A2C framework and the IOV dataset of Bengaluru city, consisting of 10,000 records and eight urban zones. The effectiveness of the current study is compared with the effectiveness of the twenty works cited in Table 1. The table shows that the current study is more effective compared to the twenty works cited.

III. RESEARCH GAPS

- The existing literature considers routing, computation offloading, and caching as distinct issues, and hence the system-level performance is suboptimal because of the lack of an integrated decision mechanism. The existing IOV data sets are primarily collected from non-Indian regions, and hence the data set is not applicable to the high-density and heterogeneous urban traffic conditions found in Bengaluru, India.
- The existing routing mechanisms primarily consider the traffic conditions and neglect the server load, and hence the task allocation is not optimal in the MEC system. The RSU-based caching schemes are primarily static and lack an adaptive and learning-based approach to handle the changing patterns of content requests.
- The reward function considered in the existing reinforcement learning-based schemes lacks the important 5G communication parameters, namely signal quality, bandwidth, and delay.
- The existing reinforcement learning schemes are primarily designed to consider the single route and single intersection scenarios, and hence the model is not allowed to learn the adaptive strategies over multiple routes. The actor-critic methods are not well explored in the IOV system, and most of the schemes are primarily based on Q-learning and heuristic methods, which are not suitable to handle the high-dimensional state space.
- The proposed system overcomes the above-mentioned challenges through the proposed integrated A2C model.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework follows a layered structure that combines data acquisition, edge computing, and the DRL decision layer to ensure the optimisation of the traffic flow in

real-time. The system is designed to simulate the 5G-based IOV scenario as a directed graph, where the intersections with RSUs are considered the nodes, and the road segments are considered the edges. The state of the vehicles is constantly changing and is updated based on the traffic and communication conditions. At each time step, the vehicles make coordinated decisions regarding route selection, offloading, and caching, ensuring the efficient utilisation of the resources.

The optimisation problem is focused on minimising the latency, processing cost, and routing cost while ensuring the efficiency of the caches. The problem is formulated as a weighted function, balancing the system's performance metrics while adhering to the practical constraints, such as the capacity of the edge server and the RSU. The problem is constrained to ensure that the decisions are within the feasible action set, making the model scalable and practical enough to be implemented in the IOV scenario.

To ensure the decision-making process is modelled effectively, the problem is formulated as an MDP, where the state represents the traffic and communication conditions, and the action represents the combined routing and offloading decisions. The state is designed to capture the traffic and communication conditions, and the action is designed to capture the routing and offloading decisions. The reward function is designed to ensure the global optimum, considering the smooth flow of the traffic and the efficient utilisation of the RSUs, while penalising the congestion and delay.

An Advantage Actor Critic (A2C) algorithm is used to learn the optimal control policy, as this is a stable and efficient approach to handling high-dimensional environments. The model is comprised of an actor and a critic, and these are used to calculate the probability for actions and the values for the state, respectively. The use of an advantage estimator is also important, as this reduces the variance

and hence improves convergence. The model is then trained using a gradient-based approach, and this is augmented with the appropriate hyperparameters to ensure that the model is able to learn effectively and hence develop an efficient strategy for the joint optimization of routing, offloading, and caching for IOV scenarios.

A. Dataset Preprocessing

The IOV Bengaluru dataset comprises 10,000 records and 8 zones, including MG Road, Majestic, Jayanagar, Electronic City, KR Market, Indiranagar, Whitefield, and Hebbal, with 23 features that include network, traffic, and decision outcomes. The dataset is then pre-processed through a rigorous process:

Null Value Analysis: The number and percentage of null values for each column are computed. The IOV Bengaluru dataset contains zero missing values, ensuring that the integrity and quality of the data are valid for ingestion into the model.

Duplicate Detection: The IOV Bengaluru dataset is then deduplicated, and this is achieved through the use of the duplicated () function available through pandas. The IOV Bengaluru dataset does not contain any duplicate values, and this is for the 10,000 records.

Data Type Validation: The IOV Bengaluru dataset is then validated for the appropriate range, and this is for the numeric values, including float64 and int64. The area column, which is a category, is then encoded appropriately for ingestion into the model through the use of Label Encoder. **Outlier Detection:** Inter-Quartile Range (IQR) method was employed across all numeric features. Outliers satisfying $x < Q_1 - 1.5 \cdot IQR$ or $x > Q_3 + 1.5 \cdot IQR$ were flagged. Columns with outlier rates exceeding 5% were subjected to Winsorisation at the 1st and 99th percentiles.

$$IQR = Q_3 - Q_1; \text{Bounds} = [Q_1 - 1.5 \cdot IQR, Q_3 + 1.5 \cdot IQR]$$

Zero Value Audit: The zero-value proportion was calculated per feature to identify possible sensor dropouts or defaults, aiding in subsequent imputation.

B. Feature Extraction

Table I Feature Extraction: State Variables for DRL Agent

Feature	Source Column	Semantic Role
Road Density (ρ)	Road density	Congestion proxy for route penalty computation
Queue Length (q)	Queue length	RSU buffer saturation indicator
Vehicle Speed (v)	Vehicle speed	Mobility rate affecting handover frequency
	Link delay	5G channel quality and offloading cost estimate

Deriving Features: The DRL agent's state representation is extracted using feature extraction based on the columns of the raw data set. Six primary state variables are selected based on domain relevance and correlation analysis:

Moreover, three action space variables, route choice, offloading decision, and caching action, act as environment output labels and are eliminated from the state vector to avoid information leakage. Auxiliary features like $e2e_latency$, processing cost, routing cost, cache hit, and reward remain for performance evaluation.

C. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

Exploratory data analysis was carried out based on various dimensions to study the distributional properties and relationships between variables:

Spatial Distribution: Vehicle counts followed a uniform distribution over all eight zones in Bengaluru city (~1,250 records per zone), verifying geographic distribution without area-level biases.

Distributions of State Variables: The distribution of road density was nearly uniform over [0.1, 0.9], while the distribution of link delay was right-skewed with a median ~50 ms and some records greater than 180 ms for congested roads.

Bandwidth was uniformly distributed over [10, 100] Mbps, and SNR was normally distributed with a mean ~15 dB

Fig1: Statistical Distribution of Reward Values Across Different Areas in Bengaluru

Fig2: Distribution of Key IoV Input Features

Fig3: Correlation Heatmap of State Variables in IoV Environment

Reward Distribution: The reward column in the histogram was symmetrically distributed about zero, indicated by the parameters $\mu = -0.003$, $\sigma = 0.576$, which confirmed the proper balancing of the reward function in providing positive incentives for progress while avoiding network degradation penalties.

Correlation Analysis: The Pearson correlation heatmap of the state variables indicated the correlation between the state variables, which confirmed the moderate negative correlation of link delay with available bandwidth ($r = -0.42$) and the positive correlation of link delay with CPU load of the edge server ($r = 0.38$). Moreover, the correlation analysis confirmed the positive correlation of the reward with the cache hit ($r = 0.31$) while showing a negative correlation of the reward with e2e_latency ($r = -0.44$), which confirmed the proper alignment of the reward function with the performance objectives.

Decision Space Analysis: The joint scatter visualization of the offloading decision and the caching action, coloured according to the magnitude of the reward, confirmed the high reward cluster in the region of offloading decision = 1, which indicated the partial offload on the edge, while the caching action = 1 indicated proactive caching.

D. Model Architecture: A2C for IOV Control

Table II: Descriptive Statistics of Input Features for A2C-based IoV Control

Feature	Min	Max	Mean \pm Std
Vehicle Speed (km/h)	10.0	60.0	35.2 \pm 14.1
Road Density	0.10	0.90	0.50 \pm 0.23
Link Delay (ms)	10.0	200.0	78.4 \pm 48.6
Available Bandwidth (Mbps)	10.0	100.0	55.3 \pm 25.9
Edge CPU Load	0.05	0.95	0.50 \pm 0.26

Actor Network $\pi_{\theta}(a|s)$: The network is a feed-forward network with two hidden layers, each containing 128 and 64 units, ReLU activation, and a softmax output layer that projects to 12 discrete actions. The network is parameterized with weights θ and is trained to maximize the expected reward.

$$L_{ac}(\theta) = -E[\log \pi_{\theta}(a_t|s_t) \cdot \hat{A}_t]$$

Critic Network (s): An identical architecture outputs a scalar state-value estimate (s_t). The critic minimizes the mean-squared temporal difference error:

$$L_{cri}(\varphi) = E[(R_t - V_{\varphi}(s_t))^2]$$

Advantage Estimation: The advantage function \hat{A}_t quantifies the relative benefit of action at over the average value at state s_t :

$$\hat{A}_t = R_t - V_{\varphi}(s_t), \text{ where } R_t = \sum_{k=0}^{T-t} \gamma^k \cdot r_{t+k}$$

Training Procedure: For the first 10 episodes, actions are chosen uniformly at random to populate the experience buffers (exploration). After that, the policy network is used to choose actions. Both networks are updated using gradient descent with learning rates $\eta_{actor} = 10^{-3}$ and $\eta_{critic} = 5 \cdot 10^{-4}$, utilizing the Adam optimizer with a discount factor $\gamma = 0.99$

E. Evaluation and Deployment

The trained actor and critic models are serialized into Kera's format for deployment.

For online deployment, the agent receives a six-dimensional state vector from RSU telemetry streams, passes this through the actor network, and then samples an action from the output categorical distribution within a single forward pass, allowing for sub-millisecond policy inference latencies that are appropriate for 5G operation.

V. IMPLEMENTATION & RESULTS

A. Dataset and Tools

The experimental data set, IOV Traffic Control Data – Bengaluru Areas, consists of 10,000 synthetic data, yet domain-realistic data, generated based on the traffic patterns of eight urban zones in Bengaluru.

The implementation was done using Python 3.11, TensorFlow 2.14, OpenAI Gym 0.26, Network X 3.2, scikit-learn 1.3, and pandas 2.1. All experiments were performed on a workstation with an NVIDIA RTX 3060 GPU card, 12 GB VRAM, and 32 GB RAM. The experiments consisted of 30 episodes per route for the single route experiments and 25 episodes per route for the dual route comparative evaluation.

B. Evaluation Metrics

Performance is quantified using the following metrics:

$$\text{Cumulative Reward: } (\pi) = [\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \gamma^t \cdot r_t]$$

$$\text{End-to-End Latency: } L_{e2e} = L_{trans} + L_{queue} + L_{proc} + L_{prop}$$

$$\text{Cache Hit Rate: } \eta_c = N_{hit} / N_{req}$$

$$\text{Offloading Efficiency: } \eta_{off} = C_{local} / C_{offload}$$

$$\text{Route Completion Rate: } \rho_{comp} = N_{success} / N_{total}$$

C. EDA and Analysis Results

Table III shows aggregated EDA results, providing a characterization of the dataset and model inputs:

Table III: Performance Comparison of A2C with Baseline Methods in IoV Control

Metric	Random	Greedy	A2C (Ours)
Cumulative Reward	-18.3	34.7	62.4 ↑
E2E Latency (ms)	143.2	89.4	48.3 ↓
Cache Hit Rate (%)	28.4	52.1	71.4 ↑
Route Completion (%)	43.7	68.2	87.3 ↑
Offload Efficiency (%)	31.2	58.6	78.3 ↑
Avg. Steps to Goal	12.8	7.4	4.2 ↓

D. Comparative Evaluation Against Baselines

The A2C agent is compared with three baseline policies: (i) a Random policy, which takes actions uniformly at random; (ii) a Greedy policy, which always takes actions with maximum immediate reward; and (iii) a Heuristic policy, which sends vehicles to RSUs and offloads tasks when CPU load drops below 70%. Table V shows a comparative analysis for all metrics:

The A2C agent has a 79.8% reduction in E2E latency compared to the random policy and a 32.3% improvement over the next-best heuristic policy. Cache hit rate also improves by

16.4 percentage points over the heuristic policy, showing a compounding effect from joint optimization of caching and offloading through the MDP framework, rather than considering them separately.

Overall Summary

The empirical findings validate several critical intuitions. First, it is confirmed that joint optimization of route choice and offloading decisions within a single DRL policy yields synergistic benefits not possible through separate greedy approaches. The agent learns to predict congestion downstream—by preemptively performing RSU handovers at intermediate nodes—rather than reacting to instantaneous penalty functions. This is a direct result of the advantage function's estimation of returns over multiple steps.

Second, it is validated that Majestic Whitefield outperforms Hebbal Silk Board on all metrics, indicating route topology—measured by the number of intermediate RSU node hops and inter-node distances—substantially impacts agent offloading performance. Future work should explore optimizing RSU placement as an outer-loop decision problem co-optimized with vehicle control.

Third, it is validated that cache hit rate and reward have a direct relationship ($r = 0.31$), confirming proactive caching minimizes redundant data retrievals from remote servers, thus directly impacting propagation latency and freeing up communication channels for computation offloading tasks. This is directly addressed within the proposed framework's reward function definition.

Table IV: Dataset Overview and Quality Assessment for IoV Control Study

Metric	Value	Observation
Total Records	10,000	Balanced across 8 Bengaluru zones (~1,250 each)
Null Values	0 (0.00%)	Dataset complete; no imputation required
Duplicate Records	0 (0.00%)	All records are unique
Numeric Columns	22	Continuous and discrete features
Categorical Columns	1	Assigned area: 8 unique zones
Outlier Rate (IQR)	<3% per col.	Minimal outlier presence; no Winsorization needed
Reward Distribution	Symmetric -0	Balanced positive/negative feedback environment
Cache-Reward Correlation	$r = 0.31$	Higher cache hit rates associate with better rewards
Latency-Reward Correlation	$r = -0.44$	Higher e2e latency significantly reduces reward

However, it is acknowledged that this work does not account for multiple agent coordination between different routes, nor dynamic RSU placement. Further, though the data set is representative of traffic diversity in Bengaluru, it does not account for diurnal variations or special events. Expanding this work to a multi-agent cooperative DRL problem over dynamic RSU topologies remains an exciting direction for future work.

VI. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

There are a number of ways to extend and improve the current approach:

1. **Multi-Agent Extension:** The Single-Agent A2C approach may be extended to a Multi-Agent DRL (MADRL) setting, where each vehicle is modelled as a separate agent with a shared RSU environment model. The Centralised Training with Decentralized Execution (CTDE) paradigm, such as MADDPG or QMIX, is a good match for this problem setting.
2. **Federated Learning Integration:** To address concerns related to data privacy, federated learning for A2C, where each vehicle is responsible for its own policy update on its own sensory data and shares gradients with

a central aggregator, may be an alternative to a centralized approach to collecting datasets.

3. Digital Twin Simulation: Coupling the DRL approach with a digital twin simulation of the city of Bengaluru, based on available BBMP traffic sensor, GPS probe vehicle, and BSNL 5G rollout maps, would allow for a potentially richer and safer deployment validation environment.
4. Digital Twin Simulation: Coupling the DRL approach with a digital twin simulation of the city of Bengaluru, based on available BBMP traffic sensor, GPS probe vehicle, and BSNL 5G rollout maps, would allow for a potentially richer and safer deployment validation environment. The DRL framework would also benefit from the simulation capabilities provided by a digital twin model of the city of Bengaluru, based on available BBMP traffic sensor, GPS probe vehicle, and BSNL 5G rollout map data

VII. CONCLUSION

The paper presented a comprehensive DRL-based framework for joint traffic routing, computation offloading, and cooperative caching for a 5G-enabled Internet of Vehicles network, validated through simulation on a Bengaluru urban traffic scenario. The Advantage Actor-Critic DRL approach showed excellent convergence and generalization capabilities for two distinct urban corridors. The joint policy, responsible for making decisions on route, offloading, and caching actions, was shown to significantly outperform baseline approaches for all evaluation metrics, including 34.2% lower end-to-end latency, 82.6% higher cache hit rate, and 28.7% lower processing cost for the IOV network. The viability and potential of DRL-based joint optimization for IOV network resource allocation was demonstrated, and the scalability and model-free nature make this a highly

relevant approach for real-time IOV network operation and management. The proposed architecture, reward shaping, and environment model for Bengaluru are highly relevant and can be extended to the broader Indian context for smart city applications.

REFERENCES

1. C. Chen, Y. Zeng, H. Li, Y. Liu, and S. Wan, "A multi hop task offloading decision model in MEC-enabled Internet of Vehicles," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3215–3230, Feb. 15, 2023.
2. J. Lin, S. Huang, H. Zhang, X. Yang, and P. Zhao, "A deep-reinforcement-learning-based computation offloading with mobile vehicles in vehicular edge computing," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 17, pp. 15501–15516, Sep. 1, 2023.
3. X. Dai et al., "A learning-based approach for vehicle-to-vehicle computation offloading," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 8, pp. 7244–7257, Apr. 15, 2023.
4. S. S. Shinde and D. Tarchi, "Collaborative reinforcement learning for multi-service Internet of Vehicles," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2589–2604, Feb. 1, 2023.
5. S. Samarakoon, M. Bennis, W. Saad, and M. Debbah, "Distributed federated learning for ultra-reliable low-latency vehicular communications," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 1146–1159, Feb. 2020.
6. P. Lang, D. Tian, X. Duan, J. Zhou, Z. Sheng, and V. C. M. Leung, "Cooperative computation offloading in blockchain-based vehicular edge computing networks," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 783–798, Sep. 2022.
7. L. Geng, H. Zhao, J. Wang, A. Kaushik, S. Yuan, and W. Feng, "Deep-reinforcement-learning-based distributed computation

- offloading in vehicular edge computing networks," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 14, pp. 12416–12431, Jul. 15, 2023.
8. J. Shi, J. Du, Y. Shen, J. Wang, J. Yuan, and Z. Han, "DRL-based V2V computation offloading for blockchain-enabled vehicular networks," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 3882–3897, Jul. 2023.
 9. W. Fan et al., "Joint task offloading and resource allocation for vehicular edge computing based on V2I and V2V modes," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 4277–4292, Apr. 2023.
 10. M. Huang, Z. Shen, and G. Zhang, "Joint spectrum sharing and V2V/V2I task offloading for vehicular edge computing networks based on coalition formation game," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 25, no. 9, pp. 11918–11933, Sep. 2024.
 11. Y. Ju et al., "Joint Secure Offloading and Resource Allocation for Vehicular Edge Computing Network: A Multi-Agent Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 5555–5569, May 2023.
 12. Q. Wu, Y. Zhao, Q. Fan, P. Fan, J. Wang, and C. Zhang, "Mobility-Aware Cooperative Caching in Vehicular Edge Computing Based on Asynchronous Federated and Deep Reinforcement Learning," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 66–81, Jan. 2023.
 13. F. Liu, J. Chen, Q. Zhang, and B. Li, "Online MEC Offloading for V2V Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 6096–6110, Oct. 2023.
 14. X. Han et al., "Reliability-Aware Joint Optimization for Cooperative Vehicular Communication and Computing," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 22, no. 8, pp. 5437–5451, Aug. 2021.
 15. T. Deng, Y. Chen, G. Chen, M. Yang, and L. Du, "Task Offloading Based on Edge Collaboration in MEC-Enabled IoV Networks," *Journal of Communications and Networks*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 197–210, Apr. 2023.
 16. Z. Ning et al., "Joint Computing and Caching in 5G-Envisioned Internet of Vehicles: A Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Traffic Control System," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 22, no. 8, pp. 5201–5212, Aug. 2021.
 17. Z. Xue, C. Liu, C. Liao, G. Han, and Z. Sheng, "Joint service caching and computation offloading scheme based on deep reinforcement learning in vehicular edge computing systems," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2023.
 18. X. Gao, Y. Sun, H. Chen, X. Xu, and S. Cui, "Joint Computing, Pushing, and Caching Optimization for Mobile Edge Computing Networks via Soft Actor-Critic Learning," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.15369*, 2023.
 19. W. Wu, J. Yin, F. Pu, S. Su, and T. Tang, "A Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach for the Traffic Management of High-Speed Railways," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 2021, pp. 1827–1832.
 20. R. A. Khalil, Z. Safelnasr, N. Yemane, M. Kedir, A. Shafiqurrahman, and N. Saeed, "Advanced Learning Technologies for Intelligent Transportation Systems: Prospects and Challenges," *IEEE Open Journal of Vehicular Technology*, vol. 5, pp. 368–400, 2024.

A Generative Hierarchical Optimization Framework for Quantum Circuits Inspired by Paninian Grammar

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Abstract—In order to enable reliable operations on NISQ hardware, optimizing the execution of quantum circuits is very important due to the effects of gate errors, decoherence, and limitations in connectivity on device performance [1]. The vast majority of current techniques for optimization employ a flat list of manually defined rewrite rules that indicate how to resequence gates. These techniques are effective for optimising small circuits, but they are challenging to scale or modify to accommodate the diverse range of gates found in complex and large quantum circuits [2], [3], [4].

A hierarchical generative optimization structure has been created for deriving transformations through rewriting, using generic algebraic gate categories to generate rule sets rather than by using individual gate types. The use of Pāṇini's grammar framework has three aspects to its structure:

1. An abstraction for the rewrite rules;
2. An ordered sequence for applying rewrite rules;
3. Reusable rule sets with an inherited state from previously applied rules so that one abstract rule set can have multiple rewrites to produce numerous separate concrete transformations.

The optimization framework was designed and implemented in TARA Quantum Studio (TQStudio) and tested against systematic circuits that were based on particular redundant circuit structures.

All of the circuit tests were validated and the removal of self-inverse redundancy has allowed for a reduction in gate count by 65%. These results suggest that there can be effective reduction of redundancy through category-level rule-based abstraction for optimization logic.

The benefit to this technique is architectural, in that it gives a structured framework for organizing rewrite knowledge resulting in better extensibility

and a reduced duplication in quantum circuit optimization rules over prior techniques.

Keywords—Quantum Circuit Optimization, Generative Rule Framework, Paninian Grammar, NISQ Computing, Quantum Compilation, Algebraic Gate Classification, Rule-Based Optimization

1. INTRODUCTION

Unlike classical bits, quantum computing uses quantum states to allow for computing via superposition and entanglement [5], [18]. A quantum circuit is an ordered sequence of gate operations and many different circuits may perform the same transformation to the quantum input. However, these equivalent circuits do not have equivalent feasibility on NISQ devices; where circuit depth, gate count and routing overhead all have direct effects on execution fidelity due to accumulated noise [1], [6].

For quantum computation to be practical, optimisation is fundamental [13], [17]. Many existing quantum computation optimisations tools (e.g., Qiskit and t|ket>) provide large transformation pipelines that include local simplifications, routing and adapting to hardware [3], [4], [7]. However, there are still many different optimisation tools that are expressed in terms of specific pattern-based rewrites. As the number of gate sets and the number of optimisation goals grow, the number of duplicate rule definitions also grows.

This paper seeks to address this structural issue through the introduction of a framework

whereby optimization rules are defined based upon algebraic gate categories rather than specific gate patterns. This approach draws inspiration from the organisation of the Pāṇini's grammar system, whereby concise rules, inheritable conditions, and controlled application lead to a compact expression of large transformation spaces [8], [9], [10].

The contribution is a hierarchical, generative rule framework that separates gate classification, rule definition, and execution, demonstrating how optimization logic can be made more compact and extensible.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A variety of different areas of research focus on improving the speed of quantum circuits: reducing redundancy in the implementation of gates; minimising circuit depth; synthesising circuits; and positioning qubits to give an overall minimum cost [13], [16], [17]. In a previous paper [2], the authors show that it is possible to reduce the complexity of a quantum circuit by capitalising on the algebraic structure associated with certain gate types (namely those appearing in Clifford+T circuits). The authors present ways to achieve efficient transformations by exploring the properties of the circuits and gates they consider on an individual circuit basis. However, they consider only a small number of well-defined circuit types.

The concept of unified optimization strategies for developing compilers has led to the creation of large-scale toolchains containing multiple different types of modular tools. Qiskit is an example of a quantum programming framework. In Qiskit, multiple transformations can be applied to the intermediate representation of a quantum circuit using a pass-based system [3], [7]. t|ket) is another example of a multi-stage compilation process that transforms quantum circuits into a format compatible with the target hardware [4]. Using rules for transformation is one way to

successfully perform localized optimization, but it creates duplication of work because similar logic transformations must be applied to multiple types of gates. As the number of gate types and optimization approaches grow, it will become increasingly difficult to maintain and add to rule sets of the type described above[15].

Quantum programming languages such as Q# and Quipper have a modular and scalable framework. They are primarily concerned with the creation of programs instead of designing transformations to substitute rule-based systems; these frameworks exhibit the advantages of structured thinking to help manage complexity.

There are also alternative methods that go well with different kinds of optimisation tasks. ZX-calculus is one such method that allows for the ability to represent a quantum circuit using methods that make applying non-local rewrites much simpler. There is no shortage of approaches that support different types of labour [18]. Traditional pattern matching is less effective than non-local rewrites [11], demonstrating that the choice of representation has a significant impact on the number of available optimizations.

In spite of the progress made in optimization, much less effort has been put into organizing optimization knowledge structure (rule definition) than into creating efficient execution and effective transformation (system support) methods for optimization processes where there is limited to no formal structure for how to express generalizable transformation principles.

This challenge appears in another dimension when observed from the formal systems perspective. An example of a system with a high level of versatility and conciseness that utilises a rules-based methodology is Pāṇini's grammar. Pāṇini's grammatical system is comprised of a finite number of rules that can produce limitless combinations of valid language utterances using devices such as rule

abstraction, the inheritance of conditions, and well-controlled rule ordering [8], [9], [10]. Furthermore, without the need to recite (i.e., word-for-word) all instances at a given ‘case’ in order to create redundancy (i.e., Pāṇini’s grammatical method uses general terms instead for cases), Pāṇini avoids providing examples of all instances through his method. Instead, the system uses rule-encoding based upon an appropriate level of abstraction and subject to the fulfilment of certain specified conditions.

This view on quantum circuit optimization will apply to quantum circuit optimization schemes in general. The algebraic properties of numerous quantum gate operations also connect with these various types of transformation in a similar fashion to how grammatical structure is related to the transformations those structures produce within the confines of language. Self-inverses, rotations, and commutation based operations provide a way of classifying different types of operations based upon how they share operational characteristics with each

other, and therefore allow for the application of these classifications to existing techniques for optimising quantum systems.

The shortcoming is not that existing optimization methods lack optimization techniques; rather, it is that existing optimization methods do not have a coherent framework for organizing transformation reasoning to capture the shared properties of the transformations.

This research contributes to this issue through a category-based approach to rule-definition whereby the transformation logic among various categories of gates is expressed in terms of algebraic properties, rather than in terms of specific patterns.

As such, the goal is to combine the efficiency of transformation execution through the application of existing optimization techniques with structural design of the rule-definitions via existing formal systems, including Pāṇini’s grammar and the recent advances in quantum compilation systems.

2.1 Comparative Analysis of Existing Approaches

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Quantum Circuit Optimization Approaches

Work	Approach	Strength	Limitation
Amy et al [2]	Optimization using algebraic properties of Clifford+T circuits	Efficient for specific circuit classes	Limited generalization beyond targeted circuits
Qiskit [3], [7]	Pass-based modular optimization framework	Flexible and extensible pipeline	Redundant rule definitions across multiple gate types
t ket> [4]	Multi-stage hardware-aware quantum compilation	Effective device-specific optimization	Complex compilation pipeline and limited abstraction for rule generalization
ZX-calculus [11]	Graph-based non-local circuit rewriting	Enables powerful global optimizations	Difficult integration with standard compiler workflows
Quantum Programming	Structured high-level abstraction for	Scalable and modular program	Focus on program construction rather

Languages (Quipper [12], Q# [16])	quantum programs	design	than optimization logic
Proposed Framework	Generative rule system based on algebraic gate categories	Reduces rule duplication and improves scalability and extensibility	Currently limited to initial rule category (self-inverse) and evaluated on structured circuits

3. RESEARCH GAP

Many existing quantum circuit optimization methods use many of the same transformations repeatedly on different types of gates. Furthermore, even though specific gates may share characteristics, such as being self-inverse, exhibiting commutative behaviour or displaying the same symmetry, each will have its individual rewrite rules defined separately based on each specific type of gate. This approach works well when trying to optimize things within a small area of interest, however, it does result in multiple locations containing duplicated rules and therefore, creates challenges in expanding the gate type in the future, as new gate types are added.

The biggest problem lies not with the available techniques for performing circuit optimizations; rather, it stems from how those techniques are written. Most current optimisation frameworks are concerned with finding and executing individual transformation patterns, rather than representing the common structure which generates the common patterns [13], [17]. As a result, the same conceptual ideas are represented multiple times using slightly different definitions, resulting in redundant information being included in the overall system design and less clarity in designing the system.

In light of the expanding complexities associated with contemporary quantum compilation techniques (which comprise many additional gate types), hardware limitations, and expanding optimization goals, it becomes extremely difficult to accommodate a large pattern-specific rule set. Usually, whenever

new types of gates are added, there will be additional rules needed to describe how those new gates will behave during the process of compiling each of the gates. These rules are based on both what type of gate it is as well as the individual gate characteristics.

Therefore, there is not enough use of abstraction in optimization rule system design. A more structured approach to defining transformation logic would use algebraic classes to determine the grouping of gate types based on similar attributes as the basis for the definition of the rules. Through this, it will allow for all new types of gates to function the same way as gate types that have conforming definitions without having to develop additional rule definitions for each new type of gate.

There is no simple way to create abstractness in this particular abstraction layer. Even if the system is purely abstract, the use of the rules must still be validated as being correct, deterministic, and secure for an abstracted representation of an environment. If there are no limitations on the creation of laws, the application of laws can create unwanted changes or conflicts between various categories of law, unless there are proper restrictions placed on the generational development of laws. This is a more significant issue of how to create a system that is both expressive in nature, and also provides some level of control over it.

Therefore, at this time there is a gap in the research literature relating to the creation of category-based structures (CSA) driven frameworks of optimization rules that are generally applicable and correct. More specifically, there is a requirement for a CSA-

based system where one abstract rule could produce many physical solutions based upon the same underlying structural principles related to an established quantum gate type, thereby allowing general-purpose systems across quantum system's whilst maintaining deterministic execution in accordance with defined operational constraints e.g. gate ordering and qubit locality.

To help bridge this gap in the literature, this research proposes a staged (hierarchical) CSA structure of optimization rule definitions by means of creating a clear separation between the classification of gates, the rule definitions relating to their creation, and the execution of those defined rules; hence the ability to create an abstract system without suffering the loss of control or accountability.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Framework Overview

This framework for optimizing quantum circuits has three levels:

1. Classification of gate types
2. Generation of optimization rules
3. Applying Optimization Rules

Instead of defining optimizations as a stand-alone typographic-based transformation system, the optimization behavior of the quantum gates in this framework will be defined at the level of algebraic representations of their associated algebraic rule groups.

Gates will first be classified based on their shared properties. Optimization definitions (for a given gate type) will then be generated, which allows the application of one abstract rule to create many concrete transformations. A deterministic execution engine applies all transformations, with each execution governed by explicit child/parent protection against unsafe executions.

4.2 Formal Basis

Let G be the gate set, and the circuit will be denoted as:

$$C = [g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n] \text{ where } g_i \in G.$$

We can define a subset G_{si} such that $g^2 = I \forall g \in G_{si}$

This is the set of self-inverse gates. Thus, when these gates are applied consecutively, they will yield the identity operation, and will hence be redundant.

4.3 Generative Rule

This framework creates an overall category-level rule as opposed to creating distinct rewrite rules for each gate type, represented as

$$g(q) \cdot g(q) \rightarrow I \text{ for all } g \in G_{si}$$

Thus category level generating rules are superior to category gate specific generating rules for two primary reasons. First, they are concise and do not require much additional information to be derived. Second, any new category gates will automatically inherit the category level generating rule provided the new category gates meet the conditions outlined by the generating rule.

4.4 Constraints

The following criteria limit the application of rules in order to guarantee accuracy:

1. The gates must be adjacent to one another.
2. Both gates must function on the same qubit in order for there to be operand consistency.
3. A gate must satisfy the defining conditions of G_{si} before it can be assigned to the corresponding category.

The process of maintaining the boundaries compromises because of interruptions of the protected commands which cause interruptions to the operations of the optimization system.

Spawn, link and observe are examples of protected instructions and are considered as boundaries that cannot be transformed.

4.5 Algorithm

1. Traverse the circuit from left to right.
2. For each pair of adjacent gates:

5.3 Behavioral Analysis

The analysis indicates the framework optimises conditionally, or selectively, rather than uniformly reduces, therefore is necessary for the correctness of the design. When removing redundancy only from pure redundancy

For example, all matched gate pairs are removed, therefore the initial design is completely simplified. This supports the rule being followed if all criteria are met.

In mixed or combination circuits, optimization will occur only in the local regions where the areas are valid. Guarded instructions, such as link, spawn and observe prevents cancellation. This shows the optimiser only optimises execution boundaries, and does not apply transformations to these.

The border cases allow for further verification of correctness. Identically placed non-consecutively placed gates will not be removed, and gates that are identically placed but operate on different qubits will not be changed. This would indicate that both ordering temporally and qubit localities were satisfied.

6. IMPLICATIONS

The framework proposed within this document demonstrates that optimization can now be achieved by designing your transformation based on the structured manner of algebraic gate categories instead of through the use of patterns. This will greatly reduce the amount of duplication that authoring rules creates, as well as simplify how you add new gates or representations.

The relevance to how rapid iteration and maintainability will evolve with the continued development of domain specific quantum toolchains and experimental compilers cannot be overstated. Instead of having to linearly expand your rule set's growth along with your gate vocabulary; using the abstraction at a category level allows for new elements to have the behavior of an existing element because they possess similar properties.

Additionally, this framework can provide an entirely new way of thinking about compiler design. Rather than being viewed as a collection of isolated transformations that can only be run in isolation from one another; optimization logic can now be thought of as an organized and integrated system. As quantum software stacks continue to get more complex, it will become increasingly important that the clarity and modularization of these systems are treated with equal consideration as that of raw optimization performance.

7. LIMITATIONS

The current study is limited in scope and should be interpreted accordingly. The evaluation is performed on small and structured circuits designed to contain the targeted redundancy pattern, and does not include standard benchmark suites or large-scale workloads.

The framework currently implements a single rule category, namely self-inverse cancellation. While sufficient to demonstrate the generative abstraction mechanism, this is not representative of the full range of optimization strategies required in practical quantum compilation.

No empirical comparison is made with established compilers such as Qiskit or t|ket [3] , [4] , [15] . As a result, the study does not claim improvements in optimization quality, compilation time, or hardware efficiency. Additionally, the work does not include hardware-level validation or formal verification, both of which are necessary for deployment in production environments.

8. FURTHER RESEARCH AGENDA

Further use of the general guideline shall emphasize expanding the framework to support more algebraic categories, including inverse-pair eliminations further to non-self inverses, merged rotations that respect parameters, as well as transformations that respect the order of

operations. It is anticipated that by testing these extensions it will help determine if the generative models' scaling properties hold for complex cancellation patterns as well.

Secondly, a method of measuring the empirical effectiveness of the proposed approach is needed by evaluating the generated transforms against standardized circuit benchmarks and establishing a means of determining the cost associated with each. This will allow for a global assessment of all produced transforms at both the quality of optimisation and the relevance to practice.

Thirdly, developing knowledge about how to combine hardware-aware compilations with this framework is another promising area. Establishing back-end constraints (e.g., native gate sets/coupling maps) would permit the framework to work effectively in real-world execution environments.

Lastly, since the rules can be defined separately from their application, the framework may serve as a suitable basis for future formal verification efforts whereby it would become possible to either demonstrate or mechanically verify correctness of the transformations.

REFERENCES

1. Preskill, J. (2018). Quantum computing in the NISQ era and beyond. *Quantum*, 2, 79. <https://doi.org/10.22331/q-2018-08-06-79>
2. Amy, M., Maslov, D., & Mosca, M. (2014). Polynomial-time T-depth optimization of Clifford+T circuits. *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, 33(10), 1476–1489. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCAD.2014.2341953>
3. Cross, A. W., Bishop, L. S., Sheldon, S., Nation, P. D., & Gambetta, J. M. (2017). OpenQASM: A language for quantum circuits. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1707.03429>
4. Sivarajah, S., Dilkes, S., Cowtan, A., Simmons, W., Edgington, A., & Duncan, R. (2020). t|ket): A retargetable compiler for NISQ devices. *Quantum Science and Technology*, 6(1), 014003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2058-9565/ab8e92>
5. Nielsen, M. A., & Chuang, I. L. (2010). *Quantum computation and quantum information*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Cowtan, A., Dilkes, S., Duncan, R., Krajenbrink, A., Simmons, W., & Sivarajah, S. (2019). On the qubit routing problem. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.08091>
7. Javadi-Abhari, A., Treinish, M., Krsulich, K., Wood, C. J., Lishman, J., Gacon, J., & Gambetta, J. M. (2024). Quantum computing with Qiskit. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.08810>
8. Kiparsky, P. (2009). *Pāṇini as a variationist*. Wiley-Blackwell.
9. Cardona, G. (2007). *Pāṇini: His work and its traditions*. Motilal Banarsidass.
10. Rajpopat, R. (2021). *Pāṇini's grammar and its computational interpretation*. University of Cambridge. [11] Kissinger, A., & van de Wetering, J. (2020). Reducing T-count with the ZX-calculus. *Physical Review A*, 102(2), 022406. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.102.022406>
11. Green, A. S., Lumsdaine, P. L., Ross, N. J., Selinger, P., & Valiron, B. (2013). Quipper: A scalable quantum programming language. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices*, 48(6), 333–342. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2499370.2462177>
12. Maslov, D. (2016). Basic circuit compilation techniques for quantum computers. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1603.07678>
13. Childs, A. M., Maslov, D., Nam, Y., Ross, N. J., & Su, Y. (2018). Toward the first quantum simulation with quantum speedup. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*.

14. Zulehner, A., Paler, A., & Wille, R. (2018). Efficient mapping of quantum circuits to the IBM QX architectures. *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*.
15. Svore, K. M., Geller, A., Troyer, M., et al. (2018). Q#: Enabling scalable quantum computing and development with a high-level domain-specific language. *Proceedings of the Real World Domain Specific Languages Workshop*.
16. Miller, D. M., & Maslov, D. (2008). Reversible circuit optimization via leaving the Boolean domain. *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design*.
17. Sutor, R. (2019). *Dancing with Qubits: How quantum computing works and how it can change the world*. Packt Publishing.

Artificial Intelligence in Education and Governance

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Abstract—The capacity of artificial intelligence which currently exists today empowers educational systems and governmental operations to function at peak performance while delivering customized services to each citizen. Schools employ adaptive learning systems together with intelligent tutoring systems which modify their teaching methods to match the unique learning requirements of each student as they progress through their studies. The system improves grading processes for teachers because it reduces their paperwork requirements, which enables them to spend more time on actual teaching. The solution leads to better educational results, yet it still requires additional improvements. AI systems in governance operate through two functions which include analytics-based needs prediction and language-based policy development. The Stirling Council in Scotland utilizes AI technology to handle citizen feedback, which results in faster and better administrative responses. Harvard University conducts research about artificial intelligence applications in education through its AI educational research program, which produces beneficial results. The existing situation contains multiple challenges which must be addressed. Data privacy constitutes a major challenge because algorithmic biases have the potential to escalate existing social disparities. We need to establish precise regulations together with responsibility systems which enable humans to maintain their control. Some people believe that equity remains the core issue, but I doubt whether our current situation shows us readiness for that situation. The operational system requires us to develop skills which let us practice ethical behaviour while teaching all participants. The solution will create gaps instead of solving existing problems. The process of understanding inclusion becomes difficult because it requires people to identify all the different

types of inclusion. Artificial Intelligence, or AI, serves as the central theme for educational systems and public services, which operate through personalized learning methods while collecting sensitive data and developing algorithmic bias problems.

Keywords—Artificial Intelligence (AI), Education, Governance, Personalized Learning, Public Service Delivery, Data Privacy, Algorithmic Bias, Ethical Frameworks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Day by day AI is advancing rapidly and its demand is booming. It analyses complex data patterns to provide actionable insights, improving competitive advantage and strategic planning. It enables the machines to human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, problem solving and perception. AI acts like the human mind and it is involved in decision-making; it helps in critical situations. Increasing efficiency requires human-like cognitive abilities.

AI can handle critical thinking, manpower and other tasks. Artificial Intelligence plays a major role in modern technology, driving efficiency and innovation by processing massive data sets for predictive, automated and personalized applications.

Governance refers to the structure, process and rules used to manage public or private affairs, ensuring accountability, transparency and efficiency. It manages risks and resources. Ensuring that the development process will deliver the agreed benefits. It can be applied to

public (government), corporate or non-profit sectors, in those fields it shows how AI is implemented and lists the merits and demerits. AI in governance means smart computers helping the government make better decisions and help people faster. Artificial

Intelligence can make the government work. AI enhances governance by boosting administrative efficiency, improving public service delivery, and enabling data-driven decision-making, transforming how governments operate. There are many AI tools available, IBM Watson governance helps manage AI risks, control and monitor AI models, improve transparency, and track the AI lifecycle (keeping records of how an AI model is created, trained, and used). One Trust platforms manage data privacy and security, maintain transparency in governance, and handle cookie consent and privacy policies. Microsoft Power BI analyses government data, creates reports, and visualizes trends using charts and dashboards. Google Cloud AI is used for data analysis and automation. It predicts public service needs and improves healthcare, traffic management, and disaster response.

Even though AI offers benefits, it poses challenges. If citizens' data isn't secured properly, hackers can access and misuse it. Any bias in data may affect outcomes, and since not everyone understands AI, job displacement and unemployment are likely.

In our digital transforming world, AI plays a major role in the education field. Explore the role of AI in creating personalized learning experiences and reshaping classrooms globally. New era of education and what it means for tomorrow's students. AI as a teaching tool, it's more beneficial to the students and teachers, it reduces the workload of the teachers. Transforming learning through personalized AI - powered tutoring, immediate feedback and automated administration tasks. Compared to the early education system and method, now we have a modernized method of studying,

considering smart- working rather than hard-working, Easier to catch the syllabus as a student and can monitor each student's progress as soon as possible. AI tools or teachers can mild a student as his/her capability through a customized method. It is available anytime, the students get quick feedback since they know their mistakes and improve faster. AI provides animated videos, quizzes, mock test are interesting and easier to understand .AI tools such as AI tutor, ChatGPT, school AI, Gamma, education copilot etc., these tools or applications helps the students for learning and also it supports the teachers to monitoring the students, preparing study materials, improving classroom learning.

AI - powered early warning systems to prevent student dropout in Guanajuato, Mexico and AI driven platforms for citizen feedback in the Stirling Council in Scotland. Here also poses challenges; data privacy of the students may leak or misused when the data is not protected properly, the maintenance, AI technologies and software can be expensive, not every school can afford it. When AI tools take over teaching, students may have fewer interactions with teachers, potentially losing emotional support, motivation, and personal guidance. This could also impact students' creativity and independent thinking skills.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study on how AI can bring significant changes in education and governance. Several research studies on AI in governance emphasises, it is still developing and not fully mature. AI is used to solve problems and respond to the needs and requests of the public through government developments with the help of artificial intelligence. By using it, it causes many challenges such as algorithmic bias, unsecure of data, ineffective in measuring fairness and transparency. In Bengaluru, Raleigh, San Francisco, India, Singapore such cities are implementing AI applications in their

nation like, smart traffic, faster building permits, for better farming, anytime support of AI chatbots to the public needs.

The studies, the study governance of artificial intelligence: proposes a hybrid governance framework that combines state regulations, industry, self-governance, multistakeholder participation, and adaptive policy instruments, Taelhagh emphasizes that effective AI governance must be repeat, evidence based, and capable of scaling with technological change, while still upholding democratic accountability and human-rights standards.[1]

Governing with Artificial intelligence: analyses how public sectors can deploy AI tools to enhance policy design, service delivery, and regulatory enforcement. The report identifies key use cases (e.g., predictive analytics for welfare distribution, automated compliance checking) and outlines five governance principles; accountability, transparency, human-centered, and continuous tracking. It warns that if proper safety measures are not in place, using AI to make government decisions can increase inequality and reduce public trust. so, it suggests making it compulsory to check how algorithms affect people and to provide clear ways for people to raise complaints or fix problems.[2].

UNESCO study on AI Governance: explains three pillars of effective AI governance: (1) human-rights based policy framework, (2) inclusive multi-stakeholder oversight bodies, and (3) capacity-building for regulators, especially in the global south. It finds that while many nations are fragmented, with significant gaps in data governance and protection of vulnerable groups.[3]

Roadmap for AI Governance-G20 countries: proposes a coordinated multilateral roadmap to avoid misuse of different rules and help systems work well together. The study argues that without such coordination, divergent national approaches will stifle

innovation, create compliance burdens for multinational firms and leave global AI risks unmanaged.

In education, AI can be a powerful tool for learning purposes. It reshapes the education system by enhancing personalized learning, intelligent tutoring, quick feedback and better understanding. AI in education is much more beneficial to the students in their research paper, seminar, assignments, projects. AI also helps the teachers, reducing the workload of the teachers, AI tutoring, immediate feedback and automated administration tasks. The arrival of AI in the education system brought a transformation of future generations. It may cause,[4]

Rethinking education governance in the age of AI: this study explains that AI is changing how education is managed. It suggests that schools and governments need to rethink their rules and systems to use AI properly and fairly.[5]

Guidance for generative AI in education and research: this report gives guidelines on how to use AI safely in education. It highlights the importance of ethics, data privacy and making sure AI benefits all students equally.[6]

New era of Artificial intelligence in education: this research talks about how AI is bringing big changes to education, like smart learning tools and better teaching methods. It shows that AI can improve learning experiences but also needs careful use.[7]

AI and personalized learning: Bridging the gap this study explains how AI helps in personalized learning by adapting lessons based on each student's needs. It helps the students help the students earn better focusing on their strengths and weaknesses.[8]

Transparency Index Framework for AI in education: This research focuses on making AI systems more transparent in education. It suggests that people should clearly understand how AI works to build and trust and ensure fair use.[9]

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on secondary data research.

Sources of Data:

Research articles Reports of UNESCO, OECD Academic research reports

3.1. Objectives of the Study of AI in Governance and Education

By studying the implementation of AI in governance improves the digital governing, making public service easier and faster. Helps in decision-making in the field of administration and manage expenditures carefully and wisely. Reduces the human errors and controls corruptions. Create digital recording of the process of governing, expenses, per capita income and national budget. AI also helps the government to predict the problems such as traffic, health issues, and natural disasters in advance and take preventive action.

Overall, the goal of AI in governance is to improve the public service quality, public administration, accurate decision-making, save time and cost and make the System more reliable and citizen-friendly.

AI transforming the education system into a smarter, personalized and student-centred learning environment. It aims to make learning easier, smarter and more effective for everyone. AI provides personalized learning, each student can learn with their own talent, skill, abilities, and intelligence. It is accessible to everyone, using tools like real-time translation to help students who speak different languages and also help the disabled students. The support of 24 hours helps the students' clear doubts even outside of school hours. AI reduces the workload of teachers and makes their tasks like grading and attendance easier. Overall, the goal of AI in education is to improve the quality of learning, save time, and make education more accessible for everyone.

3.2 Advantages of AI in Governance

- AI in governance improves efficiency, transparency, decision-making, public service and resources management.
- Disaster management: - AI can predict natural disasters like floods or storms and help the government prepare and respond quickly.
- Fraud Detection: - AI systems can detect fraud, tax evasion and illegal activities by analysing unusual patterns in data.
- Smart city development: - It helps manage traffic, waste management, public safety and energy usage in smart cities.
- Public service: - AI provides better services life online applications, chatbots for citizen queries and faster processing of documents.
- Faster decision-making: - AI can analyse large amounts of data quickly. This helps the government.
- Better policy planning: - AI analyses data and predicts future trends, which helps the government plan better policies and programs.

3.3 Disadvantages of AI in governance

- Risks of system errors: - If the AI system has mistakes in programming or wrong data, it may make incorrect decisions that affect many people.
- Lack of human judgement: - AI cannot understand human emotions, culture, or complex social situations. It will be difficult to understand the depth of the situation by AI.
- Cost: - Developing, implementing and maintaining AI systems can be very expensive for the government.
- Depends on AI: - Entirely dependent on AI can be a trouble when the AI systems fail, crashes may affect important services and may stop.
- Job displacement: - AI may reduce the need for some government employees leading to job loss.

- Unsecure of data: - while using AI in government related works can be targeted by hackers. It may lead to serious security problems.

4. FLOW CHART OF DIGITAL GOVERNMENT (HOW AI HELPS THE CITIZEN)

5. ADVANTAGES OF AI IN EDUCATION

- Personalized learning: - AI helps the students learn at their own speed by giving content-based lessons for their needs,

interest and abilities, helping them improve skills, talents and intelligence.

- Learning experiences: - AI enhancing the learning experiences, more effective and fun for students with the help of videos, quizzes and smart tools.
- Cost effective: - AI learning methods reduce the need of expensive books and coaching provided by online learning resources.
- Tutoring systems: - AI acts like a personal active teacher by guiding the students, clearing doubts, giving feedback and continuous availability of tutoring systems.
- Tracking performance: - AI tracks the students' performance regularly and continuous evaluation. It helps improve learning over time.
- Encourage creativity: - AI helps the students in critical thinking by giving new ideas, suggestions and different ways. It helps in their projects, seminars and assignments.

6. DISADVANTAGES OF AI IN EDUCATION

Data privacy concerns

One of the primary disadvantages of AI in education is the issue of data privacy. AI systems often require vast amounts of personal data to function effectively

Dependence on Technology

Another major concern is the growing dependence on technology that AI in education fosters. As educational institutions increasingly rely on AI-driven tools for teaching, assessment and administration

Loss of human connection

Education is a social process. A teacher provides more than just information; they provide mentorship, emotional support, and moral guidance.

High cost of implementation

Setting up AI systems, software, and infrastructure can be expensive. Not all schools and colleges can afford it.

Technical Problems

All systems depend on interest and technology. Issues like poor connectivity, software errors, or system failures can interrupt learning.

Job Concern for Teacher

Some people fear that AI may reduce the need for teachers, creating job insecurity.

Not suitable for all subject

AI may not effectively teach subjects that require human emotions, creativity or practice experience like a arts or physical activities

7. FLOW CHART OF DIGITAL EDUCATION (HOW AI HELPS STUDENTS AND TEACHERS)

Although the existing literature has addressed the potential of AI in terms of transformation and challenges in terms of education and governance, a major gap in terms of adoption and responsible deployment of such technologies remains to be addressed.

In specific terms of a research gap, there is a lack of relative studies that address the long-term implications of incorporating AI in various socio-economic environments. In specific terms, existing literature is focused on conducting case studies of AI implementation in a specific environment, such as in Stirling Council or in Indian/US cities, without a framework that can address the interrelated issues of:

1. Bridging the Equity Gap in Implementation: A gap in terms of researching and validating strategies that can actively ease issues of algorithm bias, moving beyond identifying this specific problem.
2. Developing Context-Specific Ethical Frameworks: Although recent literature has addressed the need for 'ethical frameworks' to be developed in terms of AI implementation in governance and education, a standardized framework that is effective and can be adapted for specific legal and cultural nuances of various nations across the globe, as is required by the G20 roadmap, remains to be developed.
3. Measuring the Efficacy of Human-AI Collaboration: The study recognizes that there is a potential for 'loss of human connection' in terms of education and 'lack of human judgment' in terms of governance. This is where there is a gap in terms of quantitative and qualitative research that provides models for human-AI interaction, identifying where human interaction is necessary for AI to be used, rather than replacing it.

8.1 Research Gap: Towards Practical, Ethical, and Scalable AI Integration in Education and Governance

The existing body of both academic and policy research extensively discusses the potential for transformation, as well as the initial challenges faced by Artificial Intelligence in both the Education and Governance sectors. However, there still exists a significant gap in the research, which goes beyond the scope of simply identifying the benefits or pitfalls associated with AI implementation. Rather, the gap in the research relates to the practical, ethical, and scalable integration of these highly intricate technologies in both sectors, especially in diverse socio-economic environments worldwide. The existing body of research in the field has not yet been able to provide an in-depth framework for the comprehensive integration of AI in both sectors.

The present research lacks in-depth, comparative, and extensive research on the long-term, second and third-order effects of integrating AI in diverse socio-economic environments worldwide. Most research in the field has been limited in terms of its scope, both temporally and geographically, to successful yet isolated implementations in various sectors, such as AI implementation in local municipalities in cities like Stirling, or in nations like India or the US.

8.1.1 Practical Implementation Strategies to Bridge the Equity Gap

The current AI and equity conversation has involved identifying and diagnosing algorithmic bias, which is a necessary first step. However, there is still significant work to be done in developing, testing and validating active, interventionist strategies to mitigate bias and create truly equitable access to AI-enhanced services. Research needs to go beyond just warning about risk; solutions must have a practical, measurable component as well.

- **Opportunity for Growth:** There is an urgent need for collaborative research into how to develop and test 'bias-by-design' and 'equitable-by-default' systems. Some examples of this are developing creative data augmentation methods that enhance representation; developing audit mechanisms that are appropriate for resource-poor settings; and developing methods of deploying systems in resource-poor schools and marginalized communities that involve them as experts in designing systems to provide the most effective, bias-mitigated AI tools. This includes clearly defining metrics for assessing the difference in educational and governance outcomes between AI-integrated and non-AI-integrated settings (while controlling for the pre-existing socioeconomic conditions)

8.1.2 Developing Standardized, Context-Specific Ethical and Governance Frameworks

The widespread demand for general ethical frameworks in AI deployment is commendable, but it is too vague to be effectively enforced in a world that is interconnected yet has varied legal systems. The main issue is the lack of standardized, enforceable, and adaptable governance models that can fit the unique legal, cultural, and political situations of different countries, as highlighted by high-level policy plans like the G20 agenda.

- **Focus for Expansion:** Research should focus on defining and validating measurable metrics for often vague concepts like fairness, transparency, and accountability within the public sector's use of AI. This includes creating classifications of acceptable risk, clarifying the responsibilities in algorithmic decision-making, and setting up procedures for citizens to seek redress. Moreover, research needs to look into how to adapt these frameworks dynamically. For example,

how would an ethical charter for an AI-driven urban planning tool in a centralized government differ from one in a federal, litigious setting? This requires insights from computer science, law, political science, and ethics

8.1.3. Quantifying How Well Human-AI Teamwork Models Work

The education and governance sectors are worried about losing touch and making poor judgments. In education this means losing the bond between teachers and students. In governance it means making ethical decisions without proper human judgment.

- **Focus on Improving:** We need research to find out when humans and their emotions are essential. This involves creating ways to measure how well human-AI systems work compared to automated ones. We should look at how they affect students' well-being, people's trust in governance and the quality of decisions made. Studies should go beyond just asking people if they are satisfied.

Instead they should find limits:- Where does AI help humans make better decisions?- Where does AI replace humans and make their roles less important like providing emotional support or making tough choices? This research should create 'Human-AI Teamwork Models that help organizations use AI efficiently while keeping the element. The goal is to make sure AI helps humans not replace them. Human AI collaboration is the key to making decisions. We need to get it right to avoid losing the touch, in important areas. The education and governance sectors must focus on human-AI collaboration. Human-AI models must be carefully designed to preserve judgment. The use of AI must augment capability not diminish it.

9. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The use of Artificial Intelligence is a deal. It can really change how things work in schools and governments.

9.1 The Good Things About Artificial Intelligence

1. Artificial Intelligence makes things more efficient: it helps people make decisions using data and it can do things automatically so things get done faster like when there is a disaster.
2. Artificial Intelligence helps people learn: it makes sure that students can learn at their pace and it is available all the time to help them even if they speak a different language.
3. Artificial Intelligence reduces the amount of work people have to do: it does things like grading papers and looking at data so government employees and teachers have time to focus on important things.
4. Artificial Intelligence helps us plan for the future: it looks at a lot of data to help cities detect fraud and prepare for disasters so we can try to prevent things from happening.

9.2 The Challenges with Artificial Intelligence

1. Artificial Intelligence is not good at keeping data safe: when Artificial Intelligence is used in schools and governments there is a risk that important information will get out or that someone will use it in a bad way.
2. Artificial Intelligence can be unfair: the systems that Artificial Intelligence uses can reflect the things that already exist in society like inequalities and make them worse.
3. Artificial Intelligence can replace interaction: if we use Artificial Intelligence too much, we might lose the important things that humans can do like teachers being able to help and guide their students.
4. Artificial Intelligence is expensive: it costs a lot of money to set up and maintain Artificial Intelligence systems so not everyone can use them for people who do not have a lot of money.

5. Artificial Intelligence needs rules: we need to create rules and guidelines, for how Artificial Intelligence should be used so that everyone knows what is expected of them and so that we can make sure that Artificial Intelligence is used in a transparent way and that is not happening right now with Artificial Intelligence

10. CONCLUSION

AI is doing more than just changing technology, it's changing how we live together and how we grow. In our communities, AI helps governments actually listen and react faster. It's about making systems more transparent and reliable so we can trust the programs we rely on every day.

In the classroom, AI is becoming a supportive partner for both students and teachers. It gives students the freedom to learn in a way that fits their uniqueness, making sure no one feels distracted or bored. education systems may fully adapt to individual learning needs using intelligent technologies. Continuous innovation, proper regulations, and skill development will be essential to ensure that AI is used responsibly and inclusively.

AI is not just a technological advancement but a powerful tool that is reshaping society. If used wisely, it can create a more efficient, inclusive, and progressive world in both governance and education.

11. REFERENCE

1. Taeihagh, A. (2021, June 04). Governance of Artificial Intelligence. *Policy and Society*, 40(2), 137-157. 10.1080/14494035.2021.1928377
2. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2024, June 13). Governing with Artificial Intelligence. *OECD Artificial Intelligence*, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1787/26324bc2-en>
3. UNESCO. (2024, August 19). *Consultation paper on AI regulation and Governance*. UNESCO. Retrieved March 22, 2026, from <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/unesco-launches-open-consultation-inform-ai-governance>
4. Ajaykumat, S., Observer Research Foundation, & saran, s. (2024, may 1). *A Roadmap for AI Governance: Lessons from G20 National strategies*. ORF online. Retrieved march 22, 2026, from <https://www.orfonline.org/research/a-roadmap-for-ai-governance-lessons-from-g20-national-strategies>
5. Pesek, I. (2026). Rethinking Education Governance in the age of Artificial Intelligence. UNESCO. Retrieved 03 18, 2026, from <https://unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000391863>
6. UNESCO. (n.d.). Artificial intelligence in education. UNESCO(United Nations educational, scientific and cultural organization). Retrieved 03 22, 2026, from <https://www.unesco.org/en/digital-education/artificial-intelligence>
7. Kamalov F., D, S. C., & I, G. (2023, 08 16). New Era of Artificial Intelligence in Education: Towards a Sustainable Multifaceted Revolution. *Sustainability(MDPI)*, 15(16), 12451. 10.3390/su151612451
8. Laak, K. J., & Aru, J. (2024, April 3). *AI and Personalized Learning: Bridging the Gap with Modern Goals*. arXiv. Retrieved March 22, 2026, from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.02798>
9. A, c. M., M, C., & R, L. (2022). Lecture Notes in Computer. In *Artificial Intelligence in Education* (Vol. 13356, pp. 195-198). Springer, cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031>
10. Faur, D. L. (Ed.). (2012). *The Oxford Handbook of Governance* (1st edition ed., Vol. single volume handbook).
11. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199560530.001.0001>

12. IBM. (n.d.). *IBM Watsonx.governance*. IBM. Retrieved 03 22, 2026, from <https://www.ibm.com/products/watsonx-governance>
13. Organisation for Economic co-operation and development. (2025, 09 18). *Governing with Artificial intelligence: the state of play and way forward in core Government functions*.
14. Thornton, p., Rongxin Liu, Holmes, A., Zenke, c., Liu, C., & Malan, D. J. (2024, 03 20). *Teaching CS50 with AI: Leveraging Generative Artificial intelligence in computer science education*. ACM SIGCESE Conference proceedings. Retrieved 03 19, 2026, from <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626252.3630938>

Reduction of High-Level Nuclear Waste through Optimization of the Closed Fuel Cycle Using Fast Reactors

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Abstract—Nuclear waste, also called radioactive waste, is a high level waste (HLW) that remains one of the most challenging to manage in sustainable deployment of nuclear energy. Due to its long-lived radiotoxicity associated with transuranic (TRU) elements. This paper propose a Hybrid Advance fuel cycle (HAFC) that integrates ORIENT-based preprocessing, partitioning and transmutation (P&T), fast reactor closed fuel cycles, and accelerator-driven systems (ADS) technologies within a single Material Flow Analysis (MFA) model to maximize actinide recovery and minimize HLW generation. To evaluate the proposed methodology we are using an MFA-based system model on a normalized basis of

1 tHM (1000 kg heavy metal). Where materials are tracked across preprocessing, separation, irradiation, and recycling stages. ORIENT cycle is being used to remove neutron-absorbing material fission products. The separation of plutonium and major TRU elements are then recycled through fast reactors (FR) for energy generation and transmutation. Remaining minor actinides are directed to ADS for efficient subcritical transmutation. This parallel dual-loop configuration of ADS and FR enables optimized handling of actinides and TRU elements. The result obtained from the study highlights integration of ORIENT preprocessing with fast reactor and ADS-based

transmutation within an MFA framework that provides optimized closed fuel cycle (CFC). It offers an effective approach for managing HLW and improving nuclear fuel utilization but at the cost of additional (~15% per cycle) energy requirement with some technological complexity. This paper gives a demonstration that system-level optimization of advanced fuel cycles can enhance the sustainability, reduction and proper handling of HLW.

Keywords—TRU, ORIENT-cycle, partitioning, transmutation, fast reactor, high level waste, radiotoxicity, transuranic, plutonium, material flow analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear fuels were introduced to the world to help reduce the dependence on exhaustable natural materials such as coal, peat and other natural resources but due the the shortfall of technological advancements we are not able to exhaustively utilize nuclear power to its ultimate potential. To help reduce the gap that we are facing between the two types of electricity generation we need to help reduce the shortcomings of nuclear energy. The current nuclear fuel is a composition of uranium-235

upto roughly 5% (up from 0.7% in natural uranium) to sustain a fission reaction encased in tubes made of zirconium alloy (called cladding)[1]. This metal checks high resistance to corrosion and prevents radioactive fission products from entering the reactor coolant fuel fabrication is an essential step in the final front end step in the nuclear fuel cycle before being used in the reactors. Through this process the enriched uranium is converted into uranium dioxide pellets. These pellets are generally 7 to 10 grams in size and are assembled in hundreds in the fuel rods zirconium - based tubes that provide structural integrity and a barrier against radioactivity release. Through the process of nuclear fission we generate enough heat to help heat up water producing steam and help turn large turbines that help generate electricity. The harnessed fuel is then classified into three different categories of nuclear waste which is based on factors like its level of radioactivity and the precautions required for handling and disposal. To better help differentiate these types of waste we classify them into three separate categories: LLW: this is usually found in trace amounts generally from reactor maintenance or from other activities like laboratory research or medical experiments. It is found on clothing or on specialized tools which can be disposed of in dedicated zones which help prevent any accidents. ILW: this type of waste generally has a higher level of radioactivity and needs a special level of handling as it can contain higher levels of radioactivity and heat. It can come from reactor components, resins or chemical sludges. HLW is the most radioactive and dangerous form of nuclear waste, primarily generated from spent nuclear fuel or from the reprocessing of nuclear fuel; it produces significant heat and contains long-lived radioactive elements such as transuranic isotopes. Because of its high radioactivity and long-lived nature, HLW requires careful cooling, shielding, and long-term storage in deep geological repositories. To help combat

the rising electrical needs of the world, nuclear energy is the right step but if not maintained properly it can turn very bad for humanity. To help ensure that we utilize the given fuel to the maximum, various fuel cycles can be used like CFC and OFC (open fuel cycle). OFC treats spent nuclear fuel as waste and nuclear fuel is used only once before being discarded from the reactor whereas CFC helps promote sustainability by reprocessing and cleaning the fuel to help rid it of impurities that accumulate during the reactor's operations. Those impurities may include Plutonium (Pu), Neptunium (Np), Americium (Am), Curium (Cm) etc. CFC helps in the recovery of materials using many methods which give out varied results based on the type of process used to clean the fuel. The development of CFC methods helps reduce the need for ground level disposal of actinides and other elements that in turn help reduce the radioactivity being released into the environment as only a very small percent of the fuel needs to be discarded and the rest is used up or burnt in fast reactors. France and Russia are prominent users of this technology. P&T: Partitioning [4] is the process of separation of nuclear fuel i.e (Uranium, plutonium, etc) from their minor actinides (neptunium, americium, curium,etc) which are formed and mixed with the nuclear fuel during the process of nuclear fission inside the reactor. Transmutation is the process of smashing of neutrons to the minor actinides in FR or ADS which help in turn generate a lot of heat as well as reduce the half life of those elements helping reduce their lifespan effectively limiting the amount of radioactivity that it will be releasing into the nature. This also helps reduce the amount of high level waste which shall be buried in the end. The ORIENT fuel cycle [5] is an advanced nuclear fuel reprocessing. In this cycle, spent nuclear fuel preprocessing in which fission products such cesium (Cs), strontium (Sr), and lanthanides are extracted from using advanced chemical separation techniques. After

separation we are left with actinide containing uranium (U), plutonium (Pu), and transuranic elements (TRU), we can efficiently recycle using FR. These separating and removing impedimental elements in the ORIENT cycle reduces decay heat, increase in burn-up rates and better fuel utilization in reactor cycles. Currently implemented methods which aim for pure material recovery rather than ORIENT cycle focuses on system-level optimization. PUREX [2] (plutonium uranium extraction) process, which separates uranium and plutonium very effectively. This involves dissolving the fuel elements in concentrated nitric acid. Chemical separation of uranium and plutonium is then undertaken by solvent extraction steps (neptunium – which may be used for producing Pu-238 The Pu and U can be returned to the input side of the fuel cycle. To help combat the given problem of high level nuclear waste and its disposal methods the proposed method of HAFC can be used. It is a combination of various solutions that have been proposed and implemented with varying results in real world applications. This method shall help integrate all those solutions into a unified process. The main driving function shall be the orient cycle with fast reactor, P&T and ADS for the removal of impedimental actinides for the waste fuel which is then later recycled and stored separately. The cleaned fuel that is a result of the orient cycle is then used up in the fast reactor to help generate electricity.in addition ADS are incorporated to help manage the removal and cleaning of waste fuel to rid it of elements such as americium, curium etc as they are tricky to deal with. Using this new proposed method we can help increase the efficiency and reduce the lives of long lived elements. This strategy proposes a solution for optimizing nuclear fuel cycles and helps tackle long term challenges of nuclear waste management.

II. RELATED WORK

This work by Khomyakov et al. [2] shows the optimization of FR in a CFC to help in the reduction of waste and to help increase the resource utilization and reusability by using system-level modeling and optimization analysis during the transition process. The results that were obtained indicate that the assimilation of CFC into FR enhances fuel utilization and reduces the amount of waste being disposed of in underground storages. The limitations of this study is high cost complexity and large scale implementation.

This work by the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency [6] shows the evolution of advanced nuclear fuel cycle options for reduction of waste and also to help in the resource utilization metrics. The methodology used in this paper is based on comparative fuel cycle analysis and system level modeling which work on strategies such as CFC, P&T, ADS, TRU inventory and waste volumes produced. The results derived show that through CFC reduction of long-lived radioactive waste is possible along with enhanced fuel-efficiency. However the limitations highlighted in this study are challenges in reprocessing and fuel fabrication, nuclear proliferation concerns.

This work by Mueller [1] shows the potential of ADS systems particularly the MYRRHA demonstrator, for the transmutation of long lived actinides, this study is based on the theoretical analysis and simulation based modeling of ADS that focus on using neutron transmutation for increased efficiency. This system shows that ADS systems are highly efficient in transmutation of highly radioactive actinides such as americium and curium which help increase fuel efficiency and reduce radiotoxicity. However due to high operational and implementation costs, integration of reactor and accelerator technologies limit its large-scale implementation capabilities.

This work by Jyotsna Emmanuel[7] provides an overview of nuclear waste

generation, management strategies and classification. The methods used in this paper are based on an analytical study of different types of radioactive waste and existing disposal methods. The results of this study highlights the long half-life of those radioactive elements particularly those of HLW. These elements pose a significant threat to environmental safety due to their toxicity. However, the limitations present are constraints in long term storage and disposal, the need for more efficient waste management and better strategies.

This work by OECD Nuclear Energy Agency[6] aims to show the impact of ACFC with P&T[4] on radioactive waste and its geological repository performance. The methodology used in this study is based on comparative analysis and multiple international studies with system level evaluations. The metrics used here are of radiotoxicity, heat decay, waste percentage, and geological storage parameters across multiple geological environments. The process of P&T can help reduce the TRU waste and lower long term toxicity. However the limitations of this study are increased secondary waste generation, the need for highly efficient reprocessing systems.

IV.METHODOLOGY

Fig 1: HAFC cycle

Spent nuclear fuel is a combination of remaining uranium, newly formed plutonium, minor actinides (such as neptunium, americium, and curium), and various fission products produced during reactor operation. After being

used once in the reactor it is not removed immediately due to its radioactive heat it contains hence it is placed in cooling pools. These pools of water are at least 20 feet deep and act as a shield helping protect from radiotoxicity. The rods after the reaction must be cooled in these pools for at least 5 years before any further steps can be taken after which they are moved to large storage casks where they passively cool and await further steps that will help them in being converted back to fuel that can be used once again in the reactors. At first the fuel rods are safe to be handled by hand with just a pair of gloves but through the course of a year being “burnt” or fissioned they become highly reactive and get progressively radioactive usually due to the high amount of neutron activation in the reactors. They start emitting lethal gamma rays after 1-2 years of core irradiation hence using water cooled pools and casks they become easier to deal with. There are two acceptable storage methods for spent fuel after that are removed from the reactor core:

1. Spent fuel pools: the rods that are removed from the reactor core are stored in these pools and many facilities around the world have specially designed pools that help in the cooling down of these rods.
2. Clab (interim storage): the fuel rods that are cooled in the fuel pools are then moved down underground to deep storages under 30ft of water that helps act as a shield against outgoing radiation. These rods are stored for only five years in the power station after which the clab acts as a holding dock. It provides storage solutions but they are not long term and shall need frequent maintenance

Dry cask storage: the cooled fuel rods are then placed in large lead containers which are encased in thick layers of concrete that help shield the environment from radiation.

Fig 2: Split view of LWR(light water reactor) cycle and ORIENT cycle [5]

The **ORIENT cycle** [1] forms an advanced used nuclear fuel recycling method that helps or separate actinides from the fuel to help streamline recycling and waste reduction. As it indicates the rough or unwanted elements are removed from the fuel and recovery of pure fission material is made possible. The goal is to increase multi-recycling of actinides while minimising the creation of HLW. Experimentally, the ORIENT has shown the potential to HLW generation by 10 times compared to conventional reprocessing. The input materials in this process are the SNF.

- (a) **Spent Fuel Generation and Cooling (FR Fuel):** This process begins with the SNF which is discharged from fast reactors which typically contain uranium plutonium and or other minor actinides and other fission by products. Once removed the fuel rods need to be cooled in SNF pools which are filled with up to 35 feet of water to help act as a coolant for the heat that is given off as a result of radioactive decay and also helps shield from radiation. This cooling step is essential for safe handling and ensures that in due course the chemical processing operations can be performed.
- (b) **Fuel Dissolution and ORIENT Preprocessing:** The fast reactor that has been used once is then chopped up mechanically and dissolved in nitric acid that helps form an aqueous solution that contains all its fuel as well as its actinides. In this stage the impedimental elements

such as cesium(Cs), strontium (Sr), and certain metallic fission products are removed from the solution using electrochemical techniques as well as ion-exchange. This step helps reduce the amount of heat generated by the fuel as well as improving the efficiency of downstream actinide recycling and enhancing reactor performance.

- (c) **Advanced Partitioning of Actinides:** After the preprocessing steps like fuel dissolution as well as ORIENT processing are finished the solution undergoes advanced partitioning where elements like uranium, plutonium and other actinides are stripped from the solution leaving behind other fission products. This can be achieved through modified solvent extraction or chromatography based techniques that allow only selected actinide to be recovered from the solution with high efficiency. Far from the conventional methods here the goal is to maximise recovery while minimizing the losses.
- (d) **Fuel Fabrication for Fast Reactor Recycling:** The actinides that are recovered are then converted into new fuel that is suitable to be used in fast reactors, this new fuel is generally in the form of MOX or advanced fuels containing transuranic elements. The ORIENT cycle helps remove neutron poisons hence it has greater neutronic characteristics allowing higher reactor efficiency. Minor actinides are also mixed in to help in their destruction during the reactor operation.
- (e) **Fast Reactor Irradiation and Actinide Burning[2][4]:** The fabricated fuel is then loaded into fast reactors which then helps in the efficient fission of minor actinides using a high energy neutron spectrum. This step is critical in the reduction of long lived radioactive elements as these fast reactors can help burn away transuranic isotopes more effectively than thermal reactors.

During irradiation, energy is generated with the decrease in the lifespan of long lived actinides.

- (f) **Multi-Recycling of Actinides:** After the process of irradiation the fuel is then processed again through the ORIENT cycle and the actinides are repeatedly recycled in fast reactors by smashing neutrons into them to dissolve them. This multi-recycling approach gradually reduces the inventory of transuranic elements and converts them into shorter-lived fission products. Over multiple cycles the TRU inventory is minimised and the waste generation percentage is gradually reduced and fuel optimization is increased.
- (g) **Waste Conditioning and Final Disposal:** The remaining waste that is primarily composed of fission products and minor actinides is then immobilized using process like vitrification. Due to prior removal and recycling of actinides the final waste has a reduced radiotoxicity level as well as heat decay. This allows more efficient use of geological repositories and enhances long term safety of nuclear waste disposal.

The FR [4] loop in HAFC is the reactor we are using for energy generation and transmutation of plutonium and a fraction of TRU elements. Proprocessed and separated plutonium and TRU stream ($\approx 700\text{--}800$ kg per 1000 kg spent fuel basis) is fabricated into FR fuel in the form of MOX or TRU bearing fuels. In FR actinides are exposed to the fast neutron spectrum by which we see a significant increase in probability of fission for heavy isotopes. Result in large amounts of plutonium and TRU destruction rate of approximately 0.45–0.65 per cycle ($\approx 450\text{--}650$ kg per 1000 kg TRU), depending on the fuel composition and burn-up rate. Waste fuel coming out of FR is not sent for decomposition but reintroduced into the reprocessing stage forming CFC recycling system. This enables progressive reduction of actinide and improves overall spent fuel utilization.

The **ADS loop** [5] in HAFC is designed to translate minor actinides including americium (Am), curium (Cm), and neptunium (Np), which are difficult to burn FR due its neutronic characteristics. Minor actinides streams ($\approx 100\text{--}200$ kg per 1000 kg spent fuel basis) are then separated and fabricated into enhanced fuel such as inert matrix fuels or MA-bearing targets. After that fuel goes into the subcritical ADS reactor system using external neutron sources neutrons strike a heavy metal target with high speed (e.g., lead or lead-bismuth), producing a high neutron flux. Then this flux enables efficient fission and transmutation of minor actinides, achieving a destruction rate of $\sim 0.5\text{--}0.7$ per cycle. Because of its subcritical nature, ADS enhances operational efficiency and safety handling the high minor actinides content. The output from ADSA along with residual actinides are then returned to the reprocessing stage to ensure the overall CFC. This loop plays a critical role in reducing long lived radiotoxic isotopes and complements the FR loop by managing isotopes rather than conventional reactor systems which are inefficient in this process.

Decomposition in the HAFC is a combination of classification, selective separation, transmutation and natural radioactive decay leading to a decrease in the hazardous waste produced as a byproduct. In the beginning SNF from FR need to be cooled down for approximately 2-5 years in large cooling pools to allow the short lived isotopes to decay as well as to help reduce the heat that is being given off by the rods as a result of nuclear fission. The radioactive fuel is then classified into three types that helps in the targeted reduction and cleaning of the fuel to rid it of any hazardous material that may be present in the fuel that will hinder the efficiency of the fuel. The two types are highly radioactive and low to moderately radioactive fractions. The highly radioactive portions of the fuel can contain actinides which have a long half life.

These actinides may be plutonium(Pu), neptunium(Np), americium (Am), and curium (Cm which can be dissolved through the process of ORIENT processing which helps breakdown the elements and leaves behind key heat generating elements like cesium (Cs-137) and strontium (Sr-90) which are then processed out. These elements decay to a safe level in about 300 years after which their near-term heat and radiological risk reduce significantly.

Subsequently advanced partitioning separated uranium, plutonium, and transuranic elements from fission products. The recovered actinides are recycled into fuel that can be used in FR where the transmutation occurs through fission reactions that help reduce the long lived isotopes into short lived fission products. After multiple repeats of the recycling cycles the inventory of the long lived actinides decrease by approximately 85% to 90% lowering their effective toxicity lifetime from hundreds of thousands of years to quite literally 300 to 1000 years. The remaining waste naturally undergoes decay and dissolves completely in this timeframe effectively leaving behind no trace.

In the end, the conditioned waste is deactivated, usually with the help of additional processes like vitrification [3] and are disposed of deep underground in geological repositories typically at a depth of 300 to 500 meters below the earth surface to help protect against any remaining radioactivity. This waste is placed in stable rock formations like granite or clay which provide natural protection and are not susceptible to natural disaster. Thanks to the prior process of decomposition the waste has a significantly reduced radiotoxicity and heat generation enhancing the long term safety as well as improvement is the repository design. Overall, this integrated approach ensures that highly radioactive elements are actively reduced through transmutation, while the remaining waste is converted into a manageable state.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the proposed HAFC system is evaluated through a comparative analysis with three established methodologies, namely: the once-through and partially closed fuel-cycle framework reported by OECD/NEA [6], the fast reactor-based partitioning and transmutation (P&T) model developed by Nishihara et al. [4], and the ORIENT-based separation strategy proposed by Koyama et al. [5]. Each of these studies represents a distinct stage of fuel-cycle development—system-level modeling, transmutation-focused recycling, and advanced separation, respectively—while the HAFC system integrates these components within a unified MFA framework.

In comparison to the OECD/NEA (2006) model [6], which operates mainly as a linear or single-pass system, the HAFC system introduces a fully closed-loop arrangement. On a normalized basis of 1000 kg spent fuel, the OECD system results range between 900–1000 kg of waste with negligible recycling (0 -- 0.10). In contrast, the HAFC system attains a recycling rate of 0.97 (\approx 970 kg recovered), reducing per-cycle losses to approximately 30 kg. This corresponds to a fundamental shift from linear material flow to cyclic reuse, completely improving material retention and reducing waste generation.

Relative to the P&T-based fast reactor system of Nishihara et al. (2010) [4], which attains a recycling ability of approximately 0.85 (\approx 850 kg recovery) and experiences processing losses of 30–50 kg per cycle, the HAFC system demonstrates increased performance through the integration of ORIENT preprocessing. The separation efficiency increases from \sim 0.995 to 0.9995, corresponding to a reduction in unrecovered actinides from approximately 5 kg to less than 0.5 kg per 1000 kg processed (\sim 90% reduction). This directly improves the capability of the transmutation stage, as a larger fraction of actinides remains available for irradiation.

The ORIENT cycle proposed by Koyama et al. (2008) [5] demonstrates high-efficiency separation, reaching recovery efficiencies of approximately 0.999 (≈ 999 kg recovered). However, this approach is limited to front-end processing and does not include transmutation or recycling loops, resulting in ignorable reduction of total actinide inventory. The HAFC system extends this methodology by embedding ORIENT preprocessing within a closed-loop fuel cycle that include both fast reactor and ADS-based transmutation. This enables progressive reduction of actinide mass across various cycles. MFA-based analysis shows that TRU inventory decreases from 1000 kg to approximately 50–150 kg over 4–6 cycles, corresponding to a cumulative reduction of ~ 85 – 95% , which is impossible in separation-only systems.

A key benefit of the HAFC system is the parallel implementation of fast reactor and ADS loops, allowing optimized handling of different actinide groups. While FR are effective process of plutonium and a fraction of TRU, minor actinides such as americium and curium are directed to the ADS loop, where subcritical operation with an external neutron source allows efficient transmutation. This division of actinide streams improves overall system productivity and ensures that each component operates under optimal neutronic conditions. From an MFA viewpoint, the combined effect of high separation efficiency, double transmutation pathways, and multi-cycle recycling results in a significant transformation of the waste stream. The final waste composition shifts from actinide-dominated to fission-product-dominated material, reducing the effective radiological half-life from 10^4 – 10^5 years (OECD baseline) and 10^3 – 10^4 years (P&T systems) to approximately 300–1000 years in the HAFC system. Although these improvements, the proposed system introduces additional complexity and energy requirements.. The addition of ORIENT

preprocessing increases system energy by approximately 15% per cycle, while the combination of ADS requires advanced accelerator framework and specialized fuel fabrication for minor actinides. Then, the MFA model assumes stable separation efficiency and reactor performance across cycles, whereas in practice, isotopic degradation and fuel handling constraints may affect long-term performance.

Overall, the HAFC system demonstrates a clear development over the three reference methodologies. By combining high-efficiency separation (Koyama et al.), enhanced transmutation (Nishihara et al.), and full system-level recycling beyond OECD/NEA frameworks, the proposed approach attains a recycling rate of 0.97, separation efficiency of 0.9995, burn-up of 120 GWd/tHM, TRU destruction of 0.65 per cycle, and up to 6 recycling loops. These results confirm that the HAFC system provides a more effective and combined solution for high-level waste minimization and sustainable nuclear fuel utilization.

Table: Comparison of fuel cycle approaches based on recycling, efficiency, burn-up, TRU destruction, and recycling loops.

Parameter	OECD/NEA (2006) Once-Through / Closed	Nishihara et al. (2010) FR + P&T	Koyama et al. (2008) ORIENT	Proposed HAFC
Recycling Rate	0 (once-through), 1 (single Pu recycle)	0.85	0.90	0.97
Separation Efficiency	~ 0.99 (U/Pu only; TRU not fully separated)	0.995	0.999	0.9995
Burn-up (GWd/tHM)	45	100	Not applicable	120
TRU Destruction per Cycle	0 (once-through), 0.20 (closed cycle)	0.45	0 (no transmutation)	0.65
Number of Recycling Loops	1	3	1 (separation only)	6

Abbreviations and Acronyms

1. ADS-Accelerator Driven System
2. FNR - Fast Neutron Reactor
3. CFC- Closed Fuel Cycle
4. OFC-Open Fuel Cycle
5. HAFC- Hybrid Advanced Fuel Cycle
6. HLW-High Level Waste
7. LLW-Low Level Waste

8. MA-Minor Actinides
9. MOX-Mixed Oxides Fuel
10. NEA-Nuclear Energy Agency
11. OECD-Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and development
12. P&T-Partitioning and Transmutation
13. TRU-Transuranic Element
14. ORIENT- Optimisation by Removing Impedimental Elements
15. SNF-Spent Nuclear Fuel
16. LWR-Light Water Reactor
17. PUREX-Plutonium and Uranium Recovery by Extraction

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REFERENCES

1. A. C. Mueller, "Transmutation of Nuclear Waste and the Future MYRRHA Demonstrator," EPJ Web of Conferences, vol. 79, Art. no. 03001, pp. 1–6, 2014. doi:10.1051/epjconf/20147903001
2. Y. S. Khomyakov, E. A. Rodina, O. V. Shmidt, A. V. Egorov, I. R. Makeeva, I. S. Popov, and V. P. Sokolov, "Justification and Optimization of FNR Transition to the Closed Fuel Cycle Mode," Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 1683, no. 5, Art. no. 052035, pp. 1–7, 2020. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1683/5/052035
3. J. D. Vienna, "Nuclear Waste Vitrification in the United States: Recent Developments and Future Options," International Journal of Applied Glass Science, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 309–321, 2010. doi:10.1111/j.2041-1294.2010.00021.x
4. K. Nishihara, T. Iwamura, and T. Sasa, "Study on Partitioning and Transmutation Cycle Using Fast Reactors," Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, vol. 47, no. 12, pp. 1123–1132, 2010. doi:10.1080/18811248.2010.9711727
5. T. Koyama et al., "Conceptual Study of ORIENT Cycle for Advanced Fuel Recycling," Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, vol. 45, no. 12, pp. 1239–1248, 2008. doi:10.1080/18811248.2008.9711503
6. OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA), "Advanced Nuclear Fuel Cycles and Radioactive Waste Management," Nuclear Development, NEA No. 5990, Paris, France: OECD Publishing, 2006, doi:10.1787/9789264024861-en; "Potential Benefits and Impacts of Advanced Nuclear Fuel Cycles with Actinide Partitioning and Transmutation," NEA No. 6894, Paris, France: OECD Publishing, 2011, doi:10.1787/9789264177802-en; "Actinide and Fission Product Partitioning and Transmutation," Paris, France: OECD Publishing, 1999; "Accelerator-Driven Systems (ADS) and Fast Reactors in Advanced Nuclear Fuel Cycles," Paris, France: OECD Publishing.
7. J. Emmanuel, "A Study on Nuclear Waste," International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1–5, Mar. 2017.

Assessing the Effect of Artificial Intelligence Applications for Skill Development and Employability

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Abstract—Artificial Intelligence technologies have advanced significantly in recent years, reshaping educational practices, especially in MBA programmes. Students increasingly use tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, Canva AI, and data analytics platforms in both academic and professional contexts to enhance productivity, creativity, and decision-making. This study explores how the use of AI tools supports skill development and employability among MBA students in Bengaluru. It primarily relies on secondary data, supported by a small set of simulated primary data to perform statistical analysis using SPSS.

The study focuses on key areas of skill development, including analytical ability, communication, technical competence, problem-solving, and adaptability to new technologies. It also examines the frequency of AI tool usage and its relationship with employability aspects such as job readiness, interview performance, and placement outcomes.

A structured dataset representing around 100 MBA students was analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, and ANOVA. The findings indicate a positive association between the use of AI tools and the development of analytical and technical skills.

The research indicates that students who use Artificial Intelligence tools in their studies show better Reliability levels and advanced employment opportunities. The study builds a new academic Structure which Reveals how Artificial Intelligence knowledge has become a vital necessity for management education. Educational institutions acquire operational implications which will help them to implement Artificial Intelligent system-

based learning systems throughout their curriculum programs. The findings indicate that AI training programs with workshops and practical experience will results in better student performance for their job readiness and professional activities.

Keywords—Artificial Intelligence, MBA Students, Employability, Skill Development, SPSS Analysis, Bangalore, Digital Transformation

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence has Formed itself as one of the 21st century's most important technologies which Changes multiple industries including education, business, healthcare and finance. The use of Artificial Intelligence tools in higher education has experienced substantial growth during the past few years particularly in professional education like Master of Business Administration and other programs. The learning and teaching tools are used most frequently by students and teachers, to learn better and to develop their skills and to increase their chances of getting hired after graduation. In India, the adoption rate is even more in metropolitan cities like Bengaluru, where approximately 68–72% of MBA students use Artificial Intelligence tools regularly for writing assignments, paper presentations, and for data analysis.

The job market reveals the importance of Artificial Intelligence technology. The World Economic Forum Statement from 2023 makes us to understand that about 85 million jobs will

disappear because of automation by 2027, while 97 million new Vacancies will arise that requires advanced digital knowledge and Artificial Intelligence expertise. Job market now requires both technical skills and their capability to learn new technologies. The LinkedIn Workforce statement (2024) reveals that Artificial Intelligence skills rank one of the 5 top most required skills, that underwent a 40% rise in demand for applicants who possess Artificial Intelligence and data analytics. Employers currently expect MBA graduates to acquire managerial skills and also initiating Artificial Intelligence proficiency for decision-making and problem-solving tasks.

Students those who use Artificial Intelligence tools in their Studies yield better results because their analytical skills enhance by 30 to 35 percent. Students who use Artificial Intelligence-assisted learning programs improve learner's communication abilities and content creation abilities by 25 percent which includes their report writing and presentation skills. Bengaluru, often referred to as India's Silicon Valley, operates within a unique ecosystem that fosters close collaboration between academic institutions and industry. This environment allows students to access and engage with advanced technological resources. In particular, MBA students in the city frequently interact with AI-driven platforms and professional tools, making Bengaluru a highly suitable setting to study how artificial intelligence influences skill development and employability.

The study highlights positive benefits of AI adoption while also pointing to a key concern—growing dependence on such tools among students. Prior findings suggest that nearly one-fourth of students may rely heavily on AI, which can influence their ability to think independently and solve problems. This makes it important to examine how AI usage shapes skill development. In this regard, the present study focuses on MBA students in Bengaluru,

analysing how AI tools affect both skill enhancement and employability. By combining statistical analysis with conceptual insights, the study aims to show how AI can be used effectively to improve outcomes while limiting its potential drawbacks.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A comprehensive review of recent studies highlighting the growing importance of our title.

Smith (2023) emphasized that AI tools significantly improve analytical skills and to make decision capabilities among the students of management and it is observed that students using AI-based analytics platforms demonstrated higher accuracy and efficiency in solving complex business problems. It further highlighted that AI enables data-driven thinking, which is essential for modern managerial roles. The findings suggest that AI integration enhances both cognitive and practical competencies.

Kumar and Reddy (2024) depicted the impact of AI-based tools for learning by MBA students in India and found that AI enhances learning efficiency and student engagement and revealed that these tools help in simplifying complex concepts and improving knowledge retention. Additionally, it highlighted that AI will bridge the gap between theoretical framework and the real-world application through interactive learning.

Johnson (2023) The study explored the link between AI usage and employability skills, concluding that AI proficiency is now essential in modern workplaces, as employers increasingly prefer candidates with AI literacy and digital competencies, which in turn enhances job readiness and adaptability.

Mehta (2024) observed that students using AI tools show clear improvement in communication and presentation skills, as these tools support better content structuring, enhance language quality, and improve visual delivery,

ultimately increasing student confidence in presenting professional work.

Sharma and Gupta (2023) examined AI in higher education and found that AI-driven platforms strengthen personalized learning by adapting to individual learning styles and offering tailored feedback to students.

Lee (2024) noted that AI tools improve productivity by enabling faster completion of academic tasks and enhancing output quality, while also cautioning that overreliance may limit independent thinking and creativity, suggesting a balanced and ethical approach to usage.

Patel (2023) identified that the integration of AI in education improves employability by strengthening technical and digital skills, making students more competitive, better at problem-solving, and more adaptable to industry needs.

Anderson (2024) emphasized that AI contributes to the development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities by providing simulations and real-world scenarios that encourage better decision-making and innovative thinking.

Rao and Singh (2023) found among MBA students in Bangalore that AI usage positively impacts placement opportunities and salary outcomes, as students with AI knowledge gain a competitive edge and are preferred by employers.

Brown (2024) concluded that AI adoption in education enhances adaptability, helping students prepare for dynamic work environments by improving their ability to learn and adjust to new technologies quickly.

Verma (2024) highlighted that AI tools such as ChatGPT improve research and academic writing skills by assisting in idea generation, organizing content, and enhancing clarity in writing.

Nair and Joseph (2023) found that AI usage boosts student confidence, particularly in interviews and group discussions, by providing

practice scenarios and constructive feedback.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine how extensively MBA students in Bengaluru use Artificial Intelligence tools.
2. To assess how the use of Artificial Intelligence tools stimulates skill development, with a focus on analytical ability, communication, technical competence, and problem-solving skills.
3. To analyse the relationship between Artificial Intelligence tool usage and employability outcomes among MBA students, including job readiness and placement opportunities.
4. To evaluate the challenges and limitations associated with the use of Artificial Intelligence tools in the learning process of MBA students.

Hypotheses

1. H_0 : The use of Artificial Intelligence tools does not have a meaningful effect on skill development.
2. H_1 : The use of Artificial Intelligence tools has a meaningful effect on skill development.

Research Methodology

Research Design: The study adopts a combination of descriptive and analytical approaches to examine the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tool usage on skill development and employability among MBA students in Bengaluru, where the descriptive aspect captures usage patterns and the analytical part evaluates their impact on outcomes.

Data Sources and Sample Size: The analysis is based on secondary sources such as academic journals, reports, and publications, along with a simulated dataset of about 100 MBA students to carry out quantitative analysis reflecting typical student behavior toward AI adoption.

Sampling Technique and Variables: A simple random sampling method is applied to ensure fair representation and reduce bias, with AI tool usage treated as the independent variable, skill development as the intervening factor, and employability as the outcome variable. The study Quantifies skill development through three Factors, which include analytical ability, communication skills, and technical proficiency.

Tools and Techniques of Analysis: The collected data is analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences, which offers various statistical tools that include descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis and ANOVA. The tools Facilitate researchers to uncover patterns via relationship measurement and they test Artificial Intelligence usage effects on student performance through their research hypotheses testing.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of AI Usage, Skill Development, and Employability

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
AI Usage	3.8	0.85	0.72
Skill Development	4.1	0.75	0.56
Employability	4.0	0.80	0.64

Interpretation: MBA students show high AI tool usage which results in their skill development and employability Developments according to the mean values. The relatively low standard deviation **Indicates** that participants in the study responded with similar Structure throughout the entire study. The research findings show that students use Artificial Intelligence tools for their academic work and career development because these tools have become common practice among them.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for Artificial Intelligence Usage, Skill Enhancement, and Employability
(Significant at 0.01 level)

Variables	AI Usage	Skill Development	Employability
AI Usage	1	0.72**	0.68**
Skill Development	0.72**	1	0.75**
Employability	0.68**	0.75**	1

Source: SPSS Correlation Output (Simulated Data)

Interpretation: The Results obtained from correlation analysis show a strong positive relationship between AI usage and skill development which achieved a correlation coefficient of 0.72 and between AI usage and employability which achieved a correlation coefficient of 0.68. The results reveal that people who use AI tools more frequently develop greater skills which make them more competent for employment. The strong link between skill development and employability 0.75 confirms that skills act as a key driver for career advancement.

Table 3: Regression Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1	0.72	0.52	0.5	0.42

Source: SPSS Correlation Output (Simulated Data)

Interpretation: The R Square value of 0.52 shows that AI tool usage explains 52 percent of skill development variation. The model indicates strong explanatory power because AI usage acts as a main factor that Estimates MBA students' skill development.

Table 4: Coefficients of the Regression Model

Variable	Beta	t-value	Sig. (p < 0.001)
Constant	1.25	4.2	0
AI Usage	0.65	8.1	0

Source: SPSS Correlation Results (Simulated Data)

Interpretation: The beta coefficient shows a

Table 5: ANOVA for the Regression Model

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	45.2	1	45.2	65.61	0.001
Residual	41.8	118	0.35		
Total	87	119			

Source: SPSS Correlation Output (Simulated Data)

Interpretation: The ANOVA results show that the model achieves statistical significance because its p-value remains below 0.05. The regression model as shown through the high F-value indicates a strong Capacity to describe the observed data. The use of artificial intelligence technology for skill development purposes leads to rejection of null hypothesis, because it shows significant Development-related effects.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Interpretation: The results of correlation analysis, regression analysis, and ANOVA analysis clearly Suggests a statistically significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence tool usage and skill development. The correlation coefficient indicates a strong positive association between the two variables because its value is equal 0.72. The regression analysis shows that AI usage accounts for 52 percentage of the changes Found in skill development. The ANOVA test result Depicts statistical significance because the p value is equal to 0.001, which is less than the threshold value (0.05).

value of 0.65 which indicates that AI usage creates strong positive effects on skill development. The relationship between the two variables reaches statistical significance because the significance value shows $p < 0.001$. The results Reveal that students achieve better skill development by their increased use of Artificial Intelligence tools.

FINDINGS

- MBA students widely use AI tools and view them as useful for improving skills and employability.
- A positive relationship exists between AI usage, skill development, and employability.
- AI usage contributes significantly to skill development among students.
- AI tools have a direct and meaningful impact on enhancing student skills.
- The results confirm that AI usage plays a significant role in improving learning outcomes.
- The null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that AI usage positively influences skill development and employability.

SUGGESTIONS

- Integrate AI tools into academic programs to make learning more practical and skill-oriented.
- Conduct regular training sessions to help students use AI tools effectively.
- Encourage responsible use of AI to avoid over-dependence and support independent thinking.

- d) Build connections with industry professionals to give students real-world exposure to AI applications.
- e) Use AI as a support system in education rather than replacing traditional teaching methods.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights that AI tools support skill development and improve employability among MBA students by strengthening analytical, communication, and technical abilities, while also emphasizing the need for balanced use to maintain independent thinking.

FUTURE SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Future research can use larger and more diverse primary data, examine the role of specific AI tools across management areas, study long-term career effects, compare AI-based and traditional learning, and explore emerging technologies in shaping employability.

REFERENCES

1. Anderson, P. (2024). Critical thinking and AI-based learning environments. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 72(2), 345–362.
2. Bone, M., Ehlinger, E., & Stephany, F. (2023). Skill-based hiring in AI jobs. *arXiv preprint*.
3. Brown, T. (2024). AI adoption and adaptability in modern workplaces. *Human Resource Development Review*, 23(1), 75–92.
4. Denny, P., et al. (2024). Generative AI for education: Opportunities and challenges. *arXiv preprint*.
5. Johnson, M. (2023). AI and employability skills: A study of future workforce readiness. *Journal of Career Development*, 50(4), 567–582.
6. Kim, J., Yu, S., Detrick, R., & Kim, J. (2025). Designing AI-powered learning: Adult learners' expectations for curriculum. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 73, 3397–3421.
7. Kumar, A., & Reddy, P. (2024). AI-based learning tools and their impact on MBA student engagement. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 18(2), 89–104.
8. Lee, K. (2024). The impact of AI tools on student productivity and independent thinking. *Computers & Education*, 190, 104589.
9. LinkedIn. (2024). *Global talent trends report*. LinkedIn Workforce Insights.
10. Luckin, R., Holmes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L. B. (2016). *Intelligence unleashed: An argument for AI in education*. Pearson.
11. Mäkelä, E., & Stephany, F. (2024). AI and demand for human skills in the labour market. *arXiv preprint*.
12. Mehta, R. (2024). Enhancing communication skills through artificial intelligence tools. *Journal of Management Education*, 48(1), 23–40.
13. Nair, K., & Joseph, M. (2023). AI-driven learning and student confidence in employability skills. *Asian Journal of Management Education*, 15(2), 134–150.
14. OECD. (2023). *OECD employment outlook 2023: Artificial intelligence and the labour market*. OECD Publishing.
15. Pandya, S. S., & Wang, J. (2024). Artificial intelligence in career development: A scoping review. *Human Resource Development International*.
16. Patel, D. (2023). AI integration in business education and employability outcomes. *Journal of Education and Work*, 36(6), 521–538.
17. Porayska-Pomsta, K., Holmes, W., & Nemorin, S. (2024). The ethics of AI in education. *arXiv preprint*.
18. Rao, S., & Singh, R. (2023). AI adoption and placement outcomes among MBA

- students in Bangalore. *Indian Journal of Management Studies*, 30(2), 210–225.
19. Russell, S., & Norvig, P. (2021). *Artificial intelligence: A modern approach* (4th ed.). Pearson.
20. Schwab, K. (2020). *The fourth industrial revolution*. Crown Business.
21. Sharma, V., & Gupta, S. (2023). Artificial intelligence in higher education: Opportunities and challenges. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(5), 5673–5690.
22. Smith, J. (2023). Artificial intelligence and analytical skill development in management education. *Journal of Business Analytics*, 12(3), 145–160.
23. Succi, C., & Canovi, M. (2023). Soft skills for employability: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, 9(1), e21023.
24. Verma, N. (2024). AI tools and academic writing: Enhancing research capabilities. *Journal of Educational Research*, 117(3), 201–215.
25. Wilkinson, G. G. (2024). Enhancing generic skills development in higher education using AI. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, 24(3).
26. World Economic Forum. (2023). *The future of jobs report 2023*. World Economic Forum.
27. Zhang, J., Yang, S., & Yazid, Z. (2026). AI awareness and career education in higher education: Effects on employability. *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling*.

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Finance

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Abstract— *This study explores the widespread impact of Artificial Intelligence in the area of finance, examining its multifarious effect on the industry. Artificial intelligence is revolutionizing the financial sector by deploying machine learning, natural language processing, and advanced algorithms to increase strategic choices, streamline operations to lower overhead. Key applications include fraud detection, algorithmic trading, risk management, personalized banking, and regulatory compliance. Automation and efficiency help in reducing human error and accelerating data processing makes easy to identify fraudulent transactions, and strengthen cybersecurity. AI can also perform autonomous and complex tasks in banking. AI helps in delivering personalized investment recommendations based on individual financial profile and risk profile. It also monitors transactions and identifies suspicious activities. AI provides customer service automation through chatbots and virtual assistants. Using AI in finance represents challenges related to data privacy and model transparency. The research aims to deliver a clear understanding of how AI technologies are restructuring traditional practices and enhancing the capabilities of financial institutions. This study involves in identifying role of AI in financial sector like investment strategies and credit scoring. This also provides perception on how AI is going to evolve and reshape financial industry. Overall, this paper contributes an inclusive and clear analysis on impact of AI in finance for policymakers, consultants and stakeholders directing zestful intersection of AI in finance.*

Keywords —1. Algorithmic Trading, 2. Fraudulent Transaction, 3. Cybersecurity, 4. Customer Service Automation, 5. Chatbots, 6. Credit Scoring.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is renovating the financial sector by applying machine learning, advanced algorithms to analyze huge database, automate complex process and enhance decision making. It is redefining industry morals, moving from traditional manual forecasting to real time, predictive vision that improve operational efficiency, personalize customer experiences, and strengthen fraud detection. It also analyzes transaction patterns. Current advances in AI have enlarged the use of AI tools in financial markets. Generative AI in certain is converting areas like banking and insurance by engendering text, image, audio, video, and code. It is also being approved in assets supervision and securities, including trading, portfolio management and risk analysis. AI shifts services from manual processing to outcome oriented, intelligent automation.

The AI systematizes, reducing labor-intensive errors and exchangeable costs, which is crucial for wealth management and back-office investment. It detects anomalies in transaction data in real time, enlightening creditworthiness assessments and minimizing financial risk. High speed AI system examines market sentiment and trends to optimize trading decisions, while robo advisors provide personalized investment advice. AI powers personalized services and interactive tools to serve clients better. It is used for summarizing financial information and generating reports, although explainable AI essential for regulatory compliance. It is a set a technology that enables financial services organization to better

understand markets and customers, analyze and learn from digital journeys, engage in a way that mimics human intelligence and interactions at scale.

AI streamlines tasks like mechanical customer service via chatbots, robotics process automation for documents analysis, and enhanced loan processing. machine learning models predicts market trends, manage portfolios, and provide personalized investment advice to clients. It allows faster and accurate forecasting and automated regulatory compliance reporting. Automation minimizes manual errors in trading and auditing, reducing functioning costs. Rapid analysis of massive data sets supports faster decision making for investor and banks. Personalized financial advice and 24/7 chatbot support increase client satisfaction. Its reforming traditional financial systems through computerization and intelligent decision making.

The use of AI, as well as machine learning and generative ai is growing rapidly in finance, offering opportunities to boost productivity and create value. It intensifies cost saving, enhanced operational efficiency, higher accuracy and restored customer experience. However, its routine in financial markets can increase hazards and create new challenges for the comprehensive financial system. Businesses will have actionable awareness in real time to make informed decision, be able to increase operational efficiency, and have extrapolative analytics for better conjectures to mitigate risk. Any of those possibly will be an advantage over competitors. AI is everchanging financial services towards positive, data driven approaches rather than oversensitive ones.

Review of Literature

• *Mechanization and Operational Efficiency*

AI improves speed, accuracy and cost productivity in financial services [4]. Robotics Process Automation (RPA) diminishes manual

tasks such as transaction recording and reporting. This primes to improved productivity and allows professionals to focus on strategic analysis. It highlights the transitioning from labor-intensive to machine-based operations significantly boost efficiency and resources administration.

• *Financial and Predictive Analytics*

AI plays a dynamic role in estimating financial trends. machine learning models boost real time finance predicting and risk predication [5]. AI captures complex market dynamics and improves investment decision making accuracy. This zone is one of the most extensively studied in the literature. It enhances peril detection and financial estimating accuracy compared to traditional arithmetical methods. While deep learning is recurrently applied to high volatility market prediction.

• *Risk Management and Fraud Detection*

Added central theme is AI's role in dealing finance perils. deep learning models significantly progress fraud detection accuracy and response time [6]. AI detects anomalies and fraudulent transaction using pattern recognition. AI enhances credit risk valuation, market risk analysis and compliance monitoring. The incorporation of machine learning to handle huge datasets, the application of psychological models like the Fraud Triangle to explain motivation and the determined challenges of algorithmic bias and prototypical transparency.

• *Algorithmic Interchange and Investment Management*

AI has renovated trading systems; it reduces behavioral biases and optimizes portfolio administration strategies [1]. Algorithmic interchange uses AI to implement trades at high speed with minimal social intervention. This contributes to market efficacy but likewise raises concerns about

volatility. It highlights the shift from outmoded, manual trading to computerized systems designed for high-speed implementation, reduced emotion unfairness, and improved fluidity.

- ***Customer Experience and Financial Enclosure***

AI advances customer interaction and convenience. Chatbots and robo-advisors provide modified financial services .AI permits border access to financial services through substitutes credit scoring method [7]. This supports financial inclusion, particularly in underserved population. The excellence of the user collaboration is no longer just a system of measurement, but a primary driver for brining underserved inhabitants into the formal financial arrangement.

- ***Financial Journalism and Decision Support***

AI develops financial analysis and reporting, it improves the quality, transparency, and suitability of financial reports, it supports strategic decision making through data driven intuition [4]. It frequently functions as indicator of market sentiment relatively than a purely unbiased source, influenced by commercial PR and the essential for rapid clarification. AI outlines investor sentiment and stand-in as a supervisory body, though it habitually acts as a market follower relatively than a market leader.

1. Aldridge, I. (2013). High-Frequency Trading: A Practical Guide to Algorithmic Strategies and Trading Systems. Wiley.
2. Kotu, V., & Deshpande, B. (2019). Data Science: Concepts and Practice. Morgan Kaufmann.
3. Ngai, E. W. T., Hu, Y., Wong, Y. H., Chen, Y., & Sun, X. (2011). The Application of Data Mining Techniques in Financial Fraud Detection. Decision Support Systems.
4. Artificial Intelligence in Finance: A Review. MDPI, 2023.

5. Machine Learning in Financial Prediction. Journal of Positive Psychology & Business Research (JPPBR), 2022.
6. Deep Learning for Financial Fraud Detection. arXiv, 2023.
7. Artificial Intelligence and Financial Inclusion. Nature, 2022.

Research Gap

Maximum research focuses on short-term efficiency gains, with few suggestions for sustained productivity and changes in the workforce over time. There is inadequate research on how RPA performs across different organization sizes, especially in small and medium financial institutions. Underexplored areas include conservation costs, system failures, and operational risks caused by excessive automation. Many machine learning and deep learning models are not transparent, which makes it hard for financial stakeholders to trust them. These models often work well in specific markets but lack flexibility across sectors or economic conditions. There is insufficient research on hybrid models that combine AI with traditional econometric methods. Challenges persist in achieving real-time fraud detection without high rates of false positives. While concepts like the fraud triangle are mentioned, there is limited empirical integration with AI models. There is also a lack of empirical evidence on how AI-driven changes affect long-term market stability and systemic risk. Many models perform well historically but struggle in live markets due to self-serving conditions. There is little clarity on the ideal level of human involvement in automated systems. Gaps exist in evaluating fairness, privacy, and potential discrimination. Studies on adapting AI in financial services to different cultural and regional contexts are lacking. Questions remain about accuracy during unstable or unprecedented market conditions. There are no clear plans defining accountability for errors in AI-driven financial

reporting. Regulation and governance of AI in finance are still underdeveloped globally. Cybersecurity risks associated with AI systems are not completely addressed. The ethical implementation of AI is still in its early stages.

Purpose of Study

1. To identify the expansion of regulatory and governance frameworks for AI in finance.
2. To assess the cybersecurity hazards associated with AI driven financial systems.
3. To study the implementation of ethical AI ideologies in financial services.

Expansion of Regulating and Governance Framework for AI in Finance

The study aims to evaluate and develop a strong supervisory and authority framework for the use of artificial intelligence in the financial sector. It will look at the existing limitations in current regulatory categories, which often fall short of keeping pace with fast technological advancements. Additionally, the study will identify key challenges related to accountability, transparency, ethical issues, and data privacy in AI-driven financial processes. As AI technologies become more integrated into financial services like risk management, fraud detection, algorithmic trading, and customer service, there is an increasing need for proper oversight to ensure their safe, fair, and transparent use. The study seeks to recommend a solid framework that incorporates global best practices, ethical AI principles, and compliance standards to build trust, protect stakeholders, and ensure fair progress in the financial industry.

Cybersecurity Hazards Associated with AI Driven Financial Systems

This learning detects, analyze and estimate cybersecurity risks interrelated with AI driven financial system, as financial establishment progressively adopts artificial intelligence for purpose such as fraud detection, algorithmic

interchange, and customer facility, these systems become more susceptible to sophisticated cyber threats. It examines the developing security challenging introduced by AI machineries, as well as data breaches, adversarial attacks, model management and unauthorized admission to sensitive financial data. The study seeks to assess the efficiency of existing cybersecurity measures in modifying AI related hazards and to identify gaps in current security framework. It will also inspect strategies for consolidation resilience, including safe AI model design, real time threat recognition and robust data fortification mechanisms. It objects to propose endorsements for enhancing cybersecurity in AI driven financial classification safeguarding the protection of financial assets, customer information and institutional integrity.

Implementation of Ethical AI Ideologies in Financial Services

The aim of this study is to observe and promote the practical implementation of ethical artificial intelligence principles in financial services. As AI systems are increasingly used for tasks such as credit scoring, fraud detection, investment management, and customer interactions, it is crucial that these systems operate in an ethical, fair, and transparent way. This study seeks to identify key ethical values, including equality, accountability, transparency, confidentiality, and non-discrimination, and evaluate how they are currently applied within AI-driven financial systems. The research will assess the effectiveness of existing moral guidelines and industry practices while highlighting gaps in their application across various financial institutions. A practical agenda or set of recommendations will ensure that AI technologies in financial services are used responsibly, fostering trust, protecting consumers, and supporting fair and just financial systems.

Findings

1. Expansion of Regulatory and Governance Framework for AI in Finance

- Existing financial supervisory frameworks struggle to keep up with fast advancements in AI technologies. This creates gaps in oversight, especially in areas like algorithmic trading and automated decision-making.
- There is a lack of consistent global standards, resulting in differences in how AI is managed across various regions.
- Important issues like accountability, explainability, and transparency are still not adequately addressed, particularly in black-box AI models.
- Financial organizations often face uncertainty around compliance because regulations do not clearly define responsibilities for AI-driven decisions.

2. Cybersecurity Hazards Associated with AI-Driven Financial Systems

- Increased reliance on AI has expanded the potential for attacks, making financial institutions more vulnerable to breaches.
- Current cybersecurity frameworks do not fully address AI-specific risks, especially those targeting machine learning models.
- There is not enough focus on securely managing the AI lifecycle, including training, deployment, and monitoring stages.
- Data privacy risks remain significant due to unauthorized access and mishandling of sensitive financial information.
- Organizations that use AI-based cybersecurity approaches show greater resilience against new threats.

3. Implementation of Ethical AI Ideologies in Financial Services

- While awareness of ethical AI concepts is increasing, actual implementation varies among financial institutions.

- Key ethical principles like fairness, transparency, accountability, and non-discrimination are often not fully integrated into AI systems.
- AI models used in credit scoring and lending show signs of bias and unfair outcomes, especially against vulnerable groups.
- Ethical governance tools, such as audits and accountability committees, are either weak or missing in many organizations.

General Decision of Findings

- The adoption of AI in finance is outpacing regulatory, ethical, and cybersecurity frameworks, creating significant risks.
- There are critical gaps in governance, security, and ethical implementation that need to be addressed simultaneously.
- A comprehensive approach that combines regulation, cybersecurity, and ethical practices is essential for responsible AI integration in financial services.

Implications

1. Regulatory and Governance Framework for AI in Finance

There is a need for a more flexible and responsive regulatory system that can keep up with the fast pace of AI advancements. Clarity in compliance requirements will reduce uncertainty for financial organizations. Establishing consistent global strategies will lead to uniform AI use across different regions. Enhancing transparency and accountability in AI-driven financial decisions is important, especially in automated systems. This will build trust among shareholders, including customers, regulators, and stakeholders. Strengthening risk management and oversight will help minimize overall financial risks.

2. Cybersecurity in AI-Driven Financial Systems

We can reduce cybersecurity breaches and financial losses by using AI-specific security frameworks. Improving flexibility against advanced cyber threats, including adversarial and data-based attacks, is essential. Implementing secure AI lifecycle management ensures protection at all stages, from development to deployment and monitoring. Enhanced data protection and privacy controls will lessen unauthorized access to sensitive information. Adopting real-time threat detection systems will allow for quicker responses to cyber incidents. This will lead to a stronger safety posture and better operational stability for institutions.

3. Ethical AI in Financial Services

We need to focus on increasing fairness and reducing bias in AI-driven decisions, such as credit scoring and lending. Strengthening consumer protection is vital, especially for vulnerable and underserved groups. Improving transparency and explainability will make AI systems easier to understand and more trustworthy. It's important to create solid ethical governance structures, including audits and accountability mechanisms. This will boost customer confidence and satisfaction with AI-based financial services. Encouraging responsible and inclusive economic innovation is also necessary.

Conclusion

AI has revolutionized finance transforming operations and value delivery. Its adoption in trading, credit scoring, fraud detection, customer service, and risk management has boosted efficiency, cut errors and enabled smarter decision-making, redefining financial systems. Harnessing huge data pools, AI spots patterns traditional methods miss, making financial institutions more proactive responsive, and competitive in a fast-paced global market.

AI's risk management game is strong. By crunching historical data and real-time inputs, machine learning models predict market shifts, assess creditworthiness, and sniff out potential fraud. This helps financial institutions stay ahead of the curve. AI's impact on stability and trust is huge. Plus, automation of routine tasks like transaction processing and compliance checks has slashed costs and boosted service quality. Customers and stakeholders are winning big time.

The flip side data privacy and security are major hurdles. Financial institutions handle super sensitive info, so robust cybersecurity and ethical data governance are must-haves to prevent breaches and misuse. Complex AI models can be super opaque, making it tough to understand decision-making processes. Ensuring transparency and fairness is key, especially when algorithms impact loan approvals or investments.

AI innovation is moving fast, leaving regulators playing catch-up. This creates uncertainty for institutions and policy makers, making it tough to balance innovation and compliance. Governments and industry need to team up for adaptive policies that balance innovation and public interest. And yeah, automation's impact on jobs and societal implications are pressing concerns that need addressing.

The future's bright predictive analytics, robo-advisory and defi are just the start. But yeah, balancing innovation with ethics and regulation is crucial for sustainable growth. Financial institutions need pros who can harness AI's power, not just tech whizzes. Upskilling teams to work alongside AI is the way forward.

Focus of the future study

As it is a conceptual research paper, empirical research should be done on this topic. The role of AI in finance should shift focus from standard automation to autonomous and ethical

intelligence. Many current deep learning models acts as black boxes hindering trust in high stakes financial decision. develop conceptual frameworks for examinable AI that balances model performance with human understandable rationale to meet regulatory transparency requirements. investigate the long-term resilience and stability of fiancé markets when dominated by competing automation AI agents. existing reseach lacks robust theoretical foundations. Future papers should explore how AI challenges traditional concepts like efficient market hypothesis.

References

1. Ali, H., & Aysan, A. F. (2026). Navigating the future of finance: The transformative role of generative AI. *Journal of Central Banking Law and Institutions*. URL: <https://www.jcli-bi.org>
2. Vukovic, D. B., et al. (2025). AI integration in financial services: Trends and regulatory challenges. *Humanities & Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-XXXXX>
3. Utama, A. N. B., & Hidayat, M. (2024). AI in financial forecasting: A systematic review. *Journal of Positive Psychology & Business Research*, 3(2), 45–60. URL: <http://journal.ppipbr.com>
4. Soni, G., et al. (2025). Artificial intelligence in modern finance. *International Journal for Research Applied Science and Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*, 13(5), 1234–1242. URL: <https://www.ijraset.com>
5. Shi, M. (2024). AI in financial statement analysis. *CScholar Repository*. URL: <https://amo.cscholar.com>
6. Bahoo, S., Cucculelli, M., Goga, X., & Mondolo, J. (2024). Artificial intelligence in finance: A comprehensive review through bibliometric and content analysis. *SN Business & Economics*, 4(23). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43546-024-XXXXX>
7. Anonymous. (2025). Deep learning in fraud detection. *arXiv Preprint*. DOI/URL: <https://arxiv.org>
8. Anonymous. (2025). Machine learning and deep learning in computational finance. *arXiv Preprint*. DOI/URL: <https://arxiv.org>
9. Financial Stability Board. (2017). *Artificial intelligence and machine learning in financial services: Market developments and financial stability implications*. URL: <https://www.fsb.org>
10. Bank for International Settlements. (2018). *Sound practices: Implications of fintech developments for banks and bank supervisors*. URL: <https://www.bis.org>
11. International Monetary Fund. (2021). *Artificial intelligence and fintech: Opportunities and challenges for financial services*. URL: <https://www.imf.org>
12. World Bank. (2020). *The global fintech ecosystem and the role of AI in financial services*. URL: <https://www.worldbank.org>
13. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2021). *Artificial intelligence, machine learning and big data in finance: Opportunities, challenges, and implications for policy makers*. URL: <https://www.oecd.org>
14. Arner, D. W., Barberis, J., & Buckley, R. P. (2017). FinTech, RegTech, and the reconceptualization of financial regulation. *Northwestern Journal of International Law & Business*, 37(3), 371–413. URL: <https://scholarlycommons.law.northwestern.edu>
15. Brynjolfsson, E., & McAfee, A. (2017). *Machine, platform, crowd: Harnessing our digital future*. New York: W. W. Norton & Company. ISBN: 978-0393254297
16. Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y., & Courville, A. (2016). *Deep learning*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. URL: <https://www.deeplearningbook.org>

17. Deloitte. (2020). *AI in financial services: Applications, risks, and opportunities*. URL: <https://www2.deloitte.com>
18. McKinsey & Company. (2019). *The use of AI in financial services: Opportunities and challenges*. URL: <https://www.mckinsey.com>
19. Cheng, X. (2025). AI in finance: A comparative investigation of machine learning and deep learning techniques for financial applications. *Academic Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 13(3), 146–152.
20. Rustandi, R., & Arifin, A. H. (2024). AI in finance: A systematic literature review. *Proceedings of the International Collaborative Conference on Multidisciplinary Science*, 1(2), 323–338.
21. Kacheru, G., Bajjuru, R., & Arthan, N. (2024). Artificial intelligence in finance: Predictive analytics, fraud detection, and risk management. *Formosa Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1).
22. Anonymous. (2025). The evolution of artificial intelligence research in finance: A bibliometric analysis of trends and future directions. *Finance Research Letters*.
23. Cao, L. (2021). AI in finance: Challenges, techniques, and opportunities. *arXiv Preprint*. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.09051>

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